

immerse

INTEGRATION MAPPING OF REFUGEE
AND MIGRANT CHILDREN

IMMERSE D3.1_V2.1

IMMERSE DELIVERABLE D3.1 REPORT ON STANDARDISATION ACROSS DATA COLLECTION/IMPLEMENTATION VERSION 2.1

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Summary

This report summarises planned methodological approaches for Work Package 3 of the IMMERSE project. We describe the formation and rationale for data collection activities of WP3, both quantitative and qualitative, across IMMERSE research partners. The report is divided into three main sections: questionnaire construction, sampling strategy for large-scale quantitative data collection, and methodologies for small-scale qualitative data collection. Appendices containing country-specific sampling strategies authored by each research partner follow.

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Table of Contents

1	Executive Summary	7
2	Harmonisation of Data	8
2.1	<i>Standardisation of Definitions and Indicators</i>	8
2.1.1	Definition of target population	8
2.1.2	Dashboard of indicators	10
2.1.3	Focus on third country nationals and economic migrants	11
3	Large-scale Quantitative Data Collection: Instruments	13
3.1	<i>IMMERSE Data Collection Instruments Overview</i>	13
3.1.1	Macro level data	13
3.1.2	Meso level data	14
3.1.3	Micro level data	14
3.2	<i>Data Collection Instruments: Questionnaires</i>	15
3.2.1	Questionnaire development process	15
3.2.2	Micro level questionnaires	18
3.2.3	Meso level questionnaires	37
4	Large-scale Quantitative Data Collection: Sampling Strategy	47
4.1	<i>Regional Sampling</i>	47
4.2	<i>School Sampling</i>	48
4.2.1	Theoretical 'ideal' sampling framework	48
4.2.2	School sampling Plan B	50
4.3	<i>Classroom Sampling</i>	51
4.4	<i>Sampling in Non-formal Environments</i>	52
4.5	<i>Timeline of Data Collection</i>	52
4.6	<i>Analysis of the Full Dataset</i>	54
5	Qualitative Data Collection	55
5.1	<i>Selection of Groups to Be Researched</i>	55
5.2	<i>Methods</i>	56
5.2.1	Focus groups / individual interviews	56
5.2.2	Diarying or journaling	58
5.2.3	Mapmaking or photovoice	58
5.2.4	Suggested steps to follow for those choosing all of the qualitative methods	60
5.3	<i>Data Analysis</i>	60
5.4	<i>Timeline of Data Collection</i>	62
6	References	64
7	Appendix A – Spain (Research Partner: Comillas)	67
7.1	<i>Regional Sampling</i>	67

7.2	<i>Region Profiles</i>	71
7.2.1	Region: Community of Madrid	71
7.2.2	Region: La Rioja	74
7.2.3	Region: Andalusia and its provinces, Huelva, Malaga and Almeria	77
7.3	<i>School Sampling</i>	85
7.3.1	Key characteristics using in sampling framework	85
7.3.2	Categories resulting from Framework and Sampling Pool	90
7.4	<i>School Sampling – Plan B</i>	91
7.5	<i>Child/classroom Sampling</i>	91
7.6	<i>Sampling in Non-Formal Education Environments</i>	91
8	Appendix B – Ireland (Research Partner: UCC)	93
8.1	<i>Regional Sampling</i>	93
8.2	<i>Region Profiles</i>	95
8.2.1	Region: Dublin	95
8.2.2	Region: Cork	100
8.2.3	Region: Limerick	104
8.3	<i>School Sampling</i>	107
8.3.1	Key characteristics used in sampling framework	108
8.3.2	Categories resulting from framework and sampling pool	109
8.4	<i>School Sampling – Plan B</i>	111
8.5	<i>Child/classroom Sampling</i>	111
8.6	<i>Sampling in Non-formal Education Environments</i>	112
9	Appendix C – Italy (Research Partner: SCIT)	113
9.1	<i>Regional Sampling</i>	113
9.2	<i>Region Profiles</i>	115
9.2.1	Region: Milan (Lombardy)	115
9.2.2	Region: Turin (Piedmont)	118
9.2.3	Region: Rome (Lazio)	120
9.2.4	Region: Naples (Campania)	123
9.2.5	Region: Catania (Sicily)	125
9.3	<i>School Sampling</i>	127
9.3.1	Key characteristics used in sampling framework	128
9.3.2	Categories resulting from framework and sampling pool	128
9.4	<i>School Sampling – Plan B</i>	131
9.5	<i>Child/classroom Sampling</i>	131
9.6	<i>Sampling in Non-formal Education Environments</i>	133
10	Appendix D – Germany (Research Partner: Doz)	134
10.1	<i>Regional Sampling</i>	134
10.2	<i>Region Profiles</i>	135
10.2.1	Region: Leipzig (State of Saxony)	135

10.2.2	Region: Cologne (State of North-Rhine Westphalia)	138
10.2.3	Region: Berlin (State of Berlin)	140
10.3	<i>School Sampling</i>	142
10.3.1	Key characteristics used in sampling framework	144
10.3.2	Categories resulting from key characteristics	146
10.4	<i>School Sampling – Plan B</i>	147
10.5	<i>Child/classroom Sampling</i>	147
10.6	<i>Sampling in Non-Formal Education Environments</i>	147
11	Appendix E – Greece (Research Partners: Panteion and RDPSEC)	149
11.1	<i>Regional Sampling</i>	149
11.2	<i>Region Profiles</i>	155
11.2.1	Region: Attica - Attiki Regional Unit	155
11.2.2	Region: Central Macedonia - Thessaloniki Regional Unit	161
11.2.3	Region: Crete – Heraklion, Lasithi, Chania, Rethymno Regional Units	166
11.2.4	Region: Thessaly – Larissa Regional Unit	171
11.2.5	Region: Epirus – Ioannina and Preveza Regional Units	175
11.2.6	Region: Eastern Macedonia and Thrace – Xanthi Regional Unit	185
11.2.7	Region: North Aegean Islands – Chios Regional Unit	189
11.3	<i>School Sampling</i>	195
11.3.1	Key characteristics used in sampling framework	198
11.3.2	Categories resulting from framework and sampling pool	199
11.4	<i>School Sampling – Plan B</i>	200
11.5	<i>Child/classroom Sampling</i>	200
11.6	<i>Sampling in Non-Formal Educational Environments</i>	201
12	Appendix F – Belgium (Research Partner: ACE)	202
12.1	<i>Regional Sampling</i>	202
12.2	<i>Region Profiles</i>	204
12.2.1	Region: Mechelen (Antwerp Province)	204
12.2.2	Region: Ghent (East Flanders)	207
12.2.3	Region: Brussels Capital Region	212
12.3	<i>School Sampling</i>	214
12.3.1	Key characteristics used in sampling framework	215
12.3.2	Categories resulting from key characteristics	216
12.4	<i>School Sampling – Plan B</i>	217
12.5	<i>Child/classroom sampling</i>	217
12.6	<i>Sampling in Non-Formal Education Environments</i>	217

Report on Standardisation across Data Collection/Implementation

IMMERSE Work Package 3 Methodological Planning

1 Executive Summary

This document reports on the data and methodological harmonisation efforts of the IMMERSE project as it moves into the data collection phase of Work Package 3 (WP3): Data Collection and Monitoring. WP3 builds on Work Package 1: Co-Creation of the Dashboard of Indicators, which was completed in February of 2020. The Dashboard of Indicators is a comprehensive set of 30 key indicators of educational integration of migrant and refugee children in schools, covering three levels: the macro, e.g. countries and regions, the meso, e.g. schools and other non-formal education centres, and the micro, e.g. children and their families. The dashboard was selected through a multi-stage process involving qualitative data collection and analysis, a Delphi evaluation, an online meso/macro evaluation across the six countries of the research consortium, and micro level workshops with migrant and refugee children. For a full description of the dashboard and its formation process, see D1.5 *IMMERSE Dashboard* (Serrano et al., 2020a) and D1.6 *Report on the Results of Evaluation System of Socio-educational Integration of Migrant Children* (Serrano et al., 2020b).

The dashboard forms the foundation for the subsequent phases of the IMMERSE project. With the finalisation of the dashboard, the tasks of WP3, which constitute the bulk of IMMERSE activity, can move forward. WP3 contains the main data collection phase of the project, both quantitative and qualitative. The data resulting from this work package are the basis on which our final reports and policy recommendations will be made.

In this document, we outline the first critical tasks of WP3: construction of data collection instruments and sampling strategy for the large-scale quantitative data collection and the methodological approach for the small-scale qualitative data collection. In Section 2, we outline the harmonised approach we are taking to the data collection in order to ensure a high degree of transparency and comparability, beginning with key definitions and critical concepts, including the dashboard. There are six data collection instruments, four at the micro level for parents and children, and two at the meso level for principals and teachers. The construction process and contents of these are described in Section 3. In Section 4, we discuss sampling strategy at the regional, school/non-formal environment, and classroom level. Appendices A-F outline the country-specific adaptations of the sampling strategy for each of the IMMERSE partner countries: Spain, Ireland, Italy, Germany, Belgium, and Greece. In the final section, we outline the methodologies proposed for the qualitative data collection, which aims to capture the experiences of those groups who will likely be underrepresented in the large-scale data collection.

2 Harmonisation of Data

In order to achieve the objective of forming national and European policy recommendations on educational integration, IMMERSE must collect and analyse data that represents the reality of migrant and refugee children in schools across the consortium. Detecting trends that can lead to such recommendations requires a large and robust set of data that, though gathered in disparate locations by different people, is nevertheless comparable. It is the quality and comparability of the data that will allow IMMERSE to affect positive change in schools for migrant and refugee children across the continent. To ensure this quality and comparability, IMMERSE research partners must use standardised instruments and follow a harmonised approach:

Harmonization is a generic term for procedures used predominantly in official statistics that aim at achieving, or at least improving, the comparability of different surveys and measures collected . . . Harmonizing procedures may be applied in any part of the survey lifecycle, such as study design, choice of indicators, question wording, translation, adaptation, questionnaire design, sampling, data collection, data coding, data editing, or documentation.

(Granda & Blasczyk, 2016, p. 1)

Granda & Blasczyk (2016) describe two basic types of harmonisation in research involving multinational surveys: input harmonization and output harmonization. Input harmonisation should be adopted when a project aims to collect primary data and is able to centrally control this process from the beginning, resulting in a high degree of comparability. Output harmonization can be used when attempting to bring together data from multiple sources after it has already been collected.

One of the strengths of IMMERSE is the collection of primary data and the cooperation of a consortium of research teams in order to achieve this. In order to take full advantage of this opportunity, we are employing an input harmonisation approach. This document reports on the harmonisation efforts of IMMERSE as it relates to the data collection instruments and sampling approaches of its large-scale quantitative data collection and the methodologies associated with its small-scale qualitative data collection. A second report (D3.2 Handbook for the IMMERSE Data Collection Fieldwork, forthcoming) will provide documentation and guidance to harmonise the fieldwork process.

2.1 Standardisation of Definitions and Indicators

2.1.1 Definition of target population

IMMERSE focuses on refugee and migrant children. “Children” comprise for us: children and young people under 18, although we restrict data collection to 6-18 years. Six is the age at which general compulsory school starts across Europe, and 18 is generally the age at which schooling finishes and represents the moment of transition to adulthood. For the purpose of IMMERSE, the definition of “migrant and refugee” children comprises children of migrant background using the following criteria:

1. First generation (foreign-born children). This includes children with at least one native parent (i.e. “returning foreign-born” according to OECD definitions below).
2. Second-generation children (born in the country, with at least one foreign-born parent), including children with one native parent (i.e. “native children of mixed heritage” according to OECD definitions below).
3. Regardless of citizenship and/or legal status (these children may or not be asylum seekers or beneficiaries of different types of international protection).
4. Regardless of the accompanied/ unaccompanied status (all included).

Figure 1. OECD/PISA Definition of Migrant Children

(OECD, 2018, p.50)

This definition reflects both the Eurydice definition of ‘students from migrant backgrounds’¹ and the OECD definition of migrant-background children in its specialized PISA-based report on resilience of migrant children.

¹**EURYDICE definition:** What do we mean by ‘students from migrant backgrounds’? The report focuses on children and young people from migrant backgrounds. They are defined as newly arrived/first generation, second generation or returning migrant children and young people. Their reasons for having migrated (e.g. economic or political) may vary, as may their legal status – they may be citizens, residents, asylum seekers, refugees, unaccompanied minors or irregular migrants. Their length of stay in the host country may be short- or long-term, and they may or may not have the right to participate in the formal education system of the host country (European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice et al., 2019)

2.1.2 Dashboard of indicators

At the foundation of IMMERSE Work Package 3 and its harmonization is the Dashboard of Indicators, the culmination of Work Package 1, which took place over the first 14 months of the project. The main objective of the IMMERSE project is to develop a dashboard of indicators about migrant children integration and provide representative data to impact policy making in the European context. The dashboard consists of 30 parameters considered most relevant for refugee and migrant children's integration in schools. A first set of 50 indicators was selected and validated through a three-stage process, then refined to the final 30 through a content validation process consisting in a Delphi methodology and later a CARA methodology that ensured migrant children's voices were represented in the co-creation of the inventory of socio-educational integration indicators. The full final dashboard is presented in D1.5 *IMMERSE Dashboard* (overview in Table 1), and the methodology of the selection process is explained in detail in D1.6 *Report on the Results of Evaluation System of Socio-educational Integration of Migrant Children* (overview in Figure 2).

Table 1. Overview of the IMMERSE Dashboard

Outcomes	
O1.2.1	Children's access to compulsory education
O1.2.3	Children's access to health care
O2.1.1	Children's perceived competence in host language
O2.2.2	Children maintain their cultural identity adopting key host country cultural values and intercultural competences
O3.1.2	Children's life satisfaction/happiness
O3.1.3	Children's sense of belonging
O4.1.1	Interconnectedness/ Friends and peers
O4.1.1	Interconnectedness/ Friends and peers
O4.1.2	Interconnectedness/ Teachers
O4.1.3	Interconnectedness/ Institutions
O5.1.1	Children's academic skills
O5.2.1	Children complete compulsory education
O5.2.2	Children remain in formal education beyond compulsory levels
O5.2.3	Types and levels of (formal) non-compulsory education attended
Determinants	
D4.2	Legislation and practice conditioning (LPC) the acquisition of superior legal status
D4.3	LPC access to education
D4.8	LPC access to healthcare
D3.7.1	Concentration in disadvantaged schools
D3.2.1	Clear leadership and school identity around intercultural values (against xenophobia, prejudice and stereotypes)
D3.2.3	School promotion of parental involvement in school activities, extra-curricular activities and parental associations
D3.4.5	Intercultural competence as part of syllabus or/and transversally
D4.15.5	LRR Intercultural education
D4.16.1	LRR Preparatory classes
D4.16.2	LRR Educational support for migrant children, particularly learning and language support
D5.6	Supplementary community services for learning/language support

D3.5.4	Extra-curricular activities available/ after-class learning centres
D3.6.2	Counselling services at school
D6.1	Experience/perception of negative attitudes
D6.2	Experience of harassment and/or physical violence (incl. bullying) outside family

Figure 2. Overview of Dashboard Building Process

2.1.3 Focus on third country nationals and economic migrants

The EC call of our project within the H2020 framework stated that, “[t]he call will also provide evidence based knowledge on the effects of migration on social systems, the access to and impact on labour markets and the cultural integration of third country nationals, in particular in urban settings” (European Commission, 2019, p.10). Additionally, the European Commission definition of integration is as follows:

Integration should be understood as a two-way process based on mutual rights and corresponding obligations of *legally resident third country nationals* and the host society which provides for full participation of the immigrant. This implies on the one hand that it is the responsibility of the host society to ensure that the formal rights of immigrants are in place in such a way that the individual has the possibility of participating in economic, social, cultural and civil life and on the other, that immigrants respect the fundamental norms and values of the host society and participate actively in the integration process, without having to relinquish their own identity.

(European Commission, 2003, p.17-18)

After discussion between the coordinators and WP3 leaders and following the focus of the initial project call under which IMMERSE was funded and in line with the European Commission definition of integration, we decided that the core of the sample will be made up of third country nationals (TCNs). This does not mean that EU nationals must be wholly excluded from the sample, but that the main focus of sampling and data collection will be on TCNs.

TCNs are any persons who are not citizens of the European Union within the meaning of Art. 20(1) of Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union and who are not persons enjoying the European Union right to free movement, as defined in Art. 2(5) of the Regulation (EU) 2016/399 (Schengen

Borders Code), the right of EU citizens and legally resident TCNs to move and reside freely within the territory of the EU Member States. The free movement of persons is a fundamental right guaranteed by the EU to its citizens. It enables every EU citizen to travel, work and live in any EU country without special formalities. Schengen cooperation enhances this freedom by enabling citizens to cross internal borders without being subjected to border checks.

Once Schengen Borders were established in the European Union, EU citizens acquired free movement and freedom of establishment and residence within the territory of the EU Member States (Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, 2006). The first two countries signed the agreement in 1985 and the majority of EU Member States joined this agreement in the following decades. There are five more EU members, that have not joined Schengen zone: Ireland (who still maintains opt-outs), Romania, Bulgaria, Croatia, and Cyprus (who are seeking to join soon).

Since the unification, the EU Strategy and Actions to promote migrant integration are oriented to TCNs as specified in the European Agenda on Migration² and in the Common Agenda on Migrant Integration through its Action Plan on the integration of TCN. Since EU unification, the concept of migrant has narrowed to TCNs and this conceptualization is reflected in the basis of EC initiatives, including this H2020 project.

Given this, in the context of IMMERSE, the definition of migrant will, in general, denote third country nationals. In addition, even if all third country nationals may be part of the sample, we strongly recommended to partners to try to avoid including children coming from high-income countries in the sample. For this decision we suggest the OECD classification of countries based on their Household Disposable Income.³ According to the OECD, “[h]ousehold disposable income is the closest to the concept of income as generally understood in economics,” and is therefore a commonly used metric for comparing individual wealth across nations. Based on this classification of countries by their Household Disposable Income, we suggest excluding the top 10 TCN of the list (2019): United States, Luxembourg, Switzerland, Australia, Norway, Austria, Canada, United Kingdom, New Zealand, and Japan.

In terms of EU nationals, we understood that each partner within the consortium has special migration flows that should be incorporated in their sample to reflect the reality of migration and integration concerns in that country. In cases where some of the principal economic migrant communities belong to EU countries, like, for instance, Romanians in Spain, who are the second biggest migrant community in the country, IMMERSE partners may justify their insertion in the sample. As another example, migrants from EU East countries, such as Poland and Latvia, make up about 45% of all migrants in Ireland, and previous research shows that this group has the lowest proportions of third level education completion (compared to Irish-born and other migrant groups) and higher levels of unemployment than Irish-born. In light of circumstances such as these, each partner can include those EU nationals that do not usually enjoy the same rights as other EU

²https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/homeaffairs/files/what-we-do/policies/european-agenda-migration/background-information/docs/communication_on_the_european_agenda_on_migration_en.pdf

³For details on definition and measurement, see OECD (2020), Household disposable income (indicator). doi: 10.1787/dd50eddd-en (Accessed on 09 July 2020) <https://data.oecd.org/hha/household-disposable-income.htm>

members (EU countries outside the Schengen Area would fall into this category) or because they are considered to be economic migrants within the context of the host country. We understand the term “economic migrant” to refer mainly to low or semi-skilled workers (though potentially highly-skilled workers, as well) who have moved from a country where potential job, earnings, or quality of living prospects are appreciably lower than the host country to which they relocate.

We clarified with the partners that we would still use a whole-classroom approach (see classroom sampling section) to collect data – they did not need to exclude anyone in a class from taking the survey because they were not from our core focus group. In addition, the partners would be free to use whatever data they collected in their own within-country analyses, whatever the origin countries of the respondents. However, we recommended that the majority of their data collection focus on economic migrant TCNs and the EU nationals they selected as the most relevant for their country, as these are the groups that will be focused on in the cross-country analyses and who will form the basis of our policy recommendations.

3 Large-scale Quantitative Data Collection: Instruments

3.1 IMMERSE Data Collection Instruments Overview

One of the primary ways the IMMERSE project aims to standardise data collection is by using the same data collection instruments across the research partner countries and across data collection sites within countries. For large-scale data collection in schools and non-formal education environments, surveys were chosen as the most efficient way to collect data on a large scale (i.e. from thousands of participants) across several countries and environments. Moreover, using standardised questionnaires would yield data suitable for cross-national comparison, allowing detection of trends and patterns (and dissimilarities) on key measures and control of influential demographic variables, like socio-economic status.

In order to gain as complete a picture as possible of integration in schools and to allow analysis to take place at any of the three levels outlined in the IMMERSE conceptual framework, data relating to all three levels needed to be collected: the macro level (country/region), the meso level (school/non-formal environment), and the micro level (the individual child).

3.1.1 Macro level data

Data relating to the macro or country level was gathered from secondary sources, such as MIPEX, and linked directly to the dashboard. Table 2 shows the macro level indicators and their sources. These indicators mainly relate to legislation and resources available in each country that support migrants and their integration. For a complete discussion of the IMMERSE macro indicators, please see D1.5 *IMMERSE Dashboard* (Serrano et al., 2020a) and D1.6 *Report on the Results of Evaluation System of Socio-educational Integration of Migrant Children* (Serrano et al., 2020b).

Table 2. IMMERSE Macro Indicators and Data Sources

Indicator	Description	Source
O1.2.1	Children's access to compulsory education	Eurostat and country administrative data
O1.2.3	Children's access to healthcare	EU-SILC survey
O5.1.1	Children's academic skills	PISA
O5.2.1	Children complete compulsory education	PIAAC survey
O5.2.2	Children remain in formal education beyond compulsory levels	Eurostat/EU-LFS
O5.2.3	Types and levels of (formal) non-compulsory education attended	PIAAC survey
D4.2	Legislation and practice conditioning (LPC) the acquisition of superior legal status	MIPEX policy indicators
D4.3	LPC access to education	MIPEX policy indicators
D4.8	LPC access to healthcare	MIPEX policy indicators
D3.7.1	Concentration in disadvantaged schools	PISA and TIMSS
D3.2.3	School promotion of parental involvement in school activities, extra-curricular activities and parental associations	Epstein's framework, PISA, collected from IMMERSE principals' survey
D4.15.5	LRR Intercultural education	MIPEX policy indicators
D4.16.1	LRR Preparatory classes	Eurydice 2019
D4.16.2	LRR Educational support for migrant children, particularly learning and language support	MIPEX policy indicators

3.1.2 Meso level data

In the context of IMMERSE WP3, the meso level refers to the schools and non-formal environments in which we will collect data. Data relating to the meso level will be collected from those environments via questionnaires to be filled out by the principal and teachers in the case of schools and by an organisation representative in the case of non-formal environments.

3.1.3 Micro level data

Micro level data will be collected from migrant children and their parents/guardians, along with non-migrant children and parents to establish baselines for comparison. Data collection at the micro level involves questionnaires for parents and children, divided into two groups: children 6-9 years old (and parents/guardians of 6-9 year old children) and children and young people 10-18 years old (and parents/guardians of 10-18 year old children and young people).

We chose to divide the children into two age ranges because of the challenges of collecting data from very young children. The younger age group required a shorter and simpler version of the questionnaire, with some indicator items removed because they were inappropriate or too complex and with some socio-demographic items transferred to their parents'/guardians' questionnaire. The validation workshops for the dashboard indicators during WP1 also demonstrated that the younger

group would likely need more facilitation from the researchers during completion of the questionnaire.

3.2 Data Collection Instruments: Questionnaires

3.2.1 Questionnaire development process

Questionnaire development took place over several months, beginning in October 2019, shortly after the start of the selection process for the dashboard of indicators. The dashboard items would constitute the core of the questionnaire, as the results from these items would ultimately form the basis for the project's policy recommendations. However, the dashboard indicators would need to be supplemented by other items, mainly socio-demographic background variables. The non-dashboard variables would allow us to contextualise the results from the dashboard variables by providing insight into the relevant histories and circumstances of our micro level participants, namely children and parents, and the circumstances of the meso level environments in which integration took place, mainly schools. We employed a collaborative and iterative approach to the construction of the questionnaires, involving a cycle of draft questionnaires, consortium partner feedback, and revision, with UCC leading this process and all research partners participating.

QUESTIONNAIRE DRAFTS, FEEDBACK, AND REVISION

In October 2019, Comillas provided partners with an extensive list of potential non-dashboard variables to include in the questionnaires, alongside the list of 50 potential indicators for the dashboard. Indicators and non-dashboard variables were divided into three lists, and members of all the research partner teams were formed into working groups and assigned a list of dashboard/non-dashboard variables for which to propose survey questions and measures. The indicators and their accompanying proposed measures, as the core items that would form the dashboard, went on to the Delphi expert panel for validation, while UCC and Comillas continued to work with the non-dashboard variables and their proposed measures.

Proposed non-dashboard variables came in several varieties:

- socio-demographic: age, gender, country of birth, religion, etc.
- socio-economic: household income, parental occupation, parental level of education, parental employment status, resources and possessions, cultural capital
- household/family characteristics: housing type, members of household, parental absence, family cohesion, parental involvement with school
- migration: legal status, circumstances of arrival, length of time in country, nationalities held
- education: level of education, academic achievement, previous education experience, barriers to accessing education, education aspirations, absenteeism, repetition of grades, special educational needs
- language: languages spoken, home language, parent language skills
- health: self-assessed physical health, self-assessed mental health, barriers to accessing healthcare
- psycho-social: self-esteem, self-efficacy, resilience, self-identity, cultural dissonance

- school factors: size and type of school, school climate, staffing, resources, resources available for student use, student population characteristics, staff characteristics/diversity, school neighbourhood characteristics

Through November and December 2019, as the dashboard was undergoing the Delphi evaluation and then the meso/macro validation, UCC and Comillas worked together to narrow the list of potential non-dashboard variables. For guidance on the selection of the non-dashboard items to be included in the questionnaire, we looked to a combination of the established research literature on integration and education, our own results from IMMERSE Work Package 1, and other large-scale national and international surveys of children and young people (PISA, HBSC, TIMSS, Growing up in Ireland). We also had to keep practical considerations in mind, such as the length of the questionnaire, capabilities of the younger children, translation to multiple languages, suitability for digital and pen-and-paper (PAP) versions, and coding and analysis of results.

Following the finalisation of the dashboard at the end of February 2020, UCC began to prepare first drafts of the questionnaires including the indicator items and the non-dashboard items. These drafts were in the form of Word documents and formatted in a PAP survey style. Each item was labelled with a comment indicating whether it was a dashboard or non-dashboard item, what it measured, and other relevant notes, e.g. how the item might be analysed later, which items we thought were candidates for dropping if the questionnaire was too long, etc. These drafts were circulated to all research partners for feedback as they were completed (over March and April 2020), starting with the 10-18 year olds questionnaire and its accompanying parent/guardian questionnaire, followed by the principal and teacher questionnaires, and finally the 6-9 year olds questionnaire and its accompanying parent/guardian questionnaire. Partner feedback was returned to UCC who compiled and reviewed all comments and further revised the questionnaires based on these critiques. Few to no changes were made to the indicator items, as these had already been through the Delphi and meso/macro expert validation, so changes were concentrated on the non-dashboard items. The sections below on the micro and meso level questionnaires in more detail.

The revised drafts were circulated to the research partners over April and May 2020 to begin translation into the consortium languages in preparation for programming the questionnaires into the online data collection platform for the piloting phase (see below). A further round of feedback and revisions resulted from the translation process, as we fine-tuned the phrasing and intention of the questions.

Because the project not only takes place in several countries but also will have participants from potentially all over the world, it is important that we attempt to offer as wide a selection of languages as possible to avoid language as a barrier to participation. The questionnaires for principals and teachers will be available in the languages of the consortium. The questionnaires for parents and children will be available in the consortium languages, plus some additional languages, no matter which country the data collection is taking place in. In order to determine which additional languages to offer the questionnaires in, we asked all the research partners which would be the most useful in their context (based on common languages amongst their migrant populations) and chose the

most cited ones. The pilot-ready versions (and the final field versions) will therefore be translated into the following languages:

- English
- Spanish
- Italian
- French
- Dutch
- German
- Greek
- Arabic
- Farsi
- Romanian
- Chinese

PILOTING

The questionnaire items contained in this document are the versions that will be used in the pilot phase. Piloting is critical for any data collection instrument and is particularly recommended for data collection focused on children using surveys (Borgers, Hox, & de Leeuw, 2000); “There’s only one way to know if you’ve got your survey right, and that’s to test it with children” (Office of the Children’s Commissioner, 2015). From September (depending on the public health advice relating to Covid and the readiness of the online data collection platform) all research teams will undertake piloting the surveys in 2 – 3 schools in one of their sampling regions. These will be selected from some of the schools which were engaged in the workshops in WP1 through convenience sampling, schools which will not be engaged in the main study. We will pilot all aspects of the survey including online consents, parents survey, children’s surveys, teachers survey, and principals survey. We will pilot the online surveys with 20 to 30 children and young people across the age ranges (6-9 years and 10-18 years) in each school. While piloting can also be conducted with paper versions, certain aspects such as download time require piloting an electronic version of the parents\children’s survey (Regmi et al., 2016).

Piloting will test the effectiveness of the surveys and address usability and design issues. The aim of piloting will be threefold - to test for clarity of questions, to ensure the survey can be completed in a reasonable timeframe, and to test the online platform. Piloting will be conducted to assess survey design and whether the quantity and quality of questions/statements are satisfactory (Merolli et al., 2014). It will help ensure the adequacy of the questions, appropriate ordering of the questions, comprehensiveness of the contents, the clarity and adequacy of instructions, feasibility of the technology, skipping patterns, data compatibility/ transfer issues, etc. (Regmi et al., 2016). The assessment of usability includes measurement of: attractiveness and aesthetics, suitability and appropriateness of functions, ease of use and user interface design, learnability, technical issues and safety and security of design. A space for feedback will be embedded into the end of the beta version of the survey to allow the pilot participants to comment on any issues they had while filling it out (Merolli et al., 2014).

It is expected that feedback from the pilots will result in another round of revisions to the questionnaires. For all the questionnaires, one of the chief concerns throughout the construction process was length. If the piloting indicates that the questionnaires are too long and take up too much time to fill out, we will need to drop questions to make them shorter. UCC and Comillas, together with IECISA who are responsible for IMMERSE's IT solutions, will work together to compile and review feedback from all the research partners and produce the final field-ready versions.

CHILDREN AND YOUNG PERSONS' ADVISORY GROUP

The Children and Young Persons' Advisory Group (CYPAG) play a critical role in IMMERSE and have been involved in the construction of the children's questionnaires and will play a vital part in the piloting process. The CYPAG was the first group outside of the IMMERSE research partners to validate the micro level children's indicator measures. Six of the older members of CYPAG were invited to comment and offer their opinions on the children's indicators and some of the non-dashboard variables at a meeting on 16th November 2019. The online data collection platform was not yet constructed at this time, so paper versions of the proposed questions were prepared and the indicators and non-dashboard variables were also displayed on a screen for the young people to view. They were asked if they understood the questions, their opinions on their relevance and adequacy, and for any further suggestions. Their feedback was incorporated into the review and revision process of the questionnaires. At this meeting CYPAG members were also updated on the progress that had been made by the IMMERSE project and the development of the questions were contextualized through the work undertaken in WP1 and thereafter in WP3. The CYPAG members were guided through the validation process by members of the IMMERSE research team.

Further piloting of the children's online and paper versions of the survey will be undertaken by members of the CYPAG from September 2020 (depending on the readiness of the online data collection platform). Depending on Covid-19 public health advice, this process will be undertaken at face-to-face meetings or digitally. Every effort will be made to ensure that face-to-face piloting can take place for these members, as it is expected that they will face challenges should the process be only advisable digitally. The importance of ensuring younger members of the CYPAG safety is of primary concern, however, so we will arrange video conference sessions via Skype or Microsoft Teams if necessary. The CYPAG will be asked to comment on the online data collection platform (its ease of use, appearance, any technical issues) and the questionnaires (the dashboard and non-dashboard items, appropriateness, wording, formatting, sequence, etc.). They will have the opportunity to provide more extensive feedback than the school pilots and their comments will be crucial in the final revisions of the data collection instruments.

3.2.2 Micro level questionnaires

We developed four questionnaires for data collection at the micro level: one for children 6-9 years old, one for parents of 6-9 year old children, one for children and young people 10-18 years old, and one for parents of 10-18 year old children and young people.

CHILDREN 6-9 YEARS OLD AND PARENTS/GUARDIANS OF 6-9 YEAR OLDS

Because IMMERSE is committed to prioritising the lived experiences of migrant and refugee children in its study of educational integration, gathering information from children must form the core of our data collection efforts. Based on previous experience of research with young children and examination of other studies involving children, we quickly realised that having a single data collection instrument for all the children in the IMMERSE age range (6-18 years) would not yield optimum results. After discussion between UCC and Comillas and on the advice of the Economic and Social Research Institute (ESRI)⁴, we divided the children into two age groups: 6-9 years old and 10-18 years old. We aimed to collect as much data as possible that would be common to both groups so as to allow for comparison in the later analyses, but we recognised that the instrument for the younger children would need to be simplified in its content and phrasing.

Developing the questionnaire for the younger children proved the greatest challenge of all the questionnaires. As Borgers, Hox, and de Leeuw note, “[a]lthough children are no longer a neglected minority in official statistics and surveys, methodological knowledge on how to survey children is still scarce” (2000, p.60). Indeed, many of the other studies from which we drew guidance, such as PISA and HBSC, did not involve children as young as 6-9 years. Most survey-based studies that do involve children this age, such as the longitudinal Growing Up in Ireland study that our consultants at ESRI conduct, do not collect data directly from the children but from parents, teachers and doctors. As such, we decided to collect some data from the parents but as much data as possible from the children.

The 6-9 year old children’s questionnaire, like all the questionnaires, began with the dashboard indicators as its core. We removed certain dashboard items if we felt they were too complex or abstract for young children, if they asked for information we felt young children would not have, or if they were not applicable to young children’s lives. Of the 15 micro-level dashboard indicator items, we excluded four from the younger children’s questionnaire (the questions can be seen in Table 3):

- O4.1.1 Interconnectedness with friends/peers – friends from different countries
- O4.1.1 Interconnectedness with friends/peers – friends from different cultures
- O2.2.2 Children maintain their culture while adopting key host country values and intercultural competences
- D6.1 Experience/perception of negative attitudes

For the rest of the indicators, if the phrasing was too complex, we used other terms, attempting to make the questions short, limit response options, use simple vocabulary, and keep the questionnaire to a reasonably short length, in line with general advice around creating questionnaires for children (Office of the Children’s Commissioner, 2015). The need to use clear and simple language was emphasised during the indicator validation workshops in December, as the workshops with the youngest groups showed that some of the wording we had used was still

⁴ESRI is a research institute in Dublin, Ireland who are experts in social and economic research and its application to the field of public policy. They have provided and will continue to provide crucial project support and guidance to IMMERSE through consultation with the Irish partners at UCC. For more information on ESRI and to view recent research and publications, see <https://www.esri.ie/>.

too complex. These workshops also indicated that even if wording was simplified, the 6-9 year olds would very likely still need some researcher facilitation in order to be able to fill out the questionnaires. More than any other questionnaire, the piloting of the 6-9 year olds will determine how the data collection is accomplished in the field and will probably result in the greatest amount of revision. See Table 3 and Table 4 for the exact items as they appear in the pilot version of the questionnaires. The second column lists the item wording and the far right column indicates whether the items is included in the younger children's questionnaire and whether it was adapted and how.

In terms of the 32 non-dashboard items, we included 10 of them in the younger children's questionnaire (see Table 3 and 4). There were a greater number of non-dashboard items that we did not think the younger children would be able to answer, but in this case, unlike the indicator items, we had the option of transferring some of them to the parent questionnaire if we felt the information was still important to obtain and would not make the parent questionnaire too long. This was the case for a further 14 of the non-dashboard items. If during piloting, the younger children have difficulty with the length of the questionnaire, candidate items to be dropped all come from the non-dashboard category.

In addition to excluding certain questions and adapting others, the younger children's questionnaire will contain some visual aids in order to assist understanding. There was a great deal of discussion around the use of visual aids, and UCC decided (in consultation with ESRI) that in order to avoid confusion and cultural misinterpretation (given that the study is taking place in six countries and the participants will come from all over the world), visual aids used will largely be simple emojis to represent answer options. An example of this is below, in an item for self-rated happiness:

15. Usually, are you:

- Very happy 😊
- Quite happy 😊
- Not very happy 😞
- Not at all happy 😞

The parent questionnaire for parents of 6-9 year old children was limited to non-dashboard items only, largely important socio-demographic, socio-economic, and migration related information that we did not think we could collect reliably from the children. This included things like household income, parental level of education, parent and child's migration status, schooling before arrival in the host country and barriers to accessing education. The parent questionnaire had to include questions about the spouse/partner/other guardian of the person filling it in (if applicable) and had to be designed for a scenario in which the parent/guardian had multiple children participating in the study. As such, it is the most complicated of the questionnaires.

In order to accommodate concerns from some of the research partners about the length of the parent questionnaire as a barrier to participation (and possibly consent for their children to participate), we developed a shortened version containing only items deemed to be essential. See

Table 5 for a comparison of items contained in the shortened ‘core’ parent questionnaire and the original ‘extended’ parent questionnaire. Each research team can decide whether they want to use the core or extended version of the parent/guardian questionnaire during their data collection. As of July 2020, research partners in Ireland, Greece, Italy, Germany, and Belgium have opted to use the extended parent questionnaire, though this decision can be changed depending on the performance of the questionnaires in the pilot phase or once data collection has begun.

CHILDREN AND YOUNG PEOPLE 10-18 YEARS AND PARENTS/GUARDIANS OF 10-18 YEAR OLDS

The questionnaire for 10-18 year old children and young people could more closely resemble a traditional survey, though we still aimed for simple phrasing and clear, straightforward questions to accommodate the children at the younger end of the age range. The 10-18 year olds questionnaire is longer than the 6-9 year olds and includes all 15 of the indicator items (see Table 3).

For the non-dashboard items, the 10-18 year olds questionnaire includes 22 of the 32 variables we want to collect. We felt that this older group would be able to answer some of the non-dashboard questions that the younger group would not, such as how long they had lived in the host country and whether they went to school before arriving. The remaining ten non-dashboard variables were included in the accompanying parent questionnaire (see Table 4 for full list). These items, such as household income, parental level of education, and parent and child migration status, are critically important for contextualisation, and we felt that this data would be more reliably gathered from the parents. As with the parent/guardian questionnaire for 6-9 year olds, the parent/questionnaire for 10-18 year olds has a ‘core’ version and an ‘extended’ version (see Table 5).

The older children’s questionnaire asks the participants what level of education they are currently in, and one of the answer options is “I am not in any kind of education.” This question and option were included to account for those participants whose data will be collected in a non-formal environment and who are not currently attending school. Data collected during WP1 of IMMERSE indicated that there is often a gap in services for young migrant people who are close to aging out of the school system, so 16-18 year olds, past compulsory school age, and as such they are often not in formal schooling. If this answer option is chosen by the participant, the next four questions, which all ask about school environment, will be skipped. It is not expected that we will need this question/skip pattern for the younger children, because the whole of this group is within the mandatory school age range.

Table 3. Micro Level Questionnaire Items Related to IMMERSE Dashboard Indicators

IMMERSE Dashboard Indicator	Question	Source of question	Included in
O3.1.3 Children’s sense of belonging	How frequently do the following occur to you? 1=almost never, 2=sometimes, 3=almost always I feel like I belong at my school I can really be myself at school I feel like people at my school care about me	Student subjective wellbeing questionnaire (School connectedness subscale)	Children’s questionnaire – 6-9 years Children’s questionnaire – 10-18 years
04.1.2 Interconnectedness/ Teachers	How frequently do the following occur to you? 1=almost never, 2=sometimes, 3=almost always My teachers really try to help me Most of my teachers really listen to what I have to say My teachers stand up for me if someone mistreats me My teachers trust my abilities to continue with my studies	ICCS survey	Children’s questionnaire – 6-9 years <i>**items 3 & 4 adapted**</i> <i>My teachers stand up for me if someone is mean to me</i> <i>My teacher thinks I can do my schoolwork if I try</i> Children’s questionnaire – 10-18 years
D5.6 Supplementary community services for learning/language support – school	Are there services in your school providing learning support for students after school hours (to help them with homework, language learning, etc.)? • Yes, and I do use them • Yes, but I do not use them • No, there is nothing I can afford/access • No, there are no such services at all at my school • I don’t know	Developed by IMMERSE Team	Children’s questionnaire – 6-9 years <i>**adapted**</i> <i>A. Do you take any classes at your school to help you learn new languages (after school finishes)?</i> • Yes, I do take classes. • My school has those, but I don’t take any. • No, my school doesn’t have those. <i>B. Do you take any classes at your school to help with your schoolwork (after school finishes)?</i> • Yes, I do take classes. • My school has those, but I don’t take any. • No, my school doesn’t have those. Children’s questionnaire – 10-18 years

IMMERSE Dashboard Indicator	Question	Source of question	Included in
D3.5.4 Extra-curricular activities available/after-class learning centres – school	Are there after-school activities (such as sports, arts, music, etc.) in your school? • Yes, and I do use them • Yes, but I do not use them • No, there is nothing I can afford/access • No, there are no after-school activities at all at my school • I don't know	Developed by IMMERSE Team	Children's questionnaire – 6-9 years <i>**adapted**</i> <i>Do you take part in any after-school activities in your school (like sports, arts, music)?</i> • Yes, I do take classes. • My school has those, but I don't take any. • No, my school doesn't have those. Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years
O2.1.1 Children's perceived competence in host language	A. You need to ask your teacher for some information in <host country language>. Can you explain yourself? • Almost never • Sometimes • Almost always B. When your teacher gives you some information in <host country language>, can you understand it? • Almost never • Sometimes • Almost always	Developed by IMMERSE team	Children's questionnaire 6-9 years <i>**adapted**</i> A. Speaking <host country language> is • Easy • Okay • Hard B. Understanding <host country language> is • Easy • Okay • Hard Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years
O3.1.2 Children's life satisfaction/ happiness	In general, would you say you are: • Very happy • Quite happy • Not very happy • Not at all happy	Adapted from European Social Survey	Children's questionnaire – 6-9 years Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years
O4.1.1 Interconnectedness with friends/peers	How often do the following happen to you? 1=Almost never, 2=Sometimes, 3=Almost always My friends really try to help me I can talk with my friends about what makes me happy and sad My friends stand up for me if someone mistreats me	Adapted from the Health Behaviour in School-aged Children Survey (HBSC), conducted by the World Health Organization	Children's questionnaire – 6-9 years <i>**item 3 adapted**</i> <i>My friends stand up for me if someone is mean to me</i> Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years

IMMERSE Dashboard Indicator	Question	Source of question	Included in
O4.1.1 Interconnectedness with friends/peers - different country	How many of your friends were born in a different country than you? • All of them • Most of them • A few • None • Don't have any friends	Adapted from the Community Life Survey UK	Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years
O4.1.1 Interconnectedness with friends/peers - different culture	How many of your friends are from a different culture (beliefs, customs, traditions, ways of eating, etc.) than you? • All of them • Most of them • A few • None • Don't have any friends	Adapted from the Community Life Survey UK	Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years
O2.2.2 Children maintain their culture while adopting key host country cultural values and intercultural competences	Do you feel close to the following groups? For each group, check yes or no. People from your neighbourhood People from <city where they live> People from <host country> People working at your school (teachers, etc.) People from the same country as you or your parents (if born outside <host country>) People with your same home language People with your same religion People of your same age People of your same gender People with your same interests and hobbies	Adapted from the Eurobarometer survey	Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years
D5.6 Supplementary community services for learning/ language support – neighbourhood	Are there services in your community/neighbourhood providing learning support for students (to help them with homework, language learning, etc.)? • Yes, and I do use them • Yes, but I do not use them	Developed by IMMERSE team	Children's questionnaire – 6-9 years <i>**adapted**</i> <i>Do you take any classes in your neighbourhood (outside of school) to help you with schoolwork?</i> • Yes, I do take classes.

IMMERSE Dashboard Indicator	Question	Source of question	Included in
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No, there is nothing I can afford/access • No, there are no such services at all in my community/neighbourhood. • I don't know 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>My neighbourhood has those, but I don't take any.</i> • <i>No, my neighbourhood doesn't have those.</i> <p><i>Do you take any classes in your neighbourhood (outside of school) to help you learn new languages?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Yes, I do take classes.</i> • <i>My neighbourhood has those, but I don't take any.</i> • <i>No, my neighbourhood doesn't have those.</i> <p>Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years</p>
<p>D3.5.4 Extra-curricular activities available/ after class learning centres – neighbourhood</p>	<p>Are there after-school activities (such as sports, arts, music, etc.) in your community/neighbourhood?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and I do use them • Yes, but I do use them • No, there is nothing I can afford/access • No, there are no such activities at all in my community/neighbourhood • I don't know 	<p>Developed by IMMERSE team</p>	<p>Children's questionnaire – 6-9 years <i>**adapted**</i></p> <p><i>Do you go to other activities (like sports, arts, music) in your neighbourhood (outside of school)?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Yes, I do go to those.</i> • <i>My neighbourhood has those, but I don't go to any.</i> • <i>No, my neighbourhood doesn't have those.</i> <p>Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years</p>
<p>O4.1.3 Interconnectedness with institutions</p> <p>D6.1 Experience/ perception of negative attitudes</p>	<p>In <host country>, do you trust the following? For each group, answer yes or no</p> <p>Teachers and schools Doctors and hospitals Police & justice system (judges, lawyers, courts, etc.)</p> <p>Do you ever avoid certain places (such as shops, cafes, public transportation, some particular neighbourhood, some places in school) for fear of being treated badly?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • Sometimes • No <p>If answer to above question is yes or sometimes, this follow-up question will appear:</p>	<p>Adapted from the Eurobarometer survey</p> <p>Adapted from EU-MIDAS Survey item</p>	<p>Children's questionnaire – 6-9 years <i>**question adapted**</i></p> <p><i>In <host country>, do you trust these groups? For each group, answer yes or no.</i></p> <p>Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years</p> <p>Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years</p>

IMMERSE Dashboard Indicator	Question	Source of question	Included in
	Is the reason for this related to any of the issues below? Choose all that apply. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Your culture (traditions, customs, dress, etc.) • Your race/ethnicity (i.e. skin colour) • Your religion • Your gender • Your sexual orientation (the gender(s) you are attracted to) • Your age • Your social class • Other 		
D6.2 Experience of harassment and violence (including bullying) outside family	Have you been bullied in <host country> by schoolmates at your school, in your neighbourhood, or online? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No, never • A few times • Many times 	Adapted from HSBC question	Children’s questionnaire – 6-9 years Children’s questionnaire – 10-18 years

Table 4. Micro Level Questionnaire Items Related to Non-dashboard Variables

Non-dashboard variables	Question	Source	Included in
Gender	How would you describe your gender? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Male • Female • In another way • Prefer not to say 	Standard questionnaire item, no specific source	Children’s questionnaire – 6-9 years <i>**adapted**</i> <i>Are you:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boy • Girl Children’s questionnaire – 10-18 years
Date of birth	When were you born? dd/mm/yyyy	Standard questionnaire item, no specific source	Children’s questionnaire – 6-9 years <i>**adapted**</i> <i>How old are you?</i> Children’s questionnaire – 10-18 years

<p>Country of birth</p>	<p>Where were you born?</p> <p>For online questionnaires, there will be a dropdown list of countries. For PAP questionnaires, the top 10 origin countries and 'other' will be listed as options (specific to each IMMERSE partner)</p>	<p>Standard questionnaire item, no specific source</p>	<p>Children's questionnaire – 6-9 years</p> <p>Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years</p> <p>Parent Questionnaire (6-9 years) – core and extended <i>Parent is also asked the country of birth of their spouse/partner/ other guardian</i></p> <p>Parent Questionnaire (10-18 years) – core and extended <i>Parent is also asked the country of birth of their spouse/partner/ other guardian</i></p>
<p>Number of years child has lived in host country</p>	<p>How many years have you lived in <host country>? (If you have lived in <host country> more than once, record only the current instance.) [If answer to country of birth question was <host country>, this question will be skipped.]</p> <p>_____ years</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I don't know 	<p>Developed by IMMERSE team</p>	<p>Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years</p> <p>Parent questionnaire (6-9 years) – core and extended **adapted** <i>How long has [Child 1] lived in <host country>?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Child 1 was born in <host country></i> • _____ years.
<p>Child's nationality (citizenship)</p>	<p>What is [Child]'s nationality (country of citizenship)? If s/he has dual citizenship, please enter both.</p> <p>For online questionnaires, there will be a dropdown list of countries. For PAP questionnaires, the top 10 origin countries and 'other' will be listed as options (specific to each IMMERSE partner)</p>	<p>Developed by IMMERSE team</p>	<p>Parent questionnaire (6-9 years) – extended only</p> <p>Parent questionnaire (10-18 years) – extended only</p>
<p>Parent/guardian nationality (citizenship)</p>	<p>What is your nationality (country of citizenship)? If you have dual citizenship, please enter both.</p> <p>For online questionnaires, there will be a dropdown list of countries. For PAP questionnaires, the top 10 origin countries and 'other' will be listed as options (specific to each IMMERSE partner)</p>	<p>Developed by IMMERSE team</p>	<p>Parent questionnaire (6-9 years) – extended only <i>Parent is also asked the nationality of their partner/spouse/other guardian (if applicable).</i></p> <p>Parent questionnaire (10-18 years) – extended only <i>Parent is also asked the nationality of their partner/spouse/other guardian (if applicable).</i></p>

<p>Child's migration status</p>	<p>What is [Child]'s legal status in <host country>? [If answer to Child's nationality was <host country>, this question will be skipped.]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Temporary permit (up to 5 years) • Permanent permit (5 years or more) • Asylum seeker • Refugee status • Subsidiary protection • Other • Prefer not to say 	<p>Developed by IMMERSE team</p>	<p>Parent Questionnaire (6-9 years) – core and extended</p> <p>Parent Questionnaire (10-18 years) – core and extended</p>
<p>Parents' migration status</p>	<p>What is your legal status in <host country>? [If answer to nationality question was <host country>, this question will be skipped.]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Temporary permit (less than 5 years) • Permanent permit (5 years or more) • Asylum seeker • Refugee status • Subsidiary protection • Other • Prefer not to say 	<p>Developed by IMMERSE team</p>	<p>Parent Questionnaire (6-9 years) – core and extended <i>Parent is also asked the migration status of their partner/spouse/other guardian (if applicable).</i></p> <p>Parent Questionnaire (10-18 years) – core and extended <i>Parent is also asked the migration status of their partner/spouse/other guardian (if applicable).</i></p>
<p>Household size</p>	<p>How many people currently live with you? Do not include yourself.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 • 2 • 3 • 4 • 5 • 6 • 7 • 8+ 	<p>Developed by IMMERSE team</p>	<p>Children's questionnaire – 6-9 years</p> <p>Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years</p>

Housing situation	Where do you and your family (including the child(ren) participating in the survey) currently live? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In an owned house or apartment • In a rented house or apartment • In temporary state-provided housing for asylum seekers • In a refugee camp • In a shelter • Other 	Developed by IMMERSE team	Parent Questionnaire (6-9 years) – core and extended Parent Questionnaire (10-18 years) – core and extended
Members of household	Who are the people who live with you? Choose all that apply. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mother(s) • Father(s) • Brother(s) and/or sister(s) • Grandparent(s) • Uncle(s) or aunt(s) • Cousin(s) • Foster parent(s) • Social worker(s) • Friend(s) • Other(s) 	Developed by IMMERSE team	Children’s questionnaire – 6-9 years Children’s questionnaire – 10-18 years
Family cohesion scale	Please read the following 5 statements and indicate whether you agree that the statement describes you: 1=always or almost always, 2=sometimes, 3=never or almost never When something is bothering or troubling me, I can turn to my family for help I like the way my family talks things over and shares problems with me I like how my family lets me try new things I want to do I like what my family does when I feel angry, sad, happy or loving I like the way my family and I share time together My family has serious arguments	Adapted from The CHAMPSEA Project (funded by the Wellcome Trust, UK) Older Child Questionnaire (for Children Aged 9 to 11), 2008 ⁵	Children’s questionnaire – 10-18 years

⁵ Source [<https://ari.nus.edu.sg/clusters/asian-migration/projects/champsea-home/>]. For further detail consult Graham, E. and B.S.A. Yeoh (2013) Introduction: Child Health and Migrant Parents in South-East Asia: Risk and Resilience among Primary School-Aged Children. *Asian and Pacific Migration Journal*, 22(3): 297-314.

Parent highest level of education	What is the highest level of education you have completed? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I did not complete <ISCED 1> • <ISCED 1> • <ISCED 2> • <ISCED 3> • <ISCED 4/5> • <ISCED 6/7/8> • I don't know 	Developed by IMMERSE team	<p>Parent Questionnaire (6-9 years) – core and extended <i>Parent is also asked highest level of education of spouse/partner/other guardian, if applicable.</i></p> <p>Parent Questionnaire (10-18 years) – core and extended <i>Parent is also asked highest level of education of spouse/partner/other guardian, if applicable.</i></p>
Parent employment status	Which of the following best describes your current situation with regard to work? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employed full-time • Employed part-time • Self-employed • Take care of home/children • Full-time student • Unemployed • On long-term sickness or disability • Not entitled to work • Retired • Other 	Developed by IMMERSE team	<p>Parent Questionnaire (6-9 years) – core and extended <i>Parent is also asked employment status of spouse/partner/other guardian, if applicable.</i></p> <p>Parent Questionnaire (10-18 years) – core and extended <i>Parent is also asked employment status of spouse/partner/other guardian, if applicable.</i></p>
Household income	What was your approximate total household income over the past 12 months? Please include all sources of income. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less than €10,000 • €10,000 – 19,999 • €20,000 – 39,999 • €40,000 – 59,999 • €60,000 – 79,999 • €80,000 – 99,999 • €100,000 – 119,999 • €120,000 or more • I don't know • Prefer not to say 	Developed by IMMERSE team	<p>Parent Questionnaire (6-9 years) – core and extended</p> <p>Parent Questionnaire (10-18 years) – core and extended</p>

<p>Household domestic resources - technology</p>	<p>How many of these are in your home? If you are not sure what the item is, choose '0'. [Answer options are 0 1 2 3+] Televisions Cars Rooms with bath or shower Mobile phones with internet access Computers (e.g. desktops, laptops) Tablets (e.g. iPads®, Galaxy Tab®) e-book readers (e.g. Kindle®, Kobo®) musical instruments (e.g. guitar, piano)</p>	<p>Adapted from PISA item</p>	<p>Children's questionnaire – 6-9 years Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years</p>
<p>Household domestic resources - cultural capital</p>	<p>Which of the following are available where you live? [Answer options are yes or no] A desk to study at A room of your own A quiet place to study A computer you can use for school work A link to the internet Classic literature Books to help with school work Technical reference books A dictionary Books on art, music or design</p>	<p>Adapted from PISA item</p>	<p>Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years</p>
<p>Household domestic resources - books</p>	<p>How many books are there where you live? Do not include magazines, newspapers, or your schoolbooks. • 0-100 books • 101-200 books • 201-500 books • 500+ books</p>	<p>Adapted from PISA item</p>	<p>Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years</p>
<p>Child's religion</p>	<p>Do you belong to any religious group? • Yes • No • Don't know • Prefer not to say</p>	<p>Growing up in Ireland</p>	<p>Children's questionnaire 6-9 years **question adapted** <i>Do you have a religion?</i> Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years</p>

	<p>If answer to previous question was yes, this follow-up question will appear.</p> <p>What religious group do you belong to?</p> <p>For online questionnaires, there will be a dropdown list of religions. For PAP questionnaires, the top 5-6 religions and 'other' will be listed as options (specific to each IMMERSE partner)</p>		
Child's religiosity	<p>In general, would you describe yourself as a religious person? 0=not at all, 5=very much so</p> <p>0 1 2 3 4 5</p>	Growing up in Ireland	Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years
Child's schooling before living in host country	<p>Did you attend school before arriving in <host country>? [If participant was born in <host country>, this question will be skipped.]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • Don't know 	Developed by IMMERSE team	<p>Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years</p> <p>Parent Questionnaire (6-9 years) – extended only **adapted** <i>Did [Child] attend school before s/he came to <host country>?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • Don't know
Child's number of years education before living in host country	<p>How many years did you attend school before arriving in <host country>?</p> <p>_____ years</p>	Developed by IMMERSE team	<p>Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years</p> <p>Parent Questionnaire (6-9 years) – extended only **adapted** <i>How many years did child attend school before arriving in <host country>? _____ years</i></p>
Child's school absences	<p>Have you ever been taken out of school for six months or more (not including Covid-19 situation of 2020)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • Don't know 	Developed by IMMERSE team	<p>Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years</p> <p>Parent Questionnaire (6-9 years) – extended only **adapted** <i>After Child 1 started school, was s/he ever taken out of school for six months or more (not including Covid-19 situation of 2020)?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • Don't know

<p>Child's access to school - meso/macro barriers</p>	<p>Have you ever been prevented from going to school in <host country> for any of the following reasons? Tick as many as apply.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There were no places at school available • The school was far away, and I had no way to get there • I could not afford to go to school • I did not know how to register for school • I did not speak the school's language • It was not safe to go to school • I was in transit waiting for relocation • Other • I have never been prevented from going to school in <host country>. 	<p>Developed by IMMERSE team</p>	<p>Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years</p> <p>Parent Questionnaire (6-9 years) – extended only <i>**adapted**</i> <i>Has [Child] ever been prevented from going to school in <host country> for any of the following reasons? Tick all that apply.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>There were no places at school available</i> • <i>The school was far away, and s/he had no way to get there</i> • <i>We could not afford to send him/her to school</i> • <i>We did not know how to register him/her at school</i> • <i>S/he did not speak the school's language</i> • <i>It was not safe to go to school</i> • <i>S/he was in transit waiting for relocation</i> • <i>Other</i> • <i>S/he has never been prevented from going to school in <host country>.</i>
<p>Child's access to school – micro barriers</p>	<p>Do any of the following reasons keep you from going to school now?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Helping with household chores like cooking, cleaning, laundry • Helping take care of younger brothers/sisters/children • Helping an elderly or sick relative • Working for a family farm or business • Working outside my home for wages (not for a family farm or business) • Lack of transport • School is not useful to me • Other • None of these has ever kept me from going to school 	<p>Developed by IMMERSE team</p>	<p>Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years</p>
<p>Child's current level of education</p>	<p>What level of school are you currently in?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <ISCED 1> • <ISCED 2> • <ISCED 3> • I take course/classes, but not in a regular secondary school (e.g. <country specific examples>) • I am not in any kind of education right now. 	<p>Developed by IMMERSE team</p>	<p>Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years</p>

<p>Child's educational aspirations</p>	<p>What is the highest level of education you expect to complete?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <ISCED 1> • <ISCED 2> • <ISCED 3> • <ISCED 4/5> • <ISCED 6/7/8> • I don't know 	<p>Adapted from ICCS</p>	<p>Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years</p>
<p>Parental involvement in school</p>	<p>During the last school year (2019/2020), have you participated in any of the following school-related activities? Tick all that apply.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parent-teacher meeting • Local school government (e.g. parent council or school management committee) • Information sessions for parents • Volunteer in physical or after-school activities (e.g. sports, field trip, school play, maintenance) • Volunteer to support daily school activities (e.g. in the school library, canteen, assisted a teacher) • Social activities for parents/families (e.g. coffee morning, cultural or religious events, open house night) • Attend school events in which your child(ren) participated (e.g. sports matches, school plays, concerts) <p>During the last school year (2019/20), has your participation in activities at your child's school been hindered by any of the following issues? For each item, tick yes or no.</p> <p>The meeting times were inconvenient I was not able to get time off work I had no one to take care of my child/children The way to school is unsafe I had problems with transport I felt unwelcome at my child's school I feel generally awkward in a school My <host language> is not very good</p>	<p>Adapted from PISA items</p>	<p>Parent Questionnaire (6-9 years) – extended only</p> <p>Parent Questionnaire (10-18 years) – extended only</p>

	<p>I think participation is not relevant for my child's development</p> <p>I do not know how I could participate in school activities</p> <p>My child(ren) do(es) not want me to participate</p> <p>The school does not provide opportunities to participate</p>		
Number of languages child speaks	How many languages do you speak?	Developed by IMMERSE team	<p>Children's questionnaire – 6-9 years</p> <p>Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years</p>
Child's home language	<p>Of the languages you speak, which would you consider your home language?</p> <p>For online questionnaires, there will be a dropdown list of languages. For PAP questionnaires, the top 10 languages and 'other' will be listed as options (specific to each IMMERSE partner)</p>	Developed by IMMERSE team	<p>Children's questionnaire – 6-9 years <i>**adapted**</i> <i>What language do you speak most of the time at home?</i></p> <p>Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years</p>
Self-rated physical health	<p>Would you say your physical health is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Excellent • Good • Fair • Poor 	Adapted from HBSC Survey item	<p>Children's questionnaire – 6-9 years <i>**question adapted**</i> <i>Would you say your health is:</i></p> <p>Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years</p>
Self-rated mental health	<p>Would you say your mental health is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Excellent • Good • Fair • Poor 	Adapted from HBSC Survey item	Children's questionnaire – 10-18 years

Table 5. Parent Questionnaires 'Core' vs 'Extended'

Parent questionnaire variables	Parent FULL (6-9)	Parent CORE (6-9)	Parent FULL (10-18)	Parent CORE (10-18)
SECTION A: PARENT AND PARTNER/SPOUSE				
Parent 1 country of birth	✓	✓	✓	✓
Parent 2 country of birth	✓	✓	✓	✓
Parent 1 country(ies) of citizenship	✓		✓	

Parent questionnaire variables	Parent FULL (6-9)	Parent CORE (6-9)	Parent FULL (10-18)	Parent CORE (10-18)
Parent 1 legal status	✓	✓ ('citizen' option added)	✓	✓ ('citizen' option added)
Parent 2 country(ies) of citizenship	✓		✓	
Parent 2 legal status	✓	✓ ('citizen' option added)	✓	✓ ('citizen' option added)
Parent 1 highest level of education	✓	✓	✓	✓
Parent 2 highest level of education	✓	✓	✓	✓
Housing situation	✓	✓	✓	✓
Parent 1 employment status	✓	✓	✓	✓
Parent 2 employment status	✓	✓	✓	✓
Total household income	✓	✓	✓	✓
Parent participation in school life	✓		✓	
Parent participation in school life - follow up (barriers)	✓		✓	
SECTION B: CHILD(REN)				
Child 1 country(ies) of citizenship	✓		✓	
Child 1 legal status	✓	✓ ('citizen' option added)	✓	✓ ('citizen' option added)
Child 1 length of time in host country	✓	✓	<i>on child's questionnaire</i>	<i>on child's questionnaire</i>
Child 1 schooling before arrival in host country	✓		<i>on child's questionnaire</i>	<i>on child's questionnaire</i>
Child 1 # years schooling before arrival in host country	✓		<i>on child's questionnaire</i>	<i>on child's questionnaire</i>
Child 1 extended absences from school	✓		<i>on child's questionnaire</i>	<i>on child's questionnaire</i>
Child 1 access to education - meso/macro barriers	✓		<i>on child's questionnaire</i>	<i>on child's questionnaire</i>
Repeat for Child 2				
Repeat for Child 3				

3.2.3 Meso level questionnaires

We developed two questionnaires for data collection at the meso level: one for school principals or staff representatives of non-formal environments and one for teachers in schools. The questionnaire for principals/staff representatives was the most critical, as these gather data not only on the meso level indicators in the dashboard, but also demographic (as it were) data on the schools.

PRINCIPAL/STAFF REPRESENTATIVE QUESTIONNAIRE

The principal/staff representative questionnaire is needed to gather information about the school or non-formal environment in which data collection with children and young people is taking place. In order to do analysis using the school/environment as the unit of analysis, we need information regarding funding, management, staffing and resources, student population, etc.

The questionnaire contains six indicator items that come from the meso level of the dashboard and 23 non-dashboard items. The indicator items look at supports for migrants and integration in curriculum and values of the institution. The non-dashboard items include a few items about the participant her/himself, such as age, country of birth, and length of professional service. The majority of the non-dashboard items, however, ask about the school/environment, gathering key contextual information such as funding sources, management structure, staffing (teaching and administrative), resources, and student population vital stats and characteristics. See Tables 6 and 7 for the list of indicator and non-dashboard items that are included in the principals' questionnaire.

TEACHER QUESTIONNAIRE

The teachers' questionnaire gathers information about the teacher's training and classroom practices. As it does not need to collect data on the school itself (this is collected in the principals' questionnaire), it is much shorter. It contains two indicator items and 12 non-dashboard items. Like the principals' questionnaire, it includes non-dashboard items relating to the participant her/himself. The other non-dashboard items ask about classroom practices, teacher training, and an attitudinal question about migrants.

The principal and teacher questionnaires will be available in the languages of the consortium:

- English
- Spanish
- Italian
- French
- Dutch
- German
- Greek

Table 6. Meso Level Questionnaire Items Related to IMMERSE Dashboard Indicators

IMMERSE Dashboard Indicator	Question	Source of question	Included in
D3.2.1 Clear leadership and school identity around intercultural values (against xenophobia, prejudice, and stereotypes)	<p>How important are the following aspects for this school (consider how it is presented to parents who approach the school for the first time)? For each item, 1=not very important, 2=somewhat important, 3=very important, 4=this is one of our insignias</p> <p>Educational excellence and/or students' results Educational innovation Intercultural values (e.g. appreciation of diversity, cultural awareness, openness and tolerance) Other types of ethical values (e.g. religious, civic)</p>	Developed by IMMERSE team	<p>Teacher questionnaire</p> <p>Principal questionnaire</p>
D3.4.5 Intercultural competence as part of syllabus or/and transversally – school curriculum	<p>Does the school curriculum include the following topics? For each item, yes or no.</p> <p>Communicating with people from different cultures or countries Knowledge of different cultures Knowledge of different religions Respect for cultural diversity Recognizing cultural prejudice and stereotypes</p>	PISA survey	Principal questionnaire
D3.4.5 Intercultural competence as part of syllabus or/and transversally – in the classroom	<p>In your lessons, do you usually include opportunities to promote the following skills? For each item, yes or no.</p> <p>Communicating with people from different cultures or countries Knowledge of different cultures Knowledge of different religions Respect for cultural diversity Recognizing cultural prejudice and stereotypes</p>	PISA survey	Teacher questionnaire

<p>D3.6.2 Counselling services at school</p>	<p>How many staff does your school currently have in the following capacities? Please note this refers to staff hired specifically to conduct these tasks, which usually require some specific training. For each item, please list the number of full-time and part-time staff. If you have staff who fill multiple roles, please count them only once.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language support teachers (to support students in gaining fluency in school's language of instruction) # full-time___ # part-time___ • Learning support teachers (excl. for language) # full-time___ # part-time___ • Psycho-social support/personal counselling # full-time___ # part-time___ • Academic counselling/guidance # full-time___ # part-time___ • Integration/cultural mediators # full-time___ # part-time___ 	<p>Developed by IMMERSE team</p>	<p>Principal questionnaire</p>
<p>D4.16.1 LRR Preparatory classes – regional/national</p>	<p>Are there provisions or recommendations at the regional or national level to offer preparatory classes for newly arrived migrant students?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, at national level. • Yes, at regional level. • Yes, at both national and regional levels. • No • I don't know 	<p>Eurydice 2019</p>	<p>Principal questionnaire</p>
<p>D4.16.1 LRR Preparatory classes – in this school</p>	<p>Does this school offer preparatory classes for newly arrived migrant students?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No 	<p>Eurydice 2019</p>	<p>Principal questionnaire</p>
<p>D3.2.3 – School promotion of parental involvement in school activities, extra-curricular activities and parental associations</p>	<p>Does your school provide the following to students' parents?</p> <p>For each item, 1=no, 2=yes, generally for all parents, 3=yes, adapted for parents' needs (e.g. language, culture, etc.)</p> <p>Information on child's progress</p> <p>Requests and ideas to help students at home with homework</p> <p>Requests to volunteer and participate in school-related activities</p> <p>Channels to participate in decision-making</p>	<p>Self-elaboration based on Epstein's framework and PISA</p>	<p>Principal questionnaire</p>

Table 7. Meso Level Questionnaire Items Related to Non-dashboard Variables

Non-dashboard Data	Question	Source of question	Included in
Gender of teacher	How would you describe your gender? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Male • Female • In another way • Prefer not to say 	Developed by IMMERSE team	Principal questionnaire Teacher questionnaire
Age of teacher	What is your age?	Standard item, no specific source	Principal questionnaire Teacher questionnaire
Country of birth	Where were you born? For online questionnaires, there will be a dropdown list of countries. For PAP questionnaires, the top 10 origin countries and 'other' will be listed as options (specific to each IMMERSE partner)	Developed by IMMERSE team	Principal questionnaire Teacher questionnaire
Time in role at school	How many years have you been a principal [teacher] at this school? (Please exclude any significant interruptions, i.e. 1 year or more.) _____ years	Developed by IMMERSE team	Principal questionnaire Teacher questionnaire
Length of professional service	How many years have you been a professional educator (in any role)? (Please exclude any significant interruptions, i.e. 1 year or more.) _____ years	Developed by IMMERSE team	Principal questionnaire Teacher questionnaire
FT/PT status	What is your current employment status as a teacher? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full-time (more than 90% of full-time hours) • Part-time (50-90% of full-time hours) • Part-time (less than 50% of full-time hours) 	Adapted from PISA	Teacher questionnaire
Temporary/permanent employment status	Is your current position permanent or temporary (i.e. on a limited contract)? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Permanent • Temporary 	Developed by IMMERSE team	Teacher questionnaire

<p>Subject area taught</p>	<p>If you focus on teaching a specific subject, which subject do you teach?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do not teach a specific subject • Mathematics • History • <host country> language • Foreign languages • Religious education • Geography • Natural sciences • Civics education • Arts education (visual arts, music, drama) • Physical education • Literacy/literature • Other 	<p>Developed by IMMERSE team</p>	<p>Teacher questionnaire</p>
<p>Intercultural competence as part of teacher training</p>	<p>Do the following statements reflect your education and training as a teacher? [Answer options are yes or no]</p> <p>I have received training on intercultural communication</p> <p>I have received training on conflict resolution strategies</p> <p>I have received training on the role education can play in confronting discrimination in all its forms</p> <p>I have studied culturally-responsive teaching approaches and techniques</p> <p>I have received training on issues related to teaching in multi-cultural classrooms.</p>	<p>PISA</p>	<p>Teacher questionnaire</p>

<p>Teacher confidence in coping with multicultural classroom</p>	<p>How do you judge your own competence to teach in a class with a high degree of cultural and ethnic diversity? 1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=agree, 4=strongly agree</p> <p>I can cope with the challenges of a multicultural classroom I can adapt my teaching to the cultural diversity of the students I can take care that students with and without migrant backgrounds work together I can raise awareness of cultural differences amongst the students I can contribute to reducing ethnic stereotypes between the students</p>	<p>PISA</p>	<p>Teacher questionnaire</p>
<p>Teacher attitudes toward intercultural competences</p>	<p>To what extent do the following statements reflect an opinion shared by the teachers of your school? 1=shared among none or almost none of the teachers, 2=shared among some of the teachers, 3=shared among many of the teachers, 4=shared among all or almost all of the teachers.</p> <p>It is important for students to learn that people from other cultures can have different values Respecting other cultures is something that students should learn as early as possible In the classroom, it is important that students of different origins recognize the similarities that exist between them When there are conflicts between students of different origins, they should be encouraged to resolve the argument by finding common ground</p>	<p>PISA</p>	<p>Principal questionnaire</p> <p>Teacher questionnaire</p>

<p>Teachers' attitudes towards immigrants</p>	<p>People are increasingly moving from one country to another. How much do you agree with the following statements about migrants? 1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=agree, 4=strongly agree</p> <p>Migrant children should have the same opportunities for education that other children in the country have Migrants who live in a country for several years should have the opportunity to vote in elections Migrants should have the opportunity to continue their own customs and lifestyle Migrants should have all the same rights that everyone else in the country has</p>	<p>PISA</p>	<p>Principal questionnaire</p> <p>Teacher questionnaire</p>
<p>School level</p>	<p>What education level is your school?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Primary • Secondary • Combined primary and secondary 	<p>Developed by IMMERSE team</p>	<p>Principal questionnaire</p>
<p>School funding</p>	<p>About what percentage of your total funding for a typical school year comes from the following sources? Please enter "0" if there are none.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government (includes departments, local, regional, state, national, European) _____ • Student fees or school charges paid by parents _____ • Benefactors, donations, bequests, sponsorships, parent fundraising _____ • Other _____ 	<p>Adapted from PISA</p>	<p>Principal questionnaire</p>
<p>School management</p>	<p>How is your school managed?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By a public education authority, government agency, or governing board appointed by government or elected by public franchise • By a non-government organisation, e.g. a church, trade union, NGO, charity, or other private institution 	<p>Adapted from PISA</p>	<p>Principal questionnaire</p>

<p>Religious affiliation</p>	<p>Is the school affiliated with a religious institution in any of the following ways? Choose all that apply.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, through funding • Yes, through management • Yes, through religious practices in school life, e.g. prayers, services, observance of religious rites/rituals/holy days, etc. • Yes, through faith formation education (classes intended to develop a particular faith, as opposed to classes to educate about religion more generally) • No, the school does not have a religious affiliation 	<p>Developed by IMMERSE team</p>	<p>Principal questionnaire</p>
<p>Type of religious affiliation</p>	<p>To what religion is it affiliated? [If the answer to the previous question is no, this question will be skipped.]</p> <p>For online questionnaires, there will be a dropdown list of religions. For PAP questionnaires, the top 5-6 religions and 'other' will be listed as options (specific to each IMMERSE partner)</p>	<p>Developed by IMMERSE team</p>	<p>Principal questionnaire</p>
<p>Staffing resources (teachers)</p>	<p>How many full-time/part-time and temporary/permanent <u>teachers</u> work at this school?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full-time, permanent _____ • Full-time, temporary _____ • Part-time, permanent _____ • Part-time, temporary _____ 	<p>Adapted from Growing Up in Ireland</p>	<p>Principal questionnaire</p>
<p>Staffing resources (administrative staff)</p>	<p>How many full-time/part-time and temporary/permanent <u>administrative staff</u> work at this school (excluding yourself)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full-time, permanent _____ • Full-time, temporary _____ • Part-time, permanent _____ • Part-time, temporary _____ 	<p>Adapted from Growing Up in Ireland</p>	<p>Principal questionnaire</p>
<p>Diversity of staff (teachers)</p>	<p>How many members of the teaching staff at this school are foreign born or from an ethnic/racial minority? If exact number is not known, an estimate is enough.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foreign born _____ • Ethnic/racial minority _____ • Don't know 	<p>Developed by IMMERSE team</p>	<p>Principal questionnaire</p>

<p>Diversity of staff (admin/support)</p>	<p>How many members of the administrative/support staff at this school are foreign born or from an ethnic/racial minority? If exact number is not known, an estimate is enough.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foreign-born _____ • Ethnic/racial minority _____ • Don't know 	<p>Developed by IMMERSE team</p>	<p>Principal questionnaire</p>
<p>Staff languages spoken (teachers)</p>	<p>How many members of the teaching staff at this school can speak a language other than <host country languages (if more than one official)>? If exact number is not known, an estimate is enough.</p> <p>_____</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Don't know 	<p>Developed by IMMERSE team</p>	<p>Principal questionnaire</p>
<p>Staff languages spoken (administrative and support staff)</p>	<p>How many members of the administrative/support staff at this school can speak a language other than <host country languages (if more than one official)>? If exact number is not known, an estimate is enough.</p> <p>_____</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Don't know 	<p>Developed by IMMERSE team</p>	<p>Principal questionnaire</p>
<p>Resources - technology available for pupil use</p>	<p>Approximately how many of the following are available in the school for student use (i.e. excluding those used solely by administrative or teaching staff)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computers (without internet connection)_____ • Computers (with stable internet connection)_____ • Tablets_____ • Interactive whiteboards/smart boards _____ • Reading rooms or libraries _____ 	<p>Adapted from Growing Up in Ireland</p>	<p>Principal questionnaire</p>

# of pupils, gender breakdown	How many pupils are there at your school? _____ boys _____ girls _____ total	Growing Up in Ireland	Principal questionnaire <i>For schools that combine primary and secondary, principals will be asked to report on these levels separately in this question.</i>
# of classes	How many classes (across all year groups) are there in the school?	Growing Up in Ireland	Principal questionnaire <i>For schools that combine primary and secondary, principals will be asked to report on these levels separately in this question</i>
Average class size	What is the average class size in your school? _____ students/class	Developed by IMMERSE team	Principal questionnaire <i>For schools that combine primary and secondary, principals will be asked to report on these levels separately in this question</i>
Pupils in minority groups	Approximately how many of each of the following groups of pupils do you have in your school? If none, please write '0' – do not leave blank. The same child can be recorded more than once. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students with migrant background (i.e. foreign-born or has at least one parent who is foreign-born) _____ • Newly arrived migrants (within the last 12 months) • Pupils with language difficulties (where native language is other than <host country language(s)> _____ • Pupils with physical/sensory disabilities _____ • Pupils with learning/intellectual difficulties _____ • Pupils from socioeconomically disadvantaged backgrounds 	Adapted from Growing Up in Ireland	Principal questionnaire

4 Large-scale Quantitative Data Collection: Sampling Strategy

Another critical way in which the IMMERSE project will achieve harmonisation across data collection is through a common approach to sampling. Sampling takes place at a number of levels: regional, school/non-formal environment, and classroom. The sampling strategy developed had to provide a clear framework that would ensure the credibility of the data collection and result in data that was comparable cross-nationally, but it also had to have enough flexibility to be adapted to the specificities of each of the partner countries. Decisions around sampling were guided by the work package leaders but were ultimately made by each research partner based on the needs of the project and country context, taking into consideration intellectual and theoretical concerns along with practical and logistical limitations. In this section, we will describe the general sampling strategy as developed by UCC, in consultation with the ESRI. The country-specific adaptations developed by each of the research partners for their own country context appear as Appendices A-F.

4.1 Regional Sampling

Region selection was guided by coverage of relevant variability within each country as far as was possible and practical. In July 2019, we asked the research partners to begin developing their plans for sampling, starting with the regions in which they intended to collect data and what axes of variability these covered, e.g. urban/rural, low/high SES, low/high proportion of migrants, etc. Based on feedback from the sample planning sheets completed by the partners, most research teams were working within a context where migrants were not evenly distributed throughout the country. Regional sampling therefore usually concentrated on those areas where data collection would yield a high enough number of participants to reach quotas agreed on in the original proposal (see Table 8 next page), while still attempting to capture important dimensions of variability. Feedback indicated that the regions sampled would be able to cover a range of socio-economic statuses (SES), though for some teams, the areas where migrant populations were concentrated tended to be in the medium to low end of the SES range.

We asked each research partner to develop regional profiles for the areas in which they would collect data and provide a rationale for including these areas. The region profiles contained key information related to the following:

- Boundaries: the geographic area to be sampled, useful to consult established boundary markers like municipal or electoral districts
- Population demographics for the defined area: total population, SES distribution, age distribution, racial/ethnic profile, level of education
- Characteristics of migrant population: proportion of population, countries of origin, how recently arrived, SES, level of education

- Schools of the region: number of schools, school types, geographic distribution, number of students, student characteristics (if data is available)

Partners were also asked to note what, if any, areas of the country would not be included, why, and what limitations this might place on the resulting data.

4.2 School Sampling

School sampling, like regional sampling, was to cover as much variability as was possible and practical. Again, based on the feedback from the sample planning sheets, an entirely randomised approach did not appear to be appropriate for most of the research teams, because we had a specific target population that was not evenly distributed. Instead, as recommended by the ESRI, we employed a *stratified random sampling technique*, which involved dividing your population into groups or strata that represent important dimensions of variability, and randomly selecting participants from within each group (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2007).

4.2.1 Theoretical 'ideal' sampling framework

The ESRI worked with UCC to develop a theoretical 'ideal' sampling framework based on the stratified random approach to be used as a starting point for each team to create a sampling pool of schools in their country. In this ideal framework, each team was to compile a list of schools in the selected regions, preferably using official data provided by a government body in charge of education or data provided by the schools themselves. Using this data, schools were to be grouped according to key characteristics that represented important sources of variability between schools in that country's context and important sources of variability in the context of the IMMERSE project. Schools would then be randomly chosen from each group to contact for participation, the number of schools depending on the number of participants from which the team was expected to collect data.

Table 8. Number of Schools/Centres and Migrant and Refugee Children per Country⁶

	BEL	GER	GRE	IRE	ITA	SPA
SCHOOLS/ CENTRES	20	70	60	30	60	90
CHILDREN	800	3,000	2,400	800	3,280	3,600

The critical part of the framework was the data available that allows grouping by key characteristics. These characteristics should reflect what was relevant for the country/region and for IMMERSE. These might have included:

⁶Note that the number of children here refers to the total number of migrant and refugee children from which data is to be collected. In reality, because we are using a whole-classroom sampling strategy within schools, we will also be collecting data from non-migrant students, resulting in a higher overall number of children in the final dataset.

- **size of school** (number of students): raw number of students preferably, but could also be grouped into categories (such as small/medium/large) for the purposes of the sampling, if all schools in the region were approximately the same size, then you would not need to include this as a variable
- **socio-economic status measure:** consistent measure across schools⁷ reflecting the SES of the student population or, failing that, the neighbourhood/district the school is in
- **proportion of migrant students:** number and proportion of students who fit our target definition of migrant student (either foreign-born or at least one foreign-born parent)
- **geographic location:** urban/rural, or if the team was concentrating on urban areas, they may have decided to include a location variable differentiating between urban/suburban (define what these categories mean) if that difference was significant in their context
- **country/region-specific characteristics:** other characteristics that were important sources of variability for the schools of the country or selected region, for example, religious denomination, academic/vocational, fee paying/non-fee paying

Each key school characteristic included in the sampling framework needed to be accompanied by a brief definition and explanation of how it was measured. We recommended using 3-5 characteristics; the more characteristics that are used, the more groups result, and the more complicated and unwieldy the framework becomes, so it was best to limit the choice to those that are necessary.

Using these variables, categories of schools were created. For example, if a team were to use size of school (big/small), location (rural/urban), and migrant concentration (low/high), this resulted in eight categories:

big/rural/low migrant concentration
big/rural/high migrant concentration
big/urban/low migrant concentration
big/urban/high migrant concentration
small/rural/low migrant concentration
small/rural/high migrant concentration
small/urban/low migrant concentration
small/urban/high migrant concentration

Using the available data, these categories were populated with the schools that fit the criteria, then schools were randomly selected from each category. At this stage, the teams would likely find that, in reality, not all categories would necessarily be viable, and therefore it would take a bit of time to go through the data available to refine the categories to cover the appropriate

⁷ Though we will not be able to have a consistent measure across all countries.

variability for their location and the number of participating schools they needed. Once the schools were sorted, random selection could be done by assigning a number to each of the schools in the list, then using a random number generator to select the schools.

The number of schools selected from each category would depend on how many schools the partner needed to participate. UCC, as WP3 leaders, recommended aiming for about 30-50 migrant children surveyed per school (covering various age groups) in order to have sufficient numbers for statistical analysis of school effects. In the initial random selection, we recommended overshooting the number needed, because not all schools selected will choose to participate.

Each partner was responsible for adapting this framework and designing and carrying out their school selection. These country-specific adaptations are documented in Appendices A-F.

4.2.2 School sampling Plan B

There was understandably concern amongst the partners about access to schools and reaching participant quotas. In the event that the stratified random sampling strategy yields poor response rates from schools, we have developed a back-up sampling plan that aims to maximise the potential for positive responses through the use of the partners' knowledge of schools, contacts, and networks. The back-up strategy will therefore be a combination of *purposive sampling* and *snowball sampling*.

Purposive sampling is a type of non-probability sampling in which the researcher makes deliberate choices about who to include in the sample, based on the nature of the research question and whether the characteristics of participants will yield data that will allow the research question to be answered; "Simply put, the researcher decides what needs to be known and sets out to find people who can and are willing to provide the information by virtue of knowledge or experience" (Etikan, Musa, & Alkassim, 2016, p.2).

There are different types of purposive sampling, and we propose to use *maximum variation sampling*. This, "involves selecting candidates from across a broad spectrum relating to the topic of the study" (Etikan, Musa, & Alkassim, 2016, p.3) in order to cover as much variability as possible. Because each team will have constructed a sampling framework dividing schools into different categories, the variability to be covered is already known. Instead of randomly selecting schools from each category, however, the researchers will purposely select schools factoring in practical concerns and knowledge, like accessibility and willingness to participate. At this stage, we believe it will also be justifiable to use *snowball sampling*, in which current participants recommend possible future participants, a technique commonly used when collecting data from populations that are difficult to access.

4.3 Classroom Sampling

Once a school has agreed to participate, teams will need to select the children in the school that will complete the survey. We have decided to go with a census-type approach and survey whole classrooms, rather than selecting from lists of individual children. This approach is common in school research and is more logistically practical and efficient. It also does not single out the migrant children in the class. Teams will need to confirm with the principal ahead of time how many classes of whatever level(s) there are in the school from which they want to collect data. We recommend collecting data from 30-50 children in each school per year group, which will likely be two classes (assuming an average class size of about 20-25 students), in order to have enough clustering to compare different school characteristics. If there are only one or two classes at the level the researchers want to collect data from, they would administer the survey to all the children at that level. If there are more than two classes, they will randomly select two to use for data collection. This can be done by assigning each class a number and using a random number generator to choose.

It is very important, however, that research teams confirm with the principal ahead of time whether children are divided into classes randomly or if they are divided using any criteria that might result in the over-representation of any group in one class and an under-representation of them in the next class. Some examples of this might be schools that group pupils by ability or by special needs, concentrating them together in one class, while another class may have none. If this is the case, then the researchers will not select classes randomly. Again, if there are only 1 or 2 classrooms at the level being sampled, both will be surveyed anyway, so there is no concern there. If there are more than 2 classrooms, and they are grouped by ability (or by some other criteria), then instead of choosing the classrooms to survey randomly, the researchers will choose the 2 classes that best capture the population we are most interested in, i.e. migrant students. If there is no difference between the classes in terms of the distribution of migrant students, but the students are grouped by, for example, academic ability, the researchers will choose 2 classes that cover the range of variability between them. So, if there are 3 classrooms that are arranged by academic ability, with 1 class representing the highest group, 1 class in the middle, and 1 class at the lower end, then the researchers would survey the highest and lowest. In cases where the researchers are choosing classes deliberately rather than randomly, this is to be documented for later reporting purposes.

It is recommended to the research teams that they sample a subset of year groups in each school if possible, rather than collecting data from across every school year group possible. Again, this is logistically more efficient and will result in data that is more amenable to looking at stage effects and school effects. Targeting subsets of the age range will give us better sample sizes by class and year, rather than a more diluted sample across years. In Ireland, for example, each year group at school will cover 2 ages; 1st class in primary school contains 6- and 7-year olds, 2nd class contains 7- and 8-year olds, 3rd class 8- and 9-year olds, etc. The Irish team can therefore survey 1st/3rd/5th classes in primary school and 1st/3rd/5th years in secondary school and still cover the whole IMMERSE age range. We encourage the

consortium research teams to pursue a similar strategy if their education system is similarly organised to cut down on the number of classrooms teams need to survey in each school.

Research teams will need to ensure that they have proportionate representation of each year/class group across all types of schools in which they are sampling. They can do this either by collecting data from all of their selected year groups in each school they visit (if you are visiting only one school for any category of your sampling framework, then this will probably be necessary), or by collecting data from a subset of their selected year groups in each school and collecting data from multiple schools of each category.

4.4 Sampling in Non-formal Environments

Non-formal educational environments are those places in which educational activities for migrant or refugee children are taking place but are outside the formal schooling system. Sampling of these environments should, like school sampling, cover as much variability as is possible and practical. However, it is much less likely that sufficient data will be available on such environments to be able to employ a stratified random sampling technique similar to what we are using in schools. In addition, these environments are also likely to be difficult to access, making any kind of probability sampling inefficient and less likely to yield results. As such, we propose a non-probability sampling technique similar to the one described in the above section on school sampling plan B, namely *maximum variation purposive sampling* and *snowball sampling*.

Research partners should survey the non-formal educational environments available in their context to gauge whether there are different types or categories of these and what those types are. If there are different types, the researchers should attempt to sample from each category to cover maximum variability. Even where the researcher deems that access and willingness to participate is extremely unlikely, an attempt to recruit should be made. If such attempts are unsuccessful, the researchers can then make use of contacts, networks, and knowledge to concentrate pursuit on those non-formal environments where they think access is more likely, still trying to cover as much variability as possible. Snowball sampling is also justified in this approach, due to the likely difficulty of accessing populations in non-formal education environments.

4.5 Timeline of Data Collection

The timeline for WP3 activities has had to be adjusted due to Covid-19. Earlier this year, we therefore proposed that the piloting take place over September and October (M22-23), recruitment begin in September (M22), and the data collection window begin in November (M24). Originally, WP3 was meant to have two separate 7-month periods of data collection with a 5-month gap in between for data analysis on the first phase (resulting in D3.3), then 8 months for analysis of the full dataset and production of the final WP3 reports (resulting in

D3.4, 3.5, and 3.6). This left four months for the production of the final reports for WP4, WP5, and WP6, all of which draw (to a greater or lesser extent) from WP3 results and reports.

Given the importance of the final data analysis, the final WP3 reports, and the final reports from the other work packages that depend on WP3 results, particularly WP4's policy recommendation documents, we do not think it is wise to shorten the amount of time allotted for these. Instead, we proposed to change the data collection timeline from two separate 7-month phases with a break in between to one continuous 12-month period of data collection from Nov 2020 to the end of Oct 2021 [M24-M35]. We can still produce an interim analysis (D3.3) when the data collection window reaches the halfway point [M29, due around M32], but data collection would not stop during the analysis and production of this report. The proposed timeline for WP3 is below:

Table 9. Timeline of Large-scale Data Collection

Task	Period	Responsible Partner
Finalisation of data collection instruments and country sampling strategies	MM. 17-18 (April - May 2020)	UCC, COMILLAS, DOZ, ACE, SCIT, PANTEION
Finalisation of online data collection platform and database (WP2 activities)	MM 18 - 20 (May -July 2020)	IECISA
Pre-testing of online data collection platform, research partner training	M 21 (August 2020)	IECISA
Finalisation of D3.2 Fieldwork Handbook	M 20 - 21 (July – Aug 2020)	UCC
Piloting of data collection instruments and online data collection platform in schools	MM 22 - 23 (Sept – Oct 2020)	UCC (lead), SCIT, COMILLAS, DOZ e. V., ACE, PANTEION
Large-scale data collection in schools and non-formal educational environments	MM 24 - 35 (Nov - Oct. 2021)	UCC (lead), SCIT, COMILLAS, DOZ e. V., ACE, PANTEION.
Interim analysis of data, completion of D3.3 Report on Interim Analysis of Data Collection	MM 29 – 32 (Apr - July 2021)	UCC (lead), COMILLAS
Analysis of full dataset	M 36 - 40 (Nov 2021 – Mar 2022)	UCC (lead), COMILLAS

Task	Period	Responsible Partner
Develop the first draft of the final reports for D3.4 and D3.5 ⁸	MM 39 - 41 (Feb – Apr 2022)	UCC (lead), COMILLAS, PANTEION
Write the final report on the quantitative data from WP3 for D3.4 D3.5 and D3.6	MM 42-43 (May – June 2022)	UCC
Upload final reports on EC platform. D3.4, D3.5 and 3.6.	M. 44 (July 2022)	D3.4 and 3.6 UCC D3.5 PANTEION

The completion of tasks according to this timeline depends, of course, on schools re-opening in September and allowing researchers in. Should the situation remain unchanged or worsen with respect to Covid by the autumn, this timeline may have to be revisited.

4.6 Analysis of the Full Dataset

The large-scale data collection will yield micro level data from migrant and non-migrant children and parents of all participating children and meso level data on schools and non-formal environments from principals and teachers. Macro level data has already been obtained from secondary sources like MIPEX and EU-SILC. The data from all three levels will be combined into a single dataset. Through the online data collection platform, data provided by parents will be linked to the data provided by their children, data provided by principals/staff and teachers will be linked to the data provided by the participating children who attend those schools/non-formal environments, and country-level data will be linked to all participating children from that country. Each line of the final full dataset will therefore represent a single child embedded within a micro, meso, and macro context.

There is a fantastic amount of analysis that can be done with such a dataset, with many relationships to explore among the variables. The specifics of the analytical strategy are currently under discussion and will be detailed in D3.3 *Report on the Interim Analysis of Data Collection*, to be submitted around July 2021 (month 32 of the project). We will cover a range of statistical approaches, from basic descriptive tables to simple correlations to complex multi-level models.

⁸D3.4 *Analysis reports after carrying out the research across countries in schools and other learning environments*, D3.5 *Analysis reports after carrying out the research across countries in reception centres and other experiential environments* and D3.6 *Final analysis report after carrying out the research* will all contain quantitative and qualitative data analysis.

5 Qualitative Data Collection

The Grant Agreement (p.102) states that the qualitative element of WP3 will build case studies to better understand how migrant and refugee children who do not attend formal schooling are integrated in society. Qualitative data collection is in some ways less amenable to harmonisation than survey-style research, however, there are still a number of ways we can ensure data comparability across the consortium countries. The methodological approach we outline here specifies some aspects to be common for all research partners but allows a significant degree of flexibility to allow for creativity, co-creation with participants, and capturing rich detail that will not be present in the large-scale quantitative data collection.

5.1 Selection of Groups to Be Researched

The group(s) selected for interrogation through qualitative research methods in WP3 should relate to the IMMERSE Dashboard of Indicators, provide variety across the consortium, but with a particular focus on underrepresented groups whose experiences may not be fully captured in the IMMERSE quantitative survey. These groups will be different across the consortium and will be identified by each partner. It is expected that they will likely include unaccompanied minors, undocumented migrants and newly arrived migrants. A key aspect of this WP3 qualitative element will be to address some of the EC concerns about co-construction and participation by including children and young children in the development/choice of methods.

The main objective of the qualitative research element of WP3 will be to provide more in-depth examination of underrepresented groups in the 10-18 year migrant cohort within the main study. For each partner in the consortium this will take perhaps a different focus but within this there should be a specific emphasis on unaccompanied minors as identified in the Grant Agreement. All partners will collect data from two groups, with 5 to 8 children/young people in each group, including at least one group from an informal centre to ensure each partner has data from 'other learning environments' as required for D3.5. All partners will focus on 10 years+ age group given the challenges and time associated with qualitative research with younger children. As an example, the Irish partner's qualitative case studies for WP3 will comprise a focus on unaccompanied minors and those young people 'ageing out' of the education system (16-18 years old) as the experiences of these groups will be harder to capture in the IMMERSE survey. This focus has emerged from our data collection to date through workshops conducted in WP1.

It will be up to each partner to choose the geographic regions in which the qualitative research is conducted and this will be guided by the location of the underrepresented groups they have chosen to focus on. Each partner should provide a clear rationale for their choice of group and region.

5.2 Methods

We suggest a suite of individual and group methods, with one method – focus groups – that will be common across all partners, and other methods to be pursued at each partner's discretion, in consultation with their child/youth participants. This strategy ensures that we will have some qualitative data that is comparable across the consortium, in addition to facilitating some flexibility, allowing the partners to tailor a part of their data collection to the needs of their context and the child/youth participants involved in co-construction in each of their collection sites. Many of the methods suggested are drawing on the *Stakeholder Engagement and Activities Training Programme* completed by DOZ in WP1 (Rutzen, Krys, & Ramadan, 2019).

We envisage small-scale and in-depth qualitative data collection with two groups of between 5 and 8 young people each aged between 10 and 18 years of age comprising focus groups; diaring/blogging; and mapmaking or photovoice; and/or other methods as developed by the partners in conjunction with young people. Each partner will conduct individual interviews/focus groups as the common methodological approach. The partners, in consultation with their participants can choose the other qualitative research methods they will use.

UCC will liaise with the partners regarding the operation of the methods outlined in this document and will provide a one-hour training session in the Autumn.

5.2.1 Focus groups / individual interviews

Focus groups will look at a small number of the Indicators from the older children's survey in more detail. This will ensure that we are addressing key indicators with these groups who are harder to capture and therefore underrepresented in the larger survey. These focus groups will be held with a maximum of 5-8 young people (see Rutzen, Krys, & Ramadan, 2019 for an overview of Focus Group methods). Partners may deem it more appropriate to conduct individual interviews with young people at this point. However, for comparative data analysis purposes it is preferable that all partners try to conduct focus groups.

If Covid 19 restrictions are still in place when fieldwork commences, then focus groups/individual interviews will need to be conducted over Google hangouts or another such platform.

A sample focus group interview guide is provided, however, some of these questions might not be appropriate – e.g. for the ageing out cohort in Ireland, one issue is that they are not in school. Partners are asked to identify the indicators they are focusing on for the particular groups they identify. UCC can develop suggested prompts for each indicator that can be adapted for a number of situations.

SAMPLE FOCUS GROUP INTERVIEW GUIDE DRAWN FROM EXISTING WORK IN WP1

School:

- What is your sense of belonging in the school/education service you attend?
(prompts: school is a place where you can really be yourself; people at your school care about you; teachers really try to help you; most of the teachers really listen to what you have to say; your teachers stand up for you if someone mistreats you; teachers trust your abilities to continue with your studies)
- Are there services in your school providing learning support for students after school hours (to help with homework, language learning, etc.)?
- Are there after-school activities (such as sports, arts, music, etc.) in your school?
- What particular challenges have you faced in school?

Language:

- What is your level of competence in the host country language?
(Prompts: can you explain yourself to your teacher; can you understand your teacher).
- Do you use your mother-tongue language at school – is this accepted/ promoted??
- Have you ever had to translate for your parent in a school situation e.g. parent-teacher meetings or other school events?

Well-being, friends and the community:

- How happy are you in your current situation? Spectrum exercise (Rutzen, Kryš, & Ramadan, 2019, p.52)
- How good is your physical health and mental health?
- Do you have good friends?
- Are many of your friends from your host country or home country?
- Are there opportunities to access school/language supports in the community?
- Are there opportunities to access dance, music, art etc. in the community?
- Do you feel safe in your local area?
- Have you experienced bullying or discrimination in your local area?

The problem tree analysis (Rutzen, Kryš, & Ramadan, 2019, p.37) may be helpful in exploring further a key problem identified by the focus group.

We encourage partners to consider engaging with the remaining methods outlined below, although these are not mandatory. UCC will be using all three methods or a variation of these in consultation with the children/youth participants.

5.2.2 Diarying or journaling

We envisage that two groups of approx. 5 – 8 young people each will document their daily experiences of education 3 times per week over a period of one month – the challenges and positives, their relationships both with their peers and teachers.

Diarying will provide children and young people with an opportunity to document their experiences in real time. These are a good way to address some of the co-construction concerns identified by the EC. Diaries are self-reporting research exercises, in which participants periodically log entries describing their experiences with a particular task, product, or activity in their lives. Researchers conduct these studies over a fixed period of time that can last for a couple of days to a number of months. Researchers pair up this approach with larger quantitative data analysis methods to dig deeper into users' particular behaviours, motivations, and perceptions. Useful tips are provided at

<https://www.uxmatters.com/mt/archives/2012/07/a-closer-look-at-diary-studies-with-children-and-teenagers.php>

It is important to keep parents involved during all stages of the process. Here are some important guidelines to follow:

- Set up contact with the adults and children, and provide all of the necessary documentation, including proof that you are a researcher working on an EU funded project.
- Describe what the IMMERSE project is about in depth, the activities that the children would perform, how you will use the data that you obtain, and how you will communicate with the child and the adults throughout the process.
- Although young people will complete the diary by themselves, you should still be sure to keep parents involved. Let them know how the process is going.
- Be sure to manage everyone's expectations. How many times a day or week should children log entries and when? Let them know how the platform we are using works too.

The diaries can be in paper or phone or online format (e.g. on Google forms). The advantage of using phone/online is that young people can insert text, photos and videos easily. Also, given the current Covid 19 conditions it may be a realistic way of obtaining the data for the qualitative element of WP3. Smartphones would also work well for the mapmaking exercise. However, the technology may not be available to all participants and so we can distribute journals in that case.

5.2.3 Mapmaking or photovoice

We envisage young people walking around their local area taking photos on their phones or drawing the spaces where they spend their time. The objective is for the young people to provide a sense of their 'world' including home, school and community and what facilitates their sense of belonging or otherwise in these spaces. If they take photos they would send

them to the researchers for printing off and then individually or together, create 'Integration maps'. If Covid 19 restrictions prevent holding a group activity this can be done by the young people individually.

Mapmaking and photovoice can be completed individually or in groups – the purpose is for children/young people to provide a sense of their 'world' including home, school and community and what facilitates their sense of belonging or otherwise.

White and Green (2012) document the rising interest in children's and young people's geographies in recent years, which has led to deeper insights into their lives. It highlights the complex meanings, frameworks, identities and subjective relationships that children and young people have in relation to place and space. Reay and Lucey (2000) and Mitchell and Elwood (2012) observe that experiences of places and spaces are structured by broader social power relations, including race, class, age and gender. From a methodological perspective, the focus on exploring and understanding young people's relationships with space and place has seen a range of innovative and mobile methods and approaches being employed to complement or replace more traditional approaches to research. Many of these creative approaches have focused on utilising young people's written, oral and visual skills. Some of the most notable research in this field has incorporated mapwork exercises, self-directed photography, writings, drawings and commentaries (Ross, 2007); mental maps, thematic and non-thematic drawings, photo diaries and daily timelines (Young & Barratt, 2001).

Below is an example which children (aged 11-12) developed on another project of UCC team members.

5.2.4 Suggested steps to follow for those choosing all of the qualitative methods

For those who wish to adopt the methods outlined in their entirety, below is a suggested template for completion. However, partners may choose to only engage with the focus group element and in conjunction with the young people develop/construct other elements. The qualitative methods planned by UCC entail four visits with the young people over the course of 7 - 8 weeks, as outlined below.

Table 10: Format/timeline for Qualitative Methods

Stage	Purpose
Stage 1	Agreement on methods
Stage 2	Selection of focus
Stage 3	Fieldwork: Diarying, photovoice, focus group, individual interviews
VISIT 1 Start Week 1:	An introduction to the project and this component of it along with consent forms for parents and young people. Explain methods to be used. Discussion with young participants about other possible methods.
VISIT 2 End Week 2:	Collect all consent forms and explain diarying methods – give diaries (templates) to the group and explain what is expected of each young person. Diary entry 2 to 3 times per week. Explain photovoice and ask young people to take photos of home, school and local area for use then in mapmaking exercises and send these to the researchers by an agreed date; one week before the next visit.
VISIT 3 Week 6:	Mapmaking for approx. one hour as detailed above.
VISIT 4 Week 7-8:	Explain focus groups. Carry out focus group for approx. one hour.

5.3 Data Analysis

The data collected in this element of WP3 will be textual and (for some partners) visual (diaries, interview transcripts, photos, maps, observational notes, researchers notes etc). Visual materials will be treated as texts. Data analysis will be thematic. This can be completed manually or through NVivo or other qualitative analysis package, or both.

Thematic analysis, a sub-set of content analysis, is a common approach to data analysis and is used by researchers with different theoretical orientations. It offers an accessible and theoretical flexible approach. In IMMERSE WP3, thematic analysis will be used to analyse the data since the approach to the data-collection is question-driven. UCC is drawing on the Growing Up in Ireland data analysis approach to qualitative methodology (Greene & Harris, 2011). It refers to Braun and Clarke's (2006) work highlighting the theoretical freedom of

thematic analysis as one of the key advantages of this approach, suggesting that thematic analysis can adopt the following perspectives:

- Essentialist or realist: reporting the experiences, meanings and reality of participants
- Constructionist: examining the ways in which events, realities, meanings and experiences are the effects of a range of discourses operating in society
- Contextualist: characterised by theories which acknowledge the ways individuals make meaning of their experience and thus also the ways the broader social context impinges on those meanings

The coding structures are based on the topics covered by the interview schedules for the qualitative research in WP3 (outlined above) which map onto the domains of the quantitative study. The overarching themes relate directly to the topics covered in the interviews. As the content of each interview is analysed, each theme can be further divided into subthemes, thus highlighting emerging themes.

The findings will be described and common and divergent themes identified. Quotes from children will be used to illustrate themes and to demonstrate the diversity within the sample. Connections between children's responses to different topics will be described, with reference to the literature. Possible explanations of findings, expected and unexpected, will be explored.

Thematic analysis entails the examination of data in order to identify patterns in respondents' behaviours or responses. A theme is thus a pattern discernible in the data that captures something important in relation to the research question. Some themes are imposed from the start and some emerge. This analytical approach allows for a rich description of the entire data-set and subsequent more detailed and nuanced analyses of one particular theme or set of themes. Thematic coding can be inductive in that the themes identified are data-driven and do not fit a pre-existing coding frame, or more theoretical in that the researcher's theoretical interests drive the analysis.

Miles and Huberman (1994) identify three concurrent activities in qualitative data analysis that can be usefully applied when approaching the analysis thematically:

1. **Data reduction:** This process helps to organise the data and sharpen the focus of the analysis. It involves identifying the data to be categorised across a particular theme, summarising the content of this data and paraphrasing.
2. **Data display:** Once the data has been reduced, it can be displayed in an organised and compressed way that allows the researcher to follow the patterns and look at relationships within the data. Matrices can be useful at this stage.
3. **Conclusion drawing and verification:** At this stage the researcher identifies regularities, patterns, similarities and differences, and draws possible configurations, causal flows, explanations and propositions.

Each partner is to analyse their own data, following which UCC will compile a draft report which the partners can then provide feedback to before we produce a final report.

5.4 Timeline of Data Collection

We recommend that partners undertake the work on the qualitative element of WP3 between April and August 2021 (M27 - M31). Leaving it later means that it will be more likely that we won't have to adjust methodology to accommodate Covid-19 restrictions. However, we are aware that there is a lot of data collection ongoing from November 2020 and so will aim to offer flexibility to partners, as long as the qualitative research for WP3 is completed by August 2021 (M31). This will be collated by UCC for Deliverables 3.4 and 3.6.

Table 11: Timeframe for Qualitative Elements of WP3

Task	Period	Responsible Partner
Develop methodology for qualitative research for WP3	MM. 17-18 (April - May 2020)	UCC
Share the draft methodology and receive feedback from partners.	MM 18 -19 (May -June 2020)	SCIT, COMILLAS, UCC, DOZ e. V., ACE, MEYSS, PANTEION.
Share the final qual. methodology and timing with partners. Partners to send their plans. Write-up for D3.1	M 19 (June 2020)	UCC
Partners to apply for ethical approval	M 20 – 23 (July – Oct. 2020)	All partners as appropriate
Data collection by research partners. These materials will be uploaded on IMMERSE Hub and ODD	MM 24 - 33 (Nov. 2020 – Aug. 2021)	UCC, SCIT, COMILLAS, DOZ e. V., ACE, PANTEION
Preliminary analysis of qualitative data at national level against the relevant literature.	MM 34 - 35 (Sept - Oct. 2021)	UCC, SCIT, COMILLAS, DOZ e. V., ACE, PANTEION.
Collating of national data analysis reports and development of first draft of qualitative research report	MM 36 – 37 (Nov- Dec. 2021)	UCC
Share the first draft of the report on the qualitative research with the Consortium partners to receive feedback	M 39 (Feb 2022)	SCIT, COMILLAS, UCC, INFODEF, IECISA ES, DOZ e. V., ZABALA, ACE, MEYSS, PANTEION, RDPSEC

Develop the first draft of the final reports for D3.4 and D3.5	MM 39 - 40 (Feb– Mar 2022)	UCC
Write the final report on the qualitative data from WP3 for D3.4 D3.5 and D3.6	MM 41-43 (Apr – June 2022)	UCC
Upload final reports on EC platform. D3.4, D3.5 and 3.6. The qualitative data will be part of all of these reports.	M. 44 (July 2022)	D3.4 and 3.6 UCC D3.5 Panteion

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D3.1 Appendices

Country-Specific Sampling Strategies

7 Appendix A – Spain (Research Partner: Comillas)

7.1 Regional Sampling

The political division of Spain comprises Autonomous Communities, which in turn are divided into provinces and municipalities. An Autonomous Community is a first-level political and administrative division subordinated to the decentralised and unitary State. Provinces are local entities determined by a group of municipalities (towns and cities). Provinces are legal entities and an administrative demarcation with full capacity to fulfil the State activities. Given the political division of the Spanish territory and the competences of the provinces in local government, regions and provinces must be selected according to territorial dispersion, rural/urban variability and percentage of foreign population and foreign students in relation to the total student body.

The regions or Autonomous Communities selected to carry out the IMMERSE survey in Spain are three: The Community of Madrid (hereinafter, Madrid), Andalusia and La Rioja. Considering the provincial division of the Spanish territory and, above all, based on the geographic size of Andalusia, which is the second largest Autonomous Community of the State, our unit of measurement will be the province. Madrid and La Rioja are single province regions, but in Andalusia the fieldwork will be done in Malaga, Almeria and Huelva because these are the provinces having the largest share of migrant population in this Community. Therefore, the fieldwork will be carried out in five provinces, all selected according to territorial dispersion, rural/urban variability and percentage of foreign population and foreign students in relation to the total student body.

In terms of territorial dispersion, the selection of the regions is intended to represent the geographic variability of the country: La Rioja is an Autonomous Community situated in the north of the country, Madrid in the centre, and Andalusia, in the south. With regard to rural/urban variability, Madrid was included because of its large metropolitan area, predominantly industrial in nature and because it has many centralized services; La Rioja because of its large rural centres of agricultural production (such as Calasparra and Haro) and Andalusia because it is predominantly rural (such as the provinces of Almeria and Huelva) and because of its fundamental role in the construction sector (as is the case with the province of Malaga).

The five selected provinces have 26% of the total foreign student body in Spain. In the case of Andalusia, the three selected provinces represent 67% of the total foreign student body in this Community reflecting the fact that the multi-provincial selection is highly representative of this region.

Table 1. shows the highest level of education attained per age for the overall population in each of these Autonomous Communities. Table 2 shows the highest level of education attained by nationals, foreigners and EU nationals at the national level.⁹

Table 1. Highest level of Education attained (%) per age group and per Autonomous Community in 2018.

	Age: 25 - 64	Age: +65
ISCED 0-2¹⁰		
National Total	39.9	78.7
<i>Andalusia</i>	49.0	81.4
<i>Community of Madrid</i>	27.7	66.1
<i>La Rioja</i>	38.2	81.0
ISCED 3-4		
National Total	22.9	8.7
<i>Andalusia</i>	20.7	7.6
<i>Community of Madrid</i>	25.1	13.2
<i>La Rioja</i>	23.0	8.2
ISCED 5-8		
National Total	37.3	12.7
<i>Andalusia</i>	30.3	11.1
<i>Community of Madrid</i>	47.2	20.7
<i>La Rioja</i>	38.7	10.7

Source: INE, 2019.

As data shows, there has been a clear generational shift in terms of the highest level of education attained by the Spanish population. While a clear majority (78.7%) of the population over 65 only attained an ISCED 0-2 level, this is more balanced for population between 25-64, where people having attained an ISCED 0-2 level (39.9%) represent a similar share of those having attained an ISCED 5-8 level (37.3%). At the level of Autonomous Communities, La Rioja is quite aligned with the national average for both age groups whereas Madrid's population tends to have higher education levels (in both age groups) while Andalusia shows the opposite.

Table 2. Highest level of Education attained by Foreign Population in Spain (and total population) (%) per age group in 2018.

	Age: 18-24	Age: 25 - 64	Age: +65
ISCED 0-2			
National Total	32.6	39.9	78.7
<i>Spanish population</i>	29.4	39.5	79.5
<i>Foreign (EU)</i>	51.1	29.8	46.3
<i>Foreign (rest of the world)</i>	54.3	50.4	63.9

⁹Unfortunately, data sources do not disaggregate this data at the level of Autonomous Communities.

¹⁰Note: ISCED Levels: 0-2: preschool, primary and lower secondary education. Levels 3-4: upper secondary education and post-secondary non-tertiary education. Levels 5-8: Short-cycle tertiary education, Bachelor, Doctoral or equivalent.

	Age: 18-24	Age: 25 - 64	Age: +65
ISCED 3-4			
National Total	50.4	22.9	8.7
<i>Spanish population</i>	52.1	21.8	8.2
<i>Foreign (EU)</i>	39.6	37.1	24.6
<i>Foreign (rest of the world)</i>	38.5	27.3	15.3
ISCED 5-8			
National Total	17.1	37.3	12.7
<i>Spanish population</i>	18.5	38.8	12.2
<i>Foreign (EU)</i>	9.3	33.2	29.1
<i>Foreign (rest of the world)</i>	7.1	22.3	20.8

Source: INE, 2019.

Table 2. shows that younger foreign-born population aged 18-24 in Spain, tends to have attained lower education levels (ISCED 0-2) than Spanish nationals. As it is possible to see, while 54.3% of third-country nationals and 51.1% of EU nationals residing in Spain have an ISCED 0-2 level, only 29.4% of Spanish citizens have it. Looking at the following levels (ISCED 3-4 and ISCED 5-8) the tendency is the opposite, showing that a larger share of Spanish nationals has attained these levels compared to foreign-born ones. In the case of ISCED 5-8 levels, the distance between both groups is greater, as 18.5% of Spanish population between 18-24 attained this level compared to 9.3% of EU nationals and 7.1% of Third-country nationals.

For the population aged 25-64, while third country nationals largely remain having ISCED 0-2 levels (50.4%), in the case of EU citizens there is a high decrease compared to the previous age groups (passing from 51.1% having attained this level to 29.8%). In the case of ISCED 3-4 levels, EU citizens having attained these levels are now a majority (37.1%) and there are more third-country nationals than Spanish citizens having attained these levels too (27.3% compared to 21.8%). Finally, regarding ISCED 5-8 levels, the difference between the three national groups is more reduced than in the previous age category, but still Spanish population shows a higher share of people having attained this educational level compared to EU citizens and third country nationals (38.8% compared to 33.2% and 22.3%).

Interestingly, the last age group (over 65) is completely different, as Spanish population tends to have attained lower education levels (79.5%) far from EU citizens (46.3%) and third-country nationals (63.9%). In both the following categories (ISCED3-4 and ISCED 5-8) foreigners' share having attained these levels are much higher than those related to the Spanish population (for instance 29.1% of EU citizens having an ISCED 5-8 level compared to 12.2% of Spanish population).

About the foreign population in Spain, the main counties of origin are Morocco and Romania, both highly represented (making almost 30% of foreign population in Spain between them). Given these numbers, in our sampling EU nationals will be excluded, except Romanians (671,985) and Bulgarians (122,813). In this research, the concept of "economic immigrants" was assumed as the focus of attention. Considering this, EU citizens will not be included, as the unification of Europe

brought new migration flows between the EU Member States (mainly residential migrations from British, Italians and Germans).¹¹ A particularly significant flow is that of northern European citizens towards Mediterranean countries. Nevertheless, Romanians and Bulgarians are not included in this kind of migration as the main reason in these two cases is still economic.¹² That is, not all third countries nationals (TCN) will be included in the sampling but only those with lower income (economic migrants) as even if some may possess specific citizenship rights (because they belong to the EU) their social conditions entail difficulties regarding their integration.

Table 3. Foreign population in Spain by nationality (2019)

Countries of Origin	Total
<i>Morocco</i>	813,587
<i>Rumania</i>	671,985
<i>United Kingdom</i>	250,392
<i>Italy</i>	228,283
<i>China</i>	224,559
<i>Colombia</i>	206,719
<i>Venezuela</i>	137,776
<i>Ecuador</i>	131,814
<i>Bulgaria</i>	122,813
Total	5,036,878

Source: INE, 2020.

Regarding the employment of migrants, Table 4 shows that 9.3% (more than 2 million) of employed people in Spain were foreigners in 2019. This data is a bit higher when looking at unemployment, where the rate of migrants without a job attains 12.1%.

Table 4. Employment/ Unemployment Statistics for Nationals and Foreigners in Spain 2019

Total labour registration	22,512,221
Foreigners in labour registration	2,104,260
% Foreigners over Total	9.3
Total unemployment	4,469,919
Foreigners in unemployment	540,906
% Unemployed foreigners over total	12.1

Source: Estadísticas de la Seguridad Social 2020.

¹¹Spain is one of the main destinations for residential migrants within Europe since the unification, not only for its climate but also for the conditions of political stability and social welfare. Source: Huete, R., & Mantecón, A. (2013). La migración residencial de noreuropeos en España (North European residential migration in Spain). *Convergencia*, 20(61), 219-245.

¹²Viruela, R. (2016). La movilidad geográfica de búlgaros y rumanos durante la Gran Recesión en España (The geographical mobility of Bulgarians and Romanians during the Great Recession in Spain). *Documents d'anàlisi geogràfica*, 62(1), 183-206.

7.2 Region Profiles

Figure 1. Map of Spain indicating the three Autonomous Communities of the sample: La Rioja, Madrid and Andalusia.

7.2.1 Region: Community of Madrid

POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS

Madrid is located in the centre of Spain, bounded by the regions of Castile and Leon and Castile-La Mancha. It is the third most populated Autonomous Community of the country (out of nineteen) and the third most densely populated region: 833 inhabitants per km². It is the 12th biggest region with an area of 8,028 km² and is a predominantly urban region where the capital of both the region and the country, the city of Madrid, is the largest city.

Table 5. Population and Household Income in Madrid. 2018

Total Population	% of Population over total	Average Household Income	Household income level in relation to National Household income
6,663,394	14%	33,055€	+16% (4th wealthiest region of the country)

Source: INE, 2019.

Densely populated despite its small extension Madrid's region represents 14% of the total population of the country and, thanks to its dynamic economy, it's the 4th wealthiest region of the country, having an average income over 30,000€.

Table 6. Age distribution of the population in Madrid. 2018.

	0-4	5-9	10-14	15-19	20-29	30-39	40-59	60 or more	Total
Total	314,163	349,272	353,692	328,133	715,216	955,530	2,096,830	1,550,558	5,803,417
% Of total	4.7%	5.2%	5.3%	4.9%	10.7%	14.3%	31.5%	23.3%	100%

Source: INE, 2019.

Madrid's population distribution by age is relatively balanced with about 20% of the population under 20, 25% between 20-39 and around 50% over 40.

Table 7. Highest level of Education attained (%) per age group in Madrid. 2018

	Age: 25 - 64	Age: +65
ISCED 0-2		
National Total	39.9%	78.7%
<i>Community of Madrid</i>	27.7%	66.1%
ISCED 3-4		
National Total	22.9%	8.7%
<i>Community of Madrid</i>	25.1%	13.2%
ISCED 5-8		
National Total	37.3%	12.7%
<i>Community of Madrid</i>	47.2%	20.7%

Source: INE, 2019.

In terms of higher education level attained, Madrid's population in both age groups has attained a higher level than the national average, mainly in ISCED 5-8 levels where the difference is ten points higher (47.2% compared to 37.3%).

Table 8. PISA results in Science, Mathematics and Reading in Madrid. 2018

	Science	Mathematics	Reading
Madrid	487	486	520
Spain	483	481	496
OECD	489	489	493

Source: PISA 2018 for Science & Mathematics & 2015 for Reading.¹³

Madrid's results in PISA 2018 (and 2015 for reading) show that this community has attained a better level in Science, Mathematics and Reading than the national average, being the difference in

¹³There are no results available in Spain for Reading 2018.

reading highly accentuated (24 points of difference). Compared to OECD, Madrid is a bit under the average in Science and Mathematics but, again, has a higher score in reading.

Table 9. Employment/ Unemployment Statistics for Nationals and Foreigners in Madrid 2019.

Total labour registration	2,801,261
Foreigners in labour registration	427,362
% Foreigners over Total	15.3%
Total unemployment	827,654
Foreigners in unemployment	70,124
% Unemployed foreigners over total	8.5%

Source: Estadísticas de la Seguridad Social 2020.

The rate of employed foreigners in Madrid is higher than at the national level, reaching 15.3% (compared to 9.3%) and the rate of unemployed foreigners over the total unemployment in the region is lower as only 8.5% of unemployed workers are foreigners (compared to 12.1% at the national level).

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

In 2018, foreign-born residents amounted to 13.23% of the region's population (881,819 inhabitants).

Table 10. Regions of Origin of foreign-born residents in Madrid. 2018

	Europe	Africa	Central America and the Caribbean	North America	South America	Asia	Oceania
Total	330,287	111,805	77,748	18,860	239,131	103,227	619
% Of Total	37.5%	12.7%	8.8%	2.1%	27.1%	11.7%	0.1%

Source: INE, 2019.

As it can be seen in table 10, the majority of foreign-born residents in Madrid come from Europe (37.5%) followed by South Americans (27.1%), summing both more than 50% of all the foreigners residing in Madrid. Africans (12.7%) and Asians (11.7%) are present in similar magnitudes while the number of North Americans and Oceanians is extremely reduced.

Asylum applicants

Madrid assumes most of Spain's asylum applications (38.16%). In addition, two of the four Refugees Reception Centres managed by the Spanish Government are in this province, one in the municipality of Vallecas and the other in Alcobendas. The main countries of origin of the asylum seekers in 2018 are Venezuela (8,107), Colombia (3,652), Palestine (1,251) and El Salvador (1,210).

Table 11. Asylum applicants in Madrid by country of origin from January to December 2018

Country of Origin	Madrid	Spain
Venezuela	8,107	20,053
Colombia	3,652	8,818
Palestine	1,251	1,970
El Salvador	1,210	2,312
Honduras	1,081	2,465
Ukraine	532	2,068
Nicaragua	492	1,368
Peru	323	532
Dominican Republic	272	291
Turkey	240	283
Guinea	238	732
Other countries	3,333	13,432
Total	20,731	54,324

Note: Asylum applications filed at embassies and resettlement are not included.

Source: Asilo en Cifras, 2019.¹⁴

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

Table 12. Number and type of schools in Madrid, foreign-born students enrolled and their share over total students. 2018

Number of schools	Public	Private	Number of students	Foreign-born Students	% Foreign Students over total
3,880	1,948	1,932	1,209,956	142,173	12%

Source: Educabase, 2019.

Practically half of Madrid's schools are either public or private with about 12% of its students being foreign-born.

7.2.2 Region: La Rioja

La Rioja is located in the north of Spain, bounded by Navarra, Aragon, Castile and Leon and the Basque Country. Is it the third least populated Autonomous Community of the country (out of nineteen), only followed by Ceuta and Melilla, and is the fifth least densely populated region: 62 inhabitants per km². It is the fourth smallest region with an area of 5,045 km². It is a predominantly rural region where the capital, Logroño, is the only municipality considered as "urban" as it is the only city of the region having more than 30,000 inhabitants.

¹⁴http://www.interior.gob.es/documents/642317/1201562/Asilo_en_cifras_2018_126190829.xlsx/0b370591-496b-4489-8049-06d6665bc87d

POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS

Table 13. Population and Household Income in La Rioja. 2018

Total Population	% of Population over total	Average Household Income	Household income level in relation to National Household income
316,798	0.6%	28,549€	+0.4% (9 th wealthiest region of the country)

Source: INE, 2019.

La Rioja is one of the less populated regions in Spain, only attaining 0.6% of the total population of the country, however, despite its small size, it is the 9th wealthiest region of the country, having a high average income.

Table 14. Age distribution of the population in La Rioja. 2018.

	0-4	5-9	10-14	15-19	20-29	30-39	40-59	60 or more	Total
Total	13,589	15,890	16,457	15,151	30,083	40,175	99,379	85,969	302,392
% Of Total	4.3%	5.0%	5.2%	4.8%	9.5%	12.7%	31.4%	27.1%	100%

Source: INE, 2019.

La Rioja's population distribution by age shows that an important majority of the population is over 40 (more than 58%) showing a more acute ageing tendency than in Madrid.

Table 15. Highest level of Education attained (%) per age group in La Rioja. 2018

	Age: 25 - 64	Age: +65
ISCED 0-2		
National Total	39.9%	78.7%
<i>La Rioja</i>	38.2%	81.0%
ISCED 3-4		
National Total	22.9%	8.7%
<i>La Rioja</i>	23.0%	8.2%
ISCED 5-8		
National Total	37.3%	12.7%
<i>La Rioja</i>	38.7%	10.7%

Source: INE, 2019.

In terms of higher education level attained, La Rioja's population in both age groups is relatively close to the national average, being only a bit higher in ISCED levels 3-4 and 5-8 for population between 25-64 and a bit lower in those levels for population over 65.

Table 16. PISA results in Science, Mathematics and Reading in La Rioja. 2018

	Science	Mathematics	Reading
<i>La Rioja</i>	487	497	520
<i>Spain</i>	483	481	496
<i>OECD</i>	489	489	493

Source: PISA 2018 for Science & Mathematics & 2015 for Reading.¹⁵

La Rioja' results in PISA 2018 (and 2015 for reading) show that this community has a better level of Science, Mathematics and Reading than the national average, being the difference in reading highly accentuated (24 points of difference) like Madrid. Compared to OECD, La Rioja is slightly below the average in Science but, again, has a higher level of Reading and Mathematics.

Table 17. Employment/ Unemployment Statistics for Nationals & Foreigners in La Rioja 2019.

Total labour registration	176,806
Foreigners in labour registration	16,483
% Foreigners over Total	9.3%
Total unemployment	51,264
Foreigners in unemployment	4,048
% Unemployed foreigners over total	7.9%

Source: Estadísticas de la Seguridad Social 2020.

The rate of employed foreigners in La Rioja is the same as the national one (9.3%) but the rate of unemployed foreigners over the total unemployment in the region is lower as only 7.9% of unemployed workers are foreigners (compared to 12.1% at national level).

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

In 2018, foreign born residents amounted to 11.75% of the region's population (37,230 inhabitants)

Table 18. Regions of origin of foreign-born residents in La Rioja. 2018

	Europe	Africa	Central America and the Caribbean	North America	South America	Asia	Oceania
<i>Total</i>	17,541	9,503	919	261	5,722	3267	10
<i>% Of Total</i>	47.1%	25.5%	2.5%	0.7%	15.4%	8.8%	0,01%

Source: INE, 2019.

As it can be seen in table 18, practically half of the foreign-born residents in La Rioja come from Europe (47.1%) followed by Africans (25.5%), who represent one quarter of its migrant population.

¹⁵ There are no results available in Spain for Reading 2018.

South Americans (15.4%) are the third category, followed by Asians (8.8%). With 0.7% and 0.01%, respectively, there are extremely few North Americans and Oceanians in the region.

Asylum applicants

La Rioja has almost no asylum applications, with 0.26% of the total applications in Spain. The main countries of origin of the asylum seekers in 2018 are Colombia (56) and Venezuela (55).

Table 19. Asylum applicants in La Rioja by country of origin from January to December 2018

Country of Origin	La Rioja	Spain
<i>Colombia</i>	56	8,818
<i>Venezuela</i>	55	20,053
<i>Honduras</i>	7	2,465
<i>Other countries</i>	24	22,988
Total	142	54,324

Note: Asylum applications filed at embassies and resettlement are not included.

Source: Asilo en Cifras, 2019.¹⁶

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

Table 20. Number and type of schools in La Rioja, foreign-born students enrolled and their share over total students. 2018

Number of schools	Public	Private	Number of students	Foreign-born Students	% Foreign Students over total
213	140	73	7,592	54,907	14%

Source: Educabase, 2019.

65% of schools in la Rioja are public, which represents a higher share than Madrid where this is more balanced. As it can be seen, 14% of the total amount of students are foreign-born.

7.2.3 Region: Andalusia and its provinces, Huelva, Malaga and Almeria

The Autonomous Community of Andalusia is located in the south of Spain bounded by Murcia, Castile-La Mancha, Extremadura and Portugal. It is the most populated Autonomous Community of the country (out of nineteen) and is the eleventh most densely populated region: 96 inhabitants per km². It is the second biggest region with an area of 87,600 km². Although the majority of its territory can be considered as “rural”, Andalusia has some of the most populated cities of the country like Sevilla (fourth) or Malaga (sixth) and has several small but urban municipalities like Roquetas de Mar (Almeria) or San Fernando (Cádiz). The fieldwork within Andalusia will be done in the provinces of Malaga, Almeria and Huelva, because these are the provinces with the largest share of migrant population in this Community.

¹⁶http://www.interior.gob.es/documents/642317/1201562/Asilo_en_cifras_2018_126190829.xlsx/0b370591-496b-4489-8049-06d6665bc87d

Figure 2. Map of the selected provinces in Andalusia

The province of Huelva is located in the western part of Andalusia bounded by three other Spanish provinces (Badajoz, Seville and Cadiz) and also by Portugal and the Atlantic Ocean. It is one of the least densely populated provinces in Andalusia (seventh out of eight): 51.53 inhabitants/km². It is the fifth biggest province within this community with an area of 10,127 km². Most of its territory can be considered as “rural” as the only urban municipality (having more than 30,000 inhabitants) is the city of Huelva.

The province of Malaga is located in the south of Andalusia bounded by Cadiz, Seville, Cordoba, Granada and the Mediterranean Sea. It is the most densely populated province in Andalusia: 227.45 inhabitants/km² (surpassing both the Spanish and the Andalusian average). It is the smallest province in this community with an area of 7,306 km². Most of its territory can be considered as “rural” although it also has some main urban areas.

The province of Almeria is located in the eastern part of Andalusia bounded by Granada, Murcia and the Mediterranean Sea. It is the fourth most populated province in Andalusia (although below the Andalusian average): 81.69 inhabitants/km²., It is the third smallest province within this community with an area of 8,775 km². Most of its territory can be considered as “rural”.

POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS

Table 21. Population and Household Income in Andalusia. 2018

Total Population	% of Population over total	Average Household Income	Household income level in relation to National Household income
8,414,240	18%	24,091€	-15% (ranked 17/19, third poorest region of the country)

Source: INE, 2019.

Table 22. Population and Household Income in the provinces of Almeria, Huelva and Malaga. 2018

	Total Population	% of Population over Andalusia	Average Household Income
<i>Almeria</i>	716,820	8.52%	22,540€
<i>Huelva</i>	521,870	6.20%	16,896€
<i>Malaga</i>	1,661,785	19.75%	32,615€

Source: Institute of Statistics and Cartography of Andalusia, 2019; INE, 2019.

While low densely populated, Andalusia represents 18% of the total population of the country thanks to its great extension (it is the second largest community of the country). Its average income attains 24,091€ making it the third poorest region of the country. However, there are several differences between its provinces as, for instance, Malaga's average income is quite similar to Madrid's one, but Huelva's average household income is 50% of Malaga's one.

Table 23. Age distribution of the population in Andalusia. 2018.

	0-4	5-9	10-14	15-19	20-29	30-39	40-59	60 or more	TOTAL
<i>Total</i>	385,011	448,571	489,369	448,704	932,069	1,165,893	2,618,824	1,923,393	8,414,240
<i>% Of total</i>	4.6%	5.3%	5.8%	5.3%	11.1%	13.9%	31.1%	22.9%	100%

Source: INE, 2019.

Andalusia's population distribution by age is relatively balanced with about 20% of the population under 20, about 25% between 20-39 and around 50% over 40. Table 24 shows that these magnitudes are more or less the same in the three selected provinces.

Table 24. Age distribution of the population in the provinces of Almeria, Huelva, and Malaga. 2018.

	0-4	5-9	10-14	15-19	20-29	30-39	40-59	60 or more	TOTAL
<i>Almeria</i>	38,417	41,227	42,042	38,051	85,110	110,751	217,692	143,530	716,820
<i>% Of total</i>	5.4%	5.8%	5.9%	5.3%	11.9%	15.5%	30.4%	20.0%	100%
<i>Huelva</i>	23,250	27,728	29,617	27,148	57,949	75,401	164,725	116,052	521,870
<i>% Of total</i>	4.5%	5.3%	5.7%	5.2%	11.1%	14.4%	31.6%	22.2%	100%
<i>Malaga</i>	75,372	89,614	95,874	86,418	174,104	235,235	522,193	382,975	1,661,785
<i>% Of total</i>	4.5%	5.4%	5.8%	5.2%	10.5%	14.2%	31.4%	23.0%	100%

Source: Institute of Statistics and Cartography of Andalusia, 2018.

Table 25. Highest level of Education attained (%) per age group in Andalusia. 2018

	Age: 25 - 64	Age: +65
ISCED 0-2		
National Total	39.9%	78.7%
<i>Andalusia</i>	49.0%	81.4%
ISCED 3-4		
National Total	22.9%	8.7%
<i>Andalusia</i>	20.7%	7.6%
ISCED 5-8		
National Total	37.3%	12.7%
<i>Andalusia</i>	30.3%	11.1%

Source: INE, 2019.

In terms of higher education level attained, Andalusia's population in both age groups has attained a lower level than the national average in ISCED3-4 and 5-8 levels but has more population in both age groups having only attained ISCED 0-2 levels. In the case of population between 25-64, the difference is practically of ten points (49% compared to 39.9%). Table 26 shows these differences at the regional level where it can be seen that Almeria and Huelva tend to have a larger share of population having attained lower education levels than Malaga.

Table 26. Highest level of Education attained by provinces (%) (data for 2017)

	Age: 25 - 64
ISCED 0-2	
Total	40.93%
<i>Andalusia</i>	50.52%
<i>Almeria</i>	58.69%
<i>Huelva</i>	55.79%
<i>Malaga</i>	47.72%
ISCED 3-4	
Total	22.72%
<i>Andalusia</i>	19.87%
<i>Almeria</i>	22.29%
<i>Huelva</i>	17.60%
<i>Malaga</i>	22.00%
ISCED 5-8	
Total	36.35%
<i>Andalusia</i>	29.61%
<i>Almeria</i>	19.02%
<i>Huelva</i>	26.60%
<i>Malaga</i>	30.28%

Source: Estadística de la Educación en Andalucía (Education Statistics in Andalusia), 2018.

Table 27. PISA results in Science, Mathematics and Reading in Andalusia. 2018

	Science	Mathematics	Reading
<i>Andalusia</i>	471	467	479
<i>Spain</i>	483	481	496
<i>OECD</i>	489	489	493

Source: PISA 2018 for Science & Mathematics & 2015 for Reading.

Andalusia results in PISA 2018 (and 2015 for Reading) show that this community has a lower level of Science, Mathematics and Reading than the national average. This is as well repeated compared to OECD, showing an important educational lag with reference to Spain and the whole OECD.

Table 28. Employment/ Unemployment Statistics for Nationals, Foreigners in La Rioja 2019.

Total labour registration	5,202,621
Foreigners in labour registration	251,112
% Foreigners over Total	4.8
Total unemployment	2,511,768
Foreigners in unemployment	81,581
% Unemployed foreigners over total	3.2

Source: Estadísticas de la Seguridad Social 2020.

The rate of employed foreigners in Andalusia is much lower than the national one (4.8%), but the rate of unemployed foreigners over the total unemployment in the region is, as well, much lower as only 3.2% of unemployed workers are foreigners (compared to 12.1% at the national level).

At the level of provinces, data is more varied as, for instance, the rate of employed foreigners over the total in Almeria is very high (16.3%) and, even if lower than the national data, in Huelva and Malaga their share of migrant workers over the total employed population is higher than the Andalusian mean (7.1% and 9.1% respectively). About unemployment rates, there is as well a huge variation as 11.4% of unemployed workers in Almeria are foreigners which is high for Andalusia (3.2%) but lower than the national average (12.1%). In the case of Huelva (5.2%) and Malaga (5.4%) the rates are very low compared to the national average but a bit higher than the Andalusian mean.

Table 29. Employment and Unemployment Statistics for Nationals and Foreigners in Almeria 2019.

Total labour registration	372,482
Foreigners in labour registration	60,614
% Foreigners over Total	16.3%
Total unemployment	174,675
Foreigners in unemployment	19,847
% Unemployed foreigners over total	11.4%

Source: Estadísticas de la Seguridad Social 2020.

Table 30. Employment/ Unemployment Statistics for Nationals, Foreigners in Huelva 2019.

Total labour registration	502,791
Foreigners in labour registration	35,877
% Foreigners over Total	7.1%
Total unemployment	208,229
Foreigners in unemployment	10,764
% Unemployed foreigners over total	5.2%

Source: Estadísticas de la Seguridad Social 2020.

Table 31. Employment/ Unemployment Statistics for Nationals, Foreigners in Malaga 2019.

Total labour registration	829,197
Foreigners in labour registration	75,870
% Foreigners over Total	9.1%
Total unemployment	376,004
Foreigners in unemployment	20,256
% Unemployed foreigners over total	5.4%

Source: Estadísticas de la Seguridad Social 2020.

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

Table 32. Foreign-born residents and their share over total population Andalusia and in the provinces of Almeria, Huelva, and Malaga over the total population in Andalusia. 2018

	Total Population	Foreign Population	%
Andalusia	8,414,240	655,555	7.79%
Almeria	716,820	145,908	20.35%
Huelva	521,870	44,838	8.59%
Malaga	1,661,785	253,153	15.23%

Source: INE, 2019.

While Andalusia has only 7.79% of the foreign-born population of all the country, as it can be seen in Table 32, in Almeria, almost 20% of its population is migrant. In the case of Malaga there is also a high share of foreigners (15.23%) while Huelva, with only 8.59%, still has a higher share than the regional one.

Table 33. Regions of Origin of foreign-born residents in Andalusia. 2018

	Europe	Africa	Central America/ Caribbean	North America	South America	Asia	Oceania
Andalusia	318,834	185,935	19,658	9,588	80,848	39,856	524
% Of Total	48.7%	28.4%	3.0%	1.5%	12.3%	6.1%	0.1%

Source: INE, 2019.

As it can be seen, practically half of all foreign-born residents in Andalusia come from Europe (48.7%) followed by Africans (28.4%), who represent more than one quarter of its migrant population. South Americans (12.3%) are the third category, followed by Asians (6.1%). With 1.5% and 0.1%, respectively, there are extremely few North Americans and Oceanians in the region. In this case, the distribution is quite similar to La Rioja.

Table 34. shows their distribution in the selected provinces. As it is possible to see, there are several variations from one to another being noticeable the fact that 50% of foreign-born residents in Almeria are Africans while 60.9%, in the case of Malaga, are European.

Table 34. Regions of Origin of foreign-born residents in the provinces of Almeria, Malaga, and Huelva. 2018

	Europe	Africa	America	Asia	Oceania	Stateless	TOTAL
<i>Almeria</i>	57,241	73,003	12,372	3,233	37	22	145,908
<i>% Of total</i>	39.2%	50.0%	8.5%	2.2%	0.0%	0.0%	100%
<i>Huelva</i>	24,724	15,541	3,350	1,211	4	8	44,838
<i>% Of total</i>	55.1%	34.7%	7.5%	2.7%	0.0%	0.0%	100%
<i>Malaga</i>	154,079	40,644	40,224	17,883	265	58	253,153
<i>% Of total</i>	60.9%	16.1%	15.9%	7.1%	0.1%	0.0%	100%

Source: Estadística de la Educación en Andalucía (Education Statistics in Andalusia), 2019.

Asylum applicants

Andalusia assumes 9.97% of Spain's asylum applications (5,414). One of the Refugees Reception Centres managed by the Government is located in this Autonomous Community (in the province of Seville). From the total applications in Andalusia, most were concentrated in Malaga (2,043). The main countries of origin of the asylum seekers in Malaga are Venezuela, Colombia, and Ukraine. In the other two provinces of our sample numbers are smaller, with a total of 503 asylum seekers in Almeria and 299 in Huelva (mainly from Venezuela, Mali and Colombia in both provinces).

Table 35. Asylum applicants in Almeria by country of origin from January to December 2018

Country of Origin	Almeria	Spain
<i>Venezuela</i>	153	20,053
<i>Mali</i>	112	707
<i>Colombia</i>	76	8,818
<i>Ukraine</i>	36	2,068
<i>Guinea</i>	28	732
<i>Ivory Coast</i>	16	449
<i>Other countries</i>	82	21,497
Total	503	54,324

Note: Asylum applications filed at embassies and resettlement are not included.

Source: Asilo en Cifras, 2019.¹⁷

¹⁷http://www.interior.gob.es/documents/642317/1201562/Asilo_en_cifras_2018_126190829.xlsx/0b370591-496b-4489-8049-06d6665bc87d

Table 36. Asylum applicants in Huelva by country of origin from January to December 2018

Country of Origin	Huelva	Spain
<i>Venezuela</i>	118	20,053
<i>Mali</i>	67	707
<i>Colombia</i>	38	8,818
<i>Ukraine</i>	22	2,068
<i>Georgia</i>	9	1,040
<i>Other countries</i>	45	21,638
Total	299	54,324

Note: Asylum applications filed at embassies and resettlement are not included.

Source: Asilo en Cifras, 2019.¹⁸

Table 37. Asylum applicants in Malaga by country of origin from January to December 2018

Country of Origin	Malaga	Spain
<i>Venezuela</i>	815	20,053
<i>Colombia</i>	392	8,818
<i>Ukraine</i>	203	2,068
<i>Russia</i>	80	663
<i>Guinea</i>	70	732
<i>Georgia</i>	63	1,040
<i>Nicaragua</i>	53	1,368
<i>Morocco</i>	49	1,321
<i>Ivory Coast</i>	32	449
<i>Honduras</i>	30	2,465
<i>Other countries</i>	256	15,347
Total	2,043	54,324

Note: Asylum applications filed at embassies and resettlement are not included.

Source: Asilo en Cifras, 2019.¹⁹

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

Table 38. Number and type of schools in Andalusia and in the provinces of Almeria, Malaga and Huelva, foreign-born students enrolled and their share over total students. 2018

	Number of schools	Public	Private	Number of students	Foreign-born Students	% Foreign Students over total
Andalusia	7422	4,736	2,686	1,608,790	93,504	6%
Almeria	693	463	230	141,313	24,862	18%
Huelva	503	374	129	100,310	6,385	6%
Malaga	1,278	744	534	308,825	31,520	10%

Source: Educabase, 2019.

¹⁸http://www.interior.gob.es/documents/642317/1201562/Asilo_en_cifras_2018_126190829.xlsx/0b370591-496b-4489-8049-06d6665bc87d

¹⁹http://www.interior.gob.es/documents/642317/1201562/Asilo_en_cifras_2018_126190829.xlsx/0b370591-496b-4489-8049-06d6665bc87d

Like in La Rioja, most schools in Andalusia (63%) are public, which represents a higher share than Madrid where this is more balanced. This distribution is quite similar at the level of the selected provinces with the notable difference of Huelva where the share of public schools over total is higher. Regarding the number of foreign-born students, while in Andalusia only 6% of the students enter in this category, in Almeria the share is much higher (18%) and in Malaga it is also higher (10%). Huelva goes in line with the regional magnitudes.

7.3 School Sampling

In Spain, as set out in the Grant Agreement, we will visit 90 centres where we will survey 3,600 migrant children in two rounds. The number of surveyed children will be finally higher as we will also collect data from non-migrant classmates. In order to define our model, we have first decided the geographical distribution of the centres and then which characteristics these centres should have. We have followed the stratified random sampling to do so.

7.3.1 Key characteristics using in sampling framework

REGIONAL DISTRIBUTION OF THE CENTRES

In total, 90 education centres have to be visited. In order to cover the regional distribution of the sample among the five selected provinces we have organized this according to the proportion of foreign-born students in each province. We set a minimum of 5 centres to visit per province, so, at least, 10% of the sample will correspond to each regional unit. Data on foreign-born students comes from: *Estadística de las Enseñanzas no universitarias. Curso 2018-19. Datos Avance* Subdirección General de Estadística y Estudios del Ministerio de Educación y Formación Profesional. (*Statistics of Non-University Teachings. Academic Year 2018-19. Preview Data*. Subdirectory of Statistics and Studies of the Ministry of Education and Vocational Training).²⁰

OWNERSHIP OF THE CENTRE

In Spain, there are three types of centres according to their financing: public, private and private with subsidised public funds (*concertado* in Spanish). We extracted from “Escuelas Católicas” the number of centres per province. We excluded private-owned centres from the sampling as according to García-Castaño and Rubio Gómez (2013)²¹ these have a low number of third country nationals. Then we calculated the share of each type of centre over the total. We transferred this percentage to the number of centres that we will visit in each province (see point a) to decide in how many centres of each type we will carry out the survey (for example, if we are going to 10 centres and in that province 80% are public and 20% are private with subsidised public funds, we will go to 8 public and 2 private with subsidised public funds). Data on ownership of the centre: Catholic Schools Statistics Service.²²

²⁰ Available here:

<http://estadisticas.mecd.gob.es/EducaDynPx/educabase/index.htm?type=pcaxis&path=/Educacion/Centros/Centrosyunid/RD2018-2019/Res&file=pcaxis&l=s0>

²¹ See García-Castaño, F.J. y Rubio Gómez, M. (2013) “«Juntos pero no revueltos»: Procesos de concentración escolar del «alumnado extranjero» en determinados centros educativos”, *Revista de Dialectología y Tradiciones Populares*, vol. LXVIII (1): 7-31.

²² Available here: <https://www.escuelascaticas.es/estadistica/>

FOREIGN STUDENTS BY EDUCATIONAL LEVEL, OWNERSHIP OF THE CENTRE AND PROVINCE

Considering the percentage of foreign students by educational level, ownership of the centre and provinces we will try to replicate the same distribution in the selection of the centres in our sample.

Table 39. Distribution of foreign students by educational level, ownership of the centre and province (%)

	Primary	Special Education	Secondary	High School	Basic Professional Training	Vocational Education and Training	TOTAL
Public Schools							
Madrid	57.47%	0.86%	27.08%	8.90%	2.08%	3.61%	100%
La Rioja	57.20%	0.66%	27.19%	5.07%	3.48%	6.40%	100%
Malaga	52.56%	0.63%	33.93%	9.59%	0.91%	2.37%	100%
Almeria	59.08%	1.06%	29.39%	6.44%	1.08%	2.95%	100%
Huelva	58.18%	0.55%	31.03%	7.18%	0.89%	2.18%	100%
TOTAL	56.98%	0.84%	28.60%	8.44%	1.77%	3.38%	100%
Private and private with subsidised public funds							
Madrid	50.12%	0.52%	35.19%	7.66%	2.00%	4.51%	100%
La Rioja	50.18%	1.08%	31.74%	2.17%	8.14%	6.69%	100%
Malaga	48.93%	0.48%	36.42%	12.06%	0.22%	1.89%	100%
Almeria	50.44%	2.40%	29.04%	4.80%	0.00%	13.32%	100%
Huelva	35.04%	0.85%	44.87%	1.28%	5.98%	11.97%	100%
TOTAL	49.83%	0.55%	35.28%	8.17%	1.89%	4.28%	100%
TOTAL Public+ private	55.25%	0.77%	30.22%	8.37%	1.80%	3.60%	100%

Given the previous distribution, the approximate distribution of the sample of 90 schools would be the following:

Table 40. Distribution of schools in the sample

	Primary	Secondary + High School	Vocational Training	TOTAL
Public Schools				
Madrid	18	12	2	32
La Rioja	4	2	2	8
Malaga	6	6	0	12
Almeria	6	4	0	10
Huelva	4	2	2	8
TOTAL	38	26	6	70

	Primary	Secondary + High School	Vocational Training	TOTAL
Private and private with subsidised public funds				
Madrid	6	4	2	12
La Rioja	2	0	0	2
Malaga	0	2	0	2
Almeria	2	0	0	2
Huelva	0	2	0	2
TOTAL	10	8	2	20
TOTAL Public+ private	48	34	8	90

Data on foreign students by educational level, ownership of the centre and province come from: *Estadística de las Enseñanzas no universitarias. Curso 18-19*. Subdirección General de Estadística y Estudios del Ministerio de Educación y Formación Profesional. (*Statistics of Non-University Teachings. Academic Year 18-19*. Subdirectory of Statistics and Studies of the Ministry of Education and Vocational Training).²³

Special education²⁴ percentages were not included in the final selection; however, it is likely that some of these students will be included in the sample, although we will not include any variable that differentiates them.

Secondary and High Schools centres count together in the sample distribution because most schools in Spain include both educational levels. Basic Professional Training and Vocational Education and Training are also grouped thus trying to incorporate centres that include these two educational levels in the same centre.

CENSUS SECTIONS WITH MORE THAN 20% OF THE POPULATION WITH FOREIGN NATIONALITY

In order to determine the exact location of the centres, we used the largest territorial breakdown of data available: the census sections²⁵. We obtained the data of foreign-born residents²⁶ per census section and so we organized them to exclude those having a share lower than 20% in order to maximize the possibilities of finding a high number of foreign-born students in schools of the sample. This data come from INE's database *Estadística del Padrón Continuo a 1 de enero de 2019. Datos por secciones censales*.²⁷

²³ Available here:

<http://estadisticas.mecd.gob.es/EducaDynPx/educabase/index.htm?type=pcaxis&path=/Educacion/Alumnado/Matriculad/2018-2019RD/Extranjeros&file=pcaxis&l=s0>

²⁴ Students who have learning difficulties that make it necessary to have special educational resources to attend them. To be considered special needs students they require an official diagnosis. They can be undertaken schooling in special education schools or in standard centres.

²⁵ Census sections are the lowest level units for the dissemination of statistical information in Spain (e.g. from the census) and are also used to organize the electoral processes. As they are basically operational, they are always defined by more or less fixed sizes.

²⁶ EU nationals will be excluded from sampling, except Romanians and Bulgarians as explained in the first section.

²⁷ See

<https://www.ine.es/dynt3/inebase/es/index.htm?type=pcaxis&file=pcaxis&path=%2Ft20%2Fe245%2Fp07%2F%2Fa2019>

CENSUS SECTION ORGANIZED BY URBAN/RURAL AREA

After excluding those census sections having less than 20% of foreign-born residents, we organized the remaining ones characterizing them as urban or rural applying the most widely used definition in Spain contained in Law 45/2007 of 13 December, for the Sustainable Development of the Rural Environment (LDSMR), which establishes that a rural environment is one with a population of less than 30,000 inhabitants. So, those census sections belonging to a municipality with less than 30,000 inhabitants were labelled as rural and the rest of the selection was left as urban.

CENSUS SECTIONS BY AVERAGE HOUSEHOLD INCOME (EXCLUDING THE HIGHER INCOMES)

Census sections with more than 20% of the migrant population were also organized according to their average household income. This data come from INE's Atlas de distribución de renta de los hogares.²⁸

In order to refine the selection, we decided to discard those census sections having a household income level considered as "high" because, as shown by Echazarra (2010),²⁹ in the case of the metropolitan area of Madrid, the majority of foreign-born residents in those sections will likely be EU citizens (as explained in section 1, residential migration will be excluded).

To determine which income levels of the Spanish population are considered as "high" we applied the division by deciles used by INE in the *Encuesta de Condiciones de Vida* (ECV) (Living Conditions Survey). Thus, the first three deciles (D1, D2, D3) are considered as "low income", the intermediate deciles (D4, D5, D6 and D7) are considered as "average" and the highest deciles (D8, D9 and D10) are considered as "high".³⁰

Table 41. Household income level per deciles in Spain. 2016

	2016	
<i>Second decile</i>	5.297,1€	Low Income
<i>Third decile</i>	7.684,1€	
<i>Fourth decile</i>	9.588,6€	
<i>Fifth decile</i>	11.634,0€	Median Income
<i>Sixth decile</i>	13.680,9€	
<i>Seventh decile</i>	15.869,0€	
<i>Eighth decile</i>	18.600,8€	High Income
<i>Ninth decile</i>	22.356,4€	
<i>Tenth decile</i>	28.437,0	

Source: Encuesta de Condiciones de vida (ECV) INE, 2016.

Since the most recent income data of census sections recorded by INE are from 2016, we used the deciles of 2016 to determine their income level. According to these data, those census sections

²⁸ See https://www.ine.es/experimental/atlas/exp_atlas_tab.htm

²⁹ See Echazarra, A (2010), "Segregación residencial de los extranjeros en el área metropolitana de Madrid. Un análisis cuantitativo, *Revista Internacional de Sociología (RIS)*, 68 (1): 165-197.

³⁰ See

https://www.ine.es/ss/Satellite?L=es_ES&c=INESeccion_C&cid=1259925432454&p=1254735110672&pagename=ProductosYServicios%2FPYSLayout¶m1=PYSDetalle¶m3=1259924822888

with a household income of more than 18,600.8 euros would be considered as "high income". However, adopting this measure as a cut-off for the selection would greatly reduce the sample in some provinces (given that these data are taken at the national level, but the average income varies according to the census sections). For example, with this criterion there would only be two census sections left in Huelva. We therefore decided to eliminate only those census sections whose average income per household belongs to the last two deciles (D9 and D10), that is, we excluded from the sample those sections with an average household income of 22,356.4 euros or more.

RELIGIONS DENOMINATION

Given that all the public centres in Spain are non-religious, it is proposed that all the private schools with subsidised public funds in the sample should be Catholic in order to guarantee that we cover this variable. In Spain, according to the Catholic Schools Statistics Service (2019) 72.1% of these schools are Catholic, therefore, of the 10 private schools with subsidised public funds that will be included in the sample, 7.2 should be religious and the other 2.8 should be lay. However, it is highly probable that the non-EU foreign student body attending to private schools with subsidised public funds will be concentrated in Catholic schools, as indicated by Poveda et al. (2007)³¹ for the municipality of Madrid. Therefore, it is proposed that the 10 subsidised centres in the sample should be Catholic. Sources: Catholic Schools Statistics Service. Available here: <https://www.escuelascatolicas.es/estadistica/> (2019) and Poveda et al. (2007).³²

SCHOOLS BY URBAN/RURAL AREA

Recalling the distribution of public and private with subsidised public funds schools by province listed in Table 39 and taking into account that 24.4% of the census section sample is in rural areas (22 sections of 90) this distribution will be replicated for the selection of public and private with subsidised public funds schools. Thus, 24.4% of the private centres with subsidised public funds will be in rural areas (6 of the 20 schools) and the rest of them will be in urban areas (i.e. 14 out of 20) and the same for public schools; 24.4% will be located in rural areas (16 out of 70) and the rest of the public schools will be in urban areas (54 out of 70).

Data on census sections distribution by urban/rural area come from section e) in this document.

SCHOOL SIZE

To ensure that small, medium and large schools are included in the sample a small centre shall be considered to be one with less than 300 students,³³ a medium one, between 300 and 450 students, a large one, more than 450.

³¹ See Poveda, David, Franzë Mudanó, Adela, Jociles Rubio, María Isabel, Rivas, Ana María, Villaamil Pérez, Fernando, Pelaez, Carlos and Sánchez, Paula (2007) *La segregación étnica en la educación secundaria de la ciudad de Madrid: un mapa y una lectura crítica*. Emigra Working Papers (91). p. 18. Available at: <https://eprints.ucm.es/32983/>

³² This source comes from an annual report made by a private organization that centralizes the catholic schools in Spain. Although it is not an official source, the data within this report comes from micro-data from "Enseñanzas no universitarias. Centros y servicios educativos. Curso 2016-2017. Resultados Detallados. MECD" (Statistics of Non-University Teachings. Academic Year 2016-17. Detailed Results. Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports). Micro-data are not publicly accessible although they can be requested by other organizations.

³³ Schools below 100 pupils will not be included because they will not let us collect enough data to be able to do analysis on school effects.

In Spain, the limit of the official maximum ratio in primary is 25 students per classroom. Considering this, a Primary School with 3 classes per year and 25 children in each class would have a total of 450 students. Considering this criterion, a school will be qualified as “large” if it has more than 3 classes with 25 students per academic level.

The distribution of the sample will be proportional according to the size of the school due to a pragmatic issue: in small schools, less children will be found and therefore less data will be available. Thus, of the 90 centres, approximately 16 will be small (1/6 of the sample), 30 medium (1/3 of the sample) and 44 large ones (1/2 of the sample).

In those schools that include primary and secondary levels, as data will be collected in all educational levels, they will be counted twice in the sample (i.e., as primary school and a secondary school). To calculate the school size, in these cases, only the number of students enrolled in a specific educational level will be considered (not the total number of students in the school). For example, one school that has both primary and secondary levels might have around 720 students in total. Considering this, it would be a large school, but if we consider separately the students in primary and secondary there will be only 360, therefore, this school should be considered a medium school. This last option is the one that will be considered when doing the sampling.

MINIMUM PERCENTAGE OF FOREIGN STUDENTS IN THE SCHOOL

Based on the previously indicated processes, the educational authorities would be requested to give us access to the educational centres with the highest percentage of students of immigrant origin in that census section (at least 15% must be foreign-born, if there is no centre with these characteristics, we would move on to the next census section of the sample). Likewise, the centres must comply with the characteristics presented below.

MINIMUM PERCENTAGE OF MIGRANT BACKGROUND STUDENTS IN THE CLASSROOM

Once the specific educational centres have been selected data will be collected from all classrooms in schools with more than 15% of foreign-born students. If any centre has been selected for a specific educational level such as “Secondary + High School” but has some other level such as Basic Vocational Training, data will also be collected for those levels.

If any classroom has less than 15% of students of immigrant origin, data will not be collected in it, although it will be collected in the rest of the educational centre. For example, if in a classroom with 30 children there are less than 4 of immigrant origin, data will not be collected in that classroom.

7.3.2 Categories resulting from Framework and Sampling Pool

- Provinces: Madrid, La Rioja, Almeria, Malaga and Huelva.
- Regional distribution of the centres: minimum of 5 per province.
- Ownership: public and private with subsidised public funds schools.
- Percentage of foreign students by educational level, ownership of the centre and province: sample distribution similar to the total distribution.

- Urban/rural census section.
- Census sections organized by average household income (excluding the higher incomes)
- School size: small, medium and large.
- Religious denomination: catholic and non-denominational.
- Minimum percentage of foreign students in the school: 15%
- Minimum percentage of migrant background students in the classroom: 15%.

Table 42. Final Sampling Distribution per categories

	Total number of centres	Total Rural	Rural - Public	Rural-Private with subsidised public funds	Total Urban	Urban-Public	Urban-Private with subsidised public funds	Small Centres	Medium Centres	Large Centres
Madrid	44	2	0	2	42	32	10	8	14	22
La Rioja	10	6	4	2	4	4	0	2	4	4
Malaga	14	2	2	0	12	10	2	2	4	8
Almeria	12	4	4	0	8	6	2	2	4	6
Huelva	10	8	6	2	2	2	0	2	4	4
TOTAL	90	22	16	6	68	54	14	16	30	44

7.4 School Sampling – Plan B

In the event that the stratified random sampling technique for selecting school sites discussed above yields low response rates, we will use the back-up strategy involving non-probability sampling techniques (as described in the general sampling strategy) that allow us to use our contacts and networks to recruit schools to participate (the organization Catholic Schools, for the subsidized, and the Ministry of Education and its regional levels for the public ones). We will still sample from each of the categories from the stratified sampling framework, but we will choose sites purposively, rather than randomly, in order to maximise response rates in order to reach our participant quota.

7.5 Child/classroom Sampling

We will use a census-type approach for sampling classrooms within schools, as described in the general sampling strategy section. We do not anticipate needing to make any adjustments to this strategy. We will ensure that we have sufficient and proportionate representation of each age group across all types of schools delineated in our school sampling framework.

7.6 Sampling in Non-Formal Education Environments

Previous studies have described different models and degrees of recognition of non-formal education in Europe (Bjornavold, 2000). Non-formal education in Spain is characterised by an open curriculum, a lower degree of prestige, certification and professionalization compared to formal education, more individualised approaches, learning that is more autonomous, more participatory

instructional methodologies and more freedom for the students to choose the subjects based on their individual interests. In this regard, the following contexts of implementation have been identified (Herrera Menchén, 2008):

Figure 3. Non-formal educational context in Spain

Source: translated from Herrera Menchén, 2008

In Spain, the vast majority of children somehow attend formal educational environments. Consequently, there is a lack of systematised data on the characteristics of key non-formal education environments for migrants in Spain, which in turn present higher levels of inaccessibility. For this reason, we will not include non-formal education centres in our sampling strategy (leaving them for the case studies).

8 Appendix B – Ireland (Research Partner: UCC)

8.1 Regional Sampling

Ireland is an island of about 84.5 thousand square kilometres and has approximately 4.76 million in habitants (2016 census), 50.6% female and 49.4% male. It is divided into four provinces, 32 counties, 137 Local Electoral Areas, and 3,409 Electoral Districts. Over the past fifty years, the population has shifted from living mainly in rural areas (towns or settlements of less than 1,500 people, about 54% in the 1966 census) to being concentrated in urban areas (almost 63% in 2016). In fact, over a third of Ireland's population now lives in five urban centres and their surrounding suburbs: Dublin, Cork, Limerick, Galway, and Waterford.¹

The national labour force participation rate² in 2016 was 61.4%, with the smallest ever gap between the male and female participation rates (67.8% for males, vs about 82% in 1966, and 55.2% for females, vs about 28% in 1966). Overall, the majority of employed people worked in managerial and technical positions, non-manual labour jobs (not at managerial level), or skilled manual labour jobs, with professional workers and unskilled labour positions making up smaller groups. It is important to note, however, that there were significant differences between counties in terms of the socio-economic distribution of their inhabitants. Almost 80% of all jobs were in the services sector. Agriculture, which employed almost a third of all workers in 1966, now counted for less than 5% of total employment. Just over a third of working adults, 36.6%, had third level education.³ Ireland is still a predominantly Roman Catholic country (78%), though there has been a steady decline over the past 30 years, with increasing numbers claiming no religious affiliation or an affiliation other than Roman Catholic or Church of Ireland.⁴

Ireland has, historically, been a migrant-sending rather than a migrant-receiving country, with small flows of immigration outweighed by much larger flows of emigration. Economic growth in the first half of the 1990s, however, triggered significant change in migration patterns. In the latter half of the decade and particularly following the enlargement of the EU in 2004, immigration numbers began to surpass emigration numbers, peaking in 2006/7. Economic change then produced a sharp reversal, with the recession of 2008 prompting a dramatic fall in the number of immigrants and a rise in the number of emigrants. Immigration began to climb slowly again in 2010, and 2019 figures

¹ Central Statistics Office. (2017a). *Census 2016 Summary Results – Part 1*. Dublin: Central Statistics Office. Data on general population stats and geographical distribution comes from Chapters 1 and 2 of this document. <https://www.cso.ie/en/media/csoie/newsevents/documents/census2016summaryresultspart1/Census2016SummaryPart1.pdf>

² Central Statistics Office. (2017b). *Census 2016 Summary Results – Part 2*. Dublin: Central Statistics Office. Data on labour force participation comes from Chapter 1 of this document. https://www.cso.ie/en/media/csoie/newsevents/documents/census2016summaryresultspart2/Census_2016_Summary_Results_%E2%80%93_Part_2.pdf

³ Economic and Social Research Institute. (2019). *ESRI Review of research 2018*. Dublin: Economic and Social Research Institute.

⁴ CSO, 2017a, p. 72.

were around the same level as 2005 (though still well below the peak of 2006/7).⁵ According to the 2016 census, 17.3% of Ireland’s population were foreign-born, and 11.4% were born somewhere other than Ireland or the UK. Figure 1 shows the proportion of Ireland’s foreign-born population by region of origin.

Figure 1. Foreign born population in Ireland by region of origin – 2016 Census

Source: Central Statistics Office, 2017c.⁶

The IMMERSE team in Ireland will carry out data collection in three areas: Dublin, Limerick, and Cork (shown in Figure 1). According to 2016 census data (the most recent census), Ireland’s migrant population is highly concentrated in urban areas, in particular the city centres of Dublin, Cork, and Limerick, and the suburbs of West and North Dublin.⁷ These areas account for about half of the country’s migrants and contain electoral districts (EDs) that have as much as 59% foreign-born residents. Most rural areas, by contrast, have less than 5% foreign-born residents, with 81 EDs having only one or no foreign-born residents. Due to practical and financial constraints related to personnel, travel, and ensuring our participant quota, we have therefore decided to concentrate on Dublin, Cork, and Limerick as our data collection regions. This means that we will not be covering migrant and refugee students who are in more rural areas, however, we will include some of the smaller communities that make up the commuter belts of our urban centres that have a high enough migrant population.

⁵ McGinnity, F., Fahey, E., Quinn, E., Arnold, S., Maitre, B., & O’Connell, P. (2018). *Monitoring Report on Integration 2018*. Dublin: Economic and Social Research Institute.

⁶ Central Statistics Office. (2017c). *Population usually resident and present in the state 2011 to 2016 by sex, birth place, census year and age group*. Retrieved from CSO StatBank website: <https://statbank.cso.ie/px/pxeirestat/Statire/SelectVarVal/Define.asp?maintable=E7055&PLanguage=0>

⁷ Fahey, E., Russell, H., McGinnity, F., and Grotti, R. (2019). *Diverse neighbourhoods: An analysis of the residential distribution of immigrants in Ireland*. Dublin: Economic and Social Research Institute.

Figure 2. IMMERSE Data Collection Sites - Ireland

Image source: <https://yourfreetemplates.com/free-ireland-island-editable-map/>

8.2 Region Profiles

8.2.1 Region: Dublin

Figure 3. Counties of Dublin Regional Authority

Source: 2016 SAPMAP Viewer (<http://census.cso.ie/sapmap/>). The purple lines indicate county boundaries.

POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS

Dublin Regional Authority contains 4 counties (Fingal, Dublin City, South Dublin, and Dun Laoghaire/Rathdown, shown in Figure 3) which make up the city centre and surrounding suburbs. Dublin is Ireland's capital, the centre of political, administrative, and economic activity in the country. This is by far the most populous and population dense area of Ireland. According to the 2016 census, the population of the region was 1,347,359 or 28% of Ireland's total population (49% male and 51% female).⁸

Table 1. Age Distribution of Dublin Regional Authority

Age range	Number	Dublin Proportion	National Proportion
0-9	181,831	13.5%	14.4%
10-19	156,870	11.6%	13.1%
20-29	203,552	15.1%	12%
30-39	243,970	18.1%	15.8%
40-49	186,747	13.9%	14.4%
50-59	148,839	11%	12%
60+	225,550	16.7%	18.4%
Total	1,347,359	100%	

Source: Central Statistics Office, 2019a, 2019b.

The population of Dublin is more highly educated, has more income, and is more likely to be in higher social class categories than populations in the rest of the country, as Table 2 indicates. It is important to note, however, that there are significant variations in wealth, education, and other SES markers within Dublin; not all areas are equally affluent. Data from the Pobal HP Deprivation Index indicates that Dublin contains the most advantaged and some of the least advantaged electoral districts in the country, based on factors such as demographic and social census data, e.g. highest level of education completed, unemployment rates, and occupation classification.⁹

Table 2. Socio-economic Status Indicators: Dublin Region

	Dublin	Ireland ¹⁰
Completed higher education ¹¹	36%	28%
Median Gross Income per Household ¹²	€52,853	€45,256

⁸Unless otherwise indicated, all data for Dublin in this section comes from: Central Statistics Office. (2019a). *Census 2016 Sapmap Area_Nuts3 2016 Dublin*. Retrieved from: http://census.cso.ie/sapmap2016/Results.aspx?Geog_Type=NUTS3&Geog_Code=F97E459B-57ED-49C0-8A28-2BC1C7F08E88#SAPMAP_T9_901

⁹ Pobal. (n.d.). Deprivation Indices. <https://maps.pobal.ie/WebApps/DeprivationIndices/index.html>. For more information on the methodology of the Deprivation Index, see Haase & Pratschke. (2017). *The 2016 Pobal HP deprivation index for small areas (SA): Introduction and reference tables*. Dublin: Trutz Haase. <http://trutzaase.eu/wp/wp-content/uploads/The-2016-Pobal-HP-Deprivation-Index-Introduction-07.pdf>

¹⁰ Unless otherwise indicated, all data for Ireland comes from: Central Statistics Office. (2019b). *Census 2016 Sapmap Area: State*. http://census.cso.ie/sapmap2016/Results.aspx?Geog_Type=S&Geog_Code=S#SAPMAP_T9_901

¹¹ Bachelor Degree or National Diploma, Honours Bachelor Degree or Professional Qualification, Postgraduate Diploma or Degree, Doctorate (PhD) or higher, ISCED levels 5-8.

¹² Ireland income figure source: *Geographical Profiles of Income in Ireland 2016*

<https://www.cso.ie/en/releasesandpublications/ep/p-gpii/geographicalprofilesofincomeinireland2016/incomeinireland/#:~:text=The%20median%20gross%20income%20per,in%202016%2C%20see%20Table%201.1.>

	Dublin	Ireland ¹⁰
Proportion in top 2 social classes ¹³	40.5%	36.2%
Proportion in bottom 2 social classes	11.4%	14.1%

Sources: Central Statistics Office, 2019a, 2019b.

Dublin is also more diverse than the rest of the country in terms of ethnicity and religious orientation. While still overwhelmingly White Irish and Catholic, there are greater concentrations of groups with different ethnic backgrounds and religions in Dublin than Ireland in general, both in raw numbers and proportions.

Table 3. Ethnicity and Religion: Dublin Region

	Dublin Region	Ireland
Ethnic or cultural background		
White Irish/White Irish Traveller	75.9%	82.8%
Other White	11.6%	9.5%
Black or Black Irish	2.2%	1.4%
Asian or Asian Irish	3.8%	2.1%
Other	2.3%	1.5%
Religion		
Catholic	68.9%	78.3%
Other	12.5%	9.2%
No religion	14.4%	9.8%

Sources: Central Statistics Office, 2019a, 2019b.

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

Approximately 21% of the population of Dublin and its suburbs was foreign-born in 2016, which is higher than the national proportion of 17.3%. Table 4 shows the breakdown of the foreign-born population by region of birth. It indicates that Dublin has much lower concentrations of UK migrants than the rest of the country and higher concentrations from EU West countries, Africa, the Americas, and especially Asia. The most popular countries of origin in Dublin in 2016, besides the UK, were Poland, Romania, India, Brazil, and Lithuania.¹⁴

City income figures source: Central Statistics Office, Geographical Profiles of Income in Ireland, Table IIA14 (2019) https://statbank.cso.ie/px/pxeirestat/Database/eirestat/Geographical%20Profiles%20of%20Income%20in%20Ireland/Geographical%20Profiles%20of%20Income%20in%20Ireland_statbank.asp?SP=Geographical%20Profiles%20of%20Income%20in%20Ireland&PLanguage=0

¹³ The Census divides occupations into six classes based on skill level: professional workers, managerial and technical, non-manual, skilled manual, semi-skilled, and unskilled. There is also a 7th “residual” category for “all others gainfully occupied and unknown”. See “Socio-economic group” at <https://www.cso.ie/en/releasesandpublications/ep/p-cp9hdc/p8hdc/p9bgn/#:~:text=Social%20class%20The%20entire%20population,Unskilled%207%20All%20others%20gainfully>

¹⁴ Central Statistics Office. (2017e.) *Population usually resident and present in the state 2011-2016 by sex, aggregate town or rural area, birthplace, county of usual residence, and census year*. Retrieved from CSO Statbank website: <https://statbank.cso.ie/px/pxeirestat/Statire/SelectVarVal/Define.asp?maintable=E7050&PLanguage=0>

Table 4. Foreign-born Population of Dublin City and Suburbs by Region of Birth¹⁵

Country of birth	Dublin	Ireland
United Kingdom	19.7%	34.2%
EU West	11.5%	7.8%
EU East	26.9%	28.4%
Other Europe	4.6%	3.3%
Africa	8%	6.3%
Asia	18.2%	11.6%
Americas	10%	7.2%
Other	1.2%	1.2%

Source: Central Statistics Office, 2017d.

18% of Dublin’s population spoke a foreign language in 2016, with Polish being the most common, and about 85% of those who spoke a foreign language said they could speak English “well” or “very well.”

Migrants in Dublin are more concentrated in the inner city and in the suburbs to the north and west; the more affluent suburbs in the south have lower proportions of foreign-born residents. There are no significant differences between EU and non-EU migrant populations in their distribution around Dublin.¹⁶

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

Schools in Ireland are split into two levels: primary (ages 4/5 to usually 12) and post-primary (ages 12/13 to usually 18). For the 2019/20 academic year, the Dublin Regional Authority had 452 mainstream primary schools (142,192 pupils, 51% male and 49% female), 49 special primary schools (2793 pupils, 65% male and 35% female), and 184 post-primary schools (hereafter referred to as secondary level, 92,392 pupils, 50% male and 50% female).¹⁷ At both primary and secondary level, the majority of schools were located in Dublin City (43% at primary level and 41% at secondary level), commensurate with the concentration of the population there.

Irish schools can be differentiated by several factors – size, language, DEIS status, and religious “ethos”. Because Irish, alongside English, is an official language in Ireland, some schools offer some or all subjects using Irish as the language of instruction. Irish medium schools are the minority, however, as the vast majority of schools (90% nationally) use English as the language of instruction for most subjects, with compulsory classes for learning Irish.

In 2005, the Department of Education and Skills established a school classification system designed to help address educational disadvantage, known as Delivering Equality of Opportunity in Schools (DEIS). This is a national programme aimed at prioritising the educational needs of children and young people from disadvantaged backgrounds. Schools who have concentrations of

¹⁵ Central Statistics Office. (2017d). *Population usually resident and present in the state 2016 by town of usual residence, census year and birthplace*. Retrieved from CSO Statbank website:

<https://statbank.cso.ie/px/pxeirestat/Statire/SelectVarVal/Define.asp?maintable=E7051&PLanguage=0>

¹⁶ Fahey, E., Russell, H., McGinnity, F., and Grotti, R. (2019). *Diverse neighbourhoods: An analysis of the residential distribution of immigrants in Ireland*. Dublin: Economic and Social Research Institute.

¹⁷ Unless otherwise stated, all school data comes from school lists made publicly available by the Department of Education and Skills, found here: <https://www.education.ie/en/Publications/Statistics/Data-on-Individual-Schools/>

students from lower socio-economic backgrounds are designated as DEIS and receive extra supports.¹⁸ For the 2019/20 academic year, 22% of all primary schools and 27% of all secondary schools in Ireland were included in the programme.

Despite increasing secularisation in Ireland, particularly over the past two decades, religious institutions continue to play a key role in education delivery. Although the majority of schools are state-funded, “they are established by patron bodies [non-governmental, usually churches] who define the ethos of the school and appoint the board of management to run the school on a day to day basis”.¹⁹ Primary schools are overwhelmingly owned and managed by local Catholic parishes (almost 89% nationally), and secondary schools are largely under either Catholic patronage (nationally, 48%) or joint Catholic and Protestant patronage (21% nationally, known as inter-denominational). There has been a move in recent years toward multi-denominational schools under the patronage of non-religious organisations, like NGOs, but these remain in the minority as yet. Multi-denominational schools do not generally provide religious ‘faith formation’ education, though they may provide education about different religions and beliefs.

Table 5 shows the breakdown of primary (mainstream only²⁰) and secondary schools in Dublin Regional Authority (and nationally) by key characteristics in the Irish education system.

Table 5. Schools in Dublin Regional Authority by Level and Key Characteristics

	Primary Dublin	Primary National	Secondary Dublin	Secondary National
Total number of schools	452	3106	184	723
Average number of pupils	314	180	502	513
Min number of pupils	7	3	30	6
Max number of pupils	949	1114	1282	1538
DEIS status	162 (36%)	691 (22%)	64 (35%)	198 (27%)
Religious ethos				
Catholic	350 (77%)	2760 (89%)	98 (53%)	344 (48%)
Church of Ireland	33 (7%)	172 (5.5%)	9 (5%)	22 (3%)
Interdenominational	3 (<1%)	17 (<1%)	38 (21%)	150 (21%)
Other religion	8 (1.8%)	21 (<1%)	3 (1.6%)	5 (<1%)
Multi-denominational	58 (13%)	133 (4.3%)	36 (20%)	202 (28%)
Irish classification				
All subjects	37 (8%)	250 (8%)	10 (5%)	49 (7%)
Some subjects	3 (<1%)	29 (1%)	0	23 (3%)
No subjects	412 (91%)	2827 (91%)	174 (95%)	651 (90%)

Source: Department of Education and Skills, 2019.

Dublin’s primary schools are, on average, larger than schools in the country more generally, while secondary schools have an average number of pupils similar to the national average. Like the rest

¹⁸ See <https://www.education.ie/en/Schools-Colleges/Services/DEIS-Delivering-Equality-of-Opportunity-in-Schools-/for-more-details>.

¹⁹ See <https://www.education.ie/en/Schools-Colleges/Information/Diversity-of-Patronage/Diversity-of-Patronage-Survey-of-Parents.html>

²⁰ We do not include special schools in these figures, because we will be sampling from mainstream schools only. We unfortunately do not have the resources to adapt the data collection instrument for special needs, and moreover, special schools tend to be very small (less than 100 pupils altogether) which would not yield sufficient numbers for statistical analysis.

of the country, both primary and secondary schools have a large range of school sizes, from very small (less than 50 pupils) to very large (close to or over 1,000). In terms of religious ethos, Dublin has a lower proportion of Catholic and a much higher proportion of multi-denominational primary schools than the rest of the country, though this pattern is somewhat reversed at the secondary level. Given Dublin's diverse population, it is perhaps unsurprising that, though there are very few schools with a religious ethos other than Catholic, Protestant, or a combination of the two, those that do exist are mainly in Dublin (8 out of 21 at primary level and 3 out of 5 at secondary level).²¹ The most noticeable difference between Dublin's schools and the schools of Ireland in general is the larger proportion of DEIS designated schools at both primary and secondary level in Dublin.

8.2.2 Region: Cork

Figure 4. Cork City and Suburbs and Surrounding Electoral Districts

Source: 2016 SAPMAP Viewer (<http://census.cso.ie/sapmap/>). The black line indicates the boundary of Cork City and Suburbs, and the red lines indicate the boundaries of electoral districts within and surrounding Cork City. Electoral Districts filled in with beige are IMMENSE sampling areas, because they are either part of Cork City or have higher proportions of migrants (13% or higher).

POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS

Cork is Ireland's second largest urban settlement and is a cultural and economic centre. It has a population in the city centre of 125,657 and 208,669 including the surrounding suburbs (49% male and 51% female).²²

²¹ At the primary level, schools with other religious affiliations include Presbyterian (16), Muslim (2), Jewish (1), Methodist (1), and Quaker (1). At the secondary level, schools with other religious affiliations include Presbyterian (1), Jewish (1), Methodist (1), and Quaker (2).

²² Unless otherwise stated, all data for Cork in this section comes from: Central Statistics Office. (2019c). *Census 2016 Sapmap Area: Settlement Cork City and Suburbs*. Retrieved from: http://census.cso.ie/sapmap2016/Results.aspx?Geog_Type=ST2016&Geog_Code=2640ADAE-4EBB-460C-BBD4-D666DEBB3C8A

Table 6. Age Distribution of Cork City and Suburbs

Age range	Number	Cork Proportion	National Proportion
0-9	25,295	12.1%	14.4%
10-19	24,978	12%	13.1%
20-29	34,063	16.3%	12%
30-39	34,828	16.7%	15.8%
40-49	27,020	12.9%	14.4%
50-59	24,766	11.9%	12%
60+	37,719	18.1%	18.4%
Total	208,669	100%	

Sources: Central Statistics Office, 2019c, 2019b.

Cork's population is more representative of national trends in terms of socio-economic markers than Dublin. Cork does have a higher proportion of residents who have completed higher education and a slightly higher median household income than the rest of Ireland but is on par with the country in terms of socio-economic distribution based on occupation. Like Dublin, however, there is significant variation across the city. The Pobal HP Deprivation Index indicates that not only are there electoral districts ranging from "affluent" to "very disadvantaged" in Cork, but also that these districts are often in very close proximity to each other.²³

Table 7. Socio-economic Status Indicators: Cork City and Suburbs

	Cork	Ireland
Completed higher education	33%	28%
Median gross income per household ²⁴	€46,783	€45,256
Proportion in top 2 social classes	36%	36.2%
Proportion in bottom 2 social classes	14.2%	14.1%

Sources: Central Statistics Office, 2019c, 2019b.

Cork is also closer to national trends in terms of ethnicity and religion than Dublin. The city has very slightly higher proportions of Other White and Asian ethnic groups than the rest of the country and a higher proportion of people who do not belong to any religion.

Table 8. Ethnicity and Religion: Cork City and Suburbs

	Cork	Ireland
Ethnic or cultural background		
White Irish/White Irish Traveller	81.6%	82.8%
Other White	10%	9.5%
Black or Black Irish	1.4%	1.4%
Asian or Asian Irish	2.5%	2.1%
Other	1.7%	1.5%

²³ Pobal. (n.d.). *Deprivation Indices*. <https://maps.pobal.ie/WebApps/DeprivationIndices/index.html>

²⁴ See footnote 12.

	Cork	Ireland
Religion		
Catholic	76.3%	78.3%
Other	8.1%	9.2%
No religion	12.8%	9.8%

Sources: Central Statistics Office, 2019c, 2019b.

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

The proportion of Cork City and its suburbs that is foreign-born is 17.3%, the same as the national proportion. However, as Table 9 indicates, Cork's foreign-born residents are more likely to be from the EU West and Asian countries and less likely to be from the UK than foreign-born residents in Ireland in general. The most common countries of origin for Cork's foreign-born residents in 2016 were Poland, EU West countries (France, Spain, and Germany), and the United States. The most common non-EU origin countries were India, Brazil, and China.²⁵

Table 9. Foreign-born Population of Cork City and Suburbs by Region of Birth²⁶

Country of birth	Cork	Ireland
United Kingdom	23.3%	34.2%
EU West	15.6%	7.8%
EU East	27.9%	28.4%
Other Europe	3%	3.3%
Africa	6.9%	6.3%
Asia	14.5%	11.6%
Americas	7.6%	7.2%
Other	1.4%	1.2%

Source: Central Statistics Office, 2017d.

14% of Cork's population spoke a foreign language in 2016, with Polish being the most common, and about 86% of foreign language speakers reported being able to speak English "well" or "very well".

Migrants in Cork are concentrated in the electoral districts in the city centre, with a few districts in the suburbs to the southwest and to the east having moderately high proportions of foreign-born residents (17-22%). There are no significant differences between EU and non-EU migrant

²⁵ Central Statistics Office. (2017d). *Population usually resident and present in the state 2016 by town of usual residence, census year and birthplace*. Retrieved from CSO Statbank website: <https://statbank.cso.ie/px/pxeirestat/Statire/SelectVarVal/Define.asp?maintable=E7051&PLanguage=0>. This dataset does not have full disaggregation of countries of origin, so many are grouped into regions rather than numbers being reported for individual countries. "Other Asia" and "Other Africa" had larger numbers than India, Brazil, or China, but these categories represent large regions with dozens of countries.

²⁶ Central Statistics Office. (2017d). *Population usually resident and present in the state 2016 by town of usual residence, census year and birthplace*. Retrieved from CSO Statbank website: <https://statbank.cso.ie/px/pxeirestat/Statire/SelectVarVal/Define.asp?maintable=E7051&PLanguage=0>

populations in their distribution around Cork, but Cork does not contain any of the country's top 10 electoral districts in terms of non-EU population (Dublin contains 6 and Limerick contains 3).²⁷

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

For the purposes of this project, we will be sampling schools from Cork City and Suburbs plus the full electoral districts of Ballincollig, Inishkenny, Lehenagh, Carrigtohill, and the settlement of Midleton. For the 2019/20 academic year, our sampling area had 83 primary schools (25,207 pupils, 51% male and 49% female), 13 special primary schools (800 pupils, 66% male, and 34% female), and 40 secondary schools (20,424 pupils, 50.6% male and 49.4% female). At both the primary and secondary level, the majority of schools are located in Cork City centre, 55% at primary and 65% at secondary.

Table 10 shows the breakdown of primary (mainstream only) and secondary schools in Cork City and surrounding suburbs and EDs by key characteristics of the Irish education system. At the primary level, Cork schools are larger on average than in the country in general, though secondary school average size is on par. Like the rest of the country, there is a wide range of school sizes in Cork. There are disproportionately more DEIS status schools in Cork, a pattern also noted in Dublin. In terms of religious ethos, Cork has proportionately more multi-denominational schools at primary level and proportionately more Catholic and fewer multi-denominational schools at secondary level than the rest of the country. Cork does not have any schools affiliated with religions other than Catholicism and the Church of Ireland (or a combination of both). Cork's schools reflect national trends in terms of Irish language classification.

Table 10. Schools in Cork City and Surrounding Suburbs and EDs

	Primary Cork	Primary National	Secondary Cork	Secondary National
Total number of schools	83	3106	40	723
Average number of pupils	303	180	510	513
Min number of pupils	7	3	71	6
Max number of pupils	840	1114	1361	1538
DEIS status	27 (33%)	691 (22%)	14 (35%)	198 (27%)
Religious ethos				
Catholic	68 (82%)	2760 (89%)	25 (62.5%)	344 (48%)
Church of Ireland	5 (6%)	172 (5.5%)	2 (5%)	22 (3%)
Interdenominational	0	17 (<1%)	10 (25%)	150 (21%)
Other religion	0	21 (<1%)	0	5 (<1%)
Multi-denominational	9 (11%)	133 (4.3%)	3 (7.5%)	202 (28%)
Irish classification				
All subjects	10 (12%)	250 (8%)	3 (7.5%)	49 (7%)
Some subjects	1 (1.2%)	29 (1%)	2 (5%)	23 (3%)
No subjects	71 (86%)	2827 (91%)	35 (87.5%)	651 (90%)

Source: Department of Education and Skills, 2019.

²⁷ Fahey, E., Russell, H., McGinnity, F., and Grotti, R. (2019). *Diverse neighbourhoods: An analysis of the residential distribution of immigrants in Ireland*. Dublin: Economic and Social Research Institute. The ED of Custom House B in Waterford has the highest concentration of non-EU migrants in the country, but this is an extremely small ED with less than 300 residents.

8.2.3 Region: Limerick

Figure 5. Limerick Local Electoral Areas and Electoral Districts

Source: 2016 SAPMAP Viewer (<http://census.cso.ie/sapmap/>). Black lines indicate Electoral Area boundaries, and red lines indicate Electoral District boundaries. The three Electoral Areas (Limerick City North, West, and East) in this figure combine to form the Municipal District of Limerick. Electoral Districts filled in with beige indicate the areas from which our school sample will be drawn, as these areas are either part of Limerick City Centre or have migrant populations over 7%.

POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS

Limerick is Ireland’s third largest urban centre, with a population in Limerick City of 94,192 and 104,952 including the electoral areas that make up the full municipal district (49.5% male and 50.5% female).²⁸

Table 11. Age Distribution of Municipal District of Limerick

Age range	Number	Limerick Proportion	National Proportion
0-9	14,266	13.6%	14.4%
10-19	13,439	12.8%	13.1%
20-29	16,079	15.3%	12%
30-39	17,323	16.5%	15.8%
40-49	13,873	13.2%	14.4%
50-59	11,738	11.2%	12%
60+	18,234	17.4%	18.4%
Total	104,952	100%	

Source: Central Statistics Office, 2019d, 2019b.

²⁸ Unless otherwise stated, all data for Limerick in this section comes from: Central Statistics Office. (2019d). *Census 2016 Sapmap Area: Municipal District Limerick*. Retrieved from: http://census.cso.ie/sapmap2016/Results.aspx?Geog_Type=MD2014&Geog_Code=C87338E0-A7B9-4305-B7F2-FC23410FEFE2

28.5% of Limerick residents had completed higher education in 2016, a proportion in line with the national rate. Median household income, however, was 13% lower, and Limerick had a lower proportion of working adults who were in professional or managerial/technical occupations (top 2 social classes), indicating that it was the least affluent overall of our three sampling areas. The Pobal HP Deprivation Index indicates that Limerick City has only two EDs that are rated as “affluent”, while 16 (out of 38) are rated as “disadvantaged”, “very disadvantaged” or “extremely disadvantaged”.²⁹ This was partially due to high unemployment in Limerick in 2016; the unemployment rate was approximately 17%, and almost half of the electoral districts in Limerick City were “unemployment blackspots”, where unemployment was over 27%.³⁰

Table 12. Socio-economic Status Indicators: Municipal District of Limerick

	Limerick	Ireland
Completed higher education	28.5%	28%
Median gross income per household ³¹	€39,373	€45,256
Proportion in top 2 social classes	32.9%	36.2%
Proportion in bottom 2 social classes	14.1%	14.1%

Sources: Central Statistics Office, 2019d, 2019b.

Limerick has higher concentrations of Asian ethnic groups and slightly higher concentrations of Black ethnic groups than in the rest of the country but is very similar in terms of religious identifications.

Table 13. Ethnicity and Religion: Municipal District of Limerick

	Limerick	Ireland
Ethnic or cultural background		
White Irish/White Irish Traveller	79.8%	82.8%
Other White	9.4%	9.5%
Black or Black Irish	1.8%	1.4%
Asian or Asian Irish	3.6%	2.1%
Other	1.6%	1.5%
Religion		
Catholic	76.8%	78.3%
Other	9.5%	9.2%
No religion	10%	9.8%

Sources: Central Statistics Office, 2019d, 2019b.

²⁹ Pobal. (n.d.). Deprivation Indices. <https://maps.pobal.ie/WebApps/DeprivationIndices/index.html>

³⁰ Central Statistics Office. (2017b). *Census 2016 Summary Results – Part 2*. Dublin: Central Statistics Office. Data on unemployment comes from Chapter 2 of this document, discussion of unemployment blackspots p.25.

https://www.cso.ie/en/media/csoie/newsevents/documents/census2016summaryresultspart2/Census_2016_Summary_Results_%E2%80%93_Part_2.pdf

³¹ See footnote 12.

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

18.4% of Limerick City and its suburbs is foreign-born, slightly higher than the national proportion of 17.3%. Table 7 indicates that Limerick has lower concentrations of UK migrants and higher concentrations of EU East and Asian migrants than are seen in the rest of the country. In Limerick City and County, the most common countries of origin (other than the UK) are Poland, Latvia, Pakistan, Afghanistan, and Lithuania.³²

Table 14. Foreign-born Population of Limerick City and Suburbs by Region of Birth³³

Country of birth	Limerick	Ireland
United Kingdom	20.8%	34.2%
EU West	5.9%	7.8%
EU East	34.3%	28.4%
Other Europe	3.4%	3.3%
Africa	7.6%	6.3%
Asia	21.5%	11.6%
Americas	6%	7.2%
Other	0.6%	1.2%

Source: Central Statistics Office, 2017d.

About 16% of Limerick residents spoke a foreign language in 2016, with Polish being the most popular, and 82% of foreign-language speakers reported being able to speak English “well” or “very well”.

Like Cork and Dublin, migrants in Limerick are heavily concentrated in the city centre, with some moderate concentrations found in electoral districts to the east and to the southwest, just outside the city centre. Also like Cork and Dublin, there is no significant difference in the distribution of EU and non-EU migrants in Limerick.³⁴

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

For the purposes of this project, we will be sampling from the Municipal District of Limerick but excluding those electoral districts outside the city centre with low concentrations of migrants, as indicated in Figure 5. For the 2019/20 academic year, our sampling area had 35 mainstream primary schools (11,028 pupils, 51% male and 49% female), 8 special primary schools (575 pupils, 67% male and 33% female), and 15 secondary schools (8,443 pupils, 50.6% male and 49.4% female). Schools at both the primary and secondary level are concentrated in Limerick City Centre.

Table 15 shows the breakdown of primary (mainstream only) and secondary schools in our Limerick sampling area by key characteristics of the Irish education system. Like Dublin and Cork, Limerick

³² Central Statistics Office. (2017e.) *Population usually resident and present in the state 2011-2016 by sex, aggregate town or rural area, birthplace, county of usual residence, and census year*. Retrieved from CSO Statbank website: <https://statbank.cso.ie/px/pxeirestat/Statire/SelectVarVal/Define.asp?maintable=E7050&PLanguage=0>. Full disaggregation of countries of birth just for the Municipal District of Limerick was not available, so data for Limerick City and County was used.

³³ Central Statistics Office. (2017d). *Population usually resident and present in the state 2016 by town of usual residence, census year and birthplace*. Retrieved from CSO Statbank website: <https://statbank.cso.ie/px/pxeirestat/Statire/SelectVarVal/Define.asp?maintable=E7051&PLanguage=0>

³⁴ Fahey, E., Russell, H., McGinnity, F., and Grotti, R. (2019). *Diverse neighbourhoods: An analysis of the residential distribution of immigrants in Ireland*. Dublin: Economic and Social Research Institute.

had larger primary schools than the national average, and slightly large schools at the secondary level, as well. Again, we see a wide range of school sizes at both levels. Religious affiliations are on par with national trends, though like Cork, Limerick does not have any schools managed by religious institutions other than Catholic or Church of Ireland (or a combination of both). Limerick has a greater proportion of DEIS designated schools at the primary level but is on par with national proportions at the secondary level. There is a greater proportion of Irish classification schools in the Limerick sampling area than is seen in the rest of the country.

Table 15. Schools in Limerick and Surrounding Suburbs and EDs

	Primary Limerick	Primary National	Secondary Limerick	Secondary National
Total number of schools	35	3106	15	723
Average number of pupils	315	180	563	513
Min number of pupils	32	3	118	6
Max number of pupils	889	1114	1200	1538
DEIS status	12 (34%)	691 (22%)	4 (27%)	198 (27%)
Religious ethos				
Catholic	32 (91%)	2760 (89%)	8 (53%)	344 (48%)
Church of Ireland	1 (3%)	172 (5.5%)	1 (7%)	22 (3%)
Interdenominational	0	17 (<1%)	3 (20%)	150 (21%)
Other religion	0	21 (<1%)	0	5 (<1%)
Multi-denominational	2 (6%)	133 (4.3%)	3 (20%)	202 (28%)
Irish classification				
All subjects	5 (14%)	250 (8%)	2 (13%)	49 (7%)
Some subjects	0	29 (1%)	0	23 (3%)
No subjects	30 (86%)	2827 (91%)	13 (87%)	651 (90%)

Source: Department of Education and Skills, 2019.

8.3 School Sampling

Following the strategy outlined in the general sampling section, we will employ a stratified sampling approach to select schools for recruitment. Our aim is to collect data from approximately 800 migrant children, though the Irish dataset will be larger than this, as we will be using the whole-class approach described in the classroom sampling section.

Because we want to capture as much variety as possible, and in order to ensure sufficient numbers for statistical analysis, we split the sample more evenly between each our sampling regions, rather than dividing by strict proportionality. Dublin is a much bigger centre than Cork or Limerick, with 5 times the number of students as Cork and 12 times the number of students as Limerick. A strictly proportional division of our sample would result in the Dublin subsample overwhelming and drowning out the Cork and Limerick subsamples. We also split the sample evenly across the

primary and secondary levels. For each of our sampling regions, therefore, we created a stratified random sample for primary level and for secondary level.

We decided to include only recognised, state-aided schools, as non-state-aided schools are very few in number in Ireland, and no central source of data could be found for them.³⁵ After reviewing the information available on individual state-aided schools from the Department of Education and Skills (DES) and previous research on schools in Ireland, we decided also to exclude very small schools (i.e. 120 pupils or fewer) and schools where Irish was the language of instruction for all subjects. A report by the DES in 2017 indicated that Irish medium schools have extremely low numbers of non-Irish students, much lower than English medium schools, giving them a poor rate of return considering our target population.³⁶ Very small schools will not yield a large enough number of participants to calculate school effects. This exclusion had the side effect of excluding most of the schools in Dublin with religious affiliations other than Catholic and Church of Ireland at the primary level; all of the Presbyterian, Methodist, Jewish, and Quaker schools had fewer than 120 pupils, and so also ended up being left out of the sample.

One key piece of information that was not available at the individual school level was proportion of migrant students, or anything that could be used as a proxy for migrant status, such as nationality, country of birth, or home language. Data on nationality/country of birth is collected by the DES, but it is not publicly available, and we were not permitted access to it for the purposes of this project. Because of this, we will employ a 2-stage sampling process. We created a sampling pool using individual school data that was available, using the characteristics described in the following section, and, in part, sampling from areas with relatively high concentrations of migrants in the general population according to data from the 2016 Census, as described in the region descriptions above. Schools will be randomly selected using this sampling framework as the first stage. They will be contacted and invited to participate if they have a minimum of 25% migrant students as the second stage.

8.3.1 Key characteristics used in sampling framework

We used individual school data from primary and post-primary school lists compiled by the Department of Education and Skills and publicly available on the DES website, found here: <https://www.education.ie/en/Publications/Statistics/Data-on-Individual-Schools/>. The characteristics we used to create the first stage sampling framework were: school size, religious affiliation, and DEIS status.

³⁵ Data from the Central Statistics Office indicates that in 2017 (most recent data available), less than 1% of students in Ireland at each primary and secondary level were attending educational institutions that were not aided by the Department of Education and Skills. See *Persons in receipt of full-time education by age, sex, type of institution and year*. Retrieved from

<https://statbank.cso.ie/px/pxeirestat/statire/SelectVarVal/Define.asp?Maintable=EDA38&Planguage=0>

³⁶ Department of Education and Skills. (2017). *Nationality/Country of Birth in Schools*. Retrieved from: <https://www.education.ie/en/Publications/Statistics/Statistical-Reports/Analysis-of-Nationality-in-Primary-and-Post-Primary-Schools-2010-2011-2015-2016.pdf>

SCHOOL SIZE

This refers to the total number of students in the school based on student registration at the beginning of the 2019 academic year. As was already mentioned, we did not include schools with 120 pupils or fewer. We divided raw numbers into two categories: small (120-400 pupils) and large (401+ pupils) to facilitate creation of the sampling framework.

RELIGIOUS AFFILIATION

This refers to an affiliation to a religious institution in the form of school management and 'ethos'. This also had two categories: religious affiliated and non-religious affiliated. Religious affiliations are almost exclusively Catholic, Church of Ireland, or a combination of the two (known as interdenominational). Schools that are not affiliated to a religious institution are known as multi-denominational.

DEIS STATUS

DEIS status is a proxy for socio-economic status (see p.36 in Dublin section above for an explanation of DEIS). Again we had two categories: DEIS and non-DEIS. DEIS status is determined by the DES, according to a formula that takes into account concentrations of students from disadvantaged backgrounds.

PRESENCE OF MIGRANT STUDENTS

Because proportion of migrant students is not publicly available, we have not included it as a key characteristic here. As discussed in the general sampling section, we are aiming to have the core of our sample be made up of TCNs and those EU nationals that are economic migrants to Ireland. Census data indicates that the most common countries of origin for Ireland's migrants are EU East countries, and the largest migrant community in each of our three sampling regions is Polish. Previous research also indicates that EU East migrants have the lower proportions of third level completion among working adults (compared to Irish-born and other migrant groups) and higher levels of unemployment than Irish born.³⁷ Moreover, Eurostat data shows that Ireland's median household income is significantly higher than EU East countries, supporting their classification as economic migrants.³⁸ Therefore, due to the significant concentration of EU East migrants in Ireland as economic migrants, we will include in our sample those countries that are outside the Schengen Area (Romania, Bulgaria, Croatia, and Cyprus), plus Poland, Estonia, Latvia, and Lithuania.

8.3.2 Categories resulting from framework and sampling pool

For each of our three sampling areas, Dublin, Cork, and Limerick, we created a sampling pool for primary level and secondary level, according to the three key characteristics above. Not all combinations of the three characteristics were viable in all areas at both levels, so some were eliminated. For example, there are no large, DEIS primary schools in Cork that have no religious affiliation, so we do not need this category for Cork.

³⁷ Economic and Social Research Institute. (2019). *ESRI Review of research 2018*. Dublin: Economic and Social Research Institute.

³⁸ Eurostat. (2020). *Mean and median income by household type*. Retrieved from: https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=ilc_di04&lang=en

After excluding very small schools and Irish medium schools, there were 364 primary schools and 165 secondary schools in Dublin, 64 primary schools and 36 secondary schools in Cork, and 28 primary schools and 12 secondary schools in Limerick eligible for our sampling pool. Using the key characteristics of size, DEIS status, and religious affiliation, we created the following categories for primary and secondary level, with the number of eligible schools in each sampling region and category listed:

Table 16. Number of eligible schools in primary sampling categories by region

Primary Level Categories	Dublin	Cork	Limerick
Small/DEIS/religious affiliation	117	21 ³⁹	9
Small/DEIS/no religious affiliation	3		
Small/non-DEIS/religious affiliation	89	19	11
Small/non-DEIS/no religious affiliation	19	3	2
Large/DEIS/religious affiliation	12		
Large/DEIS/no religious affiliation	7		
Large/non-DEIS/religious affiliation	102	20	6
Large/non-DEIS/no religious affiliation	15	1	

Table 17. Number of eligible schools in secondary sampling categories by region

Secondary Level Categories	Dublin	Cork	Limerick
Small/DEIS/religious affiliation	30	12	2
Small/DEIS/no religious affiliation	9		
Small/non-DEIS/religious affiliation	20	3	
Small/non-DEIS/no religious affiliation	5	1	1
Large/DEIS/religious affiliation	21		1
Large/DEIS/no religious affiliation	1	1	
Large/non-DEIS/religious affiliation	69	17	7
Large/non-DEIS/no religious affiliation	10		

Again, because we want to capture as much variety as possible, we will attempt to spread the schools we visit evenly across the sampling categories. Dublin has eligible schools in every category, so we will attempt to collect data from at least one school in each category. For Cork and Limerick, who do not have schools in each category, we will attempt to collect data from one school in each viable category and two schools in DEIS categories if possible, as data from the DES indicates that non-Irish students tend to be concentrated in DEIS schools.⁴⁰ Altogether, we would be visiting approximately 16 schools in Dublin, 12 schools in Cork, and 10 schools in Limerick, for a total of 38 schools.

³⁹ There was one school in the large/DEIS/no religious affiliation category, but it was only 20 students over the small/large threshold, so we decided to include it in the small/DEIS/no religious affiliation category.

⁴⁰ Department of Education and Skills. (2017). *Nationality/Country of Birth in Schools*. Retrieved from: <https://www.education.ie/en/Publications/Statistics/Statistical-Reports/Analysis-of-Nationality-in-Primary-and-Post-Primary-Schools-2010-2011-2015-2016.pdf>

We began by randomly selecting up to four schools in each category, the first (or first two) as the schools we will contact for recruitment first and the others as back-ups if needed. If all four schools are not interested in participating or do not have the required 25% migrant students, we will randomly select another four schools from that category. If we exhaust a category without being able to find a school from to collect data, we will randomly select from another category, with DEIS schools as the priority.

ASYLUM-SEEKING CHILDREN

Though the majority of our sampling will be done according to this stratified random approach, there are specific schools that we want to include in our data collection that have unique characteristics and significantly increase the likelihood of including difficult to reach participants – namely children in the asylum process. Asylum-seekers in Ireland live in state-provided accommodation known as Direct Provision, including about 1,500 children. There are 32 accommodation centres in Ireland,⁴¹ and the children who reside in them attend nearby schools. Each of our three sampling areas has at least one direct provision centre, and we are using contacts to determine which of the surrounding schools are attended by the children of those centres in order to attempt to recruit these schools into our study. If we did not locate and target such schools directly, it is unlikely that we would have any asylum-seeking children in our sample.

8.4 School Sampling – Plan B

In the event that the stratified random sampling technique for selecting school sites discussed above yields low response rates, we will use the back-up strategy involving non-probability sampling techniques (as described in the general sampling strategy) that allow us to use our contacts and networks to recruit schools to participate. We will still sample from each of the categories from the stratified sampling framework, but we will choose sites purposively, rather than randomly, in order to maximise response rates in order to reach our participant quota. To carry this out, we will make use of contacts at the Department of Education and schools, plus other networks and contacts formed during the first phase of the IMMERSE project.

8.5 Child/classroom Sampling

We will use a census-type approach for sampling classrooms within schools, as described in the general sampling strategy section. We will focus on specific year groups, i.e. 1st/3rd/5th classes at primary level and 1st/3rd/5th year at secondary level, as each year group covers two age groups. We will attempt to collect data from approximately 50 students in each group, which is likely 2 classrooms per year group, assuming an average class size of 25. If there are more than 2 classes for a given year group, we will chose the ones to survey randomly, unless they are grouped deliberately, in which case, we will make a calculated decision based on our target population and the criteria by which students are divided into classes. We will survey from all our selected year groups in each school type we visit to ensure that we have sufficient and proportionate

⁴¹ This is according to the Reception and Integration Agency (http://www.ria.gov.ie/en/RIA/Pages/Reception_Dispersal_Accommodation), though other sources give different figures.

representation of each age group across all types of schools delineated in our school sampling framework.

8.6 Sampling in Non-formal Education Environments

Formal schooling dominates the education landscape in Ireland for children of compulsory school age (6-16 years), and attendance is essentially universal, including for migrant and refugee children. In fact, most children are enrolled in full-time formal school by age 5 and remain in school until they have completed secondary school, usually age 18. Concerns about access have been raised with respect to asylum-seeking children living in emergency accommodation due to an overextended Direct Provision system⁴² and children who arrive late in the school year, but these groups appear to be quite small.⁴³ A lack of available data makes it difficult to be certain, but it appears that the majority of asylum-seeking children in Ireland are able to access primary and secondary education. The non-formal education sector therefore focuses on early childhood education (also known as preschool or pre-primary and covers children ages 2-5, which is outside the IMMERSE age range), early school leavers (young people who leave secondary education without completing qualifications), and community education geared toward adults, particularly those from disadvantaged backgrounds or with little formal education, provided through Education and Training Boards (ETBs).⁴⁴ Early school leavers can take advantage of some schemes, funded by government but provided outside formal schooling, such as Youthreach and the School Completion Programme, in order to gain education qualifications to help them enter employment or third level education.

Because school attendance is essentially universal, the numbers of young migrants or refugees who would be present in non-formal education environments and not present in formal schooling is quite low, too low to provide sufficient data for more than basic descriptive statistics. We will therefore concentrate our questionnaire-based data collection efforts on formal schools and visit non-formal environments for the qualitative data collection. Such non-formal environments may include:

Youthreach or Youthreach-type programs/organisations, e.g. the Cork Life Centre

- Migrant reception centres
- Language assistance for migrants, e.g. Welcome English Language Centre
- Specialised program for unaccompanied minors in Dublin (CDETb)

⁴² Hennigan, R. (2019). *The reception conditions directive: One year on*. Dublin: Irish Refugee Council.

⁴³ Ni Raghallaigh, M., Smith, K., & Scholtz, J. (2019). *Safe haven – the needs of refugee children arriving in Ireland through the Irish refugee protection programme: An exploratory study*. Dublin: Children's Rights Alliance.

⁴⁴ ETBs are part of the national education structure but operate on a local level.

9 Appendix C – Italy (Research Partner: SCIT)

9.1 Regional Sampling

Sampling will cover state schools and educational centres in the following Italian Regions: Lombardy, Piedmont, Lazio, Campania and Sicily, which cover different areas (north, centre, south and islands) of the Country. In these Regions, the cities surveyed will be respectively: Milan, Turin, Rome, Naples and Catania. The cities are good representatives of the Regions they are part of. The selection of the regions also follows the criterion of geographical, social, cultural and economic heterogeneity of the population surveyed. Socio-economic status is much higher in the north of the Country compared to the centre and especially compared to the south and the islands. In 2017, the per capita financial wealth of households was between 103,000 euros in the North West and almost 39,000 euros in the South.¹ According to 2018 data from the Italian Statistical Institute (ISTAT, latest figures available), 16.8% of people in the north west are at risk of poverty or social exclusion (the area in which Turin and Milan are located), compared to 23% in the Centre (where the city of Rome is) and 44% and 47.5% in the south and in the islands (against a national average of 27% for the entire population).

According to data from the National Institute for the Educational Evaluation of Instruction and Training (INVALSI, 2019), the areas considered also differ with respect to students' results and learning in the disciplines of Italian and mathematics. Starting from secondary school there is a significant divergence; results are much better in the north than in the south and the islands, while the Centre is on par with the overall Italian average.

The distribution of migrants and foreign students in the areas is very different, with higher rates in the centre-north than in the south. The south and the islands, however, are the areas where the challenge of first reception of migrants coming through the Mediterranean path has been faced in recent decades, although their routes then mostly move to other areas of the country.

Table 1: Distribution of foreign population (residents born abroad) by geographical area

Region	Foreign citizens				% Foreign citizens of Italian population
	Male	Female	Total	%	
1. Lombardy	577,342	604,430	1,181,772	22.5%	11.75%
2. Lazio	328,849	354,560	683,409	13.0%	11.62%
5. Piedmont	203,891	224,020	427,911	8.1%	9.82%
7. Campania	132,363	132,800	265,163	5.0%	4.57%
8. Sicily	105,182	94,840	200,022	3.8%	4.00%
ITALY	2,536,787	2,718,716	5,255,503		100.0%

Source: ISTAT, 1 Jan. 2019

The five cities well reflect their Regions' specificities as far as integration policies and services are concerned.

¹ See the Report of Banca d'Italia: *Economie regionali. L'economia delle regioni italiane Dinamiche recenti e aspetti strutturali*, November 2019, p. 23

Although there is a great deal of variety between the geographical contexts, in order to allow reaching the participant quota with the available time and resources, the sampling strategy will restrict data collection to those schools that are more likely to host a major number of migrants (see section 2, School sampling), and these are normally attended by students from middle/low social classes. In the five cities, the sampling will cover only the urban areas; however, different districts and zones will be involved, with the aim of recovering a certain variety internal to the city contexts.

In the school environment, the data collection will cover all school orders and grades included in the IMMERSE target (students aged 6 to 18 years). For a schematic understanding of the organization of the Italian school system, see the figure below.²

Figure 1: Italian School System

Source: OECD, 2018

² The figure is taken from OECD, Education GPS, available at: https://gpseducation.oecd.org/Content/MapOfEducationSystem/ITA/ITA_2011_EN.pdf

9.2 Region Profiles

9.2.1 Region: Milan (Lombardy)

POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS

Located in the northern Region of Lombardy, which is home to 16.6% of the entire Italian population, the city of Milan has 1,378,689 inhabitants (official residents in the city on 1 January 2019). It is the second largest municipality by number of inhabitants in the Country; 48% are male, and 52% female.

The following table reports the distribution for age groups, which shows a concentration of the population in the 45 to 59 year range.

Table 2. Milan – age groups distribution - absolute values and percentages (2019)

Age	Male	Female	Total	
			N	%
0-14	91,102	85,778	176,880	12.8%
15-29	102,756	92,439	195,195	14.1%
30-44	149,690	144,211	293,901	21.3%
45-59	156,958	164,575	321,533	23.3%
60-74	95,454	116,845	212,299	15.3%
75-89	61,302	96,367	157,669	11.4%
90-100+	5,289	15,923	21,212	2%
Total	662,551	716,138	1,378,689	100%

Source: ISTAT, 1 Jan. 2019

The population under the IMMERSE target ages (6-18 years) is 310.626 persons, or 4.7% of the inhabitants.

Table 3. Milan – IMMERSE target - age groups and gender distribution - absolute values (2019)

Age groups	Male	Female	Total
6-10	31,307	29,450	60,757
11-13	18,695	17,470	36,165
14-18	30,270	28,121	58,391
TOTAL	80,272	75,041	155,313

Source: ISTAT, 1 Jan. 2019

As far as the social-economic conditions are concerned, data regarding the resident's annual income in 2017 by income bracket shows that the majority of the population are in the medium classes of income, although a significant proportion of the population declare an income not higher

than 10,000 euros per year (24%). Overall, this city can be included among the wealthiest areas of the country, considering that in the same year the average income in Italy was of 20,949 euros.

Table 4: Milan - residents annual income in 2017 by amount class (values in percentage of the total contributors)

Amount classes	0 euros or less	0-10.000 euros	10.000-15.000 euros	15.000-26.000 euros	26.000-55.000 euros	55.000-75.000 euros	75.000-120.000 euros	120.000 euros or more
Milan	0.5%	24.1%	10.5%	25%	26%	5.1%	4.2%	3.3%

Source: ISTAT, 27 May 2020

The available data on education relates to the level of instruction (highest level completed)³ of the population of 15 years and over in Lombardy region in 2019.

They show that schooling levels in Lombardy are in line with or above the national average, as shown by the following table.

Table 5. Levels of education (ISCED classification) of 15 years and over population in Lombardy (percentages on the total)

Territory	ISCED 1 or lower	ISCED 2	ISCED 3 (half)	ISCED 3 (completed)	ISCED 4 or 5
Italy	16.2%	32.4%	5.5%	30.9%	14.9%
Lombardy	13.5%	33%	8.3%	28.8%	16%

Source: SCIT adaptation from ISTAT, 2019

In Lombardy the early school leavers among the population from 18 to 24 years old are the 11.5%, a rate lower than the national one (13.5%).

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MIGRANT POPULATION

Migrants in Milan⁴ constitute the 14.5% of the overall population (268,215) and they are equally distributed in terms of gender.

The largest foreign community is the one coming from Egypt with 12.5% of all foreigners present on the territory, followed by Romania (10.8%) and the Philippines (10.3%).

In Milan, in 2019, there have been 10,137 new requests for asylum, subsidiary protection and/or special protection, of which 2,014 have been approved.⁵

³ The correspondence of ISCED levels to the Italian education system is the following. ISCED 1: primary education; ISCED 2: lower secondary education; ISCED 3: upper secondary education; ISCED 4: post-secondary non-tertiary education; ISCED 5, 6 and 7: tertiary education

⁴ In the statistics reported, count for migrants foreign citizens, e.g. all the persons of non-Italian citizenship who are habitually resident in Italy.

⁵ National Commission for the Right to Asylum, Statistical Report, available at:

http://www.libertaciviliimmigrazione.dlci.interno.gov.it/sites/default/files/allegati/quaderno_statistico_per_gli_anni_1990_2019_0.pdf

In 2019, Lombardy was the Italian region with the second highest number of unaccompanied minors received (816 minors, equal to 11.2% of the total number of UAM in the Country) (Ministry of Labour and Social Policies official report at 31 December 2019). The most recent data concerning UAMs in Milan from 2018. In this year, the Municipality of Milan welcomed 673 unaccompanied foreign minors into its educational communities. Among the most represented nationalities are Egyptian (227), Albanian (60), Kosovan (56), Gambian (50) and Moroccan (33).⁶

Lombardy is among the top three Italian regions in terms of the number of UAM reception facilities (13.5%) (Ministry of Labour and Social Policies official report at 31 December 2019).

In Milan and more broadly in Lombardy, as in the overall national territory, UAMs mostly attend the Provincial Centres for Adult Education (CPIA). In the CPIA of the region there are minors of 18 nationalities, in particular from North Africa and sub-Saharan Africa: among the most represented are Egypt (over 200 minors), Gambia (about 90 minors), Guinea, Albania, Senegal and Somalia (from 30 to 50).

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

In Lombardy there are 1,120 schools⁷ and 19 CPIA (MIUR, 2019). In the city of Milan, there are 274 schools articulated in 510 school complexes (213 primary, 118 secondary first grade, 179 secondary second grade).⁸

The province of Milan is one of the territories with the highest presence of pupils without Italian citizenship in all school levels: 88,957 in the school year 2017/2018, which accounts for 10.6% of the total number of pupils without Italian citizenship in the whole country. 63% of these are second generation minors, a proportion in line with the percentage at the national level. With regard to their distribution in the diverse school grade (percentage on the total of students), the students without Italian citizenship are 18.1% of those in nursery school, 17.2% of those in primary school, and 15.9% and 12.3% respectively of those in secondary lower and upper school.

In the city of Milan, in the school year 2017/2018, pupils without Italian citizenship are 39,486, 20% of the total number of students. Another useful data to frame the context of Milan is the incidence of schools with 30% and over of foreign pupils, which in the province reaches 12.6% of schools, far above the national average.

With regards to the countries of origin, in 2017/2018, the top four are the Philippines (18.9%), Egypt (16.3%), China (11.4%) and Romania (5.4%). It is worth pointing out that the municipality of Milan

⁶ Data from the Municipality of Milan official website: [https://www.comune.milano.it/-/politiche-sociali.-inaugurato-il-centro-servizi-per-i-minori-stranieri-non-accompagnati-e-il-nuovo-centro-aiuto#:~:text=Nel%202018%20il%20Comune%20di,%20e%20marocchina%20\(33\).](https://www.comune.milano.it/-/politiche-sociali.-inaugurato-il-centro-servizi-per-i-minori-stranieri-non-accompagnati-e-il-nuovo-centro-aiuto#:~:text=Nel%202018%20il%20Comune%20di,%20e%20marocchina%20(33).)

⁷ The data refers to the number of school institutes at 2018 (available at: <https://dati.istruzione.it/espescu/index.html?area=anagScu>). School institutes usually include more than one (often two or three) school complexes (buildings), which can be located in different districts and host population of pupils that may be different for social, economic and other characteristics, including the migratory background. The school complexes are the unit of analysis of our study.

⁸ See footnote n. 2 on the correspondence between Italian school grades and ISCED levels.

is the area of greatest concentration of Filipino students in Italy (data from MIUR, Pupils without Italian citizenship, school year 2017/2018).

9.2.2 Region: Turin (Piedmont)

POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS

Located in the northern Region of Piedmont, the city of Turin has 875,698 inhabitants (official residents on 1 January 2019); 47.7% are male, and 52.3% are female.

The following table reports the distribution for age groups, which shows a concentration of the population in the 45 to 59 year age range.

Table 6. Turin – age groups distribution - absolute values and percentages (2019)

Age	Male	Female	Total	
			N	%
0-14	54,517	51,138	105,655	12
15-29	61,812	57,683	119,495	13.6
30-44	83,460	83,665	167,125	19
45-59	98,345	104,715	203,060	23.1
60-74	70,822	84,077	154,899	17.6
75-89	45,242	67,059	112,301	12.8
90-100+	3,565	9,598	13,163	1.5
Total	417,763	457,935	875,698	100

Source: ISTAT, 1 Jan. 2019

The population under the IMMERSE target ages is 94,150, or 10.7% of the inhabitants.

Table 7: Turin – IMMERSE target - age groups and gender distribution - absolute values (2019)

Age groups	Male	Female	Total
6-10	19,048	15,236	36,967
11-13	11,321	10,556	21,877
14-18	18,203	17,403	35,306
Total	48,572	43,195	94,150

Source: ISTAT, 1 Jan. 2019

As far as the social-economic conditions are concerned, data regarding the residents' annual income in 2017 by income bracket shows a distribution of the population similar to that of Milan. The majority of the population is in the 15,000 – 26,000 euro group (30%), and in the 26,000 – 55,000 euro group (25.2%). However, there is a significant proportion of the population with an income not higher than 10,000 euros the year (24.6%).

Table 8: Turin – residents’ annual income in 2017 by amount class (values in percentage of the total contributors)

Amount classes	0 euros or less	0-10.000 euros	10.000-15.000 euros	15.000-26.000 euros	26.000-55.000 euros	55.000-75.000 euros	75.000-120.000 euros	120.000 euros or more
Turin	0.6%	24.6%	11.6%	30%	25.2%	3%	2.4%	1.3%

Source: ISTAT, 27 May 2020

The available data on education relates to the level of instruction of the population of 15 years and over in Piedmont region in 2019 (ISTAT). They show that the schooling levels are in line with those of Milan, with a slightly higher numbers for the ISCED 2 and 3 (half course) levels, and above the national average, as shown by the following table.

Table 9. Levels of education (ISCED classification) of 15 years and over population in Piedmont (percentages on the total)

Territory	ISCED 1 or lower	ISCED 2	ISCED 3 (half)	ISCED 3 (completed)	ISCED 4 or 5
Italy	16.2%	32.4%	5.5%	30.9%	14.9%
Piedmont	15%	33.2%	8.2%	29%	14.3%

Source: SCIT adaptation from ISTAT, 2019

In Piedmont, the early school leavers amongst the 18-24 years old residents are 10.8%, a rate lower than the national one (13.5%).

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

The number of foreigners’ resident in Piedmont on 1 January 2019 was 427,911 and represents 9.8% of the resident population.⁹ 221,842 foreigners resided in the city of Turin (47% male, 53 % females), accounting for 9.8% of the resident population.

The largest foreign community is the one coming from Romania which accounts for 44.9% of all foreigners present in the territory. This large community is followed by those from Morocco (11%) and China (4.8%).

In Turin, in 2019, there have been 5,572 requests for asylum, subsidiary protection and/or special protection, of which 1,600 have been approved.¹⁰

In the region of Piedmont, 262 UAMs were present in 2019 (Ministry of Labour and Social Policies official report at 31 December 2019). Piedmont is among the top Italian regions in terms of the number of UAM reception facilities (5.3%) (Ministry of Labour and Social Policies official report at 31 December 2019).

⁹ In the statistics reported, count for migrants foreign citizens, e.g. all the persons of non-Italian citizenship who are habitually resident in Italy.

¹⁰ National Commission for the Right to Asylum, Statistical Report, available at:

http://www.libertaciviliimmigrazione.dlci.interno.gov.it/sites/default/files/allegati/quaderno_statistico_per_gli_anni_1990_2019_0.pdf

In 2017, there were 176 unaccompanied foreign minors admitted in reception facilities in the Turin area, equal to 1% of the total in Italy. The minors welcomed in the city are predominantly males (out of 176 minors, only 20 are females) (data from the Municipality of Turin, official website).

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

In Piedmont there are 534 schools and 12 CPIA (MIUR, 2019).

In the city of Turin, there are 274 school institutes articulated in 321 school complexes (156 primary schools, 69 secondary of first grade, 96 secondary of second grade).¹¹

The province of Turin is one of the territories with the highest presence of pupils without Italian citizenship in all school levels: 39,342 in the school year 2017/2018, accounting for 4.5% of the total number of pupils without Italian citizenship in the whole country. The large majority of these pupils are born in Italy (67.7% of the cases, a percentage far above the national average of 63.1%). With regard to their distribution in the diverse school grade (percentage on the total of students), students without Italian citizenship make up 14.4% of nursery school students, 14.6% of primary school students, and 12.8% and 10% respectively of secondary lower and upper school students.

In the city of Turin, still in the school year 2017/2018, pupils without Italian citizenship are 24,482, or 19.4% of the total number of students. With regards to the countries of origin, Turin hosts a significant number of pupils from Rumania (34%). The other most popular countries of origin are Morocco (17%) and China (5.7%) (data from MIUR, Pupils without Italian citizenship, school year 2017/2018).

9.2.3 Region: Rome (Lazio)

POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS

Located in the central Region of Lazio, the city of Rome, the capital of Italy, has 2,856,133 inhabitants (official residents at 1 January 2019); 47.3% are male, and 52.7% are female.

The following table reports the distribution for age groups, which shows a concentration of the population in the 45 to 59 year age range.

Table 10: Rome – age groups distribution - absolute values and percentages (2019)

Age	Male	Female	Total	
			N	%
0-14	192,974	182,599	375,573	13.1
15-29	205,873	191,042	396,915	13.8
30-44	274,333	286,023	560,356	19.6
45-59	333,627	372,498	706,125	24.7
60-74	214,342	263,240	477,582	16.7
75-89	120,466	182,140	302,606	10.5
90-100+	10,329	26,647	36,976	1.2
Total	1,351,944	1,504,189	1,504,189	100

Source: ISTAT, 1 Jan. 2019

¹¹ See footnote n.6 on the distinction between school institutes and school complexes.

The population under the IMMERSE target ages is 94.150, or 10,7% of the inhabitants.

Table 11: Rome – IMMERSE target age groups and gender distribution - absolute values (2019)

Age groups	M	F	Total
6-10	19,048	17,919	36,967
11-13	11,321	10,556	21,877
14-18	18,203	17,403	35,606
Total	48,572	45,878	94,450

Source: ISTAT, 1 Jan. 2019

As far as the social-economic conditions are concerned, the following table shows the residents' annual income in 2017 by income bracket. It is worth noting that in Rome the proportion of the population with an income not higher than 10,000 euros per year is higher compared with that of Milan or Turin (28.6%). At the same time, the proportion in the 26,000 – 55,000 euros group is larger (27.1%).

Table 12: Rome – residents' annual income in 2017 by amount class (values in percentage of the total contributors)

Amount classes	0 euros or less	0-10,000 euros	10,000-15,000 euros	15,000-26,000 euros	26,000-55,000 euros	55,000-75,000 euros	75,000-120,000 euros	120,000 euros or more
Rome	0.5%	28.6%	10.9%	24%	27.1%	4%	3.3%	1.8%

Source: ISTAT, 27 May 2020

The available data on education relates to the level of instruction of the population of 15 years and over in Lazio region in 2019 (ISTAT). They show that the population in this area is more extensively concentrated in the high schooling levels, ISCED 3 (completed) and ISCED 4 or 5, in comparison to the national average.

Table n. 13: Levels of education (ISCED classification) of 15 years and over population in Lazio (percentages on the total)

Territory	ISCED 1 or lower	ISCED 2	ISCED 3 (half)	ISCED 3 (completed)	ISCED 4 or 5
Italy	16.2%	32.4%	5.5%	30.9%	14.9%
Lazio	11.7%	28.4%	2.6%	36.6%	20.5%

Source: SCIT adaptation from ISTAT, 2019

In Lazio, the early school leavers amongst the 18-24 years old residents are 12%, a rate higher than those of Lombardy and Piedmont, but still lower than the national one (13.5%).

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

The number of foreigners resident in Lazio on 1 January 2019 was 683,409 and represents 11.6 % of the resident population.¹² 556,826 foreigners resided in the city of Rome (47.3% males, 52.6 % females) accounting for 12.8% of the resident population.

The largest foreign community is the one coming from Romania which accounts for 33.1% of all foreigners present in the territory. This large community is followed by those from the Philippines (7.9%) and Bangladesh (6.2%).

In Rome, in 2019, there have been 8,947 requests for asylum, subsidiary protection and/or special protection, of which 2,280 have been approved.¹³

In the region of Lazio 262 UAMs were present in 2019 (Ministry of Labour and Social Policies official report at 31 December 2019). Lazio is among the top Italian regions in terms of the number of UAM reception facilities (8.4%) (Ministry of Labour and Social Policies official report at 31 December 2019).

In 2018, there were 689 unaccompanied foreign minors admitted in reception facilities of Rome, equal to 6.3% of the total number of unaccompanied foreign minors in Italy. The minors welcomed in the city are predominantly from Egypt (17.1%) (data from Ministry of Labour and Social Policies official report at 31 December 2018).

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

In Lazio there are 717 schools and 10 CPIA (MIUR, 2019).

In the city of Rome, in particular, there are 504 schools¹⁴ articulated in 1,068 school complexes (524 primary schools, 252 secondary of first grade, 315 secondary of second grade).

The province of Rome has the second highest presence of pupils without Italian citizenship in Italy at all school levels: in the school year 2017/2018 they were 62,328, or 7.4% of the total number of pupils without Italian citizenship in Italy. The large majority of these pupils are born in Italy (61.9%). With regard to their distribution in the diverse school grade (percentage on the total of students), in the Province of Rome, the students without Italian citizenship make up 11.4% of nursery school pupils, 11.2% of primary school pupils, and 10.7% and 8.5% respectively of secondary lower and upper school pupils.

In the city of Rome, still in the school year 2017/2018, pupils without Italian citizenship are 41,540, the 10.6% of the total number of students in the city. With respect to the countries of origin, Rome

¹² In the statistics reported, count for migrants foreign citizens, e.g. all the persons of non-Italian citizenship who are habitually resident in Italy.

¹³ National Commission for the Right to Asylum, Statistical Report, available at: http://www.libertaciviliimmigrazione.dlci.interno.gov.it/sites/default/files/allegati/quaderno_statistico_per_gli_anni_1990_2019_0.pdf

¹⁴ See footnote n.6 on the distinction between school institutes and school complexes.

hosts a significant number of pupils from Rumania (26.6%) and from the Philippines (12.8%) (data from MIUR, Pupils without Italian citizenship, school year 2017/2018).

9.2.4 Region: Naples (Campania)

POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS

Located in the southern region of Campania, the city of Naples has 959,188 inhabitants (officially residents at 1 January 2019); 47.8% are male, and 52.2% are female.

The following table reports the distribution for age groups, which shows a larger distribution in younger age groups, compared to Milan, Turin and Rome.

Table 14: Naples – age groups distribution - absolute values and percentages (2019)

Age	Male	Female	Total	
			N	%
0-14	70,223	66,646	136,869	14.2
15-29	87,262	82,582	169,844	17.7
30-44	91,123	92,246	183,369	19.1
45-59	102,245	114,824	217,069	22.6
60-74	74,896	88,065	162,961	16.9
75-89	30,362	49,011	79,373	8.2
90-100+	2,455	6,448	8,903	0.9
Total	458,566	500,622	959,188	100

Source: ISTAT, 1 Jan. 2019

Table 15: Naples – IMMERSE target - age groups and gender distribution - absolute values (2019)

Age groups	M	F	Total
6-10	24,306	22,778	47,084
11-13	15,509	14,977	30,486
14-18	27,381	25,916	53,297
Total	67,196	63,671	130,867

Source: ISTAT, 1 Jan. 2019

In terms of social-economic conditions of the population, the following table shows the residents' annual income in 2017 by income bracket. It is worth noting that in Naples from the majority of the population falls into the 15,000 to 26,000 euros bracket.

Table 16: Naples – residents’ annual income in 2017 by amount class (values in percentage of the total contributors)

Amount classes	0 euros or less	0-10,000 euros	10,000-15,000 euros	15,000-26,000 euros	26,000-55,000 euros	55,000-75,000 euros	75,000-120,000 euros	120,000 euros or more
Naples	0.1%	5.1%	18.2%	35.8%	30.1%	3.9%	3.2%	1.4%

Source: ISTAT, 27 May 2020

The available data on education relates to the level of instruction of the population of 15 years and over in Campania region in 2019. These data show that levels of education in Campania are lower compared to the national averages.

Table 17: Levels of education (ISCED classification) of 15 years and over population in Lombardy (percentages on the total)

Territory	ISCED 1 or lower	ISCED 2	ISCED 3 (half)	ISCED 3 (completed)	ISCED 4 or 5
Italy	16.2%	32.4%	5.5%	30.9%	14.9%
Campania	18.4%	35.2%	2.4%	31.1%	12.6%

Source: SCIT adaptation from ISTAT, 2019

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

The number of foreigners residing in Campania on 1 January 2019 was 265,163 and represents 4.6 % of the resident population.¹⁵ There were 134,338 foreigners residing in the city of Naples (equally distributed among males and females). They constituted 4.3% of the overall resident population.

The largest foreign community is the one coming from Ukraine, which accounts for 17.3% of all foreigners present in the territory, followed by those from Sri Lanka (12.9%) and Romania (8.4%).

In Naples, in 2019, there have been 2,589 requests for asylum, subsidiary protection and/or special protection, of which 1,600 have been approved.¹⁶

In the region of Campania, 262 UAMs were present in 2019 (Ministry of Labour and Social Policies official report at 31 December 2019). This region is in an intermediate position in the ranking of Italian regions in terms of number of UAMs hosted in reception facilities.

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

In the Campania region, there are 988 public schools and 8 CPIA (MIUR, 2019). In Naples in particular, there are 449 school complexes (213 primary schools, 98 secondary of first grade and 138 secondary of second grade).

¹⁵ In the statistics reported, count for migrants foreign citizens, e.g. all the persons of non-Italian citizenship who are habitually resident in Italy.

¹⁶ National Commission for the Right to Asylum, Statistical Report, available at:

http://www.libertaciviliimmigrazione.dlci.interno.gov.it/sites/default/files/allegati/quaderno_statistico_per_gli_anni_1990_2019_0.pdf

The province of Naples contains 11,424 pupils without Italian citizenship, or 2.1% of the total number of students. These pupils are born in Italy in 39.7% of cases (meaning that, contrary to the national data and to the trends in the north and centre of the Country, in this southern area the majority of the students without Italian citizenship are born abroad). With regard to their distribution in the diverse school grade (percentage on the total of students), in the Province of Naples, students without Italian citizenship make up 2.1% of nursery school pupils, 2.5% of primary school pupils, and 2.2% and 1.7% respectively of secondary lower and upper school pupils.

We do not have precise data on foreign students in the municipality of Naples, as this is not one of those municipalities (i.e. where the number of students with non-Italian citizenship exceeds one thousand, or is just below, and affects locally more than 10%) for which ISTAT makes public the data. This shows that Naples is not among the Italian municipalities with the highest presence of foreign students.

9.2.5 Region: Catania (Sicily)

POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS

Located in the southern island of Sicily, the city of Catania has 311,584 inhabitants (official residents at 1 January 2019); 48.2% are male, and 51.8% are female.

The following table reports the distribution for age groups, which shows, similarly to the case of Naples, a larger distribution in younger age groups, compared to the cases in Milan, Turin and Rome.

Table 18: Catania – age groups distribution - absolute values and percentages (2019)

Age	Male	Female	Total	
			N	%
0-14	22,665	21,128	43,793	14%
15-29	27,411	25,395	52,806	16.9%
30-44	30,260	29,894	60,154	19.3%
45-59	32,959	35,286	68,245	21.9%
60-74	24,630	29,049	53,679	17.2%
75-89	11,246	18,022	29,268	9.3%
90-100+	1,020	2,619	3,639	1.1%
Total	150,191	161,393	311,584	100%

Source: ISTAT, 1 Jan. 2019

The population under the IMMERSE target ages is 94,150, or 10.7% of the inhabitants.

Table 19: Catania – IMMERSE target - age groups and gender distribution - absolute values (2019)

Age groups	M	F	Total
6-10	7,614	7,136	7,136
11-13	4,754	4,353	9,107
14-18	8,186	7,713	15,899
Total	20,554	19,202	32,142

Source: ISTAT, 1 Jan. 2019

Regarding the residents' annual income in 2017 by income bracket in the city of Catania, according to the data reported in the following table, a significant proportion of the population is in the 10,000 to 15,000 euros per year bracket (37%).

Table 20: Catania – residents' annual income in 2017 by amount class (values in percentage of the total contributors)

Amount classes	0 euros or less	0-10,000 euros	10,000-15,000 euros	15,000-26,000 euros	26,000-55,000 euros	55,000-75,000 euros	75,000-120,000 euros	120,000 euros or more
Catania	0.9%	37.1%	13%	25%	18.9%	2.1%	1.8%	0.6%

Source: ISTAT, 27 May 2020

Regarding education, in Sicily we find the lowest levels of educational attainment among the five cities considered. The percentages in the higher levels are clearly under the national averages, while the majority of the population of 15 years and over are included in the ISCED levels 1 or lower and 2.

Table n. 21: Levels of education (ISCED classification) of 15 years and over population in Lombardy (percentages on the total)

Territory	ISCED 1 or lower	ISCED 2	ISCED 3 (half)	ISCED 3 (completed)	ISCED 4 or 5
Italy	16.2%	32.4%	5.5%	30.9%	14.9%
Sicily	20%	36.5%	1.7%	30.5%	11.9%

Source: SCIT adaptation from ISTAT, 2019

Even more than in Campania, early school leaving in Sicily is a huge phenomenon, with 22.4% of the of 18-24 years old population leaving school before gaining secondary level qualifications (against the national average of 13.5%), affecting males (24.5%) more than females (20.1%).

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

There are 265,163 migrants in Sicily, or 4.5% of the overall population. In the city of Catania, there are 37,591 migrants are 37,591, or 3.4% of inhabitants.¹⁷ The most numerous foreign communities

¹⁷ In the statistics reported, count for migrants foreign citizens, e.g. all the persons of non-Italian citizenship who are habitually resident in Italy.

come from Romania with 31.1% of all foreigners present in the territory, followed by Sri Lanka (10.9%) and China (6.0%).

In Catania, in 2019, there have been 696 requests for asylum, subsidiary protection and/or special protection, of which 137 have been approved.¹⁸

Sicily is the top Italian region in terms of UAMs welcomed (1,169 in 2019, 19% of the national territory) and of number of UAM reception facilities (21.3%) (Ministry of Labour and Social Policies official report at 31 December 2019). In this region there is a particular concentration of UAMs from Bangladesh and African states (Gambia, Guinea, Eritrea, Ivory Coast, Mali, Nigeria, Egypt, Senegal, Somalia and Tunisia).

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

In Sicily, there are 841 public schools and 10 CPIA (MIUR, 2019). In Catania, there are 175 school complexes (85 primary schools, 34 secondary of first grade and 56 secondary of second grade).

The province of Catania has 4,937 pupils without Italian citizenship, or 2.8% of the total number of students. Similarly to the case of Naples, these pupils are born in Italy in the 40% of cases. In these southern areas, contrary to what happens in the north and centre of Italy, the majority of the students without Italian citizenship are born abroad. With regards to their distribution in the diverse school grade (percentage on the total of students), in the province of Catania, the students without Italian citizenship make up 2.6% of nursery school pupils, 3% of primary school pupils, and 3.2% and 2.5% respectively of secondary lower and upper school pupils.

We do not have precise data on foreign students in the municipality of Catania. As for the case of Naples, Catania is not one of those municipalities (i.e. where the number of students with non-Italian citizenship exceeds one thousand, or is just below, and affects locally more than 10%) for which ISTAT makes public the data. This shows that Catania is not among the Italian municipalities with the highest presence of foreign students.

9.3 School Sampling

The data used for the sampling have been gained from:

- Ministry of Education - Schools registry - office lists and distribution of students without Italian citizenship in public schools (school year 2017/2018)¹⁹

¹⁸ National Commission for the Right to Asylum, Statistical Report, available at: http://www.libertaciviliimmigrazione.dlci.interno.gov.it/sites/default/files/allegati/quaderno_statistico_per_gli_anni_1990_2019_0.pdf

¹⁹ The data disaggregated at school level is not publicly available. SCIT gained a special permission to access it in light of its broader collaboration with the Italian Ministry of Education.

- National Institute of School Evaluation (INVALSI) - distribution of students by origin for the 5 grades (or school years) associated with the learning assessment tests (II, V, VIII, XII, XV) (school year 2018/2019)²⁰

These data have been merged in a unique dataset and have been used to proxy the current situation.

9.3.1 Key characteristics used in sampling framework

SCIT has created a list of schools including the following key characteristics:

1. City in which the school is located (Milan, Turin, Rome, Naples, Catania)
2. School level (primary, secondary of first and second grade)
3. School code (identifier used by the Ministry of Education)
4. School address
5. Total n. of students
6. N. of migrant students (without Italian citizenship, first and second generations)
7. Percentage of migrants on the overall number of students

Preliminary data on the socio-economic status of students are not available.

According to the National Institute of Statistics (ISTAT, 2019), immigrants from EU (28 countries including UK) at 1 January 2019 in Italy are 1,583,000 (the 30% of the overall number of foreign people which are residents in Italy). Third Country Nationals are 3,683,00 (70%). If we include not resident people and irregulars, we must add 194 units to UE nationals and 770 to TCNs. Among the EU nationals the most represented countries are Romania (22.97%), Poland (1.79%) and Bulgaria (1.14%). With its 1,206,938 nationals, Romania represents the main origin of migrants in Italy in general. Their number in the Country has grown exponentially after 2007, with Romania joining the European Union. The Romanian owners of companies in Italy are about 48 thousand; the others work mainly in family care and hotel reception, but also agriculture and industry.

The 5 regions, Piedmont, Lombardy, Lazio, Campania and Sicily, are among the main 8 regions of distributions of Romanian immigrants in Italy. In particular, only in Piedmont, Lombardy, Lazio is concentrated the 46% of them. In the 2017/2018 school year, Romanian students are 158,044, a stable group of almost 19% - the most populous - of all pupils without Italian citizenship (ISMU, 2019). In light of these data, SCIT retains opportune including children from Romania among the IMMERSE main targets.

9.3.2 Categories resulting from framework and sampling pool

From these characteristics SCIT has formed the following categories in order to create the sampling pool:

²⁰ The data disaggregated at school level is not publicly available. SCIT gained a special permission to access it in light of its broader collaboration with INVALSI.

1. primary schools in Milan
2. secondary schools (first grade) in Milan
3. secondary schools (second grade) in Milan
4. primary schools in Turin
5. secondary schools (first grade) in Turin
6. secondary schools (second grade) in Turin
7. primary schools in Rome
8. secondary schools (first grade) in Rome
9. secondary schools (second grade) in Rome
10. primary schools in Naples
11. secondary schools (first grade) in Naples
12. secondary schools (second grade) in Naples
13. primary schools in Catania
14. secondary schools (first grade) in Catania
15. secondary schools (second grade) in Catania

In a second stage, we used two criteria to restrict the number of the schools that fell into each category:

- a) school size;
- b) share of migrants pupils.

In accordance with these two criteria SCIT eliminated in each category:

- a) the 25% of the smaller schools (i.e. those with the lowest quartile); this parameter has been used to facilitate data collection by concentrating it on a number of schools that can be covered reasonably with the available time and resources.
- b) the schools with a low share of migrants. The threshold has been identified at the city level because, as shown in the description, the distribution of migrants is very different in the selected geographical areas, with a greater concentration in the centre and north. In Rome, Milan and Turin, schools with a density of foreign students lower than the median have been excluded from the list; in Naples and Catania schools with a density lower than the 75th percentile have been excluded from the list (with the exception of the middle school in Catania where the number of eligible schools too low would not allow it). This allows to introduce a certain variability in the type of schools with respect to density of migrant children.

In accordance with the eligibility criteria used, the sampling pool (eligible schools) is presented in the different cities as in the following tables: for each school grade, the minimum number of foreign students (first column) and the minimum percentage of foreigners on the total number of students (second column) to admit a school to the sample are indicated.

Tab. Sampling pool (eligible schools) – Milan

School grade	minimum n.	min. % on tot.
Primary	145	17.5
Secondary first grade	138	16.3
Secondary second grade	105	7.9

Tab. Sampling pool (eligible schools) – Turin

School grade	minimum n.	min. % on tot.
Primary	180	19.5
Secondary first grade	162	16.8
Secondary second grade	148	11.9

Tab. Sampling pool (eligible schools) – Rome

School grade	minimum n.	min. % on tot.
Primary	119	8.1
Secondary first grade	146	8.5
Secondary second grade	50	7.8

Tab. Sampling pool (eligible schools) – Naples

School grade	minimum n.	min. % on tot.
Primary	88	4.5
Secondary first grade	152	3.3
Secondary second grade	97	3.9

Tab. Sampling pool (eligible schools) – Catania

School grade	minimum n.	min. % on tot.
Primary	98	5.6
Secondary first grade	190	5.5
Secondary second grade	60	4.6

On these schools a weighted random sampling have been applied (a random extraction weighed for the estimation of foreign students in that school, so all eligible schools could be extracted but the biggest ones had a proportionally higher chance).

As a result, for each category, 4 schools have been extracted and other 12 have been included in the reserve list. Overall, therefore, the selected schools are 60 (15 x 4) and 180 (15 x 12) are back-ups.

9.4 School Sampling – Plan B

In the event that the adapted random sampling technique for selecting school sites discussed above yields low response rates, we will use the back-up strategy involving non-probability sampling techniques that allow us to use our contacts and networks to recruit schools to participate. We will still sample from each of the categories from the stratified sampling framework, but we will choose sites purposively, rather than randomly, in order to maximise response rates in order to reach our participant quota. SCIT will be able to draw from the network of schools²¹ with which it has already built collaborations for intervention initiatives and activities in the selected cities.

Further alternative measures to address possible data collection restrictions due to the Covid-19 pandemic will be defined promptly.

9.5 Child/classroom Sampling

In the selected school SCIT will survey all the classes in order to maximise the effort and cover the different age groups in a proportioned manner. It is possible to estimate (with a certain degree of approximation) that, with an effective involvement of all classes in the sampled schools, the number of 5,177 migrant students is reached. In the case of unavailability of one or more schools to survey all the classes, SCIT will sample randomly among the classes made available by the part of the school heads. If necessary, new schools will be extracted from the list of those eligible until the sample pool is proportionally reached.

Based on the random extraction carried out, it is possible to estimate (with a certain degree of approximation) that, with the effective involvement of all classes, the number of 5,177 students could be reached. The amount probably overestimates the number of migrant children in the schools sampled. However, bearing in mind that the total number of migrant students that SCIT has set out to reach is of 3,280, we believe that this is the appropriate procedure for reaching the target.

²¹ In particular, the SCIT National Program for education “Fuoriclasse in Movimento” include a network of supporting SCIT’s activities, involving more than 150 teachers and schools. More information at this link: <https://www.savethechildren.it/cosa-facciamo/progetti/fuoriclasse-movimento>. Moreover, Save the Children Italy has specific national programs dedicated to combat poverty and social exclusion, The Spotlight Project, started in 2014. To tackle educational poverty, Save the Children has established 25 ‘Spotlight centres’ in network with the municipality, social services and schools. The Spotlight centres are educational hub centres where children have access to educational support, music/theatre workshops, sport classes, as well as other activities. Parents have access to legal and psychosocial support and support. More information at this link: <https://www.savethechildren.it/cosa-facciamo/campagne/illuminiamo-il-futuro/punti-luce>

The units estimated to be reached are distributed per city as in the following figure.

Figure 2. Distribution of the sampled schools per city (percentages)

The distribution of the sample by school order is shown in Figure 3. the over-representation of student units in the upper secondary segment of Milan, due to random factors that cannot be controlled in the procedure, can be "corrected" in the selection of the classes to be surveyed (the classes for those schools that contribute to the over-representation might be reduced).

Figure 3. Sample distribution by school order in the 5 cities

This said about the sampling criteria, the eligibility of the schools will also depend on their technological equipment (wireless connection, multimedia classrooms, etc.).

The sample as designed is ideally representative of the target populations (eligible schools) in the 5 cities and for the three school grades.

The analysis of the patterns of the schools eliminated from the sampling shows the recurrence of only one pattern, which therefore remains underrepresented among the sampled schools: the

general and humanistic secondary schooling (the lyceums) are mostly excluded from the sampling pool, because these types of secondary school track attracts a low number of migrant students in Italy. In other words, this limitation reflects the real unbalanced distribution of migrant students in Italian diverse secondary school tracks.

9.6 Sampling in Non-formal Education Environments

Due to the lack of data on the characteristics of non-formal education environments and their higher level of inaccessibility, we will use non-probability sampling. The students will be recruited through the contact with the educational centres that are part of the SCI local networks²².

Overall, about 2,095 children (aged 6-18) are in the database of the SCIT centres (it means they have attended the centres in 2019) in the five cities. They are distributed as follow:

- Milan: about 195 foreign minors (first and second generation) regularly attending school and 846 refugees / newly arrived / UAMs (the majority of them outside the school system);
- Turin: about 59 foreign minors (first and second generation) regularly attending school and 337 refugees / newly arrived / UAMs (the majority of them outside the school system);
- Rome: about 271 foreign minors (first and second generation) regularly attending school and 949 refugees / newly arrived / UAMs (the majority of them outside the school system);
- Naples: about 56 foreign minors (first and second generation) regularly attending school
- Catania: about 27 foreign minors (first and second generation) regularly attending school and 396 refugees / newly arrived / UAMs (the majority of them outside the school system).

It is necessary to take into account that the arrivals of UAMs in Italy during 2020 have decreased, so the amounts probably over-estimates their actual presence in the centres at the time of the data collection.

SCIT estimates to reach in these informal education environments about 328 children (the 15% of the children attending the centres and the 10% of the entire sample), equally distributed in the five cities (65 per city). However, the quota of minors to be reached in informal education might increase in the case of insufficient accesses to the sampled schools.

The recruitment will benefit from the active engagement and support by the educators working in the centres. Attention will be paid in order to recruit to a major extent the categories of migrant minors less represented in the ordinary school system (refugees, newly arrived, UAMs, early school leavers, etc.). Further alternative measures to address possible data collection restrictions due to the Covid-19 pandemic will be defined promptly.

²² See footnote n. 20.

10 Appendix D – Germany (Research Partner: Doz)

10.1 Regional Sampling

Since there is no uniform nationwide education monitoring system, we used regional data from the respective municipalities to gain an initial impression of the education and school data environment.

Around one in four people in Germany has a migration background - in West Germany this applied to 28.6% of the population in 2018 and in East Germany to 8.0%. In 2018, 95.3% of persons with a migration background lived in West Germany and Berlin. Of those, more than every fourth person with a migrant background lived in North Rhine-Westphalia (25.8%).¹

Figure 1. Germany – Regional Selection

Source: Adapted by DOZ from Wikimedia Commons. https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Karte_Deutschland.svg

The regional selection was following the rationale of the varying degrees of distribution of the population with migration background, experience in dealing with migration in an educational context, and the reachable quota throughout the regions. Therefore, the three cities were selected accordingly. Leipzig is the biggest city in Saxony and was selected as the East German representative. Berlin is the biggest city of Germany, its capital, and presents a very diverse

¹Bundeszentrale für politische Bildung. Bevölkerung mit Migrationshintergrund I. <https://www.bpb.de/nachschlagen/zahlen-und-fakten/soziale-situation-in-deutschland/61646/migrationshintergrund-i>.

environment due to its divided history. Cologne is the most populated city in North Rhine-Westphalia and is an example of high experience with migration and educational integration. Since there is no uniform nationwide education monitoring system and each federal state uses different ways, measures, indicators, and definitions for statistical records, the sampling strategy reflects on differences in data availability as well as gaps and hindrances which influence the comparability in the three different regions.

10.2 Region Profiles

10.2.1 Region: Leipzig (State of Saxony)

POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS

According to the last count of 31.12.2019, Leipzig had an overall population of 601,668² with a population density of 2,038 inhabitants per square kilometre. The male share of population is 48.7% and the female share of population is 51.3%.³ 61,170⁴ of those were foreigners.⁵ According to the latest data, the age distribution is as follows:

Table 1. Leipzig Inhabitants by Age Group - Resident Registry

Age Group	Population
0-6	62,259
6-10	21,916
10-15	45 717
15-18	12,869
Under 18 (Minors)	96,072
18 and older (Adults)	510,887
15-65 (Working Age)	401,187
65 and older (Pensioner)	122,569

Source: Ordnungsamt Leipzig (Einwohnerregister).

<https://statistik.leipzig.de/statcity/table.aspx?cat=2&rub=4&per=q>

The average net household income in Leipzig in 2018 was 1,832 € and the average personal net income (median) in 2018 was 1,384 €. ⁶ In 2017, 61.4% of households were low-income 30,1%

²Ordnungsamt Leipzig (Einwohnerregister). <https://statistik.leipzig.de/statcity/table.aspx?cat=2&rub=4&per=q>

³Statistische Ämter der Länder, ies, Deenst GmbH, eigene Berechnungen. <https://www.wegweiser-kommune.de/statistik/leipzig+bevoelkerungsstruktur+2020+koeln+berlin+tabelle>

⁴Ordnungsamt Leipzig (Einwohnerregister). <https://statistik.leipzig.de/statcity/table.aspx?cat=2&rub=4&per=q>

⁵Foreigners here means foreign-born.

⁶Sozialreport der Stadt Leipzig: 2019. 35ff.

were medium income, and 8.5% were high income.⁷ ⁸ Child poverty amounts to 22.8%, youth poverty to 20.6%, and old age poverty to 2.4% in 2017.

Regarding educational attainment, data from the micro census⁹ provide information on the educational level of the population of Leipzig. Looking at school-leaving qualifications, the (technical) university entrance qualification in 2015 was the qualification that most inhabitants had (35%). This proportion has risen steadily in recent years. On the other hand, the share of school-leaving qualifications from Lower Middle School (Hauptschule - 9th grade certificate) fell to 19%. The proportion of graduates from middle schools (Realschule - 10th grade certificate) has remained at the same level since 2012 at about 30%.¹⁰

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

The Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (BAMF) defines foreigners as those who are not Germans within the meaning of the German Constitution (Article 116, paragraph 1). In 2018, this amounted to approximately 10.92 million people in Germany. However, the statistical office of Leipzig differentiates for the different shares of population in its Foreigner statistic as follows:¹¹

- Migrants [Foreigners and Germans with Migration Background]
- Foreigners
- Germans with Migration Background
- Multinationals
- Late Resettlers
- EU Foreigners

At the end of 2018, 87,889 or 14.7% of Leipzig citizens had a migration background.¹² Both the number of persons with a migration background and their share of the total population has been growing continuously since 2011. Compared to the previous year, the number of migrants increased by 4,483 persons or 5.4 %. With 58,621 persons and a share of 9.8 % of the population, foreigners constitute the largest group of persons with a migration background. Their number increased by 4.7 % compared to 2017. The number of Germans with a migration background increased by 1,873 persons to 29,268 persons. Their share of the total population was 4.9%. The largest migrant groups come from Syria (9,059 persons), the Russian Federation (8,773), Poland (5,019), Romania (4,161) and Ukraine (3,491).

⁷Low-income = a total net income below 25.000 Euros per year. Medium income = a total net income of between 25.000 and under 50.000 Euros per year. High-income = a total net income of over 50.000 Euros per year.

⁸Statistische Ämter der Länder, Nexiga GmbH, ZEFIR, eigene Berechnungen, Bundesagentur für Arbeit, Statistische Ämter des Bundes und der Länder. <https://www.wegweiser-kommune.de/statistik/leipzig+soziale-lage+2017+koeln+berlin+tabelle>.

⁹This is a representative survey on population and labour market data carried out by the State Statistical Office. A representative sample of one percent of all households in a certain territory is included in the area sample.

¹⁰Bildungsreport Leipzig. 2016. https://static.leipzig.de/fileadmin/mediendatenbank/leipzig-de/Stadt/02.5_Deiz5_Jugend_Soziales_Gesundheit_Schule/51_Amt_fuer_Jugend_Familie_und_Bildung/Lernen_vor_Ort/Publikationen/Bildungsmonitoring/Bildungsreport-Leipzig-2016.pdf

¹¹Paradoxically, this registry also includes German citizens with a migration background.

¹² This includes both German citizens with a migration background and foreigners.

With an average age of 30.8 years, migrants were significantly younger than Germans without a migration background (44.4 years). Almost three quarters of all migrants (71.9 %) had not yet reached the age of 40. Of all Leipzig citizens with a migration background, 23.7% were under 16 years of age, i.e. children in day care and of school age. On the other hand, only 5.3% of migrants were over 65 years of age, while for all inhabitants this amounts to 20.3%.

Within the city of Leipzig, there are great differences in the proportion of people with a migration background. The share ranges from 2.8% in Baalsdorf to 41.8% in Volksmarsdorf. Apart from Volksmarsdorf, the districts close to the centre and Grünau-Mitte that show a high proportion of migrants (over 20 %). The suburban districts have low migrant percentages.¹³

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

In the school year of 2019/20, the distribution of schools and pupils in Leipzig is as follows:

Table 2. Schools and Students Leipzig

School Type	Number of Schools	Classes	Number of Teachers	Total Number of Students	Students with Migration Background *
Overall	161	2,367	4,723	54,036	11,400
Primary Schools	79	946	1499	21,054	4691
Middle Schools	34	535	1074	12,474	3172
Secondary Schools	24	529	1415	16,316	2616
Special Needs Schools	19	281	563	2,631	423
Waldorf Schools	2	30	66	743	88
Secondary Education	3	23	53	818	269

Source: Leipzig Statistics. <https://statistik.leipzig.de/statcity/table.aspx?cat=5&rub=1>

The number of students with a migrant background represents a minimum value, as this information is collected on a voluntary basis.

Data on educational attainment and socio-economic status of children with migration background is not readily available for Leipzig. However, there exist federal and state-wide statistics, such as the *Integration Monitoring of the Federal States* and the *Social Report of the City of Leipzig*. In 2017, 19% of students with migration background left school without at least a basic certificate in Saxony compared to 7.7% of students without a migration background.¹⁴

A spatial analysis of the graduates without at least a basic certificate within the municipal secondary schools showed clear differences both within the urban area and a strong concentration in a few schools. In the three-year average from 2016 to 2018, seven schools together accounted for more

¹³Sozialreport 2019. Stadt Leipzig. 2019. 19ff.

¹⁴Integrationsmonitoring der Länder. Bericht 2019 – Berichtsjahre 2015-17. 2019. 65.

than half of all school graduates without at least a basic certificate. The maximum value was 23.3% in the district Grünau-Mitte. It was mainly the schools in the priority areas of integrated urban development, which showed significantly above-average values. The geographical differentiation of these areas, apart from Grünau, was evident in the districts Schönefeld and Paunsdorf as well as in the west of Leipzig. Here, the proportion of school leavers without qualifications was more than 20% in each case. These figures correlate with the distribution of migrant population throughout the city, as some of the areas with high proportions of migrants also have high concentrations of early school leavers.

Regarding the overall educational participation, middle schools had the biggest share of children with migration background with 25.1%, followed by a 22.1% share in primary schools, and a 15.5% share in secondary schools. In a long-term comparison, an increase from 6.1% in 2010/11 to 18.2% in 2018/19 of all children with migration background in special needs schools is especially noteworthy.¹⁵

German schools do not currently have a measure or proxy statistic for socio-economic status. The detection of so-called *Brennpunktschulen* or hotspot schools especially in the State of Saxony is still not established. No direct measures can be drawn from any statistic, which has been highly criticised by experts of the German Education Union. They are calling for a social index, which:

...is intended to provide information about the conditions under which the individual schools operate and with which student clientele. To this end, it combines data from school and social area statistics for regions that are as small as possible and thus measures the social burden at a school and in the direct school environment.¹⁶

The proposed indicators would arise mainly from the following data sets:

- Official social area data (e.g. unemployment rate, social welfare payments, single-family houses, immigrant share)
- School statistics (language support needs, inclusion, migration, family language)
- Health statistics (school examinations), crime statistics
- If necessary, parent and pupil surveys on their socio-cultural situation.¹⁷

10.2.2 Region: Cologne (State of North-Rhine Westphalia)

POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS

To date, Cologne has an overall population of 1,089,984 with a population density of 2,686 inhabitants per square kilometre.¹⁸ The male share of population is 48.9% and the female share of

¹⁵Sozialreport 2019. Stadt Leipzig. 2019. 81ff.

¹⁶SVR Policy Brief 2016-1 on Demand-Oriented School Financing. 2016. 14f.

¹⁷ SVR Policy Brief 2016-1 on Demand-Oriented School Financing. 2016. 15.

¹⁸ Landesbetrieb Information und Technik Nordrhein-Westfalen. Top Ten der Städte mit der höchsten Bevölkerungsdichte am 31. Dezember 2019. <https://www.it.nrw/statistik/eckdaten/top-ten-der-staedte-mit-der-hoehsten-bevoelkerungsdichte-am-3112-938>

population is 51.1%.¹⁹ 426,646 of those were inhabitants with migration background. According to the last data, the age distribution is as follows:

Table 3. Cologne Inhabitants by Age Group - New Cologne Statistic 1/2019

Age Group	Population
0-6	64,718
6-10	38,207
10-15	46,209
15-18	26,981
18-30	183,723
30-45	245,827
45-65	293,829
65 and older (Pensioner)	190,490

Source: City of Cologne. https://www.stadt-koeln.de/mediaasset/content/pdf15/statistik-einwohner-und-haushalte/1_089_984_k%C3%B6lnerinnen_und_k%C3%B6lner_im_jahr_2018_ew_nks_1_2019.pdf

In 2017, 51.7% of households were low-income, that of medium income households 31.6%, and that of high-income households 16.7%.^{20 21} Child poverty amounts to 22.7%, youth poverty to 20.6%, and old age poverty to 7.6% in 2017.

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

In 2019, 438,249 inhabitants of Cologne (40%) had a migration background.²² Among children and young people, the proportion was 59%. Among the inhabitants who are statistically recorded as having a migration background are German citizens, people with dual citizenship, and foreigners. Inhabitants with a Turkish migration background are the largest group, with a total of 93,698 or about 22% of the total migrant background population. Here, 27,224 people have Turkish citizenship in addition to German citizenship.²³

In 2019, 212,252 foreigners (19% of the population) from over 180 nations were registered in Cologne. With a share of 14%, the vast majority of them come from Europe. Besides the 52,355 inhabitants with Turkish citizenship, people with Italian nationality form the second largest group in Cologne (19,313). The number of people from Bulgaria and Romania (14,187) has almost tripled since 2010. A further numerically significant group is made up of the 24,694 inhabitants from the

¹⁹ Statistische Ämter der Länder, ies, Deenst GmbH, eigene Berechnungen. <https://www.wegweiser-kommune.de/statistik/leipzig+bevoelkerungsstruktur+2020+koeln+berlin+table>

²⁰ Low-income = a total net income below 25.000 Euros per year. Medium income = a total net income of between 25.000 and under 50.000 Euros per year. High-income = a total net income of over 50.000 Euros per year.

²¹ Statistische Ämter der Länder, Nexiga GmbH, ZEFIR, eigene Berechnungen, Bundesagentur für Arbeit, Statistische Ämter des Bundes und der Länder. <https://www.wegweiser-kommune.de/statistik/leipzig+soziale-lage+2017+koeln+berlin+table>

²² Since 2005, statistics on the migration background of the city of Cologne have been determined using a multi-stage procedure based on a combination of different information provided by the residents' registration procedure. To allow standardisation with federal and state statistics, family migration background has been adjusted. This means that these statistics also include children and young people where only one parent has a migrant background now.

²³ Neue Kölner Statistik 1/2019: Bevölkerung. https://www.stadt-koeln.de/mediaasset/content/pdf15/statistik-einwohner-und-haushalte/1_089_984_k%C3%B6lnerinnen_und_k%C3%B6lner_im_jahr_2018_ew_nks_1_2019.pdf

Near and Middle East, most of whom have fled their homes due to conflict, and the 15,894 people from the Western Balkans.²⁴

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

In the school year of 2017/18, the distribution of schools and pupils in Cologne was as follows:

Table 4. Schools and Students in Cologne

School Type	Number of Schools	Classes	Total Number of Students	Students with Migration Background
Overall	267	1,553	108,065	49,474
Primary Schools	146		37,920	18,482
Middle Schools – Basic Certificate	17	204	5,025	3,427
Middle School – 10 th Grade	25	436	12,099	7,504
Comprehensive School	14	523	13,912	6,868
Secondary Schools	36	1,221	31,178	11,326
Special Needs Schools	23	339	4,471	1,867
Waldorf Schools	2	25	741	--
Secondary Education	4	121	2,719	--

Source: Statistical Yearbook Cologne. 2018. 222. https://www.stadt-koeln.de/politik-und-verwaltung/statistik/jahrbuecher/https://www.stadt-koeln.de/mediaasset/content/schueler-und-klassenzahlen_schuljahr_2016-2017_im_vergleich_zu_2015-2016.pdf

The share of students leaving school without at least a basic certificate of all students was 4.6% in 2017. Overall numbers identified certain districts where students are more likely to leave school without a basic certificate. Cologne Chorweiler and Mülheim present numbers of 7% and 6% each.²⁵ Regarding overall educational participation, 68.3% of middle schools with basic certificate had the biggest share of children with migration background, followed by a 62% share in middle schools with 10th grade certificate, a 49.4% share in comprehensive schools, a 48.7% share in primary schools, a 41.7% share in special needs schools and a 36.3% share in secondary schools.

10.2.3 Region: Berlin (State of Berlin)

POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS

In 2018, Berlin had an overall population of 3,644,826 with a population density of 4,090 inhabitants²⁶ per square kilometre. The male share of population is 48.7% and the female share of population is 51.3%.²⁷

²⁴Kölner Statistische Nachrichten 3/2020: Kurzinformation Bevölkerung. <https://www.stadt-koeln.de/politik-und-verwaltung/statistik/bevoelkerung-und-haushalte>

²⁵ Statistical Yearbook Cologne. 2018. 232. <https://www.stadt-koeln.de/politik-und-verwaltung/statistik/jahrbuecher/>

²⁶ Amt für Statistik Berlin- Brandenburg. https://www.statistik-berlin-brandenburg.de/regionalstatistiken/r-gesamt_neu.asp?typ=410&Sageb=12015&creg=BBB&anzwer=6

²⁷ Statistische Ämter der Länder, ies, Deenst GmbH, eigene Berechnungen. <https://www.wegweiser-kommune.de/statistik/leipzig+bevoelkerungsstruktur+2020+koeln+berlin+tabelle>

Table 5. Berlin Inhabitants - Statistical Yearbook Berlin - 2019

Age Group	Population
0-5	193,088
5-10	167,404
10-15	151,676
15-20	147,426
20-30	488,507
30-45	842,735
45-65	954,426
65 and older (Pensioner)	699,564

Source: Berlin Statistic. https://www.statistik-berlin-brandenburg.de/produkte/Jahrbuch/jb2019/JB_2019_BE.pdf

In 2017, 57% of households were low-income, that of medium income households 29.1%, and that of high-income households 13.9%.^{28 29} Child poverty amounts to 29.6%, youth poverty to 28.6%, and old age poverty to 6.1% in 2017. As such, Berlin has a significantly higher child and youth poverty rate than Leipzig and Berlin.

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

According to the latest figures, 535,998 Germans with a migration background and 758,550 foreigners were registered in Berlin. Of the 758,550 foreigners currently living in Berlin, the majority come from Europe (481,320, including 282,557 from EU countries), 47,574 from America (including 21,606 from the USA) and 34,584 from Africa. 165,760 people come from Asia, most of them from Syria (38,187), Vietnam (18,241), Afghanistan (12,852) and China (12,514).

The majority of the 758,550 foreigners live in Mitte (131,466, share: 34.2%), Charlottenburg-Wilmersdorf (86,573, 25.3%) and Neukölln (84,243, 25.6%); the fewest in Steglitz-Zehlendorf (46,095, 14.9%), Marzahn-Hellersorf (28,757, 10.7%) and Treptow-Köpenick (26,226, 9.7%).³⁰

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

In the school year of 2018/19, the distribution of schools and pupils in Berlin was as follows:

²⁸ Low-income = a total net income below 25.000 Euros per year. Medium income = a total net income of between 25.000 and under 50.000 Euros per year. High-income = a total net income of over 50.000 Euros per year.

²⁹ Statistische Ämter der Länder, Nexiga GmbH, ZEFIR, eigene Berechnungen, Bundesagentur für Arbeit, Statistische Ämter des Bundes und der Länder. <https://www.wegweiser-kommune.de/statistik/leipzig+soziale-lage+2017+koeln+berlin+tabelle>.

³⁰Office for Statistics Berlin-Brandenburg. https://www.statistik-berlin-brandenburg.de/opendata/Beschreibung_EWR_Datenpool_2018.pdf. Statistical Yearbook Berlin. 2019. https://www.statistik-berlin-brandenburg.de/produkte/Jahrbuch/jb2019/JB_2019_BE.pdf

Table 6. Schools and Students in Berlin

School Type	Number of Schools*	Classes	Number of Teachers	Total Number of Students	Foreign Students	Non-German Origin Language
Overall	817	14,617	30,835	356,963	56,251	138,881
Primary Schools	430	7,791	8,946	173,629	32,079	76,629
Integrated Secondary School ³¹	176	3,659	6,498	94,030	16,033	38,474
Secondary School	112	1,964	3,769	76,510	6,793	20,549
Special Needs Schools	88	1,042	1,380	8,167	1,143	2,943
Waldorf Schools	11	161	115	4,627	203	286

Source: Statistical Yearbook Berlin. 2019. https://www.statistik-berlin-brandenburg.de/produkte/Jahrbuch/jb2019/JB_2019_BE.pdf and <https://www.berlin.de/sen/bildung/schule/bildungsstatistik/>

Overall numbers identified certain districts where students are more likely to leave school without a basic certificate. In Marzahn-Hellersdorf (13.4%), Mitte (12.1%), Neukölln (10.9%) and Friedrichshain-Kreuzberg (10.8%), the proportion of all students without a degree is significantly higher than the Berlin-wide average.

Data is not available on educational attainment for migrant students across the system, but data is available on students with non-German origin language. Of all students with non-German origin language, 20.4%³² left school in 2019/20 without at least a basic certificate.³³

For the Integrated Secondary School, a server exists which lists the percentage of students with migration background at each school. The highest shares have schools in Neukölln with up to 97.8%, Kreuzberg with up to 93.2%, and Berlin Mitte with up to 90.8%. The lowest shares of students with migration background can be found in Pankow and Treptow-Köpenick, both of which were East-German districts until 1990.³⁴

Regarding overall educational participation, 62.6% of primary schools had the biggest share of children with migration background, followed by a 58% share in integrated secondary schools, a 50% share in special needs schools and a 35.7% share in secondary schools.

10.3 School Sampling

³¹A type of school that has existed in the state of Berlin since 2010. Together with the Gymnasium, it is part of a two-pillar model and replaces the Basic Certificate, Junior High School and Comprehensive School. The "integrated secondary school" is realized completely as an all-day school.

³²This number includes school dropouts.

³³Blickpunkt Schule. Tabellen 2019/2020. 2020. 46.

³⁴<https://www.sekundarschulen-berlin.de/migrationshintergrund>. <https://www.gymnasium-berlin.net/migrationshintergrund>.

DOZ's sampling strategy reflects both the stratified random sampling framework and the reality of data availability and accessibility in Germany and across the different regions. Since, regrettably, there is no uniform nationwide education monitoring system, we used regional data from the respective municipalities to gain an initial impression of the education and school data environment. Fortunately, all three cities have their own school databases or directories in place, which we reviewed for key data features. The following characteristics available proved to be common to all: school name, school type, number of enrolled pupils in almost each individual school (in Saxony even by grades), city district where the school is located, sponsorship, school's status of an all-day facility, and denomination.

Regarding the indication of pupils with migration background, only Berlin lists shares of pupils by accounting for pupils with a non-German native language. Compared to this, in Saxony the overall share of pupils with a migration background is accounted for only for all schools within a school type. According to these statistics, a migrant background is present when children grow up bilingual or multilingual and they themselves or at least one parent or grandparent has immigrated to Germany, regardless of their current nationality and regardless of their residence status. The characteristic migration background has been considered as a voluntary entry in the Free State of Saxony since 2008. Therefore, the data only represents a minimum value estimate and thereby loses its informative value. Cologne's school search engine in many cases provides a school portrait with yet another data feature. The engine lists schools that have integrated additional lessons in native language, including those languages available. However, this parameter was deemed to be too unreliable as those lessons must be requested specifically, making the data unsuitable as a point of comparison.

Considering this variety of data or lack thereof, we decided to also use small-scale city data for Leipzig and Cologne instead. This data proved to provide a full picture of all districts by their share of population with a migration background and enabled us to populate the sample pool with schools from minimum to maximum value districts in both cities.

Ultimately, we decided on the following list of categories to populate our sample pool: region, school type, number of students, and share of pupils with migration background by school for Berlin and share of population with migration background by district for Leipzig and Cologne. All of these provide a concise framework which yet allows for a maximum variability in age range, educational level, and share of migration background.

We will include EU nationals from Poland, Romania, Croatia, and Bulgaria as it appears that they do not enjoy the same opportunities and rights as other EU nationals in the labour market and elsewhere. We also wish to include countries from EU-candidate states (including Turkey) as the increase in labour migration by nationals of the Western Balkans countries has been particularly strong in recent years: At the end of 2018, Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia, Montenegro, Kosovo and Macedonia together accounted for almost 25% of all foreigners with a residence permit for the purpose of gainful employment. At the end of 2015, the proportion was still around 9%.³⁵

³⁵ DESTATIS. Statistisches Bundesamt. 2019. https://www.destatis.de/DE/Presse/Pressemitteilungen/2019/04/PD19_149_12521.html

Table 7. Highest Shares of Foreign Population from European Countries in Germany in 2019 by Origin

Countries of Origin	Total
EU Countries	4,882,495
Poland	862,535
Romania	748,225
Italy	646,460
Croatia	414,890
Greece	363,650
Bulgaria	360,170
EU Candidate Countries	1,966,755
Turkey	1,472,390
Serbia	237,755
North-Macedonia	115,210
Albania	65,895
Other Europe	891,475
Russian Federation	260,395
Kosovo	232,075
Bosnia and Herzegovina	203,265
Ukraine	143,545
Total Foreign Population	11,228,30

Source: DESTATIS. Statistisches Bundesamt. Ausländische Bevölkerung und Erwerbstätigkeit. 2020.

<https://www.destatis.de/DE/Themen/Gesellschaft-Umwelt/Bevoelkerung/Migration-Integration/Publikationen/>

Downloads-Migration/auslaend-bevoelkerung-2010200197004.pdf?__blob=publicationFile

Regarding the school types identified versus school types used for the sample pool, DOZ decided to leave out certain types of special needs schools as they assist pupils with disabilities which do not allow them to participate in the study. Lastly, special types of independent schools, such as Waldorf schools, are still accounted for and will be entered in the sample pool, as these schools fit in the category of joint schools (as will be defined further down).

10.3.1 Key characteristics used in sampling framework

The following key characteristics have been identified to inform the sample pool:

REGION

DOZ focuses on schools in three cities of three different regions throughout Germany. To facilitate the creation of the sampling framework, the sample pool covers all districts in all three cities. Derived from the initial sample set, the categories are as follows: Leipzig (Saxony), Cologne (North Rhine-Westphalia), and Berlin (Berlin).

SCHOOL TYPE

Overall, schools of general education in Germany can be divided into three categories: primary, middle, and secondary. However, the spectrum between primary and secondary schools is much more diverse and differs from state to state. In Cologne there are two middle school types – that of 9th and that of 10th grade (Hauptschule and Realschule) – which are not operational any more in Berlin or Saxony. Further, Cologne as well as Berlin have joint comprehensive schools in which students are educated from grade 1 to grade 10 or further as well as integrated secondary schools where students are educated from grade 5/6/7 to grade 10 or further. Therefore, DOZ divided the school types into the following categories:

Category	Characteristic
Primary Schools	1-4/5/6 grade
Middle Schools	5/6/7-9/10 grade
Joint Schools	1-10/or higher grade
Secondary Schools	5/6/7-12/13 grade
Special Needs Schools for Learning, Speech, Social-Emotional Assistance	1-5/9/10 grade

Sources for the different school types were found for each region individually as follows:

- Leipzig, Saxony – Saxony School Database:
<https://schuldatenbank.sachsen.de/index.php?id=2>
- Cologne, North Rhine-Westphalia – City of Cologne’s School Search Engine and the Cologne Education Portal:
<https://www.stadt-koeln.de/leben-in-koeln/bildung-und-schule/schulformen/suche-kolner-schulen#>
https://www.bildung.koeln.de/schule/schulen_koeln/
- Berlin, Berlin – School Directory of the Berlin Senate Department for Education, Youth and Family:
<https://www.berlin.de/sen/bildung/schule/berliner-schulen/schulverzeichnis/index.aspx>

SCHOOL SIZE

The school size derives from the total numbers of student registration per school per region at the beginning of the school year 2019/20. DOZ divided the raw numbers into three categories: small (1-299), medium (300-599), and large (>600).

Sources for the raw data were found for each region individually as follows:

- Leipzig, Saxony – Saxony School Database:
<https://schuldatenbank.sachsen.de/index.php?id=2>
- Cologne, North Rhine-Westphalia – City of Cologne’s School Search Engine and the Cologne Education Portal:
<https://www.stadt-koeln.de/leben-in-koeln/bildung-und-schule/schulformen/suche-kolner-schulen#>
https://www.bildung.koeln.de/schule/schulen_koeln/

- Berlin, Berlin – School Directory of the Berlin Senate Department for Education, Youth and Family:
<https://www.berlin.de/sen/bildung/schule/berliner-schulen/schulverzeichnis/index.aspx>

SHARE OF PUPILS WITH A MIGRATION BACKGROUND – BERLIN

Another key characteristic detected is the share of pupils with migration background in individual schools. Berlin has raw data on almost each school's individual share of pupils with migration background. The raw data available has been divided into the following three categories: low (<30%), middle (30-60%), and high (>60%).

Sources for the raw data were found for each region individually as follows:

- Berlin, Berlin – School Directory of the Berlin Senate Department for Education, Youth and Family:
<https://www.berlin.de/sen/bildung/schule/berliner-schulen/schulverzeichnis/index.aspx>

SHARE OF POPULATION WITH MIGRATION BACKGROUND BY DISTRICT – LEIPZIG AND COLOGNE

DOZ used small-scale city data available for Leipzig and Cologne on the share of population with migration background by district. Since Leipzig has a significant smaller overall number of populations with migration background than Cologne, we decided to use differing measures for each city with the same characteristics – low, middle, and high – applied in both cases. The raw data for Cologne has been divided with the following measures: low (<30%), middle (30-50%), and high (>50%). The raw data for Leipzig has been divided with the following measures: low (<10%), middle (10-20%), and high (>20%).

Sources for the raw data were found for each region individually as follows:

- Leipzig, Saxony – City of Leipzig – City Data Directory – Small-Scale Data:
<https://statistik.leipzig.de/statdist/table.aspx?cat=2&rub=4&item=207>
- Cologne, North Rhine-Westphalia – Kölner Statistische Nachrichten - 1/2019 Statistical Yearbook 2018, 95th Volume:
https://www.stadt-koeln.de/mediaasset/content/pdf15/kapitel_1bev%C3%B6lkerung_und_haushalte_2018.pdf

10.3.2 Categories resulting from key characteristics

The categories derived from the characteristics are as follows:

Region	School Type	School Size	% Share of Pupils with Migration Background by School	% Share of Population with Migration Background by District
Leipzig	Primary	Small	Low	Low
Cologne	Middle	Medium	Middle	Middle
Berlin	Joint	Large	High	High
	Secondary			
	Special Needs			

The overall target sample size for Germany is 3,000 children in 70 centres. To reach maximum variation, we decided to proportionately target the three regions according to the number of schools in each city. While Leipzig has around 150 schools and Cologne has around 270 schools, Berlin has approximately 800 schools. Wherever possible, the sampling will try to cover school types, sizes, and differing migrant proportions evenly in all three cities within the following target groups:

City	Centres	Children
Leipzig	10-15	500-600
Cologne	15-20	600-700
Berlin	40	1800

10.4 School Sampling – Plan B

In the event that the stratified random sampling technique for selecting school sites discussed above yields low response rates, we will use the back-up strategy involving non-probability sampling techniques (as described in the general sampling strategy) that allow us to use our contacts and networks to recruit schools to participate. Those contacts and networks include individual teachers, schools, and integration mediators. We will still sample from each of the categories from the stratified sampling framework, but we will choose sites purposively, rather than randomly, to maximise response rates to reach our participant quota.

10.5 Child/classroom Sampling

We will use a census-type approach for sampling classrooms within schools, as described in the general sampling strategy section. We do not anticipate needing to make any adjustments to this strategy. We will ensure that we have sufficient and proportionate representation of each age group across all types of schools delineated in our school sampling framework.

10.6 Sampling in Non-Formal Education Environments

Due to the lack of data on the characteristics of non-formal education environments and their higher level of inaccessibility, we will use non-probability sampling to select research sites from among these that allow us to use our networks to recruit them to participate. Those networks include

individual social workers and educators with contacts to non-formal education environments as well as the centres themselves. We will use maximum variation purposive sampling and will attempt to target all of the following types of non-formal environments in our chosen regions as categorised below.

TYPE	BASIC INFORMATION
Children and Youth Centres	Recreational facilities that locally provide leisure activities and social support. They can operate only within one district or city-wide. They usually provide special support for socially disadvantaged children and youth.
Community Centres	Public location which provides leisure activities, cultural events, social support, and public information for members of a community. They can locally address all members of a district (or wider community) or only for a specialised group.
Migrant-Led Self-Organised Initiatives	Initiatives that are controlled by people with migration background themselves. They can be locally supporting a certain group of Diasporas or all. Topics addressed can range from education, social support, and cultural heritage to advocacy and social justice.
NGOs and Associations	Organisations that are non-governmental and non-profit that work with migrant and/or refugee children, youth, and families in particular and provide education, social and/or legal support, civil engagement, or advocacy work.

11 Appendix E – Greece (Research Partners: Panteion and RDPSEC)

11.1 Regional Sampling

Greece, a country of 10,724,599¹ people, has historically been a migrant-sending rather than a migrant-receiving country. At the end of the 1980s and beginning of the 1990s, however, Greece started hosting increasing numbers of migrants, mainly from Albania, the Balkans, and the ex-U.S.S.R, along with a small number of migrants from Asia (Philippines, Sri Lanka, Indonesia), North Africa and Egypt. During the last decade, migration flows have continued to increase significantly, especially from Asia (Pakistan, Bangladesh) and Africa, despite the shattering effect the 2008 international economic crisis had on the Greek economy. The two-year period from 2015 to 2016 marked another radical change when massive influxes of mixed flows of mainly international protection applicants and migrants from the Middle East, the conflict zones of Asia, and Africa to the Greek islands through Turkey exceeded the reception capacity of the country, which was still regrouping from the consequences of the economic crisis.

Greece is administratively and geographically divided in 13 Administrative Districts, called “Periferia”, that in turn are divided in 74 Regional Units. Regional Units are further divided to 325 Municipalities. Each Municipality is divided in Municipal Units, Municipal Communities and Local Communities. Based on data found in open sources (discussed below), both migrants and refugees live across the country in all different regions of Greece. In order to set up our strategy we firstly needed to record the possible place of residence of migrant and refugee population.

Mapping of migrants in the country

Based on data from the Greek Statistics Service (ELSTAT), migrants live in all regions across Greece with a slightly higher concentration in big urban centres. According to Greek Statistics Service (ELSTAT), approximately 64,446 immigrants lived in Greece in 2015 (see table 1, migrant population). However, according to the United Nations Economic and Social Affairs Division, the total immigrant population present in Greece for the same year was 1,242,5142 (see table 2). Unfortunately, the data with regards to the migrant population provided by the two organizations show very big discrepancies. It is also unclear what the term “migrant” population consists of and whether this term includes refugees, asylum-seekers, second generation migrants, or returnees of Greek decent etc. For the years 2016, 2017 and 2018, the only available trusted open sources of data for migrants/ immigrants/ refugees were EUROSTAT, which bases inputs on a number of sources, including ELSTAT, IOM, UNHCR and the Greek Asylum Service, who unfortunately record only specific categories of migrant/ refugee population based on their population of concern which is usually connected to the person’s legal status.

¹ According to 2011 census, ELSTAT

² UN EcoSoc, Total migrant stock at mid-year by origin and by major area of destination 2015, Table 16, row 175, Greece <https://www.un.org/en/development/desa/population/migration/data/estimates2/estimates15.asp>, accessed on 18/05/2020

Table 7. General and Migrant-Refugee Population in Greece 2015-2020

Year	General Population	Migrant population	First time asylum applicants	Refugees and asylum seekers receiving cash assistance by UNHCR
2015	10,858,018	64,446	13,205	Non-Existent
2016	10,783,748	116,867	51,110	Non-Existent
2017	10,768,193	112,247	58,650	24,000
2018	10,741,165	119,489	66,965	41,803
2019	10,724,599	N/A	77,275	69,052
2020	N/A	N/A	18,255	96,324

Source: Column 2 and 3: EUROSTAT, 2011, <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tps00001/default/table?lang=en>, Column 4: Greek Asylum Service, February 2020, http://asylo.gov.gr/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Greek_Asylum_Service_data_February_2020_gr.pdf. Column 5: UNHCR Greece 2017-2020, <https://data2.unhcr.org/en/documents/download/75464>. Marked as N/A, means that the data is non-available by the same open source.

Table 2. Immigrant population in Greece 2015

Country of Origin	Number
Albania	437,356
Germany	114,343
Georgia	83,388
Bulgaria	72,893
Russia	54,192
Romania	46,193
Turkey	33,489
Pakistan	31,295
Egypt	28,267
Kazakhstan	26,982
USA	22,839
Cyprus	21,607
Australia	20,224
Other	249,446
Total	1,242,514

Source: UN International Migrant Stock estimates for 2015, <https://www.un.org/en/development/desa/population/migration/data/estimates2/estimates15.asp>

As a result, the total number of foreign born persons present in Greece cannot be calculated with accuracy mostly because of the lack of a unified recording system on migrants and refugees by a national/ European/ international authority and also due to the high and constant mobility of the migrant and refugee population both within the country and of people passing through the country

towards another European country. However, we have compiled what data is available in order to choose regions where migrant and refugee populations are concentrated in order to be able to collect the requisite amount of data.

Mapping of refugees and asylum seekers in the country

Though asylum seekers and refugees do not make up the majority of Greece's migrant population, they are of particular and urgent concern in Greece due to large inflows mostly after 2012 and peaking during 2015-2016 that have overwhelmed the reception system of the country, which was actually non-existent. These persons for the purpose of the study are considered, newly arrived asylum seekers and refugees, as they mostly arrived after 2015 during increased mixed population flows arrive to Greece through the eastern sea/land borders. These newly arrived populations live in various regions and in various conditions across Greece. Accommodation of this population can be divided into first line reception, second line reception and homeless people.

With regards to the first line reception, as of 3 May 2020 **38,300 refugees and asylum seekers**³ live on the **North Aegean islands** (mostly in Lesbos, Samos, Chios, Leros) and in Dodecanese (mostly in Kos, Rhodes). Access to education for children at school level is estimated to a 6%.⁴ **Evros region** is also a part of the first-line reception and is located in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, on the land border with Turkey. The number of newly-arrived migrants and asylum seekers who live in first-reception centers, or in the pre-removal centre remains unknown, since such data is not published by state or non-state actors due to the political sensitivity of the prefecture of *Eastern Macedonia and Thrace*. Children who live in these centres typically do not have access to formal education and often not even to non-formal education, as assistance provided by NGOs and other actors is not always allowed for security reasons.

Second line reception consists of **30 Open Reception Facilities (ORF) in mainland** Greece, where **25,298**⁵ "migrants, including asylum seekers and beneficiaries of international protection" live as of March 2020. Apart from the camps/ ORFs, **22,421 asylum-seekers and refugees**⁶ live under UNHCR ESTIA accommodation program in **10 different regions** across Greece (islands and mainland) as of 4 May 2020. There are also a significant number of **homeless asylum-seeking persons**. The number of homeless persons remains unknown as the Government does not publish data on this population, however, it is estimated that more than 2,000 persons remain homeless all over Greece. Homeless children do not have access to formal education and usually not even non-formal, as they strive simply for survival and constantly change locations of living.

Regional Strategy

As a consequence, since migrants and refugees live scattered across the country, Panteion University chose various geographical regions with different geographical characteristics which

³According to UNHCR data portal, <https://data2.unhcr.org/en/documents/download/75951>, accessed on 11/05/2020

⁴According to theirworld.org report <http://s3.amazonaws.com/theirworld-site-resources/RefugeeEducation-Summary-230420-1.pdf>, accessed on 18/05/2020

⁵According to IOM data, https://greece.iom.int/sites/default/files/FINAL-March.compressed_0.pdf, accessed on 11/05/2020

⁶According to UNHCR data portal, <https://data2.unhcr.org/en/documents/download/75985>, accessed on 11/05/2020

would include migrants and refugees with various, cultural, ethnic, religious, economic and social characteristics.

Since Greece is already divided into 13 Administrative Districts and 74 Regional Units, we identified various geographical characteristics of those regions and based on those, we chose 7 Administrative Regions in which to concentrate our data collection.

Figure 1. Map of Greece - Division in Administrative Districts

Table 3. Administrative Division of Greece

#	Administrative Districts	Major Regional Unit	1. Mainland/ Island	2. Geographical position	3.Regions neighbouring to the borders
1	Attica	Attiki	Mainland	Southern	No
2	Central Greece	Lamia	Mainland & Island	Southern	No
3	Central Macedonia	Thessaloniki	Mainland	Northern	Yes
4	Crete	Heraklion	Island	Southern	Yes, through sea
5	Eastern Macedonia/ Thrace	Komotini	Mainland & Island	Northern	Yes
6	Epirus	Ioannina	Mainland	Northern	Yes
7	Ionian Islands	Corfu	Island	Northern	Yes
8	North Aegean	Lesbos	Island	Northern	Yes, through sea
9	Peloponnese	Tripoli	Mainland	Southern	No
10	South Aegean	Cyclades	Island	Southern	Yes, through sea
11	Thessaly	Larissa	Mainland & Island	Northern	No
12	Western Greece	Patras	Mainland	Northern	Yes
13	Western Macedonia	Kozani	Mainland	Northern	Yes

We identified three categories of geographical characteristics of the 13 Administrative Districts, which are the ones below:

1. Mainland/ Islands / Mainland & Island Greece⁷
2. Northern/ Southern Greece
3. Regions neighbouring to the borders/ Regions in the central parts of Greece

Then, we listed the regions and their characteristics and then we established the following eight (8) categories, based on geographical characteristics:

1. Mainland
2. Mainland & Island
3. Island
4. Next to borders
5. Next to sea borders
6. Central Greece
7. Northern Greece
8. Southern Greece

In order to establish a representative regional sample and achieve maximum representation and variation in sampling of the regions we selected more than the half of the regions under each of the above mentioned eight categories (see table 3).

Therefore, we finally ended up in choosing 7 out of 13 Administrative Districts, which represent all the geographical characteristics that we set.

The process of choosing the Administrative Districts based on the geographical categories that occurred is represented in table 4.

Table 4. Geographical Selection of Administrative Areas

Geographical characteristics	# of regions fulfilling those characteristics	# of regions chosen with those characteristics	Representation
Mainland	6	3	50%
Mainland & Island	3	2	67%
Island	4	2	50%
Next to borders- No	4	2	50%
Next to borders- Yes	5	3	60%
Next to borders- Yes, sea	3	2	67%
Northern	8	5	63%
Southern	4	2	50%

⁷ Some Regions of Greece include both islands and parts of the mainland.

The final selection of Districts includes the following: Attica, Central Macedonia, Crete, Eastern Macedonia/ Thrace, Epirus, North Aegean and Thessaly.

Within the Administrative Districts “Perifereia”, we chose from one to four Regional Units “Nomos” in which to do data collection, usually choosing the Seat/ Major Regional Unit, where the majority of the population is concentrated within the administrative area, and consequently this is reflected in the number of existing schools. Therefore, for all 7 regions we chose the Seat, apart from two cases: the *North Aegean Islands* and *Eastern Macedonia and Thrace*.

In the *North Aegean Islands*, we decided not to choose the Major Regional Unit, Lesvos Regional Unit, for reasons of viability of the research, meaning that the social local and migrant environment is very complex and continuously changing due to the huge numbers of newly arrived refugees and migrants over the last five years. As per Government general practices⁸ there are always tensions between the migrants/ refugees and sometimes including the local population.⁹ We assessed that based on this situation we must put forward the principle of “do no harm” towards the population of our concern and the local population. We wanted to avoid further traumatizing the population of our concern in this very challenging experience that they are facing, which is the migration process. Instead, we chose the second biggest Regional Unit within the Administrative District, which is Chios. In Chios, as well as in the majority of the *North Aegean Islands*, situation remains unstable, but we decided that we want to include those experiences of recent arrival, including the experiences of migration. During the research period, in case we assess that the situation is quite unstable, and in case we assess that our survey might create more unrest in the local society or quite intense stress to the persons who will be interviewed, we might postpone the data collection within the predicted timeframe of Work Package 3, or choose another region, if no other option exists.

In the Administrative District of Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, we decided not to choose Evros and Rodopi Regional Units because they are quite sensitive for similar reasons of viability of research and the “do no harm” principle with regards to the sensitivity of the region. Therefore, we chose the third largest Regional Unit since we have a limitation of accessing Komotini and Evros.

⁸ The Government following the informal arrivals of mixed flows of migrants and refugees at the North Aegean Islands, especially in Lesvos which is the island that hosts the highest numbers of newly arrived third country nationals since 2015 in the First Reception Centre, in Moria Camp, in PIKPA camp, as well as at the surrounding areas. People live in substandard conditions with difficult access to water, sanitation and hygiene, as they set up tents around the reception center, while waiting for the issue of their identification papers (fingerprinting and identification). Following the receipt of their identification papers persons might be given the authority to move freely within the country. Therefore, the Government usually facilitates their move to the mainland in better living conditions. However, after continuous calls of international organizations, NGOs and the local authorities in the international and local press, it was proven that the Greek Government few times has seemed reluctant to move the people who have the necessary identification papers to the mainland due to its policy with Turkey, with regards to the rate of the inflow of refugees and migrants. os i

⁹ See articles at *the Guardian*, February 2020, <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/feb/09/tensions-refugees-and-islanders-crisis-on-lesbos>, accessed on 9/6/2020 and at BBC, March 2020, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-51781394>, accessed on 09/06/2020. See video from CNN uploaded on March 2020, <https://edition.cnn.com/videos/world/2020/03/04/lesbos-greece-tensions-refugee-migrants-lon-orig-mkd.cnn>, accessed on 09/06/2020

11.2 Region Profiles

The most recent available data on population demographics were published by the Statistic Service, ELSTAT, following the last census in 2011.¹⁰ The demographics available and useful for the research found in ELSTAT are the total number of population, level of education and number of foreign nationals.¹¹ An important gap is that Greece does not collect data on ethnicity and socio-economic status. However, the number of unemployed people is included in 2011 census, as well as in recent (2019) press release, but does not include regional breakdown information NUTS II and III), which is important for our comparative analysis.

11.2.1 Region: Attica¹² - Attiki Regional Unit¹³

Attica Administrative district is situated in the Southern part of Greece. It is considered mainland Greece and does not have any borders with other countries. On the contrary belongs to the “heart” of Greece. Attica region is the region where the most populated regional unit is located, Attiki, where the capital city of Greece, Athens city is located. The regional unit of Attiki is administratively divided in 58 Municipalities.

POPULATION DEMOGRAPHIC

The total population of Attiki region for the year of 2011 was 3,828,434¹⁴ of which 1,845,663 were male and 1,982,771 were female.¹⁵ As we can see from the table 6 the highest number of population is between 30 and 59 years old, while the lowest number is of people over 80 years old.

Table 5. Attiki Age Groups 2011

Age Group	Population
0-9	362,540
10-19	353,737
20-29	500,210
30-39	631,478
40-49	586,803
50-59	506,249
60-69	392,349
70-79	311,221
80+	183,847

¹⁰ ELSTAT, 2011 census, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/>

¹¹ Countries of origin are not included in 2011 census. The list includes numbers regarding origin from Europe, Asia and others.

¹²NUTS II level, Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics is a geocode standard for referencing the subdivisions of countries for statistical purposes. In this document we use NUTS I, NUTS II and NUTS III levels.

¹³ NUTS III level.

¹⁴ All demographic data for Attiki and all other regional units were based on ELSTAT (Greek Statistic Service), based on 2011 count. Unfortunately, there were no data more contemporary including all the sub-categories that we are interested in this research projects such as, SES distribution, migrant/ refugee population, countries of origin per administrative district or regional unit or municipality, sex and educational status, so that we can compare and contrast data across regions from a single official data source.

¹⁵ According to population demographics as of 2011, ELSTAT, Table B07

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, [https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/-, Table A01](https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/-,Table A01)

The Gross domestic product (GDP) of the region was 87.4 billion € in 2018, accounting for about 47% of the Greek economic output. The Human Development Index (HDI)¹⁶ for 2018 in Attica was 0.895 in HDI. The unemployment rate for Attiki for the last quarter of 2019 was 16.9% while in country level was 17.3%.¹⁷ In 2011, unemployment rate was 18%.

With regards to ethnic and racial background, the Greek Government's official position is that there are no ethnic or national minorities in the country, apart from the Muslim minority in Thrace, and that the entire population is Greek.¹⁸ However, according to other sources and based on field experience there are ethnic and religious groups Vlachs, Arvanites, ethnic (Slavo-)Macedonians, Roma/ Gypsies, Turks (Muslim minority), Pomaks (Muslim Minority), Pontiacs, Vorio-iprotes and Cham Albanians, Armenians and Jews all across Greece,¹⁹ but there are no specific data for the Regional Unit of Attiki. It is possible, due to the fact that in Attiki lives 35% of the population of the country, that there are people with such characteristics, but there is no official data collected.

Following the genocide of Armenians in Ottoman Empire, it is said that 80,000 Armenians came to Greece. As of 2007, the number of Armenians in Greece is estimated approximately 20,000-35,000 across the country with community among others in the city of Athens.²⁰

There are few data though about some of the Roma settlements in Attiki and are situated in Central Athens, Koropi, Chalandri, Vrilissia, Acharnes, Ano Liossia and Aspropyrgos.²¹ It is important to mention that 9 Municipalities in Attiki, have a Service Center who provides additional services to Roma people, like women's empowerment, hygiene promotion, etc.

The educational background of the Greek population of Attiki can be found in table 7. The obligatory school education is for children 6-15 years old, which correspond with the Elementary school and until the third class of Junior High School.

¹⁶ Human Development Index (HDI) is a statistic composite index of life expectancy, education, and per capita income indicators, which are used to rank countries into four tiers of human development. In Brussels for the same year, 2018, was 0,919, in Berlin was 0,950, in Dublin was 0,963, etc. Global Data Lab.

https://globaldatalab.org/shdi/shdi/BEL+DEU+GRC+IRL+ITA+ESP/?levels=1%2B4&interpolation=0&extrapolation=0&nearest_real=0&years=2018%2B2017%2B2016%2B2015, accessed on 09/06/2020

¹⁷ ELSTAT, 2019, Labour force, quarterly data, Table 09. The same source applies for all the Regional Units mentioned.

¹⁸ Britannica, Ethnic groups of Greece, <https://www.britannica.com/place/Greece/Climate#ref281568>, accessed on 09/06/2020.

¹⁹ Minority Rights Group International, Ethnic Groups, <https://minorityrights.org/country/greece/>, accessed on 09/06/2020

²⁰ Armenian minority in Greece, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Armenians_in_Greece accessed on 10/06/2020

²¹ Greek Ombudsman, Roma interactive map, <https://www.synigoros.gr/maps?i=maps.el.maps> accessed on 09/06/2020

Table 6: Attiki – Level of Education of Greek Population 2011

Education	Both sexes	Female	Male
PhD/ Post-Graduate/ University Degree	795,974	419,746	409,856
Post-Secondary/ Senior High School	1,123,357	677,798	521,287
Junior High School/ Professional schools	402,612	212,412	223,604
Elementary Graduates	586,847	362,718	247,346
Other	513,813	310,097	236,145
TOTAL	3,422,603	1,784,365	1,638,238

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/>, Table A03

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

According to 2011 count, a total of 405,831²² residents who lived in Attiki were born in a foreign country. However, the data are quite old and do not capture reality as of 9 years later and following the migrant/refugee influx of 2015.

Table 7. Attiki-Greek and Foreign Population per Citizenship Group and Sex 2011

	Greek	Total Foreign	Foreign EU	Foreign Europe	Asian	Other	Total
Both Sexes	3,422,603	405,831	72,516	219,229	86,663	27,423	3,828,434
Female	1,784,365	198,406	43,345	114,290	29,456	11,315	1,982,771
Male	1,638,238	207,425	29,171	104,939	52,207	16,108	1,845,663

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/>, Table B07

After 1989 and the fall of the Soviet Union a significant number of migrants arrived and settled in Greece from Soviet Union, eastern and central Europe and elsewhere. Such populations live mainly (but not only) at the Administrative District of Attica and the Municipality of Athens, which is the biggest capital of Greece.

According to data provided by the municipality of Athens published by the OECD, Athens Municipality had almost 78,000 migrants in 2016 who had residence permit, with the most popular origin countries being Albania, Philippines, Bangladesh, Ukraine and Egypt.²³ However, there are no data in open source collected at national/ regional/ municipal level with regards to migration/refugee background at NUTS II/ III level, so that it can be comparable with similar administrative regions within Greece.

²²ELSTAT website, Population demographics, Table B07

²³OECD, Working together for Local Integration of Migrants and Refugees in Athens, <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/docserver/9789264304116-4-en.pdf?expires=1591047681&id=id&accname=guest&checksum=EE660480CC92BCA8F904D004FBD187DA>, 2020 accessed on 02/06/2020

Table 8. Counties of Origin in Municipality of Athens – OECD 2016

	Nationality	Population
1	Albania	38,469
2	Philippines	6,083
3	Bangladesh	4,383
4	Ukraine	4,026
5	Egypt	3,549
6	Georgia	3,203
7	Pakistan	3,068
8	Moldova	2,120
9	Syrian A. R.	2,025
10	China	1,662
11	Nigeria	1,194
12	Russia	1,186
13	India	792
14	Ethiopia	726
15	Sri Lanka	499
16	Ghana	475
17	Armenia	452
18	Morocco	324
19	Iran	312
20	Others	3,258
	TOTAL	77,806

Source: OECD, Working together for Local Integration of Migrants and Refugees in Athens, https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/social-issues-migration-health/working-together-for-local-integration-of-migrants-and-refugees-in-athens/key-data-on-migrant-presence-and-integration-in-athens_9789264304116-4-en;jsessionid=umFPgqgESCtMaj05F9XwabKW.ip-10-240-5-93, accessed on 02/06/2020

As of June 2020, 53% of the total of refugees living in UNHCR sponsored apartments in Greece live in Attica which corresponds to 12,140 people.²⁴ As of April 2020, 11,977 asylum-seekers, refugees and others live in ORFs/ camps within the region of Attica.²⁵ These persons are newly-arrived in Greece, i.e. after 01/01/2015. The majority of these people originate from Syria, Afghanistan, Iraq, Iran, D.R. Congo and others.²⁶ Both in the Accommodation program and in camps children usually represent 34-62% of the population. In apartments school enrolment is 68% while in camps varies per camp from 0 to 45%.

²⁴UNHCR data portal, ESTIA Population breakdown as of 9 June 2020, <https://data2.unhcr.org/en/documents/download/76987>, accessed on 09/06/2020

²⁵IOM Factsheets, April 2020 statistics on Open Reception Facilities across Greece, <https://greece.iom.int/sites/default/files/April%20Merged.pdf>, accessed on 09/06/2020

²⁶ UNHCR data portal, Accommodation update for May 2020, <https://data2.unhcr.org/en/documents/download/76840> accessed on 09/06/2020

With regards to the integration of migrants at the regional unit of Attiki, particularly the Municipalities of Athens and Piraeus, which are two of the largest municipalities in Attiki, have been actively contributing in the integration process by hosting asylum seekers and refugees since 2016 in apartments which they provide for free to the beneficiaries under UNHCR ESTIA Accommodation Program until the asylum-seekers receive their decision on their asylum application. Additionally, in 2018 they created two Service Centers, called Migrants' Service Centers (Kentro Entaxis Metanaston, K.E.M.), which facilitate migrants' access to services such as social support, access to health care, allowances, taxation, etc.

The educational background of the foreign-born population living in Attiki according to 2011 census, can be seen in the below table 9.

Table 9. Attiki – Level of Education of Foreign-born Population

Education	Both sexes	Female	Male
PhD/ Post-Graduate/ University Degree	53,679	33,628	20,051
Post-Secondary/ Senior High School	143,260	75,728	67,532
Junior High School/ Professional schools	74,725	33,404	41,321
Elementary Graduates	54,594	23,217	36,377
Other	74,573	32,429	42,144
TOTAL	405,831	198,406	207,425

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/>, Table B10

The unemployment status of Greek and foreign-born population as of 2011, was as per the below table.

Table 10. Attiki – Unemployment of Greek and Foreign-born Population

	# of unemployed	Out of # in the region
Total	319,359	3,828,434
Greeks	258,451	3,422,603
Foreign born	60,908	405,831

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM04/>, Table A10

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

According to the available data from 2019,²⁷ there are 1814 schools (not including pre-school). More specifically, in each of the three levels, here are the below number of schools in the region.

²⁷Institute of Educational Policy, Institutouto Ekpedeftikis Politikis (IEP), List of schools in Greece, per Administrative District and per Regional Unit, see excel table at the bottom of the page. Includes all types of schools in the country, <http://iep.edu.gr/el/ereunes-programmata>, accessed on 09/06/2020.

Table 11. Attiki – Number of Schools at Each Level

1	Public Dimotiko/ Elementary	814
2	Public Gymnasium/ Junior High School	388
3	Public Lyceum/ Senior High School	367
4	Private (includes primary and secondary level)	245

Out of these schools, we are planning to select schools among the following categories of interest.

Table 12. Attiki – Primary Education: 4 Categories Chosen²⁸

1	DYEP, ZEP, Intercultural	0
2	None	636
3	ZEP	178
4	DYEP	0
5	Intercultural	4
6	DYEP, ZEP	0
7	ZEP, Intercultural	4
8	DYEP, intercultural	0

Source: Various sources such as the Greek Government Gazettes and the national database on types of school (Greek). Please refer to chapter for further explanation of the categories 5.3.1. Key characteristics, p. 136-137

Table 13. Attiki – Secondary Education: 6 Categories Chosen

1	DYEP, ZEP, Intercultural	0
2	None	646
3	ZEP	96
4	DYEP	7
5	Intercultural	3
6	DYEP, ZEP	6
7	ZEP, intercultural	2
8	DYEP, intercultural	0

Source: Various sources such as the Greek Government Gazettes and the national database on types of school (Greek). Please refer to chapter for further explanation of the categories 5.3.1. Key characteristics, p. 136-137

The total number of students was available only in Administrative District Level (NUTS II), namely Attica, and not in Regional Unit level (NUTS III), meaning Attiki, and only for two or three years ago, i.e, latest school year with available data was that of 2017-8. Therefore, the numbers provided are indicative.

²⁸ Gymnasium refers to junior high school and Lyceum to senior high school. Dimotika are Elementary schools which some of them have Zones of Educational Priority (ZEP), and other have Refugee Education Reception Classes (DYEP).

Table 14. Attica – Registered Student Population for 2017-18

School Level	Total	Boys	Girls	% of total student population
Elementary School/ Dimotiko	223,172	114,551	108,621	34.9%
Junior High School/ Gymnasium	107,609	55,868	51,741	34.4%
Senior High School/ Lyceum	88,323	42,951	45,372	35.9%

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, Press Release 31 October 2019, <https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/997dd82e-da34-b82f-3795-6904127cc113>

It is interesting to mention the number of students who graduated the same year.

Table 15. Attica – Students who Graduated 2017-18

School Level	Total	Boys	Girls
Elementary School/ Dimotiko	36,249	N/A	N/A
Junior High School/ Gymnasium	34,438	N/A	N/A
Senior High School/ Lyceum	28,600	N/A	N/A

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, Press Release 31 October 2019, <https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/997dd82e-da34-b82f-3795-6904127cc113>

There are no data on students' characteristics in open source. Such data are only collected at school level and not in central level.

11.2.2 Region: Central Macedonia²⁹ - Thessaloniki Regional Unit³⁰

Central Macedonia is located in mainland Greece, in the Northern part of Greece neighboring two countries, Northern Macedonia and Bulgaria. Central Macedonia is the largest district in the country (in terms of area in square meters) and is the second most populated district following Attica. The Administrative District of Central Macedonia is divided in 7 regional units out of which we chose Thessaloniki, which is the major regional unit/ Seat.

Thessaloniki, the capital of Central Macedonia, is the second-largest city in Greece, also known in Greek as "the co-capital". It is Greece's second major economic, industrial, commercial and political centre after Athens. Thessaloniki is located on the Thermaic Gulf, at the northwest corner of the Aegean Sea. The regional unit of Thessaloniki is subdivided into 14 municipalities: Ampelokipoi-

²⁹ NUTS II level

³⁰ NUTS III level

Menemeni, Chalkidona, Delta, Kalamaria, Kordelio-Evosmos, Lagkadas, Neapoli-Sykies, Oraiokastros, Pavlos Melas, Pylaia-Chortiatis, Thermaikos, Thermi, Thessaloniki and Volvi.

POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS

The total population of Thessaloniki region for 2011 was 1,110,551 of which 531,102 were male and 579,449 were female. As we can see from the table 17 the highest number of population is between 30 and 59 years old, while the lowest number is of people over 80 years old.

Table 16. Thessaloniki Age Groups

Age Group	Population
0-9	113,015
10-19	117,190
20-29	149,703
30-39	171,834
40-49	167,752
50-59	141,002
60-69	107,624
70+	142,431

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/-, Table A01>

In 2011, the regional unit of Thessaloniki had a Gross Domestic Product of €18.293 billion (ranked 2nd amongst the country's regional units), which stands at 63% of the EU average. Thessaloniki accounts for 8.9% of the total economy of Greece. The HDI for 2018 was 0,867, which puts Central Macedonia 4th rank among the 13 Administrative Districts. Unemployment rate in Thessaloniki for 2019, was 19,3% while at country level was 17,3%. In 2011 unemployment rate was 22%.

The education of the Greek population is depicted in the table 18, according to 2011 census.

Table 17. Thessaloniki – Level of Education of Greek Population

Education	Both sexes	Female	Male
PhD/ Post-Graduate/ University Degree	210,470	110,058	100,412
Post-Secondary/ Senior High School	321,597	166,641	154,956
Junior High School/ Professional schools	128,796	57,569	71,227
Elementary Graduates	204,329	114,809	89,520
Other	175,398	94,089	81,309
TOTAL	1,040,590	543,166	497,424

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/-, Table A03>

Greece does not collect data on ethnicity but however, based on the geographical area and the historic sources, it is well known that Thessaloniki had and still has one of the largest Jewish communities in Greece. Sephardic Jews live in the region since 15th Century, coming to Greece

due to persecution in Spain. In World War II, and more specifically in 1943 Germans occupied Greece and forced 60,000 Jews of Thessaloniki in the ghetto, in concentration camps and in labor camps. Today, only 1,200 Jews live in the city.³¹

One of the ethnic groups that live in wider area are also Slavo-Macedonians or Macedonians, who identify as such, and speak the Macedonian language and live in Central and Western Macedonia. This minority is not recognized by the Greek Government, because of fear of association with neighboring Northern Macedonia, and because Greek Government has an historical argument on the “Greekness” of Macedonians, since ancient times. However, this minority which fled Greek territories during the Greek Civil War has been discriminated since 1982 in terms of no recognition, compulsory change of names and names of places (toponymia), confiscation of property, interrogations at the borders and prohibition of entry for those who are Greeks but identify as (Slavo-)Macedonians, difficulty of obtaining visas for visits to Greece, discrimination in education and denial of freedom of political association.³²

Another visible ethnic minority in Thessaloniki are Roma. According to Ombudsman only one community of Roma is mentioned in Agia Sofia, consisting of 200 families.³³ However, according to ARSIS NGO, there are two more settlements in 2013 in Dendropotamos and Peraia. The NGO was providing social support, by empowering women of the community as well as non-formal education to all three regions and incentives for Roma people with regards to access to education, as many children do not attend school.

Central Macedonia is traditionally one of the regions that Armenians use to live. In the city of Thessaloniki, an Armenian church stands until today. Following the genocide of Armenians in Ottoman Empire, it is said that 80,000 Armenians came to Greece. As of 2007, the number of Armenians in Greece is estimated approximately 20,000- 35,000 across the country with community among others in the city of Thessaloniki.

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

According to the 2011 census 69,961 inhabitants of Thessaloniki regional unit were foreign nationals (6% of its total population).

Table 18. Thessaloniki – Greek and Foreign Population per Citizenship Group and Sex

	Greek	Total Foreign	Foreign EU	Foreign Europe	Asian	Other	TOTAL
Both Sexes	1,040,590	69,961	10,910	43,169	13,283	2,599	1,110,551
Female	543,166	36,283	6,397	21,518	7,343	1,025	579,449
Male	497,424	33,678	4,513	21,651	5,940	1,574	531,102

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/>, Table B07

³¹ Jews of Thessaloniki, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_the_Jews_in_Thessaloniki accessed on 10/06/2020

³² Report of the independent expert Gay McDougall, 2008, UN Human Rights Council, Mission to Greece, <https://www.refworld.org/docid/49b7b2e52.html>, accessed on 10/06/2020, p. 12-15

³³ Greek Ombudsman, 2008, interactive map of settlements, <https://www.synigoros.gr/maps?i=maps.el.maps> accessed on 10/06/2020.

Thessaloniki has provided refuge to those fleeing persecution and conflict, from Sephardic Jews in the 1400s to Greek refugee returnees in the 1900s. Until the end of the 20th century, Thessaloniki hosted mostly migrants of Greek origin from the former USSR, Albanian migrants, migrants from EU countries and other western origins, as well as migrants from the former Soviet Union. Today, Thessaloniki hosts asylum seekers and refugees from Syria, Afghanistan, Iraq, Turkey, plus south Asian and African countries.

The education level of the foreign-born population as per 2011 count was, as per the below table.

Table 19. Thessaloniki – Level of Education of Foreign-born Population

Education	Both sexes	Female	Male
PhD/ Post-Graduate/ University Degree	8,981	5,779	3,202
Post-Secondary/ Senior High School	23,052	12,513	10,539
Junior High School/ Professional schools	14,238	6,767	7,471
Elementary Graduates	10,739	5,041	5,698
Other	12,951	6,183	6,768
TOTAL	69,961	36,283	33,678

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/>, Table B10

The socioeconomic status, i.e. unemployment status of the foreign born and Greek population in 2011 census, was as per the below table.

Table 20. Central Macedonia – Unemployment of Greek and Foreign-born Population

	# of unemployed	Out of # in the region
Total	168,480	1,882,108
Greeks	151,564	1,765,190
Foreign born	16,916	116,918

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM04/>, Table A10

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

Schools of Thessaloniki regional unit are divided into 4 administrative categories: Directorate of Primary Education of East Thessaloniki, Directorate of Primary Education of West Thessaloniki, Directorate of Secondary Education of East Thessaloniki and Directorate of Secondary Education of East Thessaloniki. There are 1370 schools in total in the area of Thessaloniki, out of which 50 are private and the rest are public.

Table 21. Thessaloniki – Number of Schools in Each Level

1	Public Dimotiko/ Elementary	347
2	Public Gymnasium/ Junior High School	136
3	Public Lyceum/ Senior High School	134
4	Private (includes several levels)	50

Table 22. Thessaloniki – Primary Education: 5 Categories Chosen

1	DYEP, ZEP, Intercultural	0
2	None	247
3	ZEP	90
4	DYEP	3
5	Intercultural	3
6	DYEP, ZEP	2
7	ZEP, intercultural	3
8	DYEP, intercultural	0

Source: Various sources such as the Greek Government Gazettes and the national database on types of school (Greek). Please refer to chapter for further explanation of the categories 5.3.1. Key characteristics, p. 136-137

Table 23. Thessaloniki – Secondary Education: 3 Categories Chosen

1	DYEP, ZEP, Intercultural	0
2	None	500
3	ZEP	34
4	DYEP	0
5	Intercultural	2 (same with no7)
6	DYEP, ZEP	0
7	ZEP, intercultural	2
8	DYEP, intercultural	0

Source: Various sources such as the Greek Government Gazettes and the national database on types of school (Greek). Please refer to chapter for further explanation of the categories 5.3.1. Key characteristics, p. 136-137

The total number of students was available only in Administrative District Level (NUTS II), namely Central Macedonia, and not in Regional Unit level (NUTS III), meaning Thessaloniki, and only for two or three years ago, i.e, latest school year with available data was that of 2017-8. Therefore, the numbers provided are indicative.

Table 24. Central Macedonia – Registered Student Population 2017-18

School Level	Total	Boys	Girls	% of total school population
Elementary School/ Dimotiko	112,918	57,799	55,119	17.7%
Junior High School School/ Gymnasium	55,295	N/A	N/A	17.7%
Senior High School/ Lyceum	43,930	N/A	N/A	17.9%

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, Press Release 31 October 2019, <https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/997dd82e-da34-b82f-3795-6904127cc113>

It is interesting to note that the students who graduated that year are the below:

Table 25. Central Macedonia – Students who Graduated 2017-18

School Level	Total	Boys	Girls
Elementary School/ Dimotiko	18,833	N/A	N/A
Junior High School School/ Gymnasium	17,773	N/A	N/A
Senior High School/ Lyceum	14,367	N/A	N/A

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, Press Release 31 October 2019, <https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/997dd82e-da34-b82f-3795-6904127cc113>

There are no data on students' characteristics in open source. Such data are only collected at school level and not in central level.

11.2.3 Region: Crete – Heraklion, Lasithi, Chania, Rethymno Regional Units

The Administrative District of Crete is part of the regions that participate in the research, because Regional Directorate of Crete is a partner in IMMERSE project. The whole District is an island and is located in Southern Greece, neighbouring through seas with Libya and Egypt in the south. Crete is the largest island of Greece. Crete is divided in four Regional Units, out of which we chose all four.

POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS

The total population of Crete region for the year of 2011 was 623,065³⁴ of which 308,665 were male and 314,400 were female.³⁵ As we can see from the table 27 the highest number of population is between 30 and 39 years old, while the lowest number is between 60-69 years old.

Table 26. Crete Age Groups 2011

Age Group	Population
0-9	69,924
10-19	68,459
20-29	82,605
30-39	97,447
40-49	88,815
50-59	72,308
60-69	60,089
70+	83,418

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/-,Table A01>

³⁴ All demographic data for Attiki and all other regional units were based on ELSTAT (Greek Statistic Service), based on 2011 count. Unfortunately, there were no data more contemporary including all the sub-categories that we are interested in this research projects such as, SES distribution, migrant/ refugee population, countries of origin per administrative district or regional unit or municipality, sex and educational

³⁵ According to population demographics as of 2011, ELSTAT, Table B07

The Region of Crete participates in the Gross Domestic Product of the country at a percentage of 4.9%. In particular, for the year 2010, according to recent updated data of the Regional Accounts of the Hellenic Statistical Authority, the GDP of Crete amounted to 10,955 million euro and constituted 4.9% of the national GDP. The Regional Unit of Heraklion, being the most populated one, has the largest participation (49%) in the regional GDP, followed by the Regional Unit of Chania (25%). The participation of the Regional Units of Lassithi and Rethymno is at lower levels (both at 13%).

The Human Development Index (HDI)³⁶ for 2018 in Crete was 0.890 in HDI. The unemployment rate for Crete for the last quarter of 2019 was 13.8% for Heraklion, 15.6% for Rethymno and 15.1% for Chania. Lassithi is not mentioned while in country level was 17.3%.

With regards to ethnic and racial background, the Greek Government's official position is that there are no ethnic or national minorities in the country, apart from the Muslim minority in Thrace, and that the entire population is Greek.³⁷ In Crete there are not mentioned other ethnic and religious groups. What it is specific for the region and it is of a particular interest is the local dialect that it is spoken all over Crete and mostly in the countryside. It is referred as one of the closest dialect to the ancient Greek as it kept linguistic particularities lost through the years in the other regions of continental Greece. Another particularity is that the inhabitants of Crete have a strong cultural identity that they continue to keep it even if they have to leave Crete. Among their characteristics is the sense of belonging and sharing, the values of hospitality, respect and duty.

There are few data though about a Roma settlement in Crete and it is situated in the city of Heraklion near a location called Nea Alikarnassos. In Nea Alikarnassos there is also a Service Center who provides additional services to Roma people, like women's empowerment, hygiene promotion, etc. In some neighborhoods of Heraklion as "Pateles", "Xhrysopigi" and "Poros" we found some Roma populations that live in apartments.

The educational background of the Greek population of Crete can be found in table 28. The obligatory school education is for children 6-15 years old, which correspond with the Elementary school and until the third class of Junior High School.

Table 27. Crete – Level of Education of Greek Population 2011

Education	Both sexes	Female	Male
PhD/ Post-Graduate/ University Degree	90,940	43,674	47,266
Post-Secondary/ Senior High School	161,316	78,104	83,212
Junior High School/ Professional schools	87,754	49,215	38,539
Elementary Graduates	160,104	80,236	79,868
Other	122,951	57,436	65,515
TOTAL	623,065	308,665	314,400

³⁶ Human Development Index (HDI) is a statistic composite index of life expectancy, education, and per capita income indicators, which are used to rank countries into four tiers of human development. In Brussels for the same year, 2018, was 0,919, in Berlin was 0,950, in Dublin was 0,963, etc. Global Data Lab, https://globaldatalab.org/shdi/shdi/BEL+DEU+GRC+IRL+ITA+ESP/?levels=1%2B4&interpolation=0&extrapolation=0&nearest_real=0&years=2018%2B2017%2B2016%2B2015, accessed on 09/06/2020

³⁷ Britannica, Ethnic groups of Greece, <https://www.britannica.com/place/Greece/Climate#ref281568>, accessed on 09/06/2020.

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/>, Table A03

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

According to 2011 count, a total of 559,730³⁸ residents who lived in Crete were born in a foreign country. However, the data are quite old and do not capture reality as of 9 years later and following the migrant/refugee influx of 2015.

Table 28. Crete – Greek and Foreign Population per Citizenship Group and Sex 2011

	Greek	Total Foreign	Foreign EU	Foreign Europe	Asian	Other	Total
Both Sexes	559,730	63,335	25,308	29,399	6,097	2,531	623,065
Female	282,165	32,235	14,732	14,661	1,949	893	314,400
Male	277,565	31,100	10,576	14,738	4,148	1,638	308,665

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/>, Table B07

After 1989 and the fall of the Soviet Union a significant number of migrants arrived and settled in Greece from Soviet Union, eastern and central Europe and elsewhere. Such populations live also in Crete but there are not any official data.

As of June 2020, 4% of the total of refugees living in UNHCR sponsored apartments in Greece live in Crete which corresponds to 886 people.³⁹

With regards to the integration of migrants at the regional unit of Crete, the Municipality of Heraklion in collaboration with Heraklion development Agency have been actively contributing in the integration process by hosting asylum seekers and refugees since 2016 in apartments which they provide for free to the beneficiaries under UNHCR ESTIA Accommodation Program until the asylum-seekers receive their decision on their asylum application.

The educational background of the foreign-born population living in Crete according to 2011 census, can be seen in the below table 30.

Table 29. Crete – Level of Education of Foreign-born Population

Education	Both sexes	Female	Male
PhD/ Post-Graduate/ University Degree	5,530	1,868	3,662
Post-Secondary/ Senior High School	17,546	7,779	9,767
Junior High School/ Professional schools	12,821	6,668	6,153
Elementary Graduates	13,188	7,223	5,965
Other	14,250	7,562	6,688
TOTAL	63,335	31,100	32,235

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/>, Table B10

³⁸ ELSTAT website, Population demographics, Table B07

³⁹ UNHCR data portal, ESTIA Population breakdown as of 9 June 2020, <https://data2.unhcr.org/en/documents/download/76987>, accessed on 09/06/2020

The unemployment status of Greek and foreign-born population as of 2011, per the below table.

Table 30. Crete – Unemployment of Greek and Foreign-born Population

	# of unemployed	Out of # in Crete
Total	44,155	623,065
Greeks	36,532	559,730
Foreign born	7,623	63,335

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM04/>, Table A10

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

According to the available data from 2019, there are 565 schools (not including pre-school). More specifically, in each of the three levels, here are the below number of schools in the region.

Table 31. Crete – Number of Schools in Each Level

1	Public Dimotiko / Elementary	335
2	Public Gymnasium/ Junior High School	123
3	Public Lyceum/ Senior High School	96
4	Private	11
Heraklion: - Number of Schools in each level		
1	Public Dimotiko/ Elementary	158
2	Public Gymnasium/ Junior High School	53
3	Public Lyceum/ Senior High School	40
4	Private	5
Lasithi: - Number of Schools in each level		
1	Public Dimotiko/ Elementary	42
2	Public Gymnasium/ Junior High School	19
3	Public Lyceum/ Senior High School	14
4	Private	0
Rethymno: - Number of Schools in each level		
1	Public Dimotiko/ Elementary	54
2	Public Gymnasium/ Junior High School	21
3	Public Lyceum/ Senior High School	17
4	Private	0
Chania: - Number of Schools in each level		
1	Public Dimotiko/ Elementary	81
2	Public Gymnasium/ Junior High School	30
3	Public Lyceum/ Senior High School	25
4	Private	6

Source: Institute of Educational Policy, Institutouto Ekpedeftikis Politikis (IEP), List of schools in Greece, per Administrative District and per Regional Unit, see excel table at the bottom of the page. Includes all types of schools in the country, <http://iep.edu.gr/el/ereunes-programmata>, accessed on 09/06/2020.

Out of these schools, we are planning to select schools among the following categories of interest.

Table 32. Crete – Primary Education: 3 Categories Chosen

1	DYEP, ZEP, Intercultural	0
2	None	247
3	ZEP	87
4	DYEP	0
5	Intercultural	1
6	DYEP, ZEP	0
7	ZEP, intercultural	0
8	DYEP, intercultural	0

Source: Various sources such as the Greek Government Gazettes and the national database on types of school (Greek). Please refer to chapter for further explanation of the categories 5.3.1. Key characteristics, p. 136-137.

Table 33. Crete – Secondary Education: 2 Categories Chosen

1	DYEP, ZEP, Intercultural	0
2	None	226
3	ZEP	4
4	DYEP	0
5	Intercultural	0
6	DYEP, ZEP	0
7	ZEP, intercultural	0
8	DYEP, intercultural	0

Source: Various sources such as the Greek Government Gazettes and the national database on types of school (Greek). Please refer to chapter for further explanation of the categories 5.3.1. Key characteristics, p. 136-137

The total number of students was available only in Administrative District Level (NUTS II), namely Crete, and not in Regional Unit level (NUTS III), meaning Crete, and only for two or three years ago, i.e. latest school year with available data was that of 2017-8. Therefore, the numbers provided are indicative.

Table 34. Crete – Registered Student Population for 2017-18

School Level	Total	Boys	Girls	% of total student population
Elementary School/ Dimotiko	44,057	22,542	21,515	6.8%
Junior High School/School/ Gymnasium	21,352	N/A	N/A	6.8%
Senior High School/ Lyceum	15,126	N/A	N/A	6.2%

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, Press Release 31 October 2019, <https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/997dd82e-da34-b82f-3795-6904127cc113>

It is interesting to mention the number of students who graduated the same year.

Table 35. Crete – Students who Graduated 2017-18

School Level	Total	Boys	Girls
Elementary School/ Dimotiko	6.825	N/A	N/A
Junior High School/ Gymnasium	6.809	N/A	N/A
Senior High School/ Lyceum	4.785	N/A	N/A

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, Press Release 31 October 2019, <https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/997dd82e-da34-b82f-3795-6904127cc113>

There are no data on students' characteristics in open source. Such data are only collected at school level and not in central level.

11.2.4 Region: Thessaly – Larissa Regional Unit

Larissa is one of the 5 regional units of Thessaly and its largest one. It is actually the second largest regional unit in the country and is the Seat of Thessaly. Geographically Larissa is at the eastern part of central Greece. Larissa is subdivided in 7 municipalities.

POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS

The total population of Larissa as of 2011 census was 284,325 out of which 140,809 were male and 143,615 were female. As we can see from the table below the lowest population numbers were for the ages 0-9 and 10-19.

Table 36. Larissa Age Groups

Age Group	Population
0-9	71,731
10-19	74,730
20-29	82,355
30-39	101,907
40-49	102,144
50-59	94,582
60-69	82,908
70+	122,405

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/-,Table A01>

The Gross domestic product of the region of Thessaly for 2017 was 9,437 million which accounted for the 5.2% of the country's GDP ranking 3rd among the 13 regions.⁴⁰ The Human Development

⁴⁰ European Commission databases, Thessaly region 2017, <https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/regional-innovation-monitor/base-profile/region-thessalia>, accessed on 10/06/2020.

Index for 2018 was 0.850⁴¹. The unemployment rate for the last quarter of 2019 in Larissa was 16,9% while in country level was 17.3.⁴² In 2011 unemployment rate was 15.4%.

With regards to ethnic, racial and religious background of the local population within Thessaly region there are Vlachs and Roma groups. There are three Roma settlements: Volos in Aliveri; Sofades; and Farsala but their number is not known. The villages of Vlachs (Vlachochoria) of Thessaly are more than 30 including population living within Larissa.⁴³ Their population is also unknown as due to cultural assimilation, younger generations tend not to identify with a particular ethnic identity. Vlachs also called Aromanians however, have their own language which is similar to Latin.⁴⁴

The educational background of the Greek population of Ioannina can be found in table 38.

Table 37. Larissa – Level of Education of Greek Population

Education	Both sexes	Female	Male
PhD/ Post-Graduate/ University Degree	42,609	21,794	20,815
Post-Secondary/ Senior High School	65,502	31,586	33,916
Junior High School/ Professional schools	31,523	12,579	18,944
Elementary Graduates	68,856	37,968	31,788
Other	59,072	32,588	26,484
TOTAL	267,562	135,615	131,947

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/->, Table A03

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

According to 2011 count, a total of 16,763 residents who lived in Larissa were born in a foreign country. However, the data are quite old and do not capture reality as of 9 years later and following the migrant/refugee influx of 2015. For Larissa regional unit there are not any further data with regards to the migrants' country of origin or the date of arrival to the country

As of June 2020, 5% of the total of refugees living in UNHCR sponsored apartments in Greece, live in Thessaly, which corresponds to 334 people.⁴⁵ As of April 2020, 1,974 asylum-seekers and refugees and others live in 1 ORF/ camp within the region of Thessaly.⁴⁶ These persons are newly-arrived in Greece, i.e. after 01/01/2015. The majority of these people originate from Afghanistan,

⁴¹ Global Data Lab, https://globaldatalab.org/shdi/shdi/BEL+DEU+GRC+IRL+ITA+ESP/?levels=1%2B4&interpolation=0&extrapolation=0&nearest_real=0&years=2018%2B2017%2B2016%2B2015, accessed on 09/06/2020

⁴² ELSTAT, 2019, Labour force, quarterly data, Table 09. The same source applies for all the Regional Units mentioned. <https://www.statistics.gr/en/statistics/-/publication/SJO01/->, accessed on 09/06/2020

⁴³ Aromanians in Greece, Vlachs, Vlachochoria, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Aromanians_in_Greece, accessed on 10/06/2020

⁴⁴ Minorities of Greece, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Aromanians_in_Greece, accessed on 10/06/2020

⁴⁵ UNHCR data portal, ESTIA Population breakdown as of 9 June 2020, <https://data2.unhcr.org/en/documents/download/76987>, accessed on 09/06/2020

⁴⁶ IOM Factsheets, April 2020 statistics on Open Reception Facilities across Greece, <https://greece.iom.int/sites/default/files/April%20Merged.pdf>, accessed on 09/06/2020

Syria and Iraq.⁴⁷ Both in the Accommodation program and in camps children usually represent 35-60% of the population. In apartments school enrolment is 68% while at camp 70%. The majority of refugees and asylum seekers residing in the region live in the long-term accommodation site “Koutsochero”, which is located 18 km west of Larissa city. Volos camp hosts 145 persons and is situated 7.7 km from the city of Volos.

Table 38. Larissa – Greek and Foreign Population per Citizenship Group and Sex 2011

	Greek	Total Foreign	Foreign EU	Foreign Europe	Asian	Other	TOTAL
Both Sexes	267,562	16,763	2,512	13,507	528	216	284,325
Female	135,615	7,901	1,447	6,230	119	105	143,516
Male	131,947	8,862	1,065	7,277	409	111	140,809

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/>, Table B07

The educational background of the foreign-born population living in Larissa according to 2011 census, can be seen in the below table 39.

Table 39. Larissa – Level of Education of Foreign-born Population

Education	Both sexes	Female	Male
PhD/ Post-Graduate/ University Degree	822	558	264
Post-Secondary/ Senior High School	3,614	1,854	1,760
Junior High School/ Professional schools	3,676	1,727	2,040
Elementary Graduates	4,148	1,789	2,359
Other	4,412	1,973	2,439
TOTAL	16,763	7,901	8,862

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/>, Table B10

It should be noted that with regards to access to education of refugee children Covid-19 restriction measures remained in all camps and hotspots across Greece, even after the lift of measures to the general population and for tourists, which is discriminatory towards these people.⁴⁸

The unemployment status of Greek and foreign-born population as of 2011, was as per the below table. The same level specifically for Ioannina regional unit are not available for the same or later years.

⁴⁷ UNHCR data portal, Accommodation update for May 2020, <https://data2.unhcr.org/en/documents/download/76840> accessed on 09/06/2020

⁴⁸ Article at the online newspaper, Paidis.com, <https://paidis.com/2020/06/11/%ce%b1%cf%80%ce%bf%ce%ba%ce%bb%ce%b5%ce%b9%cf%83%ce%bc%ce%bf%cf%83-%cf%84%cf%89%ce%bd-%cf%80%ce%b1%ce%b9%ce%b4%ce%b9%cf%89%ce%bd-%cf%84%cf%89%ce%bd-%cf%80%cf%81%ce%bf%cf%83%cf%86%cf%85%ce%b3%cf%89/>, accessed on 11/06/2020

Table 40. Thessaly – Unemployment of Greek and Foreign-born Population

	# of unemployed	Out of # in Thessaly
Total	67,066	732,762
Greeks	60,886	688,187
Foreign born	4,625	44,575

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM04/>-, Table A10

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

According to the available data from 2019, there are 210 schools (not including pre-school) in Larissa. More specifically, in each of the three levels, below you can see the number of schools of the region.

Table 41. Larissa – Number of Schools in Each Level

1	Public Dimotiko/ Elementary	111
2	Public Gymnasium/ Junior High School	47
3	Public Lyceum/ Senior High School	39
4	Private (includes several levels)	13

Source: Institute of Educational Policy, Institutouto Ekpedeftikis Politikis (IEP), List of schools in Greece, per Administrative District and per Regional Unit, see excel table at the bottom of the page. Includes all types of schools in the country, <http://iep.edu.gr/el/ereunes-programmata>, accessed on 09/06/2020.

Table 42. Larissa – Primary Education: 3 Categories Chosen

1	DYEP, ZEP, Intercultural	0
2	None	106
3	ZEP	6
4	DYEP	3
5	Intercultural	0
6	DYEP, ZEP	0
7	ZEP, intercultural	0
8	DYEP, intercultural	0

Source: Various sources such as the Greek Government Gazettes and the national database on types of school (Greek). Please refer to chapter for further explanation of the categories 5.3.1. Key characteristics, p. 136-137

Table 43. Larissa – Secondary Education: 4 Categories Chosen

1	DYEP, ZEP, Intercultural	0
2	None	83
3	ZEP	2
4	DYEP	2
5	Intercultural	0

6	DYEP, ZEP	0
7	ZEP, intercultural	0
8	DYEP, intercultural	0

Source: Various sources such as the Greek Government Gazettes and the national database on types of school (Greek). Please refer to chapter for further explanation of the categories 5.3.1. Key characteristics, p. 136-137

The total number of students was available only in Administrative District Level (NUTS II), namely Epirus, and not in Regional Unit level (NUTS III), meaning Larissa, and only for two or three years ago, i.e, latest school year with available data was that of 2017-8. Therefore, the numbers provided are indicative.

Table 44. Thessaly – Registered Student Population 2017-18

School Level	Total	Boys	Girls	% of total school population
Elementary School/ Dimotiko	42,668	21,811	20,857	6.7%
Junior High School School/ Gymnasium	20,831	N/A	N/A	6.7%
Senior High School/ Lyceum	15,840	N/A	N/A	6.5%

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, Press Release 31 October 2019, <https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/997dd82e-da34-b82f-3795-6904127cc113>

It is interesting to mention the number of students who graduated the same year:

Table 45. Larissa – Students who Graduated 2017-18

School Level	Total	Boys	Girls	% of graduation
Elementary School/ Dimotiko	7,130	N/A	N/A	N/A
Junior High School School/ Gymnasium	6,566	N/A	N/A	N/A
Senior High School/ Lyceum	5,216	N/A	N/A	N/A

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, Press Release 31 October 2019, <https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/997dd82e-da34-b82f-3795-6904127cc113>

11.2.5 Region: Epirus – Ioannina and Preveza Regional Units

The Administrative District of Epirus is a mainland region situated in Northern Greece and bordering with Albania in its North, from which Greece hosts the highest number of migrants in the country. Epirus is divided in 4 regional units, Ioannina, Preveza, Thesprotia and Arta. The Seat of Epirus is Ioannina. Epirus is mainly a mountainous area (Pindus Mountains) famous for its biodiversity within the country, also reaching the Ionian Sea on its western part.

Within the Administrative District of Epirus we chose two Regional Units, its major Regional Unit, Ioannina, and Preveza, where the Open Reception Facility of Filippiada is located. Ioannina

regional unit is one of the 4 units of Epirus and the largest one of all. Ioannina is subdivided in 8 Municipalities. Geographically Ioannina is on the northern part of Epirus, bordering with Albania. Preveza regional unit is one of the 4 regional units (NUTS III) of Epirus. Preveza is subdivided in 9 municipalities. Geographically is situated on the western part and borders with Ionian Sea.

POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS – IOANNINA

The total population of Ioannina for 2011 was 167,901 persons out of which 81,847 were male and 86,054 female.⁴⁹ As we can see from the table the majority of people were under the age group 80+, while the lowest population numbers were for the ages 0-9 and 10-19.

Table 46. Ioannina Age Groups

Age Group	Population
0-9	14,796
10-19	16,771
20-29	22,889
30-39	23,260
40-49	22,044
50-59	21,479
60-69	18,612
70+	28,050

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/-/TableA01>

The Gross domestic product of the region of Epirus for 2017 was 4 billion which accounts for the 2% of the country's GDP.⁵⁰ The Human Development Index for 2018 was 0.866.⁵¹ The unemployment rate for the last quarter of 2019 in Ioannina was 14,1% while in country level was 17.3%.⁵² In 2011 unemployment rate was 15.8%.

With regards to ethnic, racial and religious background of the local population, Epirus and Ioannina is a very rich area in comparison with other areas of Greece. In Epirus there are originally settlements of Arvanites, Vorio-ipeiros and Cham Albanians, Vlachs, Roma and Jewish people. Additionally, there are 2nd and 3rd generation of Pontiacs,⁵³ whose parents and grandparents survived the genocide and people who identify as Greek but were persecuted in Minor Asia, such as from the cities of Constantinople (Istanbul), Smyrni, and others. All of these communities even

⁴⁹ According to population demographics as of 2011, ELSTAT, Table B07

⁵⁰ European Commission databases, Ipiros region 2017, <https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/regional-innovation-monitor/base-profile/region-ipeiros>, accessed on 10/06/2020

⁵¹ Global Data Lab, https://globaldatalab.org/shdi/shdi/BEL+DEU+GRC+IRL+ITA+ESP/?levels=1%2B4&interpolation=0&extrapolation=0&nearest_real=0&years=2018%2B2017%2B2016%2B2015, accessed on 09/06/2020

⁵² ELSTAT, 2019, Labour force, quarterly data, Table 09. The same source applies for all the Regional Units mentioned. <https://www.statistics.gr/en/statistics/-/publication/SJO01/->, accessed on 09/06/2020

⁵³ Pontiac community of Epirus honouring the memory of the genocide of Pontus in Ioannina, May 2020, <http://www.pontos-news.gr/gallery/209615/i-adelfotita-pontion-kai-mikrasiaton-ipeiroy-timise-toys-353000-nekroys-ellines-toy>, accessed on 10/06/2020.

though by years become smaller, they are active socially, keeping alive parts of their tradition and memories of their ancestors.

In Ioannina there are 4 Roma settlements, one in Nea Zoi, two in Perama and one in Pedini, amounting to a total of 1,160 persons as of 2014 research.⁵⁴ Roma usually speak their own language called Romani and are Christian Orthodox. The majority of this population are school drop-outs sometimes before the age of 15 years old, as it is important for them to create their own family instead of continuing their education.

Jewish community in Ioannina is also called, Israeli community or “Romaniotes”⁵⁵ and its population number in Ioannina is unknown, but probably much less than 500 persons. Romaniotes speak their own language usually called “Yavan”. It is worth mentioning though that the Mayor of Ioannina Municipality elected in 2019 is a Jew and member of this community.

Vlachs, Arvanites, Vorio-ipirotos and Cham Albanians, are people who were originally from the region of Epirus and North-Epirus (Voria Ipiros). Vlachs identify as greeks, are Christian Orthodox and speak their own language “Vlachika” including languages of “Arvanitika” and “Greek”, as sometimes their origin is mixed, i.e. many Vlachs are also Arvanites. They traditionally lived in the area of Northern Greece, in Pindus Mountains and Macedonia region.⁵⁶ Arvanites is an ethnic group that lives in Greece and originates from Albania and the general region of North Epiros (Voria-Ipiros) in both countries. Arvanites apart from Greek they also speak “Arvanitika”, which is a language similar originating from Albanian and Slavic languages. Their presence in several parts of Greece is extensive over many decades and as they have assimilated with the general population,⁵⁷ therefore their presence as of today is not registered.

The educational background of the Greek population of Ioannina can be found in table 47.

Table 47. Ioannina – Level of Education of Greek Population

Education	Both sexes	Female	Male
PhD/ Post-Graduate/ University Degree	27,906	14,334	13,572
Post-Secondary/ Senior High School	40,054	20,548	19,506
Junior High School/ Professional schools	18,388	7,319	11,069
Elementary Graduates	41,881	21,675	20,206
Other	30,301	17,727	12,574
TOTAL	158,530	81,603	76,927

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/>, Table A03

⁵⁴ Operational Plan for the integration of Roma plan in Epirus, 2014, Prefecture of Epirus, http://peproe.gr/espa2013/images/programa/regional/ps_roma_09_01_2015.pdf, accessed on 10/06/2020.

⁵⁵ “Romaniotes” documentary, about Jewish community in Ioannina, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=x0xNliAXDtY>, accessed on 10/06/2020

⁵⁶ Vlachs villages in Epirus are Syrrako, Kalarrytes, Metsovo, Kefalovrisso, based on the mapping of cultural associations of Vlachs, <https://www.vlahoi.net/weblinks/53-politistikoi-sillogoi-vlahon>, accessed on 10/06/2020.

⁵⁷ Arvanitika villages and language history in the Greek and Albanian territories, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Arvanitika>, accessed on 10/06/2020. The fact that they have dispersed over the years can be seen also here <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ieGbIPNyrF0> min 4.03- 4.14

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION – IOANNINA

According to 2011 count, a total of 9,371 residents who lived in Ioannina were born in a foreign country. However, the data are quite old and do not capture reality as of 9 years later and following the migrant/refugee influx of 2015.

Table 48. Ioannina – Greek and Foreign Population per Citizenship Group and Sex

	Greek	Total Foreign	Foreign EU	Foreign Europe	Asian	Other	TOTAL
Both Sexes	158,530	9,371	1,074	7,151	938	208	167,901
Female	81,603	4,451	803	3,429	125	94	86,054
Male	76,927	4,920	271	3,722	813	114	81,847

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/>-, Table B07

In Epirus administrative district according to 2011 at least 14,357 Albanians⁵⁸ were living, but the same number at Ioannina level is not available. For Ioannina regional unit there are not any further data with regards to the migrants' country of origin or the date of arrival to the country.

As of June 2020, 6% of the total of refugees living in UNHCR sponsored apartments in Greece, live in Epirus, which corresponds to 1,273 people.⁵⁹ As of April 2020, 1,974 asylum-seekers and refugees and others live in 3 ORFs/ camps within the region of Epirus.⁶⁰ These persons are newly-arrived in Greece, i.e. after 01/01/2015. The majority of these people originate from Syria, Afghanistan, Iraq, Iran, D.R. Congo and others.⁶¹ Both in the Accommodation program and in camps children usually represent 40-60% of the population. In apartments school enrolment is 68% while in camps varies per camp from 23 to 32%.

Municipality of Ioannina has been actively participating in the integration of refugees and asylum-seekers in the city by creating a monthly local coordination mechanism which includes local NGOs who provide social services and accommodation as well as representatives from Syrian, Afghan, Iraqi and Iranian communities.⁶²

The educational background of the foreign-born population living in Ioannina according to 2011 census, can be seen in the below table 50.

⁵⁸ ELSTAT data, population demographics, Table A05F.

⁵⁹ UNHCR data portal, ESTIA Population breakdown as of 9 June 2020, <https://data2.unhcr.org/en/documents/download/76987>, accessed on 09/06/2020

⁶⁰ IOM Factsheets, April 2020 statistics on Open Reception Facilities across Greece, <https://greece.iom.int/sites/default/files/April%20Merged.pdf>, accessed on 09/06/2020

⁶¹ UNHCR data portal, Accommodation update for May 2020, <https://data2.unhcr.org/en/documents/download/76840> accessed on 09/06/2020

⁶² Municipal council announcement on the successful implementation of the Council for Migrants and refugees. <https://www.ioannina.gr/%CF%83%CE%B5-%CF%80%CE%BB%CE%AE%CF%81%CE%B7-%CE%BB%CE%B5%CE%B9%CF%84%CE%BF%CF%85%CF%81%CE%B3%CE%AF%CE%B1-%CF%84%CE%BF-%CF%83%CF%85%CE%BC%CE%B2%CE%BF%CF%8D%CE%BB%CE%B9%CE%BF-%CE%BC%CE%B5%CF%84%CE%B1/>, accessed on 09/06/2020

Table 49. Ioannina – Level of Education of Foreign-born Population

Education	Both sexes	Female	Male
PhD/ Post-Graduate/ University Degree	737	474	263
Post-Secondary/ Senior High School	2,695	1,421	1,274
Junior High School/ Professional schools	2,030	907	1,123
Elementary Graduates	2,044	845	1,199
Other	1,865	804	1,061
TOTAL	9,371	4,451	4,920

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/>, Table B10

The unemployment status of Greek and foreign-born population as of 2011, was as per the below table. The same level specifically for Ioannina regional unit are not available for the same or later years.

Table 50. Epirus – Unemployment of Greek and Foreign-born Population

	# of unemployed	Out of # in the region
Total	23,659	336,856
Greeks	21,424	317,877
Foreign born	2,235	18,979

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM04/>, Table A10

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION – IOANNINA

According to the available data from 2019,⁶³ there are 164 schools (not including pre-school). More specifically, in each of the three levels, here are the below number of schools in the region.

Table 51. Ioannina – Number of Schools in Each Level

1	Public Dimotiko/ Elementary	88
2	Public Gymnasium/ Junior High School	38
3	Public Lyceum/ Senior High School	27
4	Private (includes several levels)	11

Source: Institute of Educational Policy, Institutouto Ekpedeftikis Politikis (IEP), List of schools in Greece, per Administrative District and per Regional Unit, see excel table at the bottom of the page. Includes all types of schools in the country, <http://iep.edu.gr/el/ereunes-programmata>, accessed on 09/06/2020.

Out of the above mentioned schools, we are planning to select schools among the following categories of interest.

⁶³ Institute of Educational Policy, Institutouto Ekpedeftikis Politikis (IEP), List of schools in Greece, per Administrative District and per Regional Unit, see excel table at the bottom of the page. Includes all types of schools in the country, <http://iep.edu.gr/el/ereunes-programmata>, accessed on 09/06/2020.

Table 52. Ioannina – Primary Education: 6 Categories Chosen

1	DYEP, ZEP, Intercultural	0
2	None	88
3	ZEP	10
4	DYEP	5
5	Intercultural	1
6	DYEP, ZEP	1
7	ZEP, intercultural	0
8	DYEP, intercultural	1

Source: Various sources such as the Greek Government Gazettes and the national database on types of school (Greek). Please refer to chapter for further explanation of the categories 5.3.1. Key characteristics, p. 136-137

Table 53. Ioannina – Secondary Education: 5 Categories Chosen

1	DYEP, ZEP, Intercultural	0
2	None	50
3	ZEP	12
4	DYEP	2
5	Intercultural	2
6	DYEP, ZEP	1
7	ZEP, intercultural	1
8	DYEP, intercultural	0

Source: Various sources such as the Greek Government Gazettes and the national database on types of school (Greek). Please refer to chapter for further explanation of the categories 5.3.1. Key characteristics, p. 136-137

The total number of students was available only in Administrative District Level (NUTS II), namely Epirus, and not in Regional Unit level (NUTS III), meaning Ioannina, and only for two or three years ago, i.e. latest school year with available data was that of 2017-8. Therefore, the numbers provided are indicative.

Table 54. Epirus – Registered Student Population for 2017-18

School Level	Total	Boys	Girls	% of total student population
Elementary School/ Dimotiko	17,889	9,314	8,575	2.8%
Junior High School School/ Gymnasium	8,662	N/A	N/A	2.8%
Senior High School/ Lyceum	7,219	N/A	N/A	2.9%

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, Press Release 31 October 2019, <https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/997dd82e-da34-b82f-3795-6904127cc113>

It is interesting to mention the number of students who graduated the same year:

Table 55. Epirus – Students who Graduated 2017-18

School Level	Total	Boys	Girls	% of graduation
Elementary School/ Dimotiko	3,028	N/A	N/A	N/A
Junior High School School/ Gymnasium	2,716	N/A	N/A	N/A
Senior High School/ Lyceum	2,386	N/A	N/A	N/A

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, Press Release 31 October 2019, <https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/997dd82e-da34-b82f-3795-6904127cc113>

There are no data on students' characteristics in open source. Such data are only collected at school level and not in central level.

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE POPULATION – PREVEZA

The total population of Preveza for 2011 was 57,491 persons out of which 28,514 were male and 28,977 female,⁶⁴ As we can see from the table the majority of people were belonged in the age group of 70+, while the lowest population numbers were for the ages 0-9 and 10-19.

Table 57. Preveza Age Groups

Age Group	Population
0-9	5,360
10-19	5,674
20-29	5,693
30-39	7,580
40-49	7,536
50-59	7,866
60-69	7,397
70+	10,385

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/-,Table A01>

Unfortunately, there are no data available on the gross domestic product of the region of Preveza for 2017 or any other recent year GDP. The Human Development Index of Epirus administrative district for 2018 was 0.866.⁶⁵ The unemployment rate for the last quarter of 2019 in Preveza was 17,8% while in country level was 17.3%.⁶⁶ In 2011 unemployment rate was 12.7%.

With regards to ethnic, racial and religious background of the local population, Epirus and Preveza are very rich areas in comparison with other areas of Greece. In Epirus there are originally settlements of Arvanites, Vorio-ipirotos and Cham Albanians, Vlachs, Roma and Jewish people. Additionally, there are 2nd and 3rd generation of Pontiacs.⁶⁷

⁶⁴ According to population demographics as of 2011, ELSTAT, Table B07

⁶⁵ Global Data Lab, https://globaldatalab.org/shdi/shdi/BEL+DEU+GRC+IRL+ITA+ESP/?levels=1%2B4&interpolation=0&extrapolation=0&nearest_real=0&years=2018%2B2017%2B2016%2B2015, accessed on 09/06/2020

⁶⁶ ELSTAT, 2019, Labour force, quarterly data, Table 09. The same source applies for all the Regional Units mentioned. <https://www.statistics.gr/en/statistics/-/publication/SJO01/-,> accessed on 09/06/2020

⁶⁷ Pontiac community of Epirus honouring the memory of the genocide of Pontus in Ioannina, May 2020, <http://www.pontos-news.gr/gallery/209615/i-adelfotita-pontion-kai-mikrasiaton-ipeiroy-timise-toys-353000-nekroys-ellines-toy>, accessed on 10/06/2020.

In Preveza there are 5 Roma settlements, namely in Preveza, Sampsounta, Louros and two in Filippiada, of approximately 280 persons in total.⁶⁸ Vorio-ipirotos, Cham Albanians and Arvanites can be located in Fanari, Ammoudia and Agia⁶⁹ municipalities but their exact number or even approximate number is unknown due to the cultural assimilation in the region and in the country. In the early 20th century many Greek speaking persecuted populations from Minor Asia such as Pontiacs from Sampsounta, Trapezounta, Kerasounta and Sinopi, including Turkish speaking people from other Minor Asia cities and villages (Ayatzik, Tosos, Chelantou, Karsu and others) arrived in Preveza. Another ethnic group in this region is “Sarakatsani”, who identify as Greeks and live in Greece, Albania, North Macedonia and Bulgaria.

The educational background of the Greek population of Preveza can be found in table 58.

Table 57. Preveza – Level of Education of Greek Population

Education	Both sexes	Female	Male
PhD/ Post-Graduate/ University Degree	6,880	3,594	3,419
Post-Secondary/ Senior High School	11,668	5,798	6,351
Junior High School/ Professional schools	5,876	2,932	3,411
Elementary Graduates	16,791	8,894	8,397
Other	12,021	7,759	4,746
TOTAL	53,236	28,977	26,324

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/->, Table A03

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION – PREVEZA

According to 2011 count, a total of 4,255⁷⁰ residents who lived in Preveza were born in a foreign country. However, the data are quite old and do not capture reality as of 9 years later and following the migrant/refugee influx of 2015.

Table 58. Preveza – Greek and Foreign Population per Citizenship Group and Sex

	Greek	Total Foreign	Foreign EU	Foreign Europe	Asian	Other	TOTAL
Both Sexes	53,236	4,255	443	3,537	213	62	57,491
Female	26,912	2,065	292	1,672	63	38	28,977
Male	26,324	2,190	151	1,865	150	24	28,154

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/->, Table B07

In Epirus administrative district according to 2011 at least 14,357 Albanians⁷¹ were living, but the same number at Ioannina level is not available. For Preveza regional unit there are not any further data with regards to the migrants’ country of origin or the date of arrival to the country.

⁶⁸ Operational Plan for the integration of Roma plan in Epirus, 2014, Prefecture of Epirus, http://peproe.gr/espa2013/images/programa/regional/ps_roma_09_01_2015.pdf, accessed on 10/06/2020.

⁶⁹ Arvanites, Cham Albanians and Vorio-ipirotos, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cham_Albanians#In_Greece, accessed on 10/06/2020.

⁷⁰ ELSTAT website, Population demographics, Table B07

⁷¹ ELSTAT (Hellenic Statistical Authority) data, population demographics, Table A05F.

In Preveza, there are no UNHCR sponsored apartments for refugees and asylum seekers. However, there is a Filippiada camp, which hosts 655 refugees and asylum seekers as of April 2020. These persons are newly-arrived in Greece, i.e. after 01/01/2015. The majority of these people originate from Afghanistan, Syria and Iraq.⁷² In Filippiada camps children represent 40-54% of the population. School enrolment for the children living in the camp is 23%.

The educational background of the foreign-born population living in Attiki according to 2011 census, can be seen in the below table 60.

Table 59. Preveza – Level of Education of Foreign-born Population

Education	Both sexes	Female	Male
PhD/ Post-Graduate/ University Degree	203	133	70
Post-Secondary/ Senior High School	891	481	410
Junior High School/ Professional schools	1,017	467	550
Elementary Graduates	1,096	500	596
Other	1,048	484	564
TOTAL	4,255	2,605	2,190

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/>-, Table B10

The unemployment status of Greek and foreign-born population as of 2011, was as per the below table.

Table 60. Epirus – Unemployment of Greek and Foreign-born Population

	# of unemployed	Out of # in the region
Total	23,659	336,856
Greeks	21,424	317,877
Foreign born	2,235	18,979

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM04/>-, Table A10

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION – PREVEZA

According to the available data from 2019, there are 58 schools (not including pre-school) in Preveza. More specifically, in each of the three levels, here are the below number of schools in the region.

⁷² UNHCR data portal, Accommodation update for May 2020, <https://data2.unhcr.org/en/documents/download/76840> accessed on 09/06/2020

Table 61. Preveza – Number of Schools in Each Level

1	Public Dimotiko/ Elementary	32
2	Public Gymnasium/ Junior High School	14
3	Public Lyceum/ Senior High School	12
4	Private (includes several levels)	0

Source: Institute of Educational Policy, Institutoto Ekpedeftikis Politikis (IEP), List of schools in Greece, per Administrative District and per Regional Unit, see excel table at the bottom of the page. Includes all types of schools in the country, <http://iep.edu.gr/el/ereunes-programmata>, accessed on 09/06/2020.

Out of these schools, we are planning to select schools among the following categories of interest.

Table 62. Preveza – Primary Education: 3 Categories Chosen

1	DYEP, ZEP, Intercultural	0
2	None	23
3	ZEP	3
4	DYEP	6
5	Intercultural	0
6	DYEP, ZEP	0
7	ZEP, intercultural	0
8	DYEP, intercultural	0

Source: Various sources such as the Greek Government Gazettes and the national database on types of school (Greek). Please refer to chapter for further explanation of the categories 5.3.1. Key characteristics, p. 136-137

Table 63. Preveza – Secondary Education: 4 Categories Chosen

1	DYEP, ZEP, Intercultural	0
2	None	21
3	ZEP	5
4	DYEP	1
5	Intercultural	0
6	DYEP, ZEP	1
7	ZEP, intercultural	0
8	DYEP, intercultural	0

Source: Various sources such as the Greek Government Gazettes and the national database on types of school (Greek). Please refer to chapter for further explanation of the categories 5.3.1. Key characteristics, p. 136-137

The total number of students was available only in Administrative District Level (NUTS II), namely Epirus, and not in Regional Unit level (NUTS III), meaning Ioannina, and only for two or three years ago, i.e. latest school year with available data was that of 2017-8. Therefore, the numbers provided are indicative.

Table 64. Epirus – Registered Student Population for 2017-18

School Level	Total	Boys	Girls	% of total student population
Elementary School/ Dimotiko	17,889	9,314	8,575	2.8%
Junior High School School/ Gymnasium	8,662	N/A	N/A	2.8%
Senior High School/ Lyceum	7,219	N/A	N/A	2.9%

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, Press Release 31 October 2019, <https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/997dd82e-da34-b82f-3795-6904127cc113>

It is interesting to mention the number of students who graduated the same year:

Table 65. Epirus – Students who Graduated 2017-18

School Level	Total	Boys	Girls	% of graduation
Elementary School/ Dimotiko	3,028	N/A	N/A	N/A
Junior High School School/ Gymnasium	2,716	N/A	N/A	N/A
Senior High School/ Lyceum	2,386	N/A	N/A	N/A

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, Press Release 31 October 2019, <https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/997dd82e-da34-b82f-3795-6904127cc113>

There are no data on students' characteristics in open source. Such data are only collected at school level and not in central level.

11.2.6 Region: Eastern Macedonia and Thrace – Xanthi Regional Unit

Eastern Macedonia and Thrace is an Administrative District situated in Northern Greece and is located next to the borders with Turkey, from where many mixed flows of migrants and refugees arrive to Greece and to Europe. This region is considered a sensitive region with regards to migration issues, mainly because of the ethnic/religious minority of Pomaks/Turks who are Muslims and who speak both Greek and Turkish. This happens because of historical reasons. In 1923 with the Lausanne Treaty a big number of populations was decided to be exchanged between the two states in order to better establish their borders and achieve a certain amount of homogeneity in the region⁷³. This is the only recognized minority in Greece by law and the schools of the region are the only ones called "minority schools" established by law, where children are taught in both Greek and Turkish and learn about both Islam and the Christian Orthodox Church.

⁷³ This obligatory exchange of population happened in 1923, with the Treaty of Lausanne and it was based on the religion identities of the population. It was between orthodox citizens of Turkey that were transferred to Eastern Macedonia and Thrace and Muslim citizens of Greece that were transferred to Turkey.

POPULATION CHARACTERISTICS

The total population of region of Xanthi regional unit for the year 2011 was 111,222⁷⁴ of which 55,202 were male and 56,020 female.⁷⁵ As we can see from the table below, the age group with the lowest number of population was the age group 60-69 years old, which coincides with the persons who were born during World War II.

Table 66. Xanthi Age Groups

Age Group	Population
0-9	13,680
10-19	13,460
20-29	15,867
30-39	16,524
40-49	15,454
50-59	13,294
60-69	10,195
70+	12,748

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/->, Table A01

The Gross domestic product of the region of Eastern Macedonia and Thrace for 2017 was 6,9 billion which accounts for the 3.9% of the country's GDP.⁷⁶ The Human Development Index for 2018 was 0.835.⁷⁷ The unemployment rate for the last quarter of 2019 in Xanthi was 18.6% while in country level was 17.3%.⁷⁸ In 2011 unemployment rate was 23.5%.

With regards to ethnic and racial background, in 1923 the exchange between Christian Orthodox populations of Turkey and Muslims in Greece was agreed in order for the newly established state of Greece to secure its borders by establishing a "Greek presence" of populations near the borders., In Xanthi currently there are 37.76% Muslims of which 11,000 are Turkish speakers, 25,000 Pomaks and 6,000 Roma. Historically, there were also some villages in Thrace region, were Arvanites originate from. Each of those ethnic minorities have their own language. Pomak language originates from Bulgarian and Slavic language, Turkish language is the language spoken in Turkey and Arvanitika is a language originating from Albanian and Tosk.

⁷⁴ All demographic data for Attiki and all other regional units were based on ELSTAT (Greek Statistic Service), based on 2011 count. Unfortunately, there were no data more contemporary including all the sub-categories that we are interested in this research projects such as, SES distribution, migrant/ refugee population, countries of origin per administrative district or regional unit or municipality, sex and educational status, so that we can compare and contrast data across regions from a single official data source.

⁷⁵ According to population demographics as of 2011, ELSTAT, Table B07

⁷⁶ European Commission databases, Ipiros region 2017, <https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/regional-innovation-monitor/base-profile/region-ipeiros>, accessed on 10/06/2020.

⁷⁷ https://globaldatalab.org/shdi/shdi/BEL+DEU+GRC+IRL+ITA+ESP/?levels=1%2B4&interpolation=0&extrapolation=0&nearest_real=0&years=2018%2B2017%2B2016%2B2015, accessed on 09/06/2020

⁷⁸ ELSTAT, 2019, Labour force, quarterly data, Table 09. The same source applies for all the Regional Units mentioned. <https://www.statistics.gr/en/statistics/-/publication/SJO01/->, accessed on 09/06/2020

The educational background of the Greek population of Xanthi can be found at the table below.

Table 67. Xanthi – Level of Education of Greek Population

Education	Both sexes	Female	Male
PhD/ Post-Graduate/ University Degree	12,179	5,790	6,389
Post-Secondary/ Senior High School	21,155	9,737	11,418
Junior High School/ Professional schools	11,341	4,666	6,675
Elementary Graduates	34,428	17,945	16,483
Other	30,055	16,786	13,272
TOTAL	109,158	54,921	54,237

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/>, Table A03

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

According to 2011 census, there are 2,064 people out of 111,222 (1,86%) migrants. However, the data are quite old and do not capture reality as of 9 years later and following the migrant/refugee influx of 2015.

Table 68. Xanthi – Greek and Foreign Population per Citizenship Group and Sex 2011

	Greek	Total Foreign	Foreign EU	Foreign Europe	Asian	Other	Total
Both Sexes	109,158	2,064	669	824	496	75	111,222
Female	54,921	1,099	374	449	245	31	56,020
Male	54,237	965	295	375	251	44	55,202

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/>, Table B07

Unfortunately, there is no data available with regards to the countries of origin and background of the migrant population in Xanthi.

Among the migrant population, 11.87% have academic education, 30.33% have finished high school, 20.30% have finished college, 17.54% have finished primary education and 19.96% haven't finished primary school or have never been to school.

Table 69. Xanthi – Level of Education of Foreign-born Population

Education	Both sexes	Female	Male
PhD/ Post-Graduate/ University Degree	245	162	83
Post-Secondary/ Senior High School	626	344	282
Junior High School/ Professional schools	419	199	220
Elementary Graduates	362	192	170
Other	412	202	210
TOTAL	2,064	1,099	965

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/>, Table B10

The unemployment status of Greek and foreign-born population of Xanthi as of 2011, was as per the below table.

Table 70. Eastern Macedonia and Thrace Region – Unemployment of Greek and Foreign-born Population

	# of unemployed	Out of # in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace Region
Total	47,273	608,182
Greeks	44,529	586,226
Foreign born	2,744	21,956

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM04/->, Table A10

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

The region of Xanthi has in total 139 schools, (not including pre-school). More specifically, in each of the three levels, here are the below number of schools in the region. Xanthi and its unique population across Greece, that of the recognized minority of Muslims and consequently as per the Lausanne Treaty 75 of them are official minority schools where Turkish and Greek language are equally taught including religious education, that of the Quran in Arabic and in Greek.

Table 71. Xanthi – Number of Schools in Each Level

1	Public Dimotiko	108
2	Public Gymnasium	21
3	Public Lyceum	8
4	Private (includes several levels)	2

Source: Institute of Educational Policy, Institutouto Ekpedeftikis Politikis (IEP), List of schools in Greece, per Administrative District and per Regional Unit, see excel table at the bottom of the page. Includes all types of schools in the country, <http://iep.edu.gr/el/ereunes-programmata>, accessed on 09/06/2020.

Out of these schools, we are planning to select schools among the following categories of interest.

Table 72. Xanthi – Primary Education: 4 Categories Chosen

1	DYEP, ZEP, Intercultural	0
2	None	91
3	ZEP	15
4	DYEP	0
5	Intercultural	0
6	DYEP, ZEP	0
7	ZEP, intercultural	0
8	DYEP, intercultural	0

Source: Various sources such as the Greek Government Gazettes and the national database on types of school (Greek). Please refer to chapter for further explanation of the categories 5.3.1. Key characteristics, p. 136-137

Table 73. Xanthi – Secondary Education: 6 Categories Chosen

1	DYEP, ZEP, Intercultural	0
2	None	37
3	ZEP	2
4	DYEP	0
5	Intercultural	0
6	DYEP, ZEP	0
7	ZEP, intercultural	0
8	DYEP, intercultural	0

Source: Various sources such as the Greek Government Gazettes and the national database on types of school (Greek). Please refer to chapter for further explanation of the categories 5.3.1. Key characteristics, p. 136-137

The total number of students was available only in Administrative District Level (NUTS II), namely Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, and not in Regional Unit level (NUTS III), meaning Xanthi, and only for two or three years ago, i.e, latest school year with available data was that of 2017-8. Therefore, the numbers provided are indicative.

Table 74. Eastern Macedonia and Thrace Region – Registered Student Population 2017-18

School Level	Total	Boys	Girls	% of total school population in GR
Elementary School/ Dimotiko	34,648	17,918	16,730	5.4%
Junior High School School/ Gymnasium	17,580	N/A	N/A	5.5%
Senior High School/ Lyceum	12,292	N/A	N/A	5.0%

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, Press Release 31 October 2019, <https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/997dd82e-da34-b82f-3795-6904127cc113>

It is interesting to mention the number of students who graduated the same year:

Table 75. Eastern Macedonia and Thrace Region – Students who Graduated 2017-18

School Level	Total	Boys	Girls	% of graduation
Elementary School/ Dimotiko	5,588	N/A	N/A	N/A
Junior High School School/ Gymnasium	5,322	N/A	N/A	N/A
Senior High School/ Lyceum	4,030	N/A	N/A	N/A

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, Press Release 31 October 2019, <https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/997dd82e-da34-b82f-3795-6904127cc113>

11.2.7 Region: North Aegean Islands – Chios Regional Unit

Northern Aegean Islands is an Administrative District and is comprised of ten islands and five regional units: Lesbos, Chios, Samos, Lemnos and Ikaria. Chios is the 5th largest island in the country and is located in the North-east part Greece bordering with Turkey through sea. The sea

borders around North Aegean islands are also EU borders. The North Aegean Islands belong to the first line reception of mixed flows coming from Turkey and are considered as the main gateway of migrant/refugee flows to Greece and to the European Union. Chios is comprised of three municipalities, Chios, Oinousses and Psara, of which the two latter are smaller islands very proximate Chios.

POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS

The population of the Northern Aegean region according to 2011 census is 154,637 while Chios population is 52,674 residents. In Chios 26,413 are male while 26,261 are female.

Table 76. Chios Age Groups

Age Group	Population
0-9	4,909
10-19	5,144
20-29	7,466
30-39	7,589
40-49	6,966
50-59	6,402
60-69	5,722
70+	8,476

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/->, Table A01

As we can see from the table, there is a high percentage of elderly persons living in Chios, which actually reflects the general situation in Greece (especially in rural/ island areas) of ageing Greek population. Of those aged 0-29, a total of 15,979 are Greek citizens, 186 are EU citizens, and 1540 have a country of origin outside the EU.

A higher education level is more limited in older ages than in younger ages. The majority of elderly persons are primary school graduates. This is usually because 50 years ago, persons who lived in rural/ island areas use to concentrate on agricultural and stock-farming. In Chios there is a particular focus on agriculture, Mastic, which is a unique product all across the world and is bred only in the South part of Chios.

Table 77. Chios – Level of Education of Greek Population

Education	Both sexes	Female	Male
PhD/ Post-Graduate/ University Degree	8,235	3,433	4,802
Post-Secondary/ Senior High School	14,271	6,969	7,302
Junior High School/ Professional schools	6,248	2,670	3,578
Elementary Graduates	13,202	7,529	5,673
Other	7,561	4,062	3,499
TOTAL	49,517	24,663	24,854

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/->, Table A03

The majority of the local population works in public administration, tourism and commerce. According to data from 2013, in Chios there were 2,622 persons who applied and 1,685 whose applications were approved to be part of the “Free Distribution of Food Program”, which supports the most deprived persons including those of very low income or no income at all.⁷⁹

With regards to ethnic, racial, language and other particular characteristics of local population, in Chios there are Roma people. More specifically there are approximately 210 persons who live in three areas, in the city of Chios, at the neighborhood of Aghios Vassilios, and at the villages of Varvassi (100 persons), Thymiana, Chalkios and Myrsinidi. There is no further information on other ethnic and racial characteristics of local population

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

In Chios 3,157 residents or approximately 6% of the total population was born outside of Greece. More details can be found in the below table.

Table 78. Chios – Greek and Foreign Population per Citizenship Group and Sex 2011

	Greek	Total Foreign	Foreign EU	Foreign Europe	Asian	Other	Total
Both Sexes	49,517	3,157	593	2,171	225	168	52,674
Female	24,663	1,598	391	1,029	84	94	26,261
Male	24,854	1,559	202	1,142	141	74	26,413

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/->, Table B07

Unfortunately, there are no data available regarding the time of arrival for non-Greek citizens/migrants and refugees in Greece. All of them are asylum seekers and recognized refugees. However, with regards to the nationalities of foreign persons, an indication can be drawn from the persons illegally residing or entering the district North Aegean Islands in 2015, based on Hellenic Police data.⁸⁰ According to Police data the arrests rate in Chios from 2014 to 2015 has increased to 942,27%, which corresponds to 42,892 persons.⁸¹

⁷⁹ Administrative District of Chios, Strategic Planning 2015-2019, Population demographics, p.21, Table no 16. Most deprived persons who applied for material (food) assistance, <https://www.pvaigaiou.gov.gr/dyn/userfiles/files/pdf-stratigikos-sxediasmos/stratigikos-sxediasmos-2015-2019.pdf>, accessed on 10/06/2020.

⁸⁰ Administrative District of Chios, Strategic Planning 2015-2019, Population demographics, p.14, figure no 1. Main nationalities of foreign nationals arriving to Chios, <https://www.pvaigaiou.gov.gr/dyn/userfiles/files/pdf-stratigikos-sxediasmos/stratigikos-sxediasmos-2015-2019.pdf>, accessed on 10/06/2020.

⁸¹ Administrative District of Chios, Strategic Planning 2015-2019, Population demographics, p.16. Rate of arrests in each of the North Aegean islands including Chios, <https://www.pvaigaiou.gov.gr/dyn/userfiles/files/pdf-stratigikos-sxediasmos/stratigikos-sxediasmos-2015-2019.pdf>, accessed on 10/06/2020.

Table 79. North Aegean – Main Nationalities of Foreign Nationals Who Were Arrested by the Police for Illegal Entry or Residence in 2015

Nationality	Population
Syrian Arab Republic	277,899
Afghanistan	76,620
Iraq	21,552
Pakistan	14,323
Albania	12,637
Other	7,154
Somalia	2,565
Bangladesh	2,388
Palestine	2,239
Congo (DRC)	896
Georgia	857
TOTAL	308,894

Source: Administrative District of Chios, Strategic Planning 2015-2019, Population demographics, p.16. Rate of arrests in each of the North Aegean islands including Chios, <https://www.pvaigaiou.gov.gr/dyn/userfiles/files/pdf-stratigikos-sxediasmos/stratigikos-sxediasmos-2015-2019.pdf>, accessed on 10/06/2020.

The level of education of foreign-born population according to 2011 census can be found in the below table. The majority of them are High School Graduates and Elementary School Graduates.

Table 80. Chios – Level of Education of Foreign-born Population

Education	Both sexes	Female	Male
PhD/ Post-Graduate/ University Degree	235	173	62
Post-Secondary/ Senior High School	826	457	369
Junior High School/ Professional schools	697	335	362
Elementary Graduates	727	335	392
Other	672	298	374
TOTAL	3,157	1,598	1,559

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM03/->, Table B10

The socioeconomic status of foreign-born persons can be partially drawn from the unemployment-employment rates. According to 2011 census, in the administrative district of Northern Aegean Islands 12% of foreign-born persons living in the district are unemployed. With regards to the socioeconomic status of recently arriving persons mostly asylum-seekers, in Chios there are “Vial” reception center which can host up to 1,000 persons. However, there were more than 5,600 refugees and asylum-seekers in January 2020 living at or around the reception center in precarious

living conditions.⁸² Additionally, there are 278 places sponsored by UNHCR in apartments in Chios city,⁸³ which usually host the most vulnerable persons (health, safety, violence reasons).

With regards to the integration of the newly-arrived persons, there are certain difficulties that refugees and asylum seekers face due to the negative attitude of the local community. Mayors of the islands of North Aegean have been pleading Greek Government for several years for closing the hotspots/ reception centers.⁸⁴

Table 81. Northern Aegean Islands – Unemployment of Greek and Foreign-born Population

	# of unemployed	Out of # in Northern Aegean Region
Total	13,738	199,231
Greeks	12,182	186,897
Foreign born	1,556	12,334

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011, <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SAM04/->, Table A10

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

There are 59 schools in Chios Island including all three different levels of education (elementary, junior high, and senior high school) for children aged 6-18 years old.

Table 82. Chios – Number of Schools in Each Level

1	Public Dimotiko	32
2	Public Gymnasium	16
3	Public Lyceum	10
4	Private (includes several levels)	1

Source: Institute of Educational Policy, Institutouto Ekpedeftikis Politikis (IEP), List of schools in Greece, per Administrative District and per Regional Unit, see excel table at the bottom of the page. Includes all types of schools in the country,, <http://iep.edu.gr/el/ereunes-programmata>, accessed on 09/06/2020.

At junior high school (Gymnasium) and senior high school (Lyceum), there are no special reception classes for migrant and refugee children, which would help them to integrate into Greek schools and European reality. Of the 32 Elementary schools (Dimotika) in Chios island, 6 schools have Zones of Educational Priority (ZEP), and another 5 schools have Refugee Education Reception Classes (DYEP).

⁸² Euronews, January 2020, <https://gr.euronews.com/2020/01/23/chios-vial-oi-athlies-sinthikes-diaviosis-reportaz-tou-euronews>, accessed on 10/06/2020

⁸³ UNHCR data portal, data on UNHCR Accommodation programme across Greece, map of available places, May 2020, <https://data2.unhcr.org/en/documents/download/76840>, data accessed on 10/06/2020.

⁸⁴ CNN Greece, Refugee issue: call of Mitarakis (Minister of Migration and Asylum) to the mayors of North Aegean Islands for the closure of hotspots, <https://www.cnn.gr/news/politiki/story/208775/prosfygiko-kalesma-mitaraki-stoys-dimarxoys-ton-nision-gia-to-kleisimo-ton-hotspots>, accessed on 10/06/2020.

Table 83. Chios – Primary Education: 3 Categories Chosen

1	DYEP, ZEP, Intercultural	0
2	None	21
3	ZEP	7
4	DYEP	5
5	Intercultural	0
6	DYEP, ZEP	0
7	ZEP, intercultural	0
8	DYEP, intercultural	0

Source: Various sources such as the Greek Government Gazettes and the national database on types of school (Greek). Please refer to chapter for further explanation of the categories 5.3.1. Key characteristics, p. 136-137

Table 84. Chios – Secondary Education: 2 Categories Chosen

1	DYEP, ZEP, Intercultural	0
2	None	27
3	ZEP	1
4	DYEP	0
5	Intercultural	0
6	DYEP, ZEP	0
7	ZEP, intercultural	0
8	DYEP, intercultural	0

Source: Various sources such as the Greek Government Gazettes and the national database on types of school (Greek). Please refer to chapter for further explanation of the categories 5.3.1. Key characteristics, p. 136-137

In Greece as well as in Chios there is no data on the nationality/ origin of students as well as other characteristics such as gender and socio-economic status apart from the number of students at district level.

Table 85. Northern Aegean Region – Registered Student Population 2017-18

School Level	Total	Boys	Girls	% of total school population
Elementary School/ Dimotiko	11,250	5,736	5,514	1.8%
Junior High School School/ Gymnasium	5,463	N/A	N/A	1.7%
Senior High School/ Lyceum	4,245	N/A	N/A	1.7%

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, Press Release 31 October 2019, <https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/997dd82e-da34-b82f-3795-6904127cc113>

It is interesting to mention the number of students who graduated the same year:

Table 86. Northern Aegean Region – Students who Graduated 2017-18

School Level	Total	Boys	Girls	% of graduation
Elementary School/ Dimotiko	1,762	N/A	N/A	N/A
Junior High School School/ Gymnasium	1,758	N/A	N/A	N/A
Senior High School/ Lyceum	1,396	N/A	N/A	N/A

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, Press Release 31 October 2019, <https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/997dd82e-da34-b82f-3795-6904127cc113>

On the islands apart from the schools, inside the RICs, where asylum-seekers live, there are child-friendly spaces where informal education is provided from various actors to the children. A critical number of UASC are residing in these facilities. UNHCR also identifies children at risk and helps the authorities and different actors to protect them. Metadrasi NGO operates in child-friendly space areas, outside Vial hotspot, providing non-formal education, and delivering Greek, English and other lessons. Also, the children have the opportunity to participate in activities.

11.3 School Sampling

With regards to available open data sources, we were able to identify the complete listing of schools across Greece and several of their categories mentioned at the site of the Institute of Educational Policy (Institouto Ekpedeftikis Politikis, I.E.P.⁸⁵). In Greece schools are divided as per the following table, as per ISCED categories.⁸⁶

⁸⁵ Institute of Educational Policy, Institouto Ekpedeftikis Politikis, (IEP), Complete listing of schools and list of necessary documents for submitting to the Ministry of Education a request for approving a research that includes students, <http://iep.edu.gr/el/ereunes-programmata>, accessed on 09/06/2020

⁸⁶ OECD, IESCED system and different categories of schools in Greece, https://gpseducation.oecd.org/Content/MapOfEducationSystem/GRC/GRC_2011_EN.pdf, accessed on 09/06/2020

Figure 3. OECD, ISCED levels, Schools in Greece 0-18 year olds

Source: OECD, IESCED system and different categories of schools in Greece, https://gpseducation.oecd.org/Content/MapOfEducationSystem/GRC/GRC_2011_EN.pdf, accessed on 09/06/2020

Educational levels and their duration is explained in the above Figure 3 (ISCED). Mandatory education in Greece is considered 9 years, Primary (Dimotiko) from 7 years old to Junior High School to 15 years old.

Public schools are funded by the state and their curriculum is approved by IEP and the Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs. Their calendar follows the Christian Orthodox celebrations regarding holidays during the school year and a prayer takes place every morning. Furthermore, a course on religions is provided but there is a right of exemption from this course, as well as morning prayer. Private schools are funded by private donors/ institutions. For receiving the Greek Certificate “Apolytirion”, private’s school curriculum must be approved by IEP and the Ministry. Some private schools do not follow the path of the Greek “Aplytirion” but follow other paths such as International Baccalaureate (IB).

Public schools are either General or fall into the scope of one or more of the following categories:

- General School is the school with the normal curriculum: Language, Mathematics, History, Physics, Chemistry, Biology, Environment-Geography, First foreign language (English), Second foreign language (French/ German), Religious Education, Physical Education, Information Technology, Social Sciences, Ancient Greek, Literature, Composition and other optional courses.
- Vocational or Professional schools are the schools which curriculum focus on the apprenticeship of a profession such as Administration and Financial education, Agronomy, Food and Environment, Health and Wellbeing, Electrical engineering, Maritime studies, and others.
- Intercultural schools focus their curriculum in the learning of the Greek language as a foreign language using also tools of intercultural education. They are dedicated to children with other than Greek background.
- Special Education schools have specific curriculum for children with intellectual, sensory, physical, learning or multiple disabilities. These schools create different classes for students with similar level.
- Minority schools are specific schools at the administrative district of Eastern Macedonia and Thrace only at the regional units of Evros, Rodopi and Xanthi, which were introduced with the Treaty of Lausanne⁸⁷ in 1923. Children of the Muslim minority (Pomaks, Turks, other) living in Greece are taught in two languages, Greek and Turkish as well as the Quran in Arabic and Greek apart from the general religious education they receive.
- Experimental schools use innovative teaching methods apart from some basic learning courses that are part of their curriculum.
- Model schools have educators/ teachers with higher than moderate skills, but nowadays they are mentioned as model schools, for historical reasons mostly, i.e. because they use to have a good reputation for the quality of education they provide.
- Arts/ Music schools focus their whole curriculum in music and arts apart from some basic classes that are mandatory.
- Ecclesiastical schools focus their curriculum in Religious education, namely Christian Orthodox.
- European Schools are schools mostly for the children of professionals working at EU institutions (no tuition fees) with a diverse background. Children whose parents do not work for EU institutions can also apply for this school but must pay tuition fees. Their curriculum focuses on basic courses such as Languages and Mathematics.

Private schools are funded by private donors/ institutions. For receiving the Greek Certificate “Aplytirion”, private’s school curriculum must be approved by IEP and the Ministry. Some private schools do not follow the path of the Greek “Aplytirion” but follow other paths such as International Baccalaureate (IB), which are not equal to Aplytirion.

⁸⁷ The Treaty of Lausanne settled the issue of the exchange of Muslim/ orthodox populations between Turkey and Greece living in their countries

11.3.1 Key characteristics used in sampling framework

We will select a minimum of 60 schools across Greece reaching to a minimum of 2,400 migrant/ refugee/ indigenous children across the country. Based on the selection of the 7 Administrative Districts, from which we selected 11 Regional Units, we registered all schools covering the age range of children from 6 to 18 years old. From the registry of 3,722 schools we will select the 60 schools from all three levels of education, primary (Dimotiko), lower secondary (Gymnasium) and upper secondary (Lyceum). Primary and lower secondary are considered compulsory education, while upper secondary is optional.

Each of the three levels of education will be represented – as much as possible- in the sample pool of schools as follows: 40% for primary schools, 30% for lower secondary and 30% for upper secondary in each Regional Unit, in each Administrative District and in Greece as a whole.

In order to reach our target number of migrant children participants, we focused on schools where migrant children is more likely to enroll, without excluding the rest of schools because migrant children can be present in any school of the country. Therefore, we decided to use the following characteristics to create the sample pool:

- a) DYEP schools: Schools with preparatory classes (*Δομές Υποδοχής και Εκπαίδευσης Προσφύγων*, DYEP). A Ministerial Decision issued in August 2016 established a programme of afternoon preparatory classes for all school-age children aged 4 to 15 (Ministerial Decision 152360/ΓΔ4/2016) in order to integrate asylum-seeking children into public schools on the Greek mainland. Enrolled children could attend lessons in Greek, English, mathematics, sports, arts, and computer science between 2 p.m. and 6 p.m.. The programme is implemented in public schools neighbouring camps or places of residence. Schools with DYEP classes included in the research are listed in the Ministerial Decision 147357/Δ1/2019 of October 2019, which establishes the schools with DYEP for the school year 2019-2020. DYEP applies only to primary education.
- b) ZEP schools: The “Zones of Educational Priority” (ZEP) program allows public schools with nine or more registered pupils who are not Greek native speakers to set up an “integration” class. Children in these classes receive special lessons in Greek, English, science, and mathematics to prepare them for full integration into Greek schools. They join their Greek peers in other classes, such as sports, information technology, and music. The schools included in the research are listed by Ministerial Decisions as schools where it is possible to operate as ZEP for the school year 2019-2020 (Ministerial Decision Φ1/108909/Δ1/2019 for primary education and Ministerial Decision 152661/Δ2/2019 for secondary education).
- c) Intercultural schools: These schools implement special research and innovation programs with emphasis on intercultural communication and the educational and cultural needs of students. Teachers are selected and hired on the basis of their experience of intercultural education, the knowledge of the mother tongues of their students and teaching Greek as a foreign language.

d) “Plain” schools: All the rest of schools who do not have any of those characteristics

Therefore, we will list all schools in our preselected 11 Regional Units by the above categories and choose schools from each of these categories. We will choose schools from all four categories, sometimes falling into more than one category. We do not intend to leave any of the schools out of our criteria but just focusing on schools where we expect bigger concentration of migrant population for the purposes of the research.

In order to facilitate the survey in the schools of Greece it is necessary, according to the national law we will apply to the Ministry of Education in order to receive official authorization for realizing the survey in schools. For this reason, Panteion University and RDPSEC will request the authorization through IEP, Institute of Educational Policy in June 2020, providing a smaller list of schools that are selected for the survey including the complete questionnaires that will be addressed to children as well as the full text of the consent forms.

11.3.2 Categories resulting from framework and sampling pool

The four characteristics listed in the previous section (DYEP, ZEP, intercultural, plain) and their possible combinations, because the same school might fulfil more than one characteristics (e.g. a school with DYEP classes can also be intercultural), result in the following 8 categories:

Table 88. Categories Resulting from Framework and Sampling Pool 2019-2020

	8 School categories	n° of Primary Schools in all regions	n° of Lower Secondary Schools in all regions	n° of Upper Secondary Schools in all regions
1	DYEP, ZEP and Intercultural	0	0	0
2	None (plain schools)	1,437	689	651
3	ZEP	415	109	48
4	DYEP	24	12	2
5	Intercultural	12	7	2
6	DYEP, ZEP	6	7	2
7	ZEP, intercultural	7	4	1
8	DYEP, intercultural	1	0	0

For each one of the 7 selected Administrative Districts, our sample will include Primary, Lower Secondary and Upper Secondary schools from each of the 8 school categories.⁸⁸ The number of schools that we will include from each category will be selected proportionally, depending on the total number of schools falling in the specific category. However, some adjustments will be necessary in order to include a sufficient number of schools from categories with less school than others. Schools from each category will be selected randomly.

⁸⁸ For some Districts not all categories apply.

11.4 School Sampling – Plan B

In the event that the stratified random sampling technique discussed above yields low response rates, we will use a back-up strategy involving non-probability sampling techniques that allows us to use our contacts and networks to recruit schools to participate. We will still sample from each of the categories from the stratified sampling framework, but we will choose sites purposively, rather than randomly, in order to maximise response rates in order to reach our participant quota. Thus, we have identified approximately 200 schools (Plan B list), which are likely to respond positively. In case some of the approximately 60 randomly selected schools do not respond or they do not host a sufficient number or migrant students, they will be replaced by schools included in the Plan B list. In case we find difficulty accessing schools even from the Plan B list, we will increase our sample from Non-Formal Education environment.

In case of COVID-19 restrictions we plan to use on-line digital classroom with the authorization of principals of the school, if possible.

11.5 Child/classroom Sampling

For the general category of school (schools with not any characteristic) will use a census-type approach⁸⁹ for sampling classrooms within schools, as described in the general sampling strategy section. We will include all year groups at primary level and at secondary level and will attempt to collect data from approximately 40 students in each school which is likely 2 classrooms per school. We will make a calculated decision based on our target population and the criteria by which students are divided into classes. We will survey from all our selected year groups in each school type we visit to ensure that we have sufficient and proportionate representation of each age group across all types of schools delineated in our school sampling framework.

We will set the 20% of children with migrant/ refugee background as minimum standard for choosing the class. If this amount is not fulfilled then we will not do the survey in this class and we will randomly select another class from the school. If the school does not have another class with a minimum of 20% migrant/ refugee background children within the class, we will choose another school based on the criteria explained in the school sampling section.

In Greece some schools have specific classes for migrants/ refugees of children who need language support (ZEP and DYEP classes). In those cases, we will choose those classes per se, as they meet the needs of the survey. If they are more than three classes, we will choose randomly. These such classes, based on law in Greece, have a standard minimum number of migrants/ refugees in the class so that their creation can be approved by MoE.⁹⁰ Therefore, it is expected that in those classes minimum amount of 20% with migrant/ refugee background will be reached.

⁸⁹ Because of the heterogeneity of the student population we will do a research with the assistance of the school management before we choose the classes.

⁹⁰ School Principals apply at the MoE for the creation of such classes, in case they assess that more than 10 students within the class need language support. It is expected that the majority of ZEP classes will have migrant/ refugee children. However, it is possible that the profile of the students is not solely migrants/ refugees. DYEP classes on the other hand

In Intercultural schools, where all classes comprise of children that are of migrant and refugee profile we will choose randomly one to three classes, ensuring age groups representation in the sample.

Census-type approach will be used for the sampling in ORFs (camps) based on data provided by RECs of the Ministry of Education. We will identify different and various age groups of children and we will select age-groups covering the biggest age-range possible in the sample.

11.6 Sampling in Non-Formal Educational Environments

Out of the 30 State Open Reception Facilities (camps) which host mostly asylum-seekers (approximately 25,298 persons⁹¹ across Greece), we will try to include at least three ORFs, most probably located in Central Macedonia, Epirus and Attiki where the majority of ORFs are located. Given that these sites are temporary, they will be selected at a later stage. According to IOM data, 64.26% of children (4,986 out of 7,759) in all ORFs are enrolled in formal education in schools. According to the same data source 28 ORFs/ sites out of 30 have access to formal education and are supported with Non-Formal Education activities, usually provided by Greek NGOs specializing in this sector.

ORFs are formal government sites, established informally in 2016 and formally established by law in 2020. Currently they are managed by the Government, Camp Managers and International Organizations, and International Non-Government Organizations assist in management in a “Site-Management-Support” (SMS) role. Those organizations are the International Organization of Migration (IOM), ASB (a German based international NGO) and the Danish Refugee Council (a Danish based international NGO). In all ORFs except one, the Ministry of Education has set Representatives, called Regional Education Coordinators (RECs) who are responsible for the assessment of the education needs of children and ensuring their access to formal education. Usually, the majority of children are enrolled in schools of the region. Therefore, we will avoid including the same children twice, both in schools and in camps and we will use snowball sampling, making use of any contacts and recommendations.

ORFs include also Safe Zones, where unaccompanied children (UASC) live. We will choose at least one ORF with one Safe Zone. Safe Zones are specific areas protected from the rest of the camp, where usually an NGO, through the appointment of Public Prosecutor orders, appoint Legal Guardians, who are legally responsible for the minor children. The NGOs provide accommodation and psychosocial support to the children. They usually also provide Non-Formal Education activities.

are specifically for recently arrived refugees who need complete introduction to the Greek school. Therefore, in DYEP there are only refugees.

⁹¹ IOM March Factsheet on ORFs across Greece, https://greece.iom.int/sites/default/files/FINAL-March.compressed_1.pdf, data accessed on 12/05/2020

12 Appendix F – Belgium (Research Partner: ACE)

12.1 Regional Sampling

In Belgium foreign nationals represent about 11% of the population (1.1 million people).²²⁶ Data from 2016 showed 68% of migrants were from EU-28 countries and up to 75% from the European continent.

The picture of migration to Belgium is statistically skewed due to the fact that Brussels houses most of the EU institutions and therefore large numbers of EU migrants live and work in Belgium in the institutions or in related sectors due to Brussels status as “capital of Europe”. Most of the immigrants in Belgium are from other European countries (54% of the migrant population).²²⁷ However for IMMERSE we wish only to include sampling of EU migrants from countries outside the Schengen zone who do not enjoy the exact same rights as other EU members. This means migrants from Eastern European countries including Romania (96,034), Poland (71,331), and Bulgaria (37,277).²²⁸ Eastern European migrants from non-Schengen countries are more likely to be driven by economic reasons and migrants work disproportionately in low-skilled, semi-skilled or skilled (blue-collar) work.

Non-European migrants were mainly Moroccans.²²⁹ In 2017, asylum application numbered 18,710; much lower than 2015 (44,760). The majority of those came from the war zones: Afghanistan, Syria and Iraq.²³⁰ Regarding UAMs the number applications also decreased significantly in 2016 compared to 2015 (from 3,099 to 1,076 applications).²³¹

Table 1. Foreign Population of Belgium in 2019, by Origin

Country of Origin	Foreign Population
France	167,508
Netherlands	157,474
Italy	155,866
Romania	96,034
Morocco	80,295
Poland	71,331
Spain	65,476
Portugal	47,677
Germany	39,608
Bulgaria	37,277
Others	454,038

Source: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/517235/foreign-population-of-belgium-by-origin/>

²²⁶ EUROSTAT, Asylum statistics.

²²⁷ <https://www.caritas.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/CommonHomeBelgiumEN.pdf>

²²⁸ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/517235/foreign-population-of-belgium-by-origin>

²²⁹ Hoofdstuk 2 Migratie in België

²³⁰ Commissariaat General Voor de Vluchtelingen en de Staatlozen <http://www.cgvs.be/nl/cijfers>

²³¹ EMN 2016 Annual Report on Asylum and Migration Policy in Belgium

Belgium is divided into three Regions: Flanders, Wallonia, and Brussels Capital Region.

Flanders is made up of the territory of the five Flemish provinces. Wallonia encompasses the territory of the five Walloon provinces. There are also 9 German-speaking municipalities in Wallonia, but they do not constitute a German-speaking region. The Brussels-Capital Region includes the territory of the nineteen municipalities of Brussels.²³²

Flanders was selected because it comprises more than half the Belgian population (majority Dutch speaking). In 2018, the population of Flanders was 7 million people and education in Flanders is under its own educational authority. Ghent is the second largest city in Flanders, located in East Flanders and has a population of 248,358.²³³ Mechelen is in the Antwerp region and was selected because it is a relatively small city, but with a very high number of children from a migrant background (one in two children born in Mechelen has a migrant background). We have not been able to find clear data on the educational level of the Mechelen population but we have endeavoured to show through employment data that the educational level remains generally lower amongst those from a migration background than among the indigenous population.

Brussels was selected because it is the most populous city in Belgium and although officially bilingual is predominantly French speaking, and the French schools fall under the competence of the Wallonia education authority. It is a capital city, has its own government and status, is officially French and Dutch, education is covered by both education ministries in each commune, and it has a high concentration of migrants.

Whether in Flanders or in Wallonia, schools in Belgium can be divided into 3 main categories:

- Schools owned by the communities (GO! Onderwijs In the Flemish Community; réseau de la Communauté française in the French community)
- Subsidized public schools (officieel gesubsidieerd onderwijs; réseau officiel subventionné), organized by provinces and municipalities
- Subsidized free schools (vrij gesubsidieerd onderwijs; réseau libre subventionné), mainly organized by an organization affiliated to the Catholic church²³⁴

In terms of income, the average income of inhabitants is highest in Mechelen at 19,240 euro, followed by Gent at 18,789 euro and Brussels has the lowest average income at 12,801.²³⁵

²³² <https://www.flemishparliament.eu/about-the-flemish-parliament/structure-belgium#:~:text=In%20addition%2C%20Belgium%20is%20divided,of%20the%20five%20Walloon%20provinces.>

²³³ https://www.citypopulation.de/en/belgium/oostvlaanderen/gent/44021__gent/

²³⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Education_in_Belgium

²³⁵ <https://www.hln.be/geld/in-kaart-bekijk-hier-hoeveel-het-gemiddeld-inkomen-in-uw-gemeente-bedraagt~a1b043d8/>

12.2 Region Profiles

12.2.1 Region: Mechelen (Antwerp Province)

POPULATION CHARACTERISTICS

The population is 86,616. Males make up 49% (42,555) of the population, and females make up 51% (44,366).²³⁶ In terms of age distribution 22% are 0-17, making Mechelen one of Flanders youngest cities; 60.8% are 18-54 and 17.2% are 65+.²³⁷

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

Mechelen is home to 138 nationalities, and one in two children born there today has a migration background. 24,995 people of non-Belgian origin live in Mechelen. Of the total population this is around 30%. That is almost double the provincial average of 15.4% (Province of Antwerp excluding the city of Antwerp). The majority of people of foreign origin (45% of the 24,995 people with one foreign origin) has an origin in the Maghreb countries. 9% have an origin in the European non-EU countries, 9% also in Asian countries, 8% has an origin in the other African countries and in Turkey. For children between 0 and 12 years, half or more are of foreign origin. With young people between 12 and 20 years this share is between 40% and 45%. Only from the age category between 25 and 49 year, the percentage approaches the average of 30%.²³⁸

Definitions used when grouping countries of origin:

- Other neighbouring countries: France, Germany and Luxembourg;
- West and North EU 14: Ireland, United Kingdom, Austria, Denmark, Sweden, and Finland
- Southern EU14 countries: Italy, Spain, Portugal, Greece.
- EU12 countries: Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Hungary, Slovenia, Bulgaria, Romania, Malta, and Cyprus.
- Maghreb countries: Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Libya and Mauritania.
- Rich OECD countries outside of Europe: North America, Oceania, and other countries that bank describes as "High-income OECD countries" outside of Europe.

It has not been able to find clear data on the educational level of the Mechelen population. However, the type of employment and, in particular, the breakdown of the day wage, class and origin may provide some insight into disparities between people of migrant origin and Belgian origin. People of Belgian origin are more often represented in the higher wage classes. 38% of them earn more than 150€ a day, only 10% earn less than 90€ a day. For employees, wages of people of EU origin are lower: only 25% of them earn more than 150€ a day, 21% earn less than 90€ per day. Workers of non-EU origin receive the least: 36% of them earn less than 90€ a day, and only 7% of them earn more than 150€ a day.²³⁹

²³⁶ https://www.citypopulation.de/en/belgium/antwerpen/mechelen/12025__mechelen/

²³⁷ https://www.citypopulation.de/en/belgium/antwerpen/mechelen/12025__mechelen/

²³⁸ <https://www.mechelen.be/2017-03-07-verslag-bijlage-commissie-samenleving>

²³⁹ Ibid.

In Mechelen, the percentage of 18-64 year-olds receiving a living wage, or an equivalent was 1.2% of the total number of 18-64 year olds to 1 January 2013. If we look at this according to the origin of the people of Mechelen, there are major differences. For 18-64-year-olds of Belgian origin, 0.4% receive an (equivalent) living wage. At the staff from EU origin, this is slightly higher (0.5%), noticeably higher among people from the neighbouring countries (0.8% - neighbouring countries including the Netherlands). Among the 18-64-year-olds of non-EU origin, the figure is clearly higher: 4.4% of them receive an (equivalent) living wage. This figure is mainly found among people of European non-EU origin: 10.1% of them receive an (equivalent) living wage. With the people of Maghreb origin in this age category, the figure is lower in comparison with the average of persons of non-EU origin.²⁴⁰

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

It is not possible to find a breakdown of student numbers for schools across the city of Mechelen, but the city contains the following categories of schools.

Table 2. School Categories in Mechelen

Region	School type	Generic Type	Funding Authority	Number of schools
Mechelen	Primary	Official Community	GO! basisschool GO! Flemish community (government)	16
		Official Community Method school	GO! freinetschool GO! Flemish community (government)	2
		Official subsidized education comprises municipal education (organized by the municipal authorities OVSG vzw) and provincial education (organized by the provincial authorities POV)	Vrije basisschool OVSG vzw/ POV vzw	0
		Free Education Subsidised free education (GVO) includes religious and non-denominational schools	Vrije Gesubsidieerd Basisschool Katholieke Onderwijs Katholiek Onderwijs Vlaanderen	20
		Free Education Subsidised free education GVO includes religious and non-denominational schools	Vrije Gesubsidieerd Basisschool Protestants Onderwijs Inrichtende Machten van het Protestants-Christelijk Onderwijs (IPCO)	1

²⁴⁰ Ibid.

Region	School type	Generic Type	Funding Authority	Number of schools
	Secondary	Official Community	GO! Atheneum GO! Flemish community (government)	7
		Official Community Method school	GO! freinetschool GO! Flemish community (government)	0
		Official subsidized education comprises municipal education (organized by the municipal authorities OVSG vzw) and provincial education (organized by the provincial authorities POV)	Secondair Onderwijs POV	2
		Free Education Subsidised free education GVO includes religious and non-denominational schools	Secondair Onderwijs Katholiek Onderwijs Vlaanderen	8

Statistical information is not available for the city of Mechelen, however the region of Antwerp province provides a breakdown of students of foreign nationality and for the academic year 2019-2020 in Antwerp Province. The percentages in Mechelen city are likely higher than the provincial average owing to the already mentioned number of people from a migration background in the city's overall population.

Table 3. Students of Foreign Nationality in Antwerp, 2019/20 Academic Year

	Total students			Number of students of foreign nationality			Percentage of students of foreign nationality		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
Ordinary Primary education	63,322	62,535	125,857	8,454	8,257	16,711	23.89	23.72	13.28
Special Primary education	4,646	2,405	7,051	758	384	1,142	16.32	15.97	16.20
Ordinary Secondary education	60,297	58,771	119,068	7,038	6,759	13,797	11.67	11.50	11.59
Special Secondary Education	3,830	1,966	5,796	526	295	821	13.73	15.01	14.16

Source: Vorming, 2020.

Table 4. Number of Students of Foreign Nationality in Primary and Secondary Education by Education Level, Type of School Board and Province

	Foreign nationality Antwerp Province		
	Male	Female	Total
Primary Education			
<i>Ordinary education</i>			
Community education	1,461	1,499	2,960
Private education	4,285	4,130	8,415
Province	-	-	-
Township	2,708	2,628	5,336
Total	8,454	8,257	16,711
<i>Special Ordinary education</i>			
Community education	168	64	232
Private education	344	193	537
Province	-	-	-
Township	246	127	373
Flemish Community Commission	-	-	-
Total	758	384	1,142
Secondary Education			
<i>Ordinary education</i>			
Community education	1,712	1,641	3,353
Private education	3,700	3,878	7,578
Province	239	230	469
Township	1,387	1,010	2,397
Total	7,038	6,759	13,797
<i>Special Ordinary education</i>			
Community education	111	62	173
Private education	248	155	403
Province	-	-	-
Township	167	78	245
Flemish Community Commission	-	-	-
Total	526	295	821

Source: Pupils of foreign nationality (excel doc), Statistical yearbook of Flemish education 2018-2019, <https://onderwijs.vlaanderen.be/nl/nl/onderwijsstatistieken/statistisch-jaarboek/statistisch-jaarboek-van-het-vlaams-onderwijs-2018-2019>

12.2.2 Region: Ghent (East Flanders)

POPULATION CHARACTERISTICS

The population of Ghent is 248,358. 49.8% (131,543) are male and 50.2% (132,384) are female.²⁴¹

²⁴¹ https://www.citypopulation.de/en/belgium/oostvlaanderen/ghent/44021__ghent/

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

Generally, the breakdown by nationality in Ghent in 2019 looked like this: Belgium 223,426; EU 28 21,537; Europe (other) 1,664; Asia 10,046; Africa 4,053; Other/Unknown Nationality 1,493.²⁴²

Information regarding migration in Ghent was available mainly from a statistical analysis of 2012 statistics published in 2016. In 2016, 933 non-Belgians came to live in Ghent. Ghent has 222,107 Belgians and 36,012 non-Belgians, or 14%. The Bulgarians form the largest group with 8,504 inhabitants, followed by the Turks (4,100) and the Dutch (2,897). In the ranking of fastest growing groups compared to 2015, the refugees are now increasing. The Syrians lead the rankings (+342), followed by the Bulgarians (+320), Afghans (+124), Somalis (+107) and Iraqis (+61).²⁴³

The report stated that in the period covered, migrants in Ghent mainly had a Turkish or Moroccan background. In this report from 2016 there is a diversification and so-called Europeanization of the Ghent migrant population with an increase in the number of migrants from Eastern Europe. More than half (55%) were EU citizens from one of the new EU member states. The Bulgarian influx dominated these statistics. In the Bulgarians we see that almost all age groups came to Ghent with a peak among the 20 and 30 year-olds, the most mobile age group across categories, but Bulgarian children also came to live in Ghent. The largest group of migrants after the Bulgarians were the Dutch who came to Ghent as employees (40%) or as students (28%).²⁴⁴

According to the 2016 report, the number of Slovakian nationals has increased significantly in recent years. In the 1990s there was a stream of Slovakian migration to Ghent, so Slovak migration had a strong existing link with Ghent: more than half of the Slovaks registered in Flanders reside in Ghent. Half of the newly registered Slovaks came to Belgium under one family reunification. Slightly more than one in four of the Slovaks were registered as working entrepreneurs. Furthermore, according to the same report, the number of Polish nationals has increased continuously since Poland joined the EU and these Polish immigrants were mainly young people in their twenties. The number of Romanians continued to rise in Ghent. According to the report, the Romanian new entrants mainly register as students, family sponsors and employees.

The report also notes that there are slightly more men than women among non-Belgian inhabitants of Ghent, but there are differences by nationality group. Certain nationality groups are strikingly male: Afghanistan, Ethiopia, United Kingdom, India, Pakistan and Iraq. Other nationality groups turn out to be strikingly female, namely Thailand, Philippines, and the Czech Republic and Brazil. Family-based immigration is by far the most important immigration channel in Ghent. Of the 5,629 new registrations in 2012, 37% were related to family ties. Labour migration is the second immigration channel and accounts for 27%. Migration to study

²⁴² https://www.citypopulation.de/en/belgium/oostvlaanderen/gent/44021__gent/

²⁴³ https://stad.gent/sites/default/files/page/documents/160086_Gent_rapport-Hiva_opmaak-online-v10_LR.pdf

²⁴⁴ Ibid.

is the third immigration channel in Ghent. 23% of the new registrations in 2012 were for study purposes, and 4% was based on international protection status.²⁴⁵

According to a Policy memorandum by the City of Ghent for 2014-2019 on Education and Youth, 20% of inhabitants of Ghent are estimated to have a low level of literacy.²⁴⁶ This statistic includes both those born in Ghent and those with a migration background, including those that have been living in Ghent long-term. The size and diversity of the population means that a considered analysis of integration of the migrant population is useful.

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

It is not possible to find a breakdown of student numbers for schools across the city of Ghent, but the city contains the following categories of schools:

Table 5. School Categories in Ghent

Region	School type	Generic Type	Funding authority	Number of Schools
Ghent	Primary	Official Community	GO! basisschool GO! Flemish community (government)	13
		Official Community Method school	GO! freinetschool GO! Flemish community (government)	5
		Official subsidized education comprises municipal education (organized by the municipal authorities OVSG vzw) and provincial education (organized by the provincial authorities POV)	Vrije basisschool OVSG vzw/ POV vzw	0
		Free Education Subsidised free education (GVO) includes religious and non-denominational schools	Vrije Gesubsidieerd Basisschool Katholieke Onderwijs Katholiek Onderwijs Vlaanderen	15
		Free Education Subsidised free education GVO includes religious and non-denominational schools	Vrije Gesubsidieerd Basisschool Protestants Onderwijs Inrichtende Machten van het Protestants-Christelijk Onderwijs (IPCO)	1

²⁴⁵ https://stad.gent/sites/default/files/page/documents/160086_Gent_rapport-Hiva_opmaak-online-v10_LR.pdf

²⁴⁶ https://stad.gent/sites/default/files/page/documents/Beleidsnota%20Onderwijs%20Opvoeding%20en%20Jeugd_2.pdf

Region	School type	Generic Type	Funding authority	Number of Schools
	Secondary	Official Community	GO! Atheneum GO! Flemish community (government)	4
		Official Community Method school	GO! freinetschool GO! Flemish community (government)	4
		Official subsidized education comprises municipal education (organized by the municipal authorities OVSG vzw) and provincial education (organized by the provincial authorities POV)	Secondair Onderwijs POV	3
		Free Education Subsidised free education GVO includes religious and non-denominational schools	Secondair Onderwijs Katholiek Onderwijs Vlaanderen	13

Source: <https://stad.gent.nl/onderwijs-kinderopvang/scholen/overzicht-van-de-scholen-gent>²⁴⁷

Statistical information is available for the regions for the academic year 2019-2020 showing the number of students in East Flanders who are listed as having a foreign nationality. This statistic is likely higher in Gent due to the University and size of the city compared to other less populated areas of East Flanders.

Table 6. Students of Foreign Nationality in East Flanders, 2019/20 Academic Year

	Total students			Number of students of foreign nationality			Percentage of students of foreign nationality		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
Ordinary Primary education	50,456	50,129	100,585	3,993	3,968	7,961	7.91%	7.92%	7.91%
Special Primary education	3,480	1,797	5,277	437	221	658	12.56%	12.30%	12.47%
Ordinary Secondary education	50,310	48,955	99,265	3,284	3,166	6,450	6.53%	6.47%	6.50%
Special Secondary Education	3,107	1,517	4,624	299	183	482	9.62%	12.06%	10.42%

²⁴⁷ Additional breakdown of numbers of schools acquired from:
<https://www.freinetschool.be/freinet/oostvlaanderen/>
<https://scholengroep.gent/>
<http://www.onderwijsregioent.be/>
<http://www.pov.be/site/>
<https://www.ipco.be/>

Source: Pupils of foreign nationality (excel doc), Statistical yearbook of Flemish education 2018-2019, <https://onderwijs.vlaanderen.be/nl/nl/onderwijsstatistieken/statistisch-jaarboek/statistisch-jaarboek-van-het-vlaams-onderwijs-2018-2019>

Table 7. Number of Students of Foreign Nationality in Primary and Secondary Education by Education Level, Type of School Board and Province.

	Foreign nationality East Flanders		
	Male	Female	Total
Primary Education			
Ordinary Education			
Community Education	833	830	1,663
Private Education	2,389	2,351	4,740
Province	-	-	-
Township	771	787	1,558
Total	3,993	3,968	7,961
Special Education			
Community Education	101	46	147
Private Education	251	128	379
Province	18	8	26
Township	67	39	106
Flemish Community Commission	-	-	-
Total	437	221	658
Secondary Education			
Ordinary Education			
Community Education	1,009	929	1,938
Private Education	1,888	1,838	3,726
Province	153	157	310
Township	234	242	476
Total	3,284	3,166	6,450
Special Education			
Community Education	73	27	100
Private Education	156	109	265
Province	6	2	8
Township	64	45	109
Flemish Community Commission	-	-	-
Total	299	183	482

Source: Pupils of foreign nationality (excel doc), Statistical yearbook of Flemish education 2018-2019, <https://onderwijs.vlaanderen.be/nl/nl/onderwijsstatistieken/statistisch-jaarboek/statistisch-jaarboek-van-het-vlaams-onderwijs-2018-2019>

12.2.3 Region: Brussels Capital Region

POPULATION CHARACTERISTICS

The population of Brussels in 2020 was 1,218,255. 50.9% (620,549) was female, and 49.1% (597,706) was male.²⁴⁸

In terms of age distribution 22.7% are 0-17, 64.2% are 18-54, and 13.1% are 65+.²⁴⁹ The average age in Brussels is younger than the rest of the country with an average age of 37.5.

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANT POPULATION

In Belgium statistics based on ethnicity are not formally collected. Nonetheless Brussels is home to many people from a migration background and it is estimated that 32% of residents are from other European countries and about 36 % are from outside of Europe including Morocco, Turkey and Sub Saharan Africa.

In Brussels, 45% of inhabitants are immigrants, compared to 15% in Wallonia and 12% in Flanders. The table shows the breakdown of nationalities residing in Brussels.²⁵⁰

Table 8. Nationality of Brussels Residents by Region, 2020

Region	Number of Residents
Belgium	788,698
EU 27 (w/o UK)	276,979
Europe (other)	18,818
Asia	43,961
Africa	67,629
Other / Unknown Nationality	22,170

Source: <https://www.citypopulation.de/en/belgium/brussels/>

SCHOOLS OF THE REGION

The right to education is enshrined in Article 25 of the Belgian constitution. Education is compulsory for all Belgians and non-Belgians on Belgian territory in full-time education until the age of 16. Most children begin formal school at the age of 2.5 years, although school attendance is not mandatory until the sixth birthday.²⁵¹

Statistical information is available for the regions for the academic year 2019-2020.

Table 9. Brussels Capital Region: Student Enrolment figures

	Primary	Secondary
Brussels	94,881	93,760

Source: <http://statistics.brussels/themes/education#.XxAYROd8JPY>

²⁴⁸ <https://www.citypopulation.de/en/belgium/brussels/>

²⁴⁹ <https://www.citypopulation.de/en/belgium/brussels/>

²⁵⁰ <https://www.citypopulation.de/en/belgium/brussels/>

²⁵¹ http://statistics.brussels/files/themes/education_methodology

Table 10. Students in Brussels, by Type, Characteristic (ordinary education, specialised) and Language (French -FR, or Flemish-NL), 2018/19 Academic Year

	Primary			Secondary		
	FR	NL	Total	FR	NL	Total
Région de Bruxelles-Capitale	80,576	19,270	99,46	83,941	15,706	99,647
Belgique	342,804	467,059	809,863	382,550	448,000	830,550

Source: <http://statistics.brussels/themes/education#.XxGpzed8JPZ>

Officially bilingual but with French as the majority language, French speaking Education in the capital falls under the competence of Wallonia-Brussels Federation.²⁵²

According to an OECD report, in 2015 the Brussels Capital Region had an employment rate of 59% for those aged 25-64 with upper secondary level educational attainment, while in the Flemish Region the employment rate for the same group was 76%.²⁵³

The document, Jobs for Immigrants (Vol. 2): Labour Market Integration in Belgium, France, the Netherlands and Portugal Summary and Recommendations, BELGIUM, stated, “The OECD PISA study revealed that the differences in the educational outcomes between the second generation and the children of natives are larger in Belgium than in any other OECD country.”²⁵⁴

This document noted that while there are differences across all of Belgium, these differences are particularly high in Flanders. Indeed, in both Flanders and Brussels educational attainment for students from non EU countries is disproportionately represented amongst those classed as having low-qualifications. The report suggested that the socio-economic background of the children of immigrants was partially responsible for this disparity, but it noted that even when controlling for that factor the gap in relation to children from Belgium backgrounds was very high.²⁵⁵

In Belgium, there are four networks of schools in operation:

- **Community education.** Organised by the main language communities (Dutch and French), this is the equivalent of state education in other countries. It is officially neutral system in respecting the religion, philosophy and ideological beliefs of parents and children.
- **Official subsidized education.** Organised by the municipal and provincial authorities.

²⁵² <https://www.caritas.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/CommonHomeBelgiumEN.pdf>

²⁵³ <http://www.oecd.org/education/Education-Policy-Outlook-Country-Profile-Belgium.pdf>

²⁵⁴ <https://www.oecd.org/belgium/jobsforimmigrantsvol2labourmarketintegrationinbelgiumfrancethenetherlandsandportugal.htm>

²⁵⁵ <https://www.oecd.org/belgium/jobsforimmigrantsvol2labourmarketintegrationinbelgiumfrancethenetherlandsandportugal.htm>

- **Free subsidized education.** Organised by private people or organisations. Mainly religious schools, majority Catholic, though also Protestant, Jewish, Orthodox and Islamic schools. Also includes free non-religious schools and schools based on a particular educational methods, such as Rudolf Steiner Schools and Freinet Schools.
- **Private schools.** Small number of schools – these are not recognized by the government and get no governmental financial support. Includes European and international schools in this category. In some cases, private schools allow themselves to be inspected by the Belgian authorities, and issue students with certificates that are equivalent to official Belgian diplomas.²⁵⁶

Table 11. Number of Schools in Ordinary Education for the French and Flemish Communities in Brussels, 2018/19 Academic Year:

Type of School	Number of Schools
Foundational education (pre-primary and primary) French	343
Foundational education (pre-primary and primary) Flemish	139
Total Foundational education (pre-primary and primary)	482
Secondary education French	119
Secondary education Flemish	35
Total Secondary education	154

Source: <http://statistics.brussels/themes/education#.XxGpzed8JPZ>

Table 12. Number of Schools in Specialised Education for the French and Flemish Communities in Brussels, 2018/19 Academic Year:

Type of School	Number of Schools
Foundational education (pre-primary and primary) French	40
Foundational education (pre-primary and primary) Flemish	6
Total Foundational education (pre-primary and primary)	46
Secondary education French	14
Secondary education Flemish	5
Total Secondary education	19

Source: <http://statistics.brussels/themes/education#.XxGpzed8JPZ>

12.3 School Sampling

The sampling strategy in Belgium reflects both the stratified random sampling framework and the reality of data availability and accessibility and across the different regions. In Belgium, the authority for education does not fall under state jurisdiction but is the responsibility of the two regional areas of Wallonia and Flanders. Statistical analysis is usually broad in scope covering the regions and the provinces but with little detailed information regarding school sizes and composition. It proved impossible to find regional or national databases for numbers of enrolled students. Although it is possible to find resources for school type and name and function.

²⁵⁶ <http://www.commissioner.brussels/i-am-an-expat/education/84-education/115-education-system>

There is no breakdown of percentages of students with migration backgrounds in schools, although information about student numbers and percentages enrolled in schools from non-Belgian nationality backgrounds is available across the broader regions as has been shown with the statistics provided for East Flanders, Antwerp Province and Brussels Capitol Region.

Without the ability to use school demographics (size, background, etc.) we would choose instead to use secondary schools with OKAN (Flemish) Reception education for foreign-language newcomers/ DASPA (French Reception); schools that have these units will by their nature have a higher level of students from a migration background. We would aim to select primary schools from Official community and Official subsidised categories, as these are the schools most like to contain students from our target migrant backgrounds. This means excluding students attending private educational establishments because they are proportionally few in number in Belgium and, while they include students from migration backgrounds (largely economic), they are unlikely to contain large numbers of asylum seekers, UAM's and students from socio-economically deprived backgrounds and would also have to include the sizeable and relatively wealthy European schools and International schools in Brussels which would potentially skew data as these students are educated wherever possible in their mother tongue and may not generally face the same pressure to integrate to Belgium as those entering Community organised, subsidised or free schools.

ACE will follow the example of DOZ in Germany and leave out certain types of Special Needs schools for the same reasons of difficulty in participation in the study but will include schools such as Freinet and Waldorf schools for similar reasons.

12.3.1 Key characteristics used in sampling framework

The following key characteristics have been identified to inform the sampling pool.

REGION

ACE focuses on schools in three cities of two different educational authorities in Belgium, Flanders and Wallonia. To facilitate the creation of the sampling framework, the sample pool covers all districts in all three cities. Derived from the initial sample set, the categories are as follows: Mechelen, Antwerp Province, Flanders; Ghent, East Flanders, Flanders; Brussels, Brussels Capitol Region. The first two cities are in Flanders, while Brussels is in the autonomous Brussels Capitol region and is officially bilingual. As previously outlined, the competence for education in Brussels is held by the Flemish authority for Dutch language schools and by Wallonian authority for French language schools. We will focus our sample on the French schools under Wallonian competency in Brussels because it is majority French speaking and has a large migrant population.²⁵⁷

²⁵⁷[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Education_in_Belgium#:~:text=Education%20in%20Belgium%20is%20regulated,with%20small%20differences%20among%20them.&text=The%20schools%20can%20be%20divided,%3A%20netten%3B%20French%3A%20r%C3%A9seaux\)%3A](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Education_in_Belgium#:~:text=Education%20in%20Belgium%20is%20regulated,with%20small%20differences%20among%20them.&text=The%20schools%20can%20be%20divided,%3A%20netten%3B%20French%3A%20r%C3%A9seaux)%3A)

SCHOOL TYPE

Overall, schools of general education in Belgium can be divided into two categories: primary and secondary. Even between the language communities the structures of education are broadly similar, Primary from age 6-12, Secondary (early) 12-14, and Secondary (higher) 14-18.²⁵⁸ Special schools and method schools are similarly structured with Primary, Secondary (early) and Secondary (higher) levels. We will divide students into these 3 levels to conduct the targeted research.

CONCENTRATION OF MIGRANT STUDENTS

The proportion of migrant students is not available as a statistic and neither is school size in Belgium, so they are not included as a key characteristic. As stated, we intend to focus our research on secondary schools that have reception education for newcomers at Secondary (OKAN and DASPA units), as no new arrival to a Belgian secondary school may attend ordinary classes before completing approximately a year in such a reception class. OKAN and DASPA units are generally attached to community organised, community subsidised or free subsidised schools. Students attending reception classes are then filtered into ordinary education either in the school with the reception class or in another school offering a programmed deemed suitable for their educational level. Therefore, sampling from these schools with attached units and local schools receiving students from OKAN and DASPA units will enable us to target schools likely to have more sizable concentrations of migrant students.

12.3.2 Categories resulting from key characteristics

Table 13. Categories for Sampling

Region	School Type	Language Reception Classes for Secondary Education
Mechelen	Lower Secondary	OKAN
	Upper Secondary	OKAN
Ghent	Lower Secondary	OKAN
	Upper Secondary	OKAN
Brussels	Lower Secondary	DASPA
	Upper Secondary	DASPA

We are aiming to have the majority of our sample taken from Third Country Nationals and EU nationals that are from outside the Schengen zone. Eastern European migrants from non-Schengen countries are more likely to be driven by economic reasons and migrants work disproportionately in low-skilled, semi-skilled or skilled (blue-collar) work. This means we will include migrants from Eastern European countries including Romania, Poland and Bulgaria.

The overall target sample size for Belgium is 800 students in 20 centres. To reach maximum variation across the 2 language communities where Brussels is clearly the more populated

²⁵⁸<https://education.stateuniversity.com/pages/152/Belgium-EDUCATIONAL-SYSTEM-OVERVIEW.html#:~:text=The%20education%20system%20is%20divided,nonuniversity%20format%20averaging%20four%20years.>

city but represents only one language community, we have decided to divide the sample evenly between schools in Flanders and schools in Brussels and then divide the Flanders cities equally in 2 owing the fact that each city has roughly the same number (approximately 60) of schools.

Table 14. Distribution of Sample Schools across Regions

City	Centres	Children
Brussels	10	400
Ghent	5	200
Berlin	5	200

12.4 School Sampling – Plan B

Ace will follow the Sampling Plan B of DOZ who are conducting the research in Belgium in the event that the stratified random sampling technique for selecting school sites discussed above yields low response rates. Following DOZ, we will use the back-up strategy involving non-probability sampling techniques (as described in the general sampling strategy) that allow us to use our contacts and networks to recruit schools to participate. Those contacts and networks include individual teachers, schools, and integration mediators. We will still sample from each of the categories from the stratified sampling framework, but we will choose sites purposively, rather than randomly, to maximise response rates to reach our participant quota.

12.5 Child/classroom sampling

We will use a census-type approach for sampling classrooms within schools, as described in the general sampling strategy section. We do not anticipate needing to make any adjustments to this strategy. We will ensure that we have sufficient and proportionate representation of each age group across all types of schools delineated in our school sampling framework.

12.6 Sampling in Non-Formal Education Environments

Due to the lack of data on the characteristics of non-formal education environments and their higher level of inaccessibility, we will use non-probability sampling to select research sites from among these that allow us to use our networks to recruit them to participate. Those networks include individual social workers and educators with contacts to non-formal education environments as well as the centres themselves. We will use maximum variation purposive sampling and will attempt to target all of the following types of non-formal environments in our chosen regions as categorised below.

Table 15. Non-Formal Environments

Type	Basic Information
Children and Youth Centres	Recreational facilities that locally provide leisure activities and social support. They can operate only within one district or city-wide. They usually provide special support for socially disadvantaged children and youth.
Community Centres	Public location which provides leisure activities, cultural events, social support, and public information for members of a community. They can locally address all members of a district (or wider community) or only for a specialised group.
Migrant-Led Self-Organised Initiatives	Initiatives that are controlled by people with migration background themselves. They can be locally supporting a certain group of Diasporas or all. Topics addressed can range from education, social support, and cultural heritage to advocacy and social justice.
NGOs and Associations	Organisations that are non-governmental and non-profit that work with migrant and/or refugee children, youth, and families in particular and provide education, social and/or legal support, civil engagement, or advocacy work.